

PROCEEDINGS OF THE SECOND ANNUAL INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON RELIGION, CULTURE, AND PEACE EDUCATION

April 27 – 28, 2023

Hybrid Onsite and Online Conference

Singtoh Changtrakul Seminar Room

Sirindhorn Learning Resource Center

Payap University

Editor-in-Chief:

Dr Rey Ty

Work-Study Graduate Assistant:

Salai David ST Van Bawi Mang

Department of Peace Studies

Religion, Culture, and Peace Laboratory

Faculty of Humanities and Communication Arts

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Second Annual International Conference on Religion, Culture, and Peace Education
Department of Peace Studies (DPS), Religion, Culture, and Peace Laboratory (RCPL),
in Collaboration with Mennonite Central Committee (MCC)
International College, Payap University, Chiang Mai, Thailand

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Conference Host

Payap University

Conference Sponsors:

Department of Peace Studies

Religion, Culture, and Peace Laboratory

Faculty of Humanities and Communication Arts

Mennonite Central Committee

Consortium for Global Education

Research Institute

Editor-in-Chief

Dr Rey Ty

Work-Study Graduate Assistant

Salai David ST Van Bawi Mang

Chiang Mai, Thailand

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Department of Peace Studies (DPS), Religion, Culture, and Peace Laboratory (RCPL),
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International College, Payap University, Chiang Mai, Thailand**

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FAQ SHEET

THE PROCEEDINGS OF THE ANNUAL INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON RELIGION,

CULTURE, PEACE, AND EDUCATION is an annual publication of the Department of Peace Studies; Religion, Culture, and Peace Lab; & the Faculty of Humanities and Communication Arts, Payap University, Chiang Mai, Thailand.

Department of Peace Studies and the Religion, Culture, and Peace Lab

The faculty members of the Department of Peace Studies of Payap University include Dr Mark Tamthai, Dr Le Ngoc Bich Ly, Dr Tony Waters, and Dr R. Ty.

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Editor-in-Chief: **Rey Ty**

Work-Study Graduate Assistant: **Salai David ST Van Bawi Mang**

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Conference Proceedings

Published by:

Department of Peace Studies (DPS)

Religion, Culture, and Peace Laboratory (RCP Lab)

Faculty of Humanities and Communication Arts

Payap University, Chiang Mai, Thailand

Second Annual International Conference on Religion, Culture, and Peace Education
Department of Peace Studies (DPS), Religion, Culture, and Peace Laboratory (RCPL),
in Collaboration with Mennonite Central Committee (MCC)
International College, Payap University, Chiang Mai, Thailand

CALL FOR PROPOSALS

Second International Annual Conference on Religion, Culture, Peace, and Education

Department of Peace Studies
 Religion, Culture, and Peace Lab
 International College, Payap University
 Mennonite Central Committee
 Chiang Mai, Thailand
 And Consortium for Global Education
 Research Institute
 U.S.A.

Start Date: Thursday April 27, 2023

End Date: Friday April 28, 2023

Hybrid Meeting

Important Dates

Public Announcement:	January 15, 2023
Submission of 1-Page Proposals:	February 15, 2023
Notification of Acceptance:	March 1, 2023
Submission of Final Paper:	March 22, 2023
Blended Conference:	April 27-28, 2023

Conference Theme

Educating for Justice and Peace

Rationale

As scholars and practitioners, we constantly try to understand, describe, explain, rethink, and propose ways by which we improve our world, society, communities, economy, politics, culture, as well as the way we live and interact with each other as a response to evolving needs and shifting priorities.

For this reason, we invite you to take part in the forthcoming International Conference on Religion, Culture, Peace, and Education to be held from April 27 to 28, 2023. In this regard, we enjoin you to [register online and submit a short abstract proposal](#) for a paper presentation and publication in the electronic Proceedings. Please click [here](#) to submit a proposal. See [2022 Book of Abstracts](#) and [2022 Conference Proceedings](#) to give you an idea of writing your 200-word-maximum abstracts.

For the 2023 Conference, see [Call for Abstract Proposals](#), [Co-Sponsor CGE](#), [Co-Sponsor CGE Research Institute](#), [Conference Poster](#), and [Keynote Speakers](#).

International Editorial Board Members

If you have completed a doctorate, you are welcome to join our team of international blind peer reviewers. If you are interested, kindly [register online](#) to be formally recognized as a member of the International Review Board. Please click [here](#) to register. Upon request, we will be glad to send you an e-Certificate of Membership in the International Editorial Board. Thank you.

Chiang Mai, Thailand

Chiang Mai is situated in the north of Thailand, bordering Myanmar to the west and Laos to the East, while China is a little farther to the North. Called the Rose of the North, Chiang Mai provides several historic and natural attractions for you to explore: The Old City, ancient temples, waterfalls, mountains, caves, and ethical animal sanctuaries.

Payap University

Payap University has a long and rich history beginning in 1888 with the founding of the Thailand Theological Conference. That conference was integrated into Payap University as the McGilvery College of Divinity, one of eleven academic divisions comprising the university. Established in 1974, Payap University is a private and non-profit institution founded by the Foundation of the Church of Christ in Thailand.

Payap University has obtained official recognition from the United States government, through its Department of Education (DOE), as eligible for federal financial aid. Payap University is a liberal art and pre-professional school offers a doctoral degree in Peace Studies; masters in divinity, linguistics, TESOL, law, MBA and music; and bachelor degrees in arts, sciences, accountancy, business, economics nursing, law, and Christian theology. Payap is a founding member of the Association of Private Higher Education Institutions in Thailand and an active member of the Association of Christian Universities and Colleges in Asia, as well as the Association of Southeast Asian Institutions of Higher Learning.

Department of Peace Studies (DPS)

The Department of Peace Studies at Payap University works closely and exists to foster mutual appreciation and cooperation among the world's religious communities and enact new initiatives in peacebuilding. The Department of Peace Studies is the academic unit that offers a Ph.D. program and a Certificate program in Peacebuilding.

Conference Objective

The objective of the conference is to convene researchers, scholars, practitioners, and other interested parties to showcase, share, examine, and evaluate their state-of-the-art research, performing arts, community work related to trends in religion, culture, peace, or a combination thereof.

Conference Participants

Registration is open to both presenters and observers who are academics, practitioners, policy makers, civil society organizers, community members, and other parties interested in the issues of religion, culture, peacebuilding, and education.

Interdisciplinary Conference Sub-Themes

Papers in different areas of studies and research are most welcome, including among others the following:

- Anthropology, Arts, Business, Communication Science, Cultural Studies, Development Studies, Divinity, Economics, Education, History, Interdisciplinary Studies, Languages, Linguistics, Literature, Performing Arts, Peace Studies, Political Science, Public Administration, Social Sciences, Sociology, Theology, Visual Arts

Some major issues that you are most welcome to discuss include, among others, the following:

- Action research, business for social progress, caste, civil society, class, community development, conflict management| resolution| transformation, discrimination, diversity, electoral democracy, environmentalism, ethnicity, fake news, gender, hate speech, human rights, human trafficking, inclusion, information technology, inner peace, interfaith and interreligious activities, international law, leadership, migrant labor, peace building| keeping| making, peace education, philosophy, racism, refugees, religion, self-determination, sexual orientation, social entrepreneurship, social justice, social media, stateless people, student activism, United Nations, violent extremism, women empowerment, xenophobia, and other matters;
- Causes and effects of these burning issues; and,
- Agenda for social change

Conference Format

There will be short remarks, keynote speeches, paper presentations, and breakout sessions, as necessary. Individual and panel presentations are most welcome. Ten-minute paper presentations shall be organized thematically into panels. Each panel session goes for one hour, including Q&A.

Conference Publication

All papers accepted for presentation at the Conference shall be published in the electronic *Conference Proceedings*. The editor-in-chief who prepares the proceedings reserves the right to revise papers, as necessary.

Review Process

- All submissions shall undergo a blind review process. Reviewers shall provide constructive feedback for each submission approximately two weeks after the submission deadline.

Author Submission Guidelines

- Proposal: For your [submission](#), please submit your name, affiliation, country, email address, and a 200-word max proposal, 12-point Times New Roman font, which includes the following: the title, name, Faculty/Student/or Other Job Description,

Name, Affiliation, Country; problem statement, rationale, and importance of the study, purpose, research questions (or hypothesis for quantitative papers), theory (optional), and methods in one page maximum. Longer submissions will be rejected.

- **Paper:** Once your paper proposal will be approved for presentation, please submit a 6-page max, single-spaced A4 paper, both margins justified, 12-point Times New Roman font, with APA citation and APA references. Contents include Title of the Paper, Name, Faculty/Student/or Other Job Description, Name, Affiliation, Country; Email; Introduction; Literature Review; Methodology; Findings; Conclusion; and References. Papers with longer than 6 pages and not following the author guidelines will be rejected.
- [Download sample templates here.](#) [Samples of single-spaced 6-page conference papers here.](#) [Last year's \(2022\) International Conference Proceedings.](#)

Free Conference Registration

Participation in the conference is free for all speakers, paper and poster presenters, observers, participants, and drop-in visitors. Please explore the cafeteria, cafés, and restaurants in the surrounding areas for your meals.

Conference Format and Free Publication

The Conference shall be held in blended format. However, in the event that travel to Thailand will not be possible for all due to the pandemic or other acts of nature, the conference shall be held online 100%. All papers will still be published in the electronic Conference Proceedings.

Social Media Presence

If you plan to submit a paper to the Conference, kindly join our [FB Bulletin Board closed group](#) for all announcements, questions, and answers.

Here is the [link](#) to [our Lab's FB page](#) for the live-casting of our two-day conference. Photos and videos will be shared [our Lab's FB page](#). Thank you.

Conference Partners

As of this writing, the partner of this year's includes the Consortium for Global Education Research Institute in the United States. The Department of Peace Studies, the Religion, Culture, and Peace Laboratory (RCPL), and the International College (IC) of Payap University welcome individuals, foundations, and organizations to partner with the annual conference. Partners could choose (1) to provide a lump-sum financial grant for conference-related expenses, (2) to disseminate information about the conference with their networks, or (3) to sponsor a keynote speaker, a guest speaker, or a participant by paying all the conference-related expenses, such as local and international travel, room and board. Partners are welcome to use a display table and disseminate promotional materials. Funds will be received under the Dean's office.

Accommodation

If you plan to come to the university, please book your own accommodation at [Paradornparp International House](#) (PIH) on campus or in any private hotels nearby. Feel free to share your

hotel room to split the bill. If you plan to share a double room with a conference participant to reduce your expenses, please contact one another directly through the FB closed group once you will have officially registered. Most hotels provide free breakfast. If you want to be sure, please contact them directly.

Contact Us

For more information, please contact us at

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**Hybrid Second Annual International Conference on
 Religion, Culture, Peace, and Education**
Organized by the Department of Peace Studies
Co-Sponsored by the Consortium for Global Education
Date: 27-28 April 2023

CONFERENCE COMMITTEE

1	Ajarn Apicha Insuwan	Payap University	Advisor
2	Asst. Prof. Dr. Wallapa Songprakun	Payap University	Advisor
3	Asst. Prof. Dr Taien Layraman	Payap University	Advisor
4	Asst. Prof. Dr. Pachara Boontharak	Payap University	Advisor
5	Dr. Rey Ty	Payap University	Chair of committee
6	Assoc. Prof. Dr. Mark Tamthai	Payap University	Member
7	Dr. Le Ngoc Bich Ly	Payap University	Member
8	Dr. Abellia A. Wardani	Payap University	Member
9	Dr. Benya Lertsuwan	Payap University	Member
10	Dr. Kenneth Dobson	Payap University	Member
11	Assist. Prof. Dr. Sakunee Kriangchaiporn	Payap University	Member
12	Ajarn Wutthichula Khunpatwattana	Payap University	Member
13	Ajarn Surachet Wongchomphu	Payap University	Member
14	Dr. Pornnarong Pongklang	Payap University	Member
15	Ms. Tannipa Pongjukta	Payap University	Member & Secretary

International Review Board

No	First Name	Last Name	Institution	Location
1.	Assoc. Prof. Dr Flavius Floris	Andries	Christian State Institute of Ambon	Indonesia
2.	Dr Iva	Angelova	New Jersey Enrichment Academy	U.S.A.
3.	Dr Hope	Antone	United Board for Christian Higher Education in Asia	Hong Kong SAR, China
4.	Assist. Prof. Dr Shajini Judith Diana J	Ashok	Women's Christian College	India
5.	Dr Rungrawee	Chalermripinyorat	Prince of Songkla University	Thailand

6.	Dr Jeanny	Dhewayani	Duta Wacana Christian University	Indonesia
7.	Dr Ken	Dobson	Payap University	Thailand
8.	Prof. Dr Eleazar	Fernandez	Union Theological Seminary,	Philippines
9.	Assoc. Prof. Mneesha	Gellman	Emerson College	U.S.A.
10.	Dr Phill	Gittins	World beyond War	U.S.A.
11.	Assist Prof Dr Sanchita	Ghosh	West Bengal State University	India
12.	Dr Tammy	Holmes	Prairie View A&M University	U.S.A.
13.	Prof. Dr Iqbal	Hossain	Islamic University,	Bangladesh
14.	Dr Johnathan	Jodamus	University of the Western Cape (UWC)	South Africa
15.	Assoc. Prof. Dr Lily	Kadoe	Myanmar Institute of Theology	Myanmar
16.	Dr Ngoc Bich Ly	Le	Payap University	Thailand
17.	Dr Anthony	Le Duc	Saengtham College	Thailand
18.	Dr Benya	Letsuwan	Payap University	Thailand
19.	Assist. Prof. Dr Staci	Martin	Portland State University	U.S.A.
20.	Assis. Prof. Dr Sanjana Sharma	Marwaha	Amity University Uttar Pradesh, India	India
21.	Assist. Prof. Dr Shameer	Modongal	University of Kerala	India
22.	Prof. Dr Jeffrey	Moore	Anderson University	U.S.A.
23.	Assist. Prof. Dr Obasesam	Okoi	University of St Thomas	U.S.A.
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26.	Dr Buenafe	Quillope	Notre Dame of Marbel University	Philippines
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30.	Dr Nabyendu	Roy Choudhury	Banaras Hindu University	India
31.	Dr Lee-Shae Salma	Scharnick- Udemans	University of the Western Cape	South Africa
32.	Assist. Prof. Dr Rafał	Śpiewak	University of Economy in Bydgoszcz	Poland

33.	Assist. Prof. Dr Cynthia	Stevens	Lewis University	U.S.A.
34.	Dr Alfred	Taboada	STI College Cotabato / Notre Dame University	Philippines
35.	Assoc. Prof. Dr Mark	Tamthai	Payap University	Thailand
36.	Dr Rey	Ty	Payap University	Thailand
37.	Dr Maria	Vetter	Northern Illinois University Alumna Independent Researcher	U.S.A.
38.	Dr Abellia Anggi	Wardani	Payap University	Thailand
39.	Prof. Dr Tony	Waters	Leuphana Universität Lüneburg	Germany

Session Chair

Ref/ Profiles	Names	Institutions	Countries	Frequency
1.	Arnøy, Joakim	Narvik War & Peace Centre // Centre for Peace Studies, UiT - Norway's Arctic University	Norway	1
2.	Angelova, Iva	Freelance	U.S.A. Bulgaria	1
3.	Anwar, Iyad Febrian	Center for Social Integrity	Myanmar Indonesia	1
4.	Bakshi, Progoti Chetana	Tripura University	India	Multiple
5.	Battioui, Abdedaim	Duke University - Duke UNC Rotary Peace Center	U.S.A. Morocco	1
6.	Chris Aimee Osamudiamen	Nigeria Institute of Leather and Science Technology Zaria	Nigeria	1
7.	Chakhesang, Kushelu	Payap University	Thailand India	1
8.	Franco, Alexander	Payap University	Thailand U.S.A.	Multiple
9.	Gadi, Jarken	Gokhale Institute of Politics and Economics Pune	India	1
10.	Gittins, Phill	World Beyond War	U.S.A. U.K.	1
11.	Hamonangan, Ranto	Huria Kristen Batak Protestan (HKBP). Universitas Kristen Duta Wacana (UKDW)	Indonesia	1
12.	Jadhav, Ravindra	K.J. Somaiya College of Arts, Commerce and Science, Kopergaon	India	1
13.	Kaur, Navdeep	Department of Education, Guru Nanak Dev. University, Amritsar	India	1
14.	Kumar, Shiv	Tripura University	India	1

		Surymaninagar Agartala		
15.	Le Ngoc Bich Ly	Payap University	Thailand Vietnam	1
16.	Lynn Saw Than Htut	Payap University	Thailand Myanmar	1
17.	Nasiru Bello Mohammed	FCE GOMBE	Nigeria	1
18.	Owczarek, Karolina	Adam Mickiewicz University	Poland	1
19.	Paguio, Job	Bataan Peninsula State University	Philippines	Multiple
20.	Prakash, Rochelle	Madras Christian College, Chennai	India	Multiple
21.	Pulamau, Lucy Herlina	Eden Theological Seminary	U.S.A. Indonesia	1
22.	Quiroga, Sergio Ricardo	ICAES	Argentina	1
23.	Rajarithnam, Belinda	Madras Christian College	India	Multiple
24.	Rak, Joanna	Adam Mickiewicz University, Poznań	Poland	1
25.	Rogers, Steven	Freelance	U.S.A.	Multiple
26.	Roy Choudhury, Nabyendu	Independent Researcher	India	1
27.	Ruiz, Alma	Payap University	Thailand Philippines	1
28.	Sain, Zohaib Hassan	Superior University	Pakistan	Multiple
29.	Scharnick-Udemans, Lee-Shae Salma	Desmond Tutu Centre for Religion and Social Justice, University of the Western Cape	South Africa	Multiple
30.	Taboada, Alfred	STI College Cotabato	Philippines	Multiple
31.	Tamrat, Sisaye	Bahir Dar University	Ethiopia	1
32.	Ty, Rey	Payap University	Thailand	Multiple
33.	Vengatesan, Ruthra	Madras Christian College	India	Multiple
34.	Vincent, Baily	Madras Christian College	India	1
35.	Yasin, PP Mohammed	Telhara Data and Development Lab	India	Multiple

2023 Book of Abstracts

Hybrid Second Annual International Conference on Religion, Culture, Peace, and Education

Review Guidelines

1. For your convenience, please review abstract proposals related to your specialization/s only. For instance, if your specialization, please write down your reviews for abstract proposals related to education only. Skip all other abstracts. However, you are optionally most welcome to review other submissions as well, if you have time.

2. Criteria for review:

a. In general, submissions must not be simply descriptive only as such, but must explicitly identify a problem that the author will address.

b. In particular: Clarity of the Use of Words | Problem Statement | Purpose | Methodology | Evidence; Logical Coherence (the whole abstract consistently deals with the same variables or factors; nothing off tangent). Here's an extreme example: If the title deals with religion only, but the research problem deals with education only, the findings deal with culture only, and the conclusion deals with sustainable development only, then the abstract is not logically coherent.

c. Original Contribution; Relationship to the literature; and Writing Convention (grammar, spelling...).

d. Please indicate that "all caps for all words" are not allowed: please rewrite conforming to standard writing style." In the meantime, please provide constructive feedback to the contents of the abstract.

e. The title must have 15 words maximum only.

f. Note that some papers are still in progress; thus, authors are allowed to say the research is still in progress.

g. For entries which are too long, please put such remarks as: "The abstract submission is too long. Please condense your abstract to 200 words total or less" or "Limit your answers to one sentence per item." "Write your longer answers in the full paper."

h. The first time an acronym is used must be accompanied by spelling of the words in full.

i. When authors identify very specific locations, they must identify the country, as we cannot assume all readers know where they are located.

j. Ask authors who wrote very generic key words such as "role," "experience," etc. to delete them and replace them with specific academic concepts.

k. Literature review materials could be theories or background materials: thus, if authors already give the definitions of terms or actual findings of the paper in the "literature review" section, please alert them to revise their answers and give constructive feedback.

Bibliographic entries written as literature review are not acceptable: Please advise authors to include concept, themes, or theories in the literature review.

l. Website links are not allowed in the Abstract

m. In the "Problem" section, the author must identify a theoretical or empirical problem that the paper will address. It could be a gap the paper will fill. A research question is NOT a

problem. When authors write about solutions only in the “Problem” section, that means they did not identify the problem yet; they assume we know the problem. Remind them to delete and change their answers and identify concisely the problem.

3. For “Purpose of the Study,” authors could choose to write Purpose, Research Questions, Qualitative Thesis, or Quantitative Hypothesis

4. Here are your possible decisions. Please inform authors to incorporate revisions in their full papers.

a. “Accept without Revision:” Additional comments are optional

b. “Accept with Minor Revision:” Please give constructive feedback

c. “Accept with Major Revision:” Please provide detailed constructive feedback

d. “Reject:” Please explain in detail the reasons for which the paper was rejected

e. First, please try to save abstracts by providing constructive feedback. Only when an abstract proposal is hopelessly useful should you, as a last resort, reject the abstract proposal with a detailed explanation.

f. Do not hesitate to reject outrightly nonsense abstracts of authors who clearly have no clue what they are writing.

5. Authors for “Poster Session” only submit a short essay related to the Conference and will only give presentations but neither abstracts nor full papers. No need for acceptance or rejection, as long as the titles are relevant to the Conference.

6. You can also go back to the online review form to add or revise your reviews.

7. If you have submitted an abstract proposal, please do not review your own submission.

8. Thank you for your generous help and kind compliance.

Abstract Submissions: Authors, Titles, and Countries

Info /Ref	Author	Title	Country of Institution Citizenship Residence
1.	Anand, Amit	Women Empowerment in India	India
2.	Angelova, Iva	Bulgarian Immigrants' Educational Experiences in U.S. Higher Education	U.S.A. Bulgaria
3.	Anwar, Riyad Febrian	Environmental Consequences of Myanmar Coup on Karen's Forest and Nature Reserves: Violence Monitoring Perspective	Myanmar Indonesia
4.	Aung, Myint Myint	The Psychotherapeutic Value of Abhidhamma Teachings: An Analysis of Emotional Conflict	Singapore Myanmar
5.	BAKSHI, PROGOTI CHETANA	The Tantric Elements in Vaishnav Religion and Literature	India
6.	Battioui, Abdedaim	Natural Resources in the Context of International Conflict and Cooperation	U.S.A. Morocco
7.	Arnøy, Joakim	Looking at the European Youth Programme Erasmus + with a Critical Peace Education Lens	Norway
8.	Benu, Yuliana Magdalena	The Silent Hagar: A Feminist Intersectional Perspective on the Biblical Narrative of Hagar in Genesis 16:1-16 Reflecting the Context of Women Migrant Workers	Indonesia
9.	Chakhesang, Kushelu	Impact of Religious Institution in Peacebuilding: The Role of the Naga Shisha Hoho in the Formation of the Forum for Naga Reconciliation (FNR)	Thailand India
10.	Chng, Kin Noi	A Local Voice: Life Experiences and Reflections of a Woman Human Rights Defender in Thailand	Thailand Singapore
11.	Chris, Aimee Osamudiamen	Socioeconomic and Cultural determinants of Family Planning Services Use among Women in Northern Nigerian	Nigeria
12.	Faustin, Britney Belinda, R	Casteism in India - Conflicts	India
13.	Franco, Alexander	Cultural Factors Behind Thailand's Declining Birth Rate	Thailand U.S.A.
14.	Gadi, Jarken	Vedanta Philosophy and Harmonious World	India
15.	Ghosh, Rajashri	Devadasi or Indian Temple Prostitution System – A form of Human Trafficking in Disguise	Poland India
16.	Ginting, Bayu Kaesarea	The Traditional Calendar as a Practical Guide of Church Eco- Theology to Address the Issue of Environmental Crisis	Indonesia
17.	Gittins, Phill Proskova, Vanda Frljak, Emina Gilbert-Roberts, Gilbert-Roberts	Improving Intergenerational Dialogue and Action for Peace and Security	U.S.A. U.K. Czech Republic Bosnia and Herzegovina
18.	Hamonangan, Ranto	Padan AS A CONCEPT OF Religious Tolerance	Indonesia

19.	Hendry, Asha Belinda, R	Gender Inequity Associated with Increased Child Abuse and Neglect in Rural Economy	India
20.	Jayanti, Candra Dvi	Post-Religious Conflict Peacebuilding Strategy in Mareje, West Lombok	Indonesia
21.	Jadhav, Ravindra	A Descriptive Study of impact of Festivals on Indian Culture	India
22.	Kaur, Navdeep Rai, Monkia	Role of Culture in Social Development	India
23.	Kauts, Amit	Peace Education and Conflict Handling Mode	India
24.	Komimbin, Alfian Rico	Globalization, Identity Politics and The Ethics of Solidarity: An Indonesia Perspective	Indonesia
25.	Kumar, Shiv	The Vedic Hindu Law and misinterpretation: Its Relevance and Reflection on Modern Hindu Society	
26.	Le Duc, Anthony	Interculturality as a Paradigm to Promote Social and Environmental Flourishing in the Present Milieu	Thailand U.S.A.
27.	Le Ngoc Bich Ly	Enhancing Interreligious Dialogue Competency for Peace: Dealing with Difficult Dialogue from a Buddhist Perspective	Thailand Vietnam
28.	Lertsuwan, Benya	TikTokers and Thai Music Business	Thailand
29.	Lynn Saw Than Htut	Human Rights and Peacebuilding: Addressing the Potential to Incorporate the Different Perspectives	Thailand Myanmar
30.	Lwin, Moe Thida	Buddha's Teaching Approach to Peace	Thailand Myanmar Australia
31.	Makuba, Elvira Hubertina	The Role of The Evangelical Christian Church in Papua Land, To Achieve SDGs No Poverty in Papua Province	Indonesia
32.	Martin, Staci Thongsan, Nuchsara	International Exchanges: Impacting Research and Teaching	U.S.A. Thailand
33.	Nasiru Bello Mohammed Ahmed, Ibrahim Shehu, Ali	Evaluation of functionality, adequacy and electrical lecturers' preparedness in utilization of multimedia micro teaching laboratories constructed by TET Fund in colleges of education in northern Nigeria	Nigeria
34.	NUÑEZ, RACHEL ANNE TABOADA, ALFRED FERNANDEZ HAROLD LUMIBAO MARK ANTHONY	Clan Feud: Its Impact to the Academic Performance of Tertiary Students in Cotabato City	Philippines
35.	Owczarek, Karolina	Becoming violent: case study of anti-COVID protest in February 2021 in Dublin	Poland
36.	Ogunsakin, Oluwasegun	THE NEXUS BETWEEN Religious Tolerance AND Peaceful Coexistence IN DEMOCRATIC NIGERIA	Nigeria
37.	Ottenhof, Robert	Jesus' Principles for Peace and Intractable Conflicts	Thailand Netherlands

38.	Paguio, Job	Mapping and Preserving the Cultural Properties of Balanga City, Philippines	Philippines
39.	Patagani, Andrea Catel, Bonyang Caturas, Vicky Diesto, Frenzel	The Experience of Social Exclusion of People with Psychosocial Disability	Philippines
40.	Philips, Akhila Belinda, R	Post Traumatic Effects and Mental Health of Trafficked Children	India
41.	Prakash, Rochelle	Building Sustainable Peace between Migrants and the State in India: Exploring SDG Development Strategies	India
42.	Pulamaui, Lucy Herlina	Working Together and Seeking for Harmony and Integration of Creation	U.S.A. Indonesia
43.	Quiroga, Sergio Ricardo	Reimagining the World, Reimagining Internet towards Global Citizenship	Argentina
44.	Rajarithnam, Belinda	The Role of Service Learning in building Inner Peace in Students	India
45.	Rak, Joanna	Epistemic Injustice in Protest Policing Online: The Case Study of the Polish Women's Strike	Poland
46.	Rezmer-Płotka, Kamila	The Consequences of Partisan Policing for the Development of Civil Disorder: Between Justice and Injustice during the Protests of Business Owners in Pandemic-ridden Poland	Poland
47.	Rogers, Steven	How Afghanistan University Women' Motivations to Succeed Mirror's Their Disabled American Lecturer's Need to Succeed and Thrive	U.S.A.
48.	Roy Choudhury, Nabyendu	Esoteric Elements as Ascribed in Buddhist Charyapada in India	India
49.	Ruiz, Alma	The Challenges and Opportunities for Interfaith Dialogue as Peacebuilding	Thailand Philippines
50.	Ruttanasatain, Ngamsuk	Everyday Peace Discourse from the Scholar Perspectives	Thailand
51.	Sain, Zohaib Hassan	Challenges Faced in Online Education and Learning in Pakistan during Covid-19 Pandemic	Pakistan
52.	Scharnick-Udemans, Lee-Shae Salma	Mediated and Mediated Expressions of Religious Diversity in South Africa	South Africa
53.	Shah, Sama	Marginalizing the Faithful: The Assad Regime's Use of War on Terror Language to Suppress Religious Dissent in the Syrian Civil War	U.S.A. Pakistan
54.	Sindra Ribeiro, Laise	Child Marriage among Muslims in Thailand	Thailand Brazil
55.	Soe, Aung Mya	Exploring Livelihoods under Protracted Displacement: A Case Study of Internally Displaced Persons in Kachin State.	Thailand Myanmar
56.	Śpiewak, Rafał Seroka, Aleksandra Demirel, Mustafa	Sustainable Development Goals in European and Polish Transport Policy	Poland Poland Turkey
57.	Tamrat, Sisaye	Reversing Community Relationship from the I-It to I-Thou as a tool for Peace Building in	Ethiopia

		Ethiopia: The Role of Youth Participation in National Dialogue	
58.	Thang, Min	The 2021 Military Coup in Myanmar: Religious Response	Myanmar
59.	Ty, Rey	Political Culture and Clashing Narratives in the Ukraine identity politics	Thailand
60.	Ummah, Syifaul	The Implementation of Peace Education in English for Guidance and Counseling Teacher Candidates	Indonesia
61.	Vengatesan, Ruthra Rajarathnam, Belinda	A Study on the Role of Life Skills Education among School Students in Building Peace	India
62.	Vincent, Baily	Social Work Education: An instrument for Conflict Resolution and Peace Building	India
63.	Wardani, Abellia Anggi	Understanding Rohingya Refugees Journey to and from the Refugee camps in Bangladesh	Thailand Indonesia
64.	Yasin, PP Mohammed	Communal Tension and Social Cohesion in India: Pathways for Positive Praxis	India
65.	Ying Ting	Explicating Reinhold Niebuhr's Christian Realism in Myanmar's Rakhine-Rohingya Conflict	Myanmar
66.	YUSOPH, RAIHAN	Guns Don't Kill Gun-Culture Does: A Case Study on the Proliferation of Firearms in Lanao del Sur	Philippines
67.	Zabala, Kenth John VALENCIA, EULYNNE CHESKA G. CRUZ, AARON ANGELO G. MUNGICAL, JAY R. DE JESUS, JAYCOB V., VALENCIA, EULYNNE CHESKA G. HERNANDEZ, HANNAH B.	FROM Theory to Practice: EXAMINING THE Pedagogical CONTENT Knowledge IN World History OF Pre-Service Teachers PRIOR TO AND DURING Field Study Immersion	Philippines
68.	Zulfa, Umi	Implementation of Peace and Gender Education Values of University Management	Indonesia

PROGRAM SCHEDULE

Hybrid Second Annual International Conference on
 Religion, Culture, and Peace Education

Department of Peace Studies (DPS)

Religion, Culture, and Peace Laboratory (RCP Lab)

International College, Payap University

In Cooperation with

Mennonite Central Committee (MCC)

Consortium for Global Education (CGE)

Consortium for Global Education (CGE) Research Institute (RI)

Conference Room, Sirindhorn Learning Resource Center

Payap University, Chiang Mai, Mae Khao Main Campus, Thailand

Thursday-Friday, April 27-28, 2022, from 9 AM to 6 PM Bangkok Time

Zoom:

<https://us02web.zoom.us/j/89590375179?pwd=cHJVdW9GdjRCRHZotXFJTzdFMkZsUT09>

Meeting ID: 895 9037 5179, Passcode: 54321

Facebook Closed Group: <https://www.facebook.com/groups/1649246688756722>

Facebook Livestreaming Simulcast: <https://www.facebook.com/pyuircp>

Day 1: Thursday, April 27, 2023, 8:30 am to 6 pm Bangkok Time

8:30-9 am	<p>-Onsite Registration and Online Sign In</p> <p>-For mutual respect: Kindly have a formal profile photo in your videocam as well as turn on your videocam with your name and country, please. Please use Payap logos as your video background image.</p> <p>-Kindly pick up your refreshments now. No break in the morning. Thank you.</p>
9-9:30 am	<p>Session 1</p> <p>Opening Ceremonies. Mandatory Session for Registered Paper Presenters</p>
Thai Welcome Dance:	CCI Payap University
Opening Remarks:	<p>-Dr Apicha Insuwan, President, Payap University</p> <p>-Assist. Prof. Dr Wallapa Songprakun, Vice-President of Academic Affairs, Payap University</p> <p>-Asst. Prof. Dr Taien Layraman, Assistant to the President (International Affairs), Payap University</p> <p>-Assist. Prof. Dr Phatchara Boonteerarak, Dean, International College, Payap University</p> <p>-Dr Le Ngoc Bich Ly, Acting Chair, Department of Peace Studies, Payap University</p>
Co-Sponsors:	-Phyllis & Arthur Mann , Mennonite Central Committee, Area Directors for Southeast and Northeast Asia.

	<p>- Represented by Adam and Sarah Sesamaust, MCC Area Directors for Central and Southern Asia</p> <p>-Dr Carolyn Bishop, Consortium for Global Education</p> <p>-Prof. Dr Jeffrey Moore, Consortium for Global Education Research Institute</p>
Emcee & Logistics:	Dr R. Ty, Conference Chair
9:30-10 am	<p>Keynote Speaker 1: Assoc. Prof. Dr Mark Tamthai Department of Peace Studies, Payap University, Chiang Mai, Thailand “Peacebuilders as Passionate and Compassionate Disruptors” Mandatory Session for Registered Paper Presenters</p>
No Break	<p>Online and Onsite Group Photos Please Grab Your Refreshments and Return Next Session Resumes Immediately.</p>
10-11 am	<p>Session 2 Co-Chairs: Dr Ken Dobson (Moderator) and Kushelu Chakhesang (Time Manager)</p> <p>-31 Dr Angelova, Iva. (U.S.A.). Bulgarian Immigrants’ Educational Experiences in U.S. Higher Education</p> <p>-30 Rogers, Steven. (U.S.A.). How Feminist and Disability Theory Relate: A Case Study of Afghan Women and a U.S. Lecturer</p> <p>-2 Quiroga, Sergio Ricardo. (Argentina). Reimagining the world, reimagining Internet towards global citizenship</p> <p>-14 Dr Martin, Staci (U.S.A.); & Thongsan, Nuhsara. (Thailand). International Exchanges: Impacting Research and Teaching</p> <p>-28 Shah, Sana. (U.S.A.). Marginalizing the Faithful: The Assad Regime's Use of War on Terror Language to Suppress Religious Dissent in the Syrian Civil War</p> <p>-9 Battioui, Abdedaim. (Morocco). Energy, International Cooperation, and Sustainable Peace Nexus: A Case Study of Morocco</p>
11am-12 noon	<p>Session 3 Co-Chairs: Dr Ravindra Jadhav (Moderator) and Iyad Febrian Anwar (Time Manager)</p> <p>-5 Dr Ty, R.2 Political Culture and Clashing Narratives in the Ukraine Identity Politics</p> <p>-10 Rev. Dr Le Duc, Anthony. (U.S.A.; in Thailand). Interculturality as a Paradigm to Promote Social and Environmental Flourishing in the Present Milieu</p> <p>- 73 Dr Wardani, Abellia Anggi. (Indonesia); & Shahpur, Tengku. Understanding Rohingya refugees’ journey to and from the refugee camps in Bangladesh</p> <p>-1 Thang, Min. (Myanmar). The 2021 Military Coup in Myanmar: Religious Response</p> <p>-17 Lwin, Moe Thida. (Australia). Buddha’s Teaching Approach to Peace</p> <p>-35 Chng, Kin Noi. (Singapore). A Local Voice: Life Experiences and Reflections of a Woman Human Rights Defender in Thailand</p>
12-1 pm	Lunch Break
1-2 pm	<p>Session 4 Co-Chairs: Ranto Hamonangan (Moderator) and Jarken Gadi (Time Manager)</p> <p>-8 Dr. Scharnick-Udemans, Lee-Shae Salma. (South Africa). Mediated and Mediated Expressions of Religious Diversity in South Africa</p>

	<p>-4 Dr Le Ngoc Bich Ly (Vietnam; in Thailand). “Enhancing Interreligious Dialogue Competency for Peace: Dealing with Difficult Dialogue from a Buddhist Perspective”</p> <p>-46 Aung, Myint Myint. (Myanmar; in Singapore). The Psychotherapeutic Value of Abhidhamma Teachings: An Analysis of Emotional Conflict</p> <p>-58 BAKSHI, PROGOTI CHETANA. (India). The Tantric Elements in Vaishnav Religion and Literature</p> <p>-21 Dr Lertsuwan, Benya; & -74 Paprach, Thapthep. (Thailand). Impact of TikTok as the form of UGC on Thai music Industry during COVID-19 pandemic</p> <p>-11 Paguio, Job. (Philippines). Mapping and Preserving the Cultural Properties of Balanga City, Philippines</p>
2-230 pm	<p>Session 5</p> <p>Keynote Speaker 2: Dr Tejendra Pherali Professor of Education, Conflict and Peace at IOE, UCL’s Faculty of Education and Society, University College London, U.K. “Education, Conflict, and Peace” Mandatory Session for Registered Paper Presenters</p>
2:30-3 pm	Refreshments
3-4 pm	<p>Session 6</p> <p>Co-Chairs: Karolina Owczarek (Moderator) and Baily Vincent (Time Manager)</p> <p>-25 Dr Rak, Joanna. (Poland). Epistemic Injustice in Protest Policing Online: The Case Study of the Polish Women’s Strike</p> <p>-20 Dr Ty, R. Divergent Perspectives of Social Justice and Peace</p> <p>- 63 Ruiz, Alma. (Philippines). The Possibilities and Challenges of Interfaith Dialogue for Peacebuilding by the Faith Practitioners in Mindanao Philippines</p> <p>-6 Lynn, Saw Than Htut (Myanmar). Human Rights and Peacebuilding: Addressing the Potential to synthesize these two contending Perspectives</p> <p>-15 Chris, Aimee Osamudiamen. (Nigeria). Socioeconomic and cultural determinants of family planning services use among women in northern Nigerian</p> <p>- 69 Prakash, Rochelle. (India). Building Sustainable Peace between the Indian Internal Migrant Labor and the State of India: Exploring SDG Development Strategies</p>
4-5 pm	<p>Session 7</p> <p>Co-Chairs: Dr Joanna Rak (Moderator) and Lynn Saw Than Htut (Time Manager)</p> <p>-26 Benu, Yuliana Magdalena. (Indonesia). The Silent Hagar: A Feminist Intersectional Perspective on the Biblical Narrative of Hagar in Genesis 16:1-16 Reflecting the Context of Women Migrant Workers</p> <p>-27 Anwar Riyad Febrian. (Indonesia). Environmental Consequences of Myanmar Coup on Karen’s Forest and Nature Reserves: Violence Monitoring Perspective</p> <p>-13 Rev. Hamonangan, Ranto. (Indonesia). Padan as a Concept of Religious Tolerance</p> <p>- 41 Ruttanasatain, Ngamsuk. (Thailand). Everyday Peace Theories, Concepts and Application to the DeepSouth Conflict of Thailand</p> <p>-22 Ginting, Bayu Kaesarea. (Indonesia). The Karo Batak Traditional Calendar as a Practical Guide of Church Eco-theology: The Case of Karo Batak Protestant Church (GBKP) in Indonesia</p> <p>-29 Vincent, Baily. (India). Social Work Education: An instrument for Conflict Resolution and Peace Building</p>
5-6 pm	Session 8

	<p>Co-Chairs: Dr Alfred Taboada (Moderator) and Sisaye Tamrat (Time Manager)</p> <p>-32 NUÑEZ, RACHEL ANNE. TABOAD ALFRED; FERNANDEZ HAROLD; LUMIBAO MARK ANTHONY. (PHILIPPINES). Clan Feud: Its Impact to the Academic Performance of Tertiary Students in Cotabato City</p> <p>-33 Dr Ottenhof, Robert. (Netherlands; in Thailand). Jesus’ Principles for Peace and Intractable Conflicts</p> <p>-34 Jayanti, Candra Dvi. (Indonesia). Post-Religious Conflict Peacebuilding Strategy in Mareje, West Lombok, Indonesia</p> <p>-36 Gadi, Jarken, & Abhyankar Aashay (India). Vedanta philosophy and harmonious world</p> <p>-37 Patagani, Andrea; Catel, Bonyang; Caturas, Vicky; & Diesto, Frenzel. (Philippines). The Experience of Social Exclusion of People with Psychosocial Disability</p> <p>-16 Dr Nasiru Bello Mohammed. Ali Shehu. (Nigeria). Evaluation of functionality, adequacy and electrical lecturers’ preparedness in utilization of multimedia micro teaching laboratories constructed by TET Fund in colleges of education in northern Nigeria</p>
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Day 2: Friday, April 28, 2023, 8:30 am to 6 pm Bangkok Time

8:30-9 am	<p>Onsite Registration and Online Sign In</p> <p>For mutual respect: Kindly have a formal profile photo in your videocam as well as turn on your videocam with your name and country, please. Please use Payap logos as your video background image. Thank you.</p>
9-930 am	<p>Session 9</p> <p>Keynote Speech 3: Dr. Edward J. Brantmeier Professor in the Learning, Technology, and Leadership Education Department at James Madison University, U.S.A. “Spirituality, Religion, and Peace Education: Toward an Integrated Spirituality for Peace” Mandatory Session for Registered Paper Presenters</p>
9:30-10 am	Refreshments
10 am -11am	<p>Session 10</p> <p>Co-Chairs: Dr Iva Angelova (Moderator) and Steven Rogers (Time Manager)</p> <p>-7 Sindra Ribeiro, Laise. (Brazil; in Thailand). Child Marriage among Muslims in Thailand</p> <p>- 53 Pulamau, Lucy Herlina. (Indonesia. In the U.S.A.). Working Together and Seeking for Harmony and Integration of Creation</p> <p>- 39 Roy Choudhury, Nabyendu. (India). Esoteric Elements as Ascribed in Buddhist Charyapada in India</p> <p>- 40 Yasin, PP Mohammed. (India). Communal Tension and Social Cohesion in India: Pathways for Positive Praxis</p> <p>- 42 Komimbini, Alfian Rico. (Indonesia). Globalization, Identity Politics and The Ethics of Solidarity: An Indonesia Perspective</p> <p>- 43 Makuba, Elvira Hubertina. (Indonesia). The Role of The Evangelical Christian Church in Papua Land to Achieve SDGs No Poverty in Papua Province</p>
12 – 1 pm	Lunch Break
1-2 pm	<p>Session 11</p> <p>Co-Chairs: Dr Lee-Shae Salma Scharnick-Udemans (Moderator) and Job Paguio (Time Manager)</p> <p>-44 KUMAR, SHIV. (India). The Vedic Hindu Law and misinterpretation: Its Relevance and Reflection on Modern Hindu Society</p>

	<p>-12 Zabala, Kenth John. (Philippines). From theory to practice: Examining the pedagogical content knowledge in World history of pre-service teachers prior to and During field study immersion</p> <p>-47 Philips, Akhila. (India). Post Traumatic Effects and Mental Health of Trafficked Children</p> <p>-48 Zulfa, Umi. (Indonesia). Implementation of Peace and Gender Education Values of University Management</p> <p>-49 Faustin, Britney. (India). Casteism in India – Conflicts</p> <p>-54 Vengatesan, Ruthra; Rajarathnam, Belinda. (India). A Study on the Role of Life Skills Education among School Students in Building Peace</p>
2-2:30 pm	<p>Session 12 Co-Chairs: Dr Le Ngoc Bich Ly (Moderator) and Ruthra Vengatesan (Time Manager)</p> <p>- 45 Arnøy, Joakim. (Norway). Compatible with critical peace education? A reflexive thematic analysis of the European youth programme Erasmus+</p> <p>-50 Rajarathnam, Belinda. (India). The Role of Service Learning in building Inner Peace in students</p> <p>-51 Hendry, Asha; & Belinda, R. (India). Gender Inequity associated with increased child abuse and neglect in rural economy</p> <p>-52 Ummah, Syifaul. (Indonesia). The Implementation of Peace Education in English for Guidance and Counseling Students of UNUGHA Indonesia</p> <p>-55 Dr Kaur, Navdeep; & Monkia Rai (India). Role of Culture in Social Development</p> <p>-23 Ogunsakin, Oluwasegun. (Nigeria). THE NEXUS BETWEEN RELIGIOUS TOLERANCE AND PEACEFUL CO-EXISTENCE IN DEMOCRATIC NIGERIA</p>
2:30-3:30 pm	<p>Session 13 Co-Chairs: Dr Belinda Rajarathnam (Moderator) and Chris Aimee Osamudiamen (Time Manager)</p> <p>-60 Rezmer-Plotka, Kamila. (Poland). The Consequences of Partisan Policing for the Development of Civil Disorder during the Protests of Business Owners in Pandemic-ridden Poland</p> <p>-38 Ghosh, Rajashri. (India. In Poland). Devadasi or Indian Temple Prostitution System – A form of Human Trafficking in Disguise</p> <p>-59 Owczarek, Karolina. (Poland). Becoming violent: a case study of anti-COVID19 restrictions protest in February 2021 in Dublin (Ireland)</p> <p>-56 Kauts, Amit; & -74 Rohini. (India). Peace education and conflict handling mode</p> <p>-57 Soe, Aung Mya. (Myanmar). Exploring livelihoods under protracted displacement; a case study of internally displaced persons in Kachin state, Myanmar.</p>
3:30-4 pm	Refreshments
4-5 pm	<p>Session 14.1 (4-4:30 pm) Co-Chairs: Dr Phill Gittins (Moderator) and Rochelle Prakash (Time Manager)</p> <p>-66 Sain, Zohaib Hassan (Pakistan). Challenges faced in Online Education & Learning in Pakistan during Covid-19 Pandemic</p> <p>-62 Jadhav, Ravindra. (India). A Descriptive Study of Impact of Festivals on Indian Culture</p> <p>-64 Anand, Amit. (India). Women Empowerment in India</p> <p>Session 14.2 (4:30 – 5 pm) Co-Chairs: Rajashri Ghosh (Moderator) and Zohaib Hassan Sain (Time Keeper)</p>

	<p>-61 Dr Gittins, Phill. (UK). Panel: Improving Intergenerational Dialogue and Action for Peace and Security</p> <p>-65 Proskova, Vanda, (Czech Republic). Panelist.</p> <p>-67 Frljak, Emina (Bosnia and Herzegovina); Panelist.</p> <p>-75 Mpogi Zoe Mafoko. (The Commonwealth Secretariat-South Africa/UK). Panelist.</p>
5-6 pm	<p>Chairs: Dr Abellia Anggi Wardani (Moderator) & Alma Ruiz (Time Manager)</p> <p>-3 Dr Śpiewak, Rafał (Poland); Seroka Aleksandra; & Demirel Mustafa (Turkey). Sustainable Development Goals in European and Polish Transport Policy</p> <p>-18 Demirel, Mustafa. (Turkey); Śpiewak Rafał, (Poland); & Seroka Aleksandra (Poland). Sustainable Development Goals in European and Polish Transport Policy</p> <p>-19 Seroka, Aleksandra (Poland); Dr Śpiewak Rafał (Poland); & Demirel Mustafa (Turkey). Sustainable Development Goals in European and Polish Transport Policy</p> <p>-24 Chakhesang, Kushelu. (India). Impact of Religious Institution in Peacebuilding: The Role of the Naga Shisha Hoho in the Formation of the Forum for Naga Reconciliation (FNR)</p> <p>- 68 Tamrat, Sisaye; Degwale Gebyehu. (Ethiopia). Reversing Community Relationship from the I-It to I-Thou as a tool for Peace Building in Ethiopia: The Role of Youth Participation in National Dialogue</p> <p>- 71 Ying, Ting. (Myanmar). Explaining Reinhold Niebuhr's Christian Realism in Myanmar's Rakhine-Rohingya Conflict</p> <p>- 70 Dr Franco, Alexander. (U.S.A. in Thailand). Cultural Factors Behind Thailand's Declining Birth Rate</p> <p>- 72 YUSOPH, RAIHAN. (Philippines). Guns Don't Kill Gun-Culture Does: A Case Study on the Proliferation of Firearms in Lanao del Sur</p> <p>Closing Speech: Dr Le Ngoc Bich Ly</p> <p>Acknowledgments: Dr R. Ty</p>

Academic Papers

01 – The 2021 Military Coup in Myanmar: Religious Response

Min Thang

Problem Statement: How the 2021 military coup has impact to the life of religious groups in Myanmar?

Purpose of the Study: What are different religious groups responded towards the 2021 military coup in Myanmar. The research will used qualitative research.

Literature or Theory: The paper contributes to recent studied on religious responses especially in regard to their problems and challenges in Myanmar.

Research Methods: This study centers on the author's personal experiences, observation, and book related to articles and online sites.

Summary of Findings: In the beginning of the coup there was activities involvement of religious groups but the following years young people I have not want any religion since the coup. The religious leaders are also becoming silent and the SAC politicized religious to divided and confuse the people of Myanmar.

Conclusion: To provide awareness on socio-political and religious issues in

Myanmar. To understand the situation of local community and political crisis in Myanmar. To provide grounded situation and reasonable hope to the people.

Keywords

1 Coup

2 Covid-19

3 Conflict

4 Religious Response

5 Myanmar

Area: Religion

02 - Reimagining the World, Reimagining Internet towards Global Citizenship

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Introduction

The world is undergoing important changes and education must adapt to them. Nowadays, education faces various challenges, such as globalization, intolerance, individualism, lack of civic commitment and the exclusion of social segments. The persistence of global differences, the need to reimagine education and the threat posed by the invasion of the natural environment of human beings, shows that education is not fulfilling its promise to contribute to forging a better future. In addition, inequalities, the loss of the social and democratic fabric, and the lack of equity and inclusion are problems that must be addressed by education.

Our time is marked by sensitive epochal changes that societies have experienced since the end of the great narratives and the disenchantment of the world. National and international politics are notably faced with problems that transcend geographical borders. Complex difficulties that include climate change, care for the environment, cyber terrorism, global migratory flows, financial instability and the COVID-19 pandemic, among others (Quiroga, 2022a, Quiroga, 2022b)

Crossing state borders in an era of intense global connectivity, these problems mean that disruptions, difficulties and interference in one part of the world are quickly felt in other countries through highly integrated global networks. In the midst of the climate and biodiversity crises, the way we meet and communicate, the natural world and the world we create, is changing (Quiroga, 2022a).

However, there is reason for optimism as we have the greatest access to knowledge and tools that allow us to collaborate with each other like never before. The potential to engage humanity in co-creating better futures has never been greater. Human creativity, the increase in technological capacity, accessibility and connectivity have allowed a proliferation of content, platforms and consumption of digital visual media.

Our times are marked by sensitive epochal changes that societies have experienced since the end of the great narratives and the disenchantment of the world. National and international politics are notably faced with problems that transcend geographical borders. Complex difficulties that include climate change, care for the environment, cyber terrorism, global migratory flows, financial instability and the COVID-19 pandemic, among others. In an era of intense global connectivity, problems spill over and interference in one part of the world is quickly felt in other countries through highly integrated global networks.

The persistence of global differences, the need to reimagine how, what, where and when we learn and the threat posed by the invasion of the natural environment by human beings show that education is not fulfilling its promise to contribute to forging a better future. In addition, inequalities, the loss of the social and democratic fabric, and the lack of an adequate orientation towards equity and inclusion are problems that must be addressed through education. These challenges call for a new approach to sustainable development, education, and global citizenship that take into account the interconnectedness of the world and the need for collaborative efforts to address them.

New Agreements in Education

The report of the International Commission on the Futures of Education (2022) is a global initiative that advocates rethinking how knowledge and learning can shape the future of humanity and the planet. This report is an invitation to think and imagine and must be addressed in communities, countries, schools and educational programs and systems of all kinds around the world. The document suggests the need to generate a new social contract for education that allows facing current and future challenges, and building a fairer, more peaceful and sustainable future for all. According to the International Commission on the Futures of Education, this social contract must be based on respect for human rights, non-discrimination, social justice, respect for life, human dignity and cultural diversity. To achieve this, the report suggests an ethic of care, reciprocity and solidarity, which reinforces education as a public project for the common good.

For this, it is essential to promote quality public education for all children, youth and adults, and to take full advantage of the transformative potential of education as a path to a sustainable collective future. For this, an education that promotes equity, inclusion, democratic participation and lifelong learning is proposed.

The idea of a great agreement, of broad consensus, is potentially beneficial to advance in the transformation of education with a democratic sense, it should focus on the development of skills for the 21st century that allow people to adapt to a constantly changing world and training better teachers. Skill development includes developing critical thinking, problem solving, creativity, collaboration, communication, global citizenship, and digital literacy. In addition, it must address the global challenges facing humanity, include skills for sustainability and environmental management, cultural diversity and peacebuilding. These skills are essential for people to fully participate in society and in the global knowledge economy.

The new social consensus for education must be based on founding principles that promote the right to quality education throughout life and the development of skills for the 21st century. In addition, it must address current and future challenges, such as environmental sustainability, social justice and cultural diversity, and involve citizens in its creation, maintenance and deepening, listening to the voices of all. This requires active and ongoing collaboration between governments, educational institutions, intellectuals, the media, teachers, students and society as a whole.

Societies that expect positive transformations must renew social agreements for education, taking into account the multiple challenges facing today's society, such as social and economic inequalities, climate change, biodiversity loss and disruptive automation technologies. The task of reinforcing education as a public and common good, and involving society in general in public debates on education, is a clear challenge, understanding the importance of organizing education around the principles of cooperation, collaboration and solidarity, and the promotion of the intellectual, social and moral capacities of the students.

Sustainable Development towards Global Citizenship

The adoption of the 2030 Agenda in September 2015, with 17 goals and 169 targets, has been a fundamental milestone in the international context and in the field of democratic multilateralism. An important innovation of this Agenda is that these goals are inextricably linked to social inclusion and good governance as an essential condition for sustainable development (Herrero, Cembra nosy Pascual, 2019).

The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) integrate three dimensions of development: economic, social and environmental, with an integral and indivisible nature, and provide peace and security as novelties. Many states in the global South need international

cooperation in order to implement the SDGs. The principle of "common but differentiated responsibility" is therefore central to the 2030 Agenda (Sanahuja, 2018). One of the most relevant aspects in the 2030 Agenda, focused on the SDGs, is the role that education must play, especially that focused on global citizenship. Goal 4 on education states the following: "Ensure inclusive, equitable and quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all." And in particular, goal 4.7 proposes to guarantee by the year 2030 that students acquire the theoretical and practical knowledge necessary to promote sustainable development through, among others, the following constructs (UNESCO and the Objectives of Development):

- Education for sustainable development and the adoption of sustainable lifestyles.
- Human rights.
- Gender equality.
- The promotion of a culture of peace and non-violence.
- Global citizenship.
- Valuation of cultural diversity and the contribution of culture to sustainable development.

SDG target 4 recognizes the central role of education in promoting sustainable development, and target 4.7 in particular highlights the importance of education for sustainable development and global citizenship. By incorporating these constructs into the education system, we can ensure that future generations are equipped with the knowledge and skills to address global challenges such as climate change, poverty, inequality, and conflict.

Citizenship

Global citizenship is a concept that refers to the ability of individuals to act globally and be responsible for actions that have an impact on the world. This term has been used by international organizations such as the OECD and UNESCO and refers to religious, philosophical, moral and political traditions that have advocated for a universalism that promotes human rights and justice in the world (UNESCO and the Objectives of Development). Citizenship in the 21st century is linked to a commitment to the environment in which we operate, that is, to a certain degree of awareness of what is happening around us and which should drive us to search for specific solutions (Pérez Martell, 2019).

In the current context of globalization, global citizenship has been incorporated into the educational curricula and educational goals of school systems in many countries. Development NGOs have played a crucial role in promoting development education and global citizenship with a focus on ethical and political education to transform the world. Global citizenship is a concept that seeks to promote the responsibility and commitment of individuals in the world, and its incorporation into education is essential to train citizens who are committed and aware of their actions at a global level (Quiroga, 2022a). The NGOs propose a new perspective on this Education for Development. They consider that it should be transformed into what they call Education for Global Citizenship (EGC). This new conception allows a better understanding of globalization and its effects and focuses more on the ethical and political formation of individuals to engage in the transformation of the world.

Platforms and Internet

The emergence of powerful commercial digital platforms poses multiple challenges for the sustainability of communication media and services that must treat data and information as

a public good. Democracy, sustainable development and respect for human rights and fundamental freedoms, as well as good governance at all levels, are interdependent and mutually reinforcing (Quiroga, 2022). Respect for the rule of law in international and national affairs and the incorporation of policies through mechanisms of Internet governance compatible with democracy, progress towards the improvement of digital literacy, allowing the voices of the civil society and take action. It is also about advancing cultural citizenship renews its contract with society Digital capitalism constitutes a threat to democracy due to several social problems that have arisen with the increase in technology and digitization. These problems include capitalist monopolization of the communication industry, an individualistic and competitive digital culture, the creation of a surveillance industrial complex, the fragmentation of digital public spheres, and the emergence of fake news and post-factual politics in the media. social networks.

The Internet has been consolidated as a set of technologies and means of communication in contemporary media ecology. The interest in accounting for the social implications of its use remains particularly valid in academic activity. Research on the Internet has acquired, since the mid-nineties, notorious academic legitimacy. Currently, there are over five billion Internet users around the world. In our daily lives, not many things may happen in one minute. Nothing might happen in a minute, but when you measure the depth of Internet activity that happens all at once, it can be extraordinary. Currently, there are around five billion Internet users around the world. This annual infographic shows how much activity happens in a given minute and the amount of data users generate. According to the *Digital 2023: global overview report*, the number of Internet users in the world reached 5.160 million people, which represents 64.4% of the world population. The number of Internet users increased by 1.9% compared to 2022, by 98 million people, a slightly lower rate than in previous years. The two regions with the highest internet penetration today are Northern Europe (97.4%) and Western Europe (93.5%), followed by North America (92%). On the other hand, the regions with the lowest internet penetration are Central Africa (27.9%) and Eastern Africa (23.1%). *Digital 2023: global overview report* study shows a detailed graphic on the main reasons for Internet use in the world. Thus, finding information is the main cause with 57.8% of the total, followed by keeping in touch with friends and family (53.7%), and keeping up with events and news (50.9%). In the ranking of countries with the highest Internet penetration, the United Arab Emirates (99%) and Ireland (99%) continue to lead, which share leadership with Norway and Saudi Arabia. They are followed by Switzerland (98.54%) and Denmark (98.1%).

The development of the Internet as a means of communication on a global scale, greatly favored by its public opening and the subsequent increase in the number of service providers at a commercial level, facilitated the expansion of its possibilities of use, and enriched the analysis scenario. of this communication technology. The Internet has been described as a digital space capable of radically transforming society, revitalizing democracy and finally improving the conditions of certain social minorities (Flichy, 2001).

In ***“The Public Service Media and Public Service Internet Manifesto” (2021)*** by Fuchs & Unterberger, K. (Eds), the authors note that these key principles and messages focus on the importance of public service media in a print and digital democracy. that play in the promotion of equity, citizen participation, equality, diversity, and the creation of new content and services. They also recognize the need to adequately support and finance public service media so that they can fulfill their mandate. These principles defend the importance of public service media in a digital democracy and their role in promoting equality, citizen participation, and innovation in the creation of content and services on the Internet. The Manifesto calls for renewing public service media and creating a public Internet service. The

original idea of public service broadcasting originated in Great Britain in the 1920s and was a cornerstone in future waves of democratization. In the year 2021, the world faces a global crisis with disorders of democracy, such as political polarization, the cyber crisis and the impact of digital technologies on reliable information (Fuchs & Unterberger, 2021).

Installing a customer service channel on platforms controlled by digital business giants is not a sufficient option and requires an alternative to current operating procedures and business models. Therefore, this is a call to save and promote democratic communications through the renewal of public service media and the creation of a public Internet service. Rebuilding a public service Internet and rebuilding public media service so that they can respond to the needs of society and individuals means:

- Create a public service Internet that offers accessible, democratic, secure, and non-commercial services that promote diversity, privacy, equity, culture, and the common good.
- Strengthen and fund public service media to ensure that they cover the costs of producing high-quality, research-based content, and to ensure that it is available to all.
- Establish a regulatory framework that protects freedom of expression and privacy on the Internet, and that promotes an equitable distribution of wealth and power.
- Establish a mechanism for supervision and regulation of commercial Internet platforms to ensure that they comply with democratic norms and standards.

The vision of a public Internet service is a call to action. It is time to work together to create an Internet that respects the rights of citizens and is a space for connection, exchange and participation. An Internet that promotes democracy, the public sphere and active citizenship, and that allows users and civil society to contribute to the development and progress of society.

Consideration should be given to incorporating measures to incorporate democratic principles and respect for human rights on the way to Internet governance, while acknowledging the diversity caused by a multicentric world on the way to global citizenship. Public Internet service platforms should promote equity, democracy, participation, dialogue and promote participation on the Internet, civic imagination is necessary.

A civic imagination (Jenkins, Peters-Lazaro, & Shresthova, 2020) understood as the ability to imagine alternatives to current cultural, social, political or economic conditions requires and is achieved through the ability to imagine the process of change, of see yourself as a civic agent capable of making change, of empathizing with others whose perspectives and experiences are different from your own, of joining a larger collective with shared interests, and of bringing imaginative dimensions to real-world spaces and places (Jenkins et al, 2020).

The idea of "civic imagination" of Jenkins and other authors (2020) can be taken as a tool for change and social transformation, fostered by popular cultures to use them in the establishment and mold of political claims. In the essay, Jenkins, Peters-Lazaro, and Shresthova, (2020) define civic imagination as the ability to imagine alternatives to existing cultural, social, and economic conditions, and stress the importance of the individual recognizing himself as a civic agent. capable of making changes in society, of being open and showing solidarity with other perspectives and grouping together in groups that share the same interests.

On the other hand, the use of the term "civic" attempts to express the political dimension of the concept, since it implies a commitment to public life. With this presumption, the authors open the conversation, and put into dialogue a series of ideas such as 'political imagination',

'radical imagination', 'creative insurgency' or 'public fantasy' and claim the need for utopias. Interesting terms to propose and retrace the idea of a development of civic culture.

The challenges raised illustrate the extent, complexity and attention that governments and citizens must pay to current problems. An agenda loaded with challenges, inequalities, inequities, gaps, also made up of communication-technology-citizenship-climate change issues that will accompany humanity in the next fifty years.

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03 - Sustainable Development Goals in European and Polish Transport Policy

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Abstract

In 2015, the United Nations' 193 member states adopted the "2030 Agenda", which established 17 major sustainable development goals. Several steps have been taken to accomplish these objectives, including by the European Union and its member countries. The rate and techniques of achieving the sustainable development objectives differ between countries based on their economic development level. The transportation industry, along with the power sector, is one of the fields with the biggest environmental impact. This material confirms the standards for executing the EU's transport policy and that of Poland (as a member state). Two leading models in this area have been identified and their positives and negatives assessed. The study also assessed the correspondence between Poland's transport policy and the EU's objectives. The findings of this analysis offer the major factors that influence the changes in the way transport operates.

Sustainable development goals

In 2015, the United Nations' 193 member states unanimously agreed to a resolution known as "Transforming our world: The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development." This resolution established Agenda 2030, a strategy for global progress and success over the next decade and a half that consists of 17 Sustainable Development Goals. These objectives are all interrelated.

The two most prominent objectives of the 2030 Agenda (1 and 2) are the abolishment of poverty and hunger on a global level. The achievement of these goals in the limited time span of the next dozen years or so appears to be inconceivable. These conditions will only be able to be permanently wiped out in the course of several generations, requiring a long period of time to generate a modern service and production capacity in the countries in question, taking into consideration the objectives 8 and 9 of the 2030 Agenda. This is referred to as a pledge of employment and consequent assurance of adequate wages and incomes (per capita). This should reduce disparities in society (goal 10) with support targeted at the most deprived groups. To construct a modern service and production capacity in the given countries requires substantial funds and a long period of time for education and training of the highly qualified personnel indispensable for the operation of the economy, which is a provision of the 2030 Agenda - target 4 - growth of high-level education. The successful transition of the Polish economy in 1989, which was in part due to their highly skilled workforce, is evidence of how beneficial this factor is. The 2030 Agenda outlines two goals, 6 and 7, which focus on providing a minimum quality of life, such as access to clean water, sanitation, and affordable energy. This is a costly endeavor, and is nearly impossible to achieve in areas affected by long-term wars and conflicts, like in the Middle East, Asia, Africa, and South America.

How long-term these investments are can be proved, for example, by the Polish realities.

In spite of the aggressive development of water and sewage systems, especially since 2004, there is still a need for further expansion, particularly in rural areas. The same applies for the new energy sources, such as renewable energy, which are still in the early stages of being adopted, even in nations that are more prosperous, like Poland. Poor countries are likely to cling to their traditional energy sources, such as wood and coal, because of their affordability, which is also the case in Poland.

The 2030 Agenda's 12th goal assumes the implementation of sustainable consumption and production, which will take much longer to accomplish. This means lessening the speed of production of goods, making them more modern, and taking over the market. Without regulation from the government and the development of eco-friendly consumer behavior, this goal is unattainable. Doing so will result in more energy usage, environmental degradation, and more waste production.

Achieving an excellent standard of living necessitates the consumption of optimally and the safeguarding of health (goal 3) and the provision of suitable (sustainable) conditions in bustling cities and rural towns (goal 11). This is a costly challenge that may be impossible to conquer. Decreasing urban conglomeration (often with no foliage or parks) and eliminating vast slums in certain megalopolises, e.g. India, is also not a feasible option. As regards healthcare, the primary issue is the persistent growth in costs of treatment due to the utilization of modern, pricey apparatus and medications.

The governing body of an individual nation is usually powerless to counter the expensive costs of medications created by international private companies. These businesses are profit-driven, so their primary aim is to produce treatments that treat the symptoms, rather than the root of the disease. This is because, in the end, a deceased individual or a healthy

one will not be in a position to buy the medicine created by either company, making them unprofitable. Consequently, human health is a secondary priority.

This has even more serious implications. In numerous developed countries, natural medicine has been replaced by conventional medicine. In medical training, doctors are instructed on how to address the signs, not the root of the problem. If doctors were effective in their treatments, there would be fewer patients, yet health facilities are still overcrowded and there is a shortage of doctors in the workforce that has been ongoing for years.

In the coming years, the outlay for medical procedures is likely to remain higher than what patients are able to pay. The 2030 Agenda includes three objectives geared toward protecting the environment: Goal 13 focuses on taking action to combat climate change, Goal 14 targets safeguarding water resources and aquatic life, and Goal 15 concentrates on protecting land and agricultural areas of significance. Regrettably, some highly developed countries have refused to ratify and execute international climate agreements established by the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change for many years now.

The two afore-stated objectives (14 and 15) for the conservation of nature necessitate a universal agreement and dedication from all nations to keep at least a small number of resources, such as marine areas and oceans, and to keep the fertility of agricultural land and the diversity of plants and animals in good condition. But exploiting the seas and oceans, for example through tuna fishing, and intensifying and expanding crops destructively - with soil, plants and wildlife - like the Amazon rainforest, are still happening. The remaining three goals of the 2030 Agenda are more abstract social-political and institutional objectives, such as Goal 5 - gender equality, Goal 16 - peace, justice and strong institutions, Goal 17 - partnerships for the implementation of the 2030 Agenda goals, which are more intricate to implement.

The current state of military disputes, wars, and interventions from countries around the globe (including in the Middle East) hinders the spread of peace and justice (Goal 16). Additionally, the cultural, moral and geographical differences among nations makes it difficult to ensure universal gender equality (Goal 5). If we are to reach the aims of the 2030 Agenda (Goal 17), it is essential to increase the commitment of both governments and non-governmental organisations to drive sustainable development initiatives.

In order to meet the objectives of the 2030 Agenda globally, all signatories must have well-functioning institutions and skilled personnel that can combat poverty and promote sustainable growth.

Transport policy in general

Public administration bodies are involved in a range of initiatives to shape the transport system. These initiatives include establishing a physical and organizational framework, formulating financial and legal regulations for the functioning and operation of the transport system, and influencing the transport needs of the public and the demand for transport services. Their goal is to provide the necessary conditions for the construction and maintenance of a suitable transport infrastructure, managing the functioning of the transport system, and encouraging its usage to meet the larger objectives of social policy, such as labor market policy, educational policy, or regional policy. Moreover, the prevailing values and ideologies of the general social policy should be well-reflected in the transport policy, particularly from the perspective of regional policy.

Polish transport policy

In Poland, the transport policy is divided across several entities due to the constitutional principle of subsidiarity, which states that governmental intervention is only required when the desired aims cannot be achieved by people or subordinate structures. The Council of Ministers and the Ministry of Infrastructure are responsible for transport policy on a national level, as well as a few other central government institutions such as the General Directorate for National Roads and Motorways and the Railway Transport Office. Additionally, the state owns companies that have influence in this area.

At the regional and local stages, the proper administrative authorities of local government divisions are in control of transporting policy. Such an approach, while in accordance with the idea of self-government and the principle of subsidiarity, raises a certain issue in the overall examination of transport policy in Poland. This tangible problem is also connected to the fact that the local government is not responsible for the overall transport policy in its area if, for instance, a national road or a railway line operated by a national operator goes through it, which makes responsibility ambiguous (especially from the point of view of citizens) and often retards investment processes.

The Transport Development Strategy until 2020 (with a vision for 2030) highlights the value of up-to-date infrastructure, with the aim of promoting the flow of economic growth from flourishing areas to those parts of the nation that are in financial hardship. The fundamental purpose of the state's transport approach is to construct a connected transport system and the necessities for the effective operation of transport systems and the growth of efficient transport systems. The essential test was to eliminate the backlog in the extension, modernization and revitalization of transport infrastructure, and then - to boost saturation with infrastructure and construct an integrated transport system.

European transport policy

International organizations recognize that the arrangement and functioning of the transport system is essential for the attainment of overarching or worldwide objectives. From the perspective of assessing the Polish transport system, the strategy followed by the European Union is particularly significant. Already when the European Communities were first established, the topic of transport was accepted as one of the key components of the common policy intended for Member States. As stated in the White Paper, the plan to build a single European transport zone was designed to bring about a cost-effective and resource-efficient transport system. The European Commission has given more publicity to the principle of sustainable development in relation to transport. A unified European transport system is still seen as indispensable for economic progress, but now the European transport policy also has the goal of raising the standard of living of citizens of the European Union, promoting autonomy from non-renewable resources (especially oil), and reducing the adverse effect on the natural environment.

The specific objectives of the European transport policy in the horizon of 2050 include:

1. Reducing by half the number of conventionally powered cars (i.e. non-hybrid internal combustion engines) in urban transport by 2030 and their complete elimination from cities by 2050.
2. Achieving CO₂-free logistics in large urban centers by 2030.
3. Achieving 40% of low-emission fuel use in aviation by 2050.
4. Reducing emissions from marine liquid fuels by 40% (and if possible, by 50%) by 2050.
5. Transfer to other modes of transport (especially rail or waterborne transport) 30% of road freight transport over distances greater than 300 km by 2030 and over 50% by 2050.

6. Achieving a three-fold increase in the high-speed rail network by 2030 and completing the European high-speed rail network by 2050, while maintaining a dense rail network in all Member States.
7. Creation of the TEN-T5 multimodal core network by 2030, and the achievement of high quality and capacity of this network by 2050, as well as the creation of appropriate information services.
8. Connect all core network airports to the high-speed rail network and ensure that key seaports are well connected to rail freight and inland waterways by 2050.
9. Introduction of a modernized air traffic management infrastructure in Europe by 2020 and completion of works on the Common European Aviation Area, as well as the introduction of analogous land and water transport management systems.
10. Establishing a framework for a European information, management and payment system for multimodal transport by 2020.
11. Achieve almost zero fatalities in road transport by 2050 and halve the number of road fatalities by 2020.
12. Introducing the "user pays" and "polluter pays" principles and engaging the private sector to eliminate distortions or secure investment in transport (European Commission 2011).

It is worth noting that the principles of European transport policy have a direct or indirect impact on the Member States of the EU, and therefore also on Poland. In recent years, the alarming consequences of climate change and other environmental issues have been increasingly highlighted by international organisations. As a result, they have strongly advocated for reducing greenhouse gas emissions and other pollutants coming from transport. This has been referred to as the decarbonisation paradigm, and has become an important aspect of the transport policy.

Ideas

The distinction between two conceptions becomes conspicuous. The earlier one, which can be tagged as traditional or modernist, puts a premium on economic expansion and views conveyance as a means for boosting the performance of the economy without any acknowledgment of the boundaries of this growth or the adverse aspects of the extension of the transport system. The latter, deemed as fresh or sustainable transport paradigm, acknowledges the limits of the economy's growth and the bad consequences of the expansion of transportation systems, along with the need to balance economic concerns with social and ecological aspects.

Evidently, the past few years have seen a surge in motor vehicle use across the entirety of the former Eastern Bloc countries, which appears to back up the predetermined notion that these societies must go through the same journey of transport development as their Western counterparts and have the same adverse effects. Nevertheless, Poland has already achieved one of the highest levels of car ownership in Europe, surpassing many affluent Western countries. This begs the question of whether more extensive roads will inspire an increased number of citizens to take to their cars as the default method of transportation, thus further increasing traffic congestion and resulting in the loss of time that the Strategy makes mention of (albeit erroneously).

The alleged rise of cars during the period of change can be attributed not only to society's increasing desire for wealth, but also to the inadequacy of the current transport policy. This policy does not take into account the need for collective transportation, and the notion of

limiting the use of individual cars is met with opposition. Therefore, these negative trends are yet to be reversed.

Conclusions

The emphasis of economic growth remains critical, with a view to reaching areas that are encountering economic struggle and less communicative access. Infrastructure has a significance in this equation that is almost idolized; if the transport system is equipped with enough infrastructure, then it's assumed any and all transport issues can be resolved. Infrastructure is frequently privileged over ensuring communication availability in the transport system and reinforcing social unity.

The Polish transport policy pays less attention to how transportation impacts people's well-being and safeguarding the natural environment, whereas safety is largely dependent on the behavioral patterns of those utilizing the transport system.

It appears that the creators of Poland's transport policy still view it through a neoliberal and modernist lens, in which economic gains are prioritized above social and environmental considerations. This is a common belief in the former Eastern Bloc countries, where transport systems must go through the same development stages as those in Western societies. However, the increasing pressure from international organizations and the heightened ecological awareness of the Polish public (especially in light of the air quality controversy that began at the end of 2016) may lead to further changes in the transport policy.

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04 - Enhancing Interreligious Dialogue Competency for Peace: Dealing with Difficult Dialogue from a Buddhist Perspective

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Abstract

*There is a lack of literature on how to deal with problems in interreligious dialogue. This paper contributes to this problem-solution through a study of the Buddha's principles in dealing with difficult dialogues in the *Dighanikaya* and *Majjhimanikaya* through a qualitative content analysis approach. The study found five groups of difficult dialogue and four principles to deal with difficult dialogue. The study argues that dialogue skill is needed to overcome obstacles in dialogue.*

Keywords: Interreligious Dialogue, Dialogue Skills, Buddha, *Suttapiṭaka*

Introduction

Problem Statement

Interreligious dialogue has been recognized as an important tool for building a peaceful pluralistic society. However, its practice is challenging, especially for doctrinal type of dialogue. Scholarly studies of the topic show that the limitation of this dialogue is mostly due to its high level of sensitivity, difficulty, knowledge and skill-demand. Some dialogue scholars have admitted that this type of dialogue is not easy and even dangerous (Cilliers, 2002, p. 47; Ingram, 1986, pp. 91–92; Ochs, 2015, p. 488).

Some scholars and practitioners of interreligious dialogue have tried to minimize problems by proposing principles on dos and don'ts that dialogue participants should observe such as no confrontation, no debate, no superior truth claim, no negative criticism, and no proselytization (King, 2014, p. 18; Suwanbubbha, 2004, pp. 157–158; Swidler, 2014, pp. 39–67). The World Council of Churches has publicly discouraged dialogue of truth persuasion and the practice of evangelization in dialogue since 1970s (Smith, 2007, pp. 64–66). These principles aim to avoid or prevent problems in dialogue. However, there is a lack of studies that explore ways to deal with problems if they do happen. Therefore, the purpose of this paper is to explore some insights into how to deal with difficult dialogues by learning from the Buddha's dialogue skills in the Buddhist Pali Canon, particularly the two collections of the *Suttapiṭaka*: *Dighanikaya* (Collection of Long Discourses) and *Majjhimanikaya* (Collection of Middle Length Discourses).

The *Suttapiṭaka* is a rich source of intellectual dialogue. The Buddha is portrayed as a dialogue expert who skillfully communicates with different types of people from different backgrounds in various situations. He successfully transforms several of his dialogue partners including those who view him as rival and enemy into positive attitudes. For forty-five years of dialogue, he accumulates and passes down many of his dialogue insights to his disciples. Therefore, it is worth learning from the Buddha's experiences in order to enlighten the work of dialogue in our time. Particularly this study answers the following two questions:

Research questions:

1. What kinds of difficult dialogue did the Buddha encounter?
2. How did the Buddha deal with problems arising in those dialogues?

Research objectives:

The objectives of this study are to identify types of difficult dialogue encountered by the Buddha and what underlying principles he embodied to handle those dialogues in order to minimize problems and maximize benefits for all.

Literature Review

Defining interreligious dialogue

There are different definitions of interreligious dialogue from broad to narrow ones. In this study, based on the nature of the Buddha's dialogues with people of other faiths, interreligious dialogue is defined as "verbal communication" between the Buddha and people of other religious views and worldviews for various purposes in which the Buddha used his religious view to address the issues raised. During the Buddha's time, people came to him for various purposes such as political consultation, settling doctrinal disputes, clarifying rumors or accusations, seeking truth, and so on. Therefore, the scope of the Buddha's interreligious dialogue in this study is broader than the modern common understanding of interreligious dialogue which limits its purpose to exchange of religious views for mutual understanding.

Scholarly studies of the Buddha's interreligious dialogue in the Pali Canon

Studies of interreligious dialogue concerning the Buddha of the Pali Canon have been few and mostly influenced by the Western Christian paradigm or the three truth models: exclusivism, inclusivism, and pluralism. They place the Buddha's position toward other religions from exclusivism to somewhere between inclusivism and pluralism (Hayes, 1991; J. Abraham Velez de Cea, 2013). Different from the above, Elizabeth J. Harris argues that the Buddha of the Pali texts responded to the religious others with five faces: respectful debate, teaching ideas that opposed those taught by others, ridicule of the 'other', subordination of the 'other, and appropriation of the 'other' (Harris, 2013). Some other Buddhist scholars devoted their studies to show how the Buddhist values and teachings foster dialogue such as "deep listening", respect for different views, non-argumentative attitude, non-dogmatism, rationality, tolerance, openness, and loving kindness (de Silva, 2009; Jayatilleke, 1987; Sek, 2017). The above frameworks are useful to understand the underlying views, values, and attitudes of Buddhism toward the religious others. This study takes interest in conduct principles when dealing with problems in dialogue. Conduct principles mean the rules of behavior that the Buddha embodied.

Research Methodology

This study used a qualitative content analysis (QCA) approach to study the Buddhist narratives of dialogue between the Buddha and people of other faiths in the two collections - *Dighanikaya* (D), and *Majjhimanikaya* (M). QCA is best suited for describing the selected aspects of the material guided by the research questions (Schreier, 2012, pp. 1–9). This method was suitable for this study because the study only focused on some aspects of the dialogue narratives, namely the difficult types of dialogue, and the conduct principles that the Buddha applied in the dialogues.

Research Findings

According to the research findings, there are five groups of difficult interreligious dialogue that the Buddha encountered ranging from dialogues that involve politics and conflict resolution to those that involve defending one's religious doctrine, settling doctrinal disputes, criticizing other's religious beliefs and practices, and facing aggression, hostility, insults, and challenge to debate. Concerning the Buddha's conduct principles in dealing with those problems, this study found four main principles.

Types of difficult interreligious dialogue encountered by the Buddha

From the two collections, *Dighanikaya* and *Majjhimanikaya*, this study found five types of difficult interreligious dialogue. These types are considered as difficult because they involve sensitive issues such as politics, doctrinal debate and criticism, negative emotions. If these things are not well handled, they can lead to violent conflicts and other negative consequences.

The first difficult type of interreligious dialogue the Buddha encountered is dialogue that involves politics and violent conflicts. There are three cases from the dialogue narratives: giving advice to brahmin how to make meritorious burned sacrifice (D I 5), giving consultation to King Ajatasattu who asked whether or not he should invade a neighboring country (D II 16), and taming the cruel robber Angulimala from his evil behavior of killing people. All the dialogues above involved different types of power: cultural power (brahmin sacrificial system), political power (the king), and evil power of violence and suffering (Angulimala's violent behavior and suffering). Many violent conflicts of our time have religious dimension and involve the above powers. How a religious leader can involve in dialogue with various groups to resolve conflict in a good way is a difficult question. The Buddha could provide some insight into this question.

The second type of difficult dialogue the Buddha encountered is the one in which he had to defend his own religious teachings and position against rumor, misunderstanding, and criticism. The study found six dialogues of this type. The Buddhist path had its unique training and experiences which were not easy to be comprehended by the outsiders. Therefore, misunderstanding of the Buddha's teachings by the outsiders (D I 8; M I 55; M II 71, 90) and even the insiders as in the case of his disciple Sunakkhatta (D III 24) was unavoidable. For example, there was rumor that Buddha discredited all forms of asceticism which was popularly practiced at that time (D I 8) and that he consumed animal meat which had been intentionally killed for him (M II 55). His practice of seclusion and avoiding metaphysical questions and debates was also attacked as cowardice and incapability of public speaking (D III 25). Discrediting rumors with the truth and how to explain truth satisfactorily is not an easy task if a person does not know well one's own tradition and other relevant traditions.

The third type of difficult dialogue the Buddha encountered is settling doctrinal disputes and doubts. The study found 5 dialogues of this type which can be classified into two sub-types. The first sub-type is the dialogue in which the religious others had disputes among themselves on competing teachings within their own tradition, and they were unable to convince each other about their own doctrinal stance. As a result, they sought the Buddha as an external authority to settle the dispute (D I 13; M II 98). The other sub-type of this dialogue includes conversations in which the religious others doubted various truth claims and the claimed spiritual achievements of different religious figures of the time. As a result, they sought the Buddha's answer on the issue whether or not these religious teachers had spoken the truth (D II 16 (Chapter 5), M I 30; M II 79). Giving judgment on religious doctrine is a sensitive issue. If it is not well-handled, it may cause offence.

The fourth type of difficult interreligious dialogue the Buddha encountered is the one in which the Buddha criticized the understanding or beliefs of other religions that he viewed as

wrong or unprofitable for the wellbeing and happiness of the believers. This study found 13 dialogues of this type in which the Buddha offered criticisms of the teachings of other religions. These dialogues can be divided into two groups. In the first group (D I 9; D II 16 (Chapter 4); M I 7; M II 74, 80, 96; M III 152), the religious others such as brahmins, ascetic wanderers, and disciples of other religious sects came to see the Buddha, presented their religious belief, and invited the Buddha's opinion on it. In the second group of dialogue (D I 9, 12; D III 24, 31; M I 14; M II 79; M III 101), the Buddha took initiative to approach other religious groups or individuals to question and criticize their beliefs and practices which he viewed as baseless and unprofitable for them. This type of dialogue is difficult because it is sensitive and provocative.

The final type of difficult interreligious dialogue that the Buddha encountered is the one that involved disrespect, aggressive attitudes, insults, hostility, and the challenge to debate from his dialogue partners. This study found 14 dialogues of this type from the two collections. This study divides the Buddha's dialogue partners into three groups: the Brahmins (D I 3, 4; M II 93, 95, 99, 100; the ascetic wanderers who were described as lovers of noises and debates (D I 9; M I 18); and the *Niganthas* or the Jains who viewed the Buddha as a rival and occasionally planned to trap the Buddha in a debate to insult and defeat him (D III 24; M I 35, 36; M II 56, 58). Indeed, these situations were extremely challenging to deal with. In modern interreligious dialogue, these negative emotions are seen as tough problems to handle.

Whether or not and to which extent these dialogue narratives were real events is beyond the scope of this paper. My interest is to know how the Buddha handled all these dialogue problems as narrated in the scriptures. What conduct principles can be inferred from these dialogue narratives? The following section will present some insights I have found from these narratives.

The Buddha's principles in handling difficult interreligious dialogues

In this section, I will present the four main underlying conduct principles that the Buddha embodied in the above dialogues.

The first principle is communicating truth in its wholesome framework with concrete criteria for verification by the listener. For example, in *Mahaparinibbana Sutta* (D II 16), Chapter 1, when the king's minister asked the Buddha whether or not the king should invade the Vajjians, the Buddha did not answer it immediately but constructed a concrete wholesome truth framework to evaluate the issue in question through his conversation with his disciple, the Venerable Ananda, in front of the minister. The Buddha listed seven principles for a thriving people:

1. Have frequent public assemblies.
2. Have harmony in their public affairs.
3. Respect ancient traditions and their authority.
4. Respect, honor the elders, and listen to their words.
5. Not take wives and daughters of others illegally and forcibly.
6. Preserve native traditions and spiritual practices in the country and abroad.
7. Rightly protect, defend and support Arahants to live peacefully in the land. (*the author's summary of the text* (Walshe, 1987, pp. 231–232).

The Buddha asked Ven. Ananda to confirm if the Vajjians had kept these seven principles. After Ven. Ananda had confirmed it, the Buddha said to the minister that as long as the Vajjians kept these seven principles, they would not decline but prosper. The Buddha limited

his answer to this point and let the king's minister make his own decision. As a result, the violence war was prevented. This method of giving advice to politicians is wise because it provides good moral framework for reflection and freedom for the other to make decision.

The second principle is being sincere and brave to speak both pleasant and unpleasant truth out of compassion, with good purpose, in due time, and appropriate for the level of the listener. The Buddha's sincerity and bravery were seen clearly in his being alone speaking out reasonable criticisms against the caste system, the baseless absolute truth claims and unprofitable practices of the religious others. According to what revealed from the Buddha's teachings, being sincere and brave is not sufficient for speaking truth because if truth is spoken in the wrong time or in the wrong place, it may lead to more negative consequences than positive ones. Speaking truth must go with conditions. In *Abhaya-Raja-Kumara Sutta* (M II 58), the Buddha gave four principles of his speaking truth both pleasant and unpleasant: (1) it is true and fact; (2) it is relevant to the purpose; (3) it is spoken in due season; (4) it is spoken out of compassion. In *Samyuttanikaya 42.7, Desana (aka Khettupama) Sutta*, the Buddha stated though he had one message of liberation, he discerned what to teach according to each individual's capacity and need. Those principles helped the Buddha focus on his purpose and skillfully lead the conversation away from discussing things which finally did not go anywhere nor bring any benefit.

The third principle is tranquility of mind in the face of praises and criticisms. According to the Buddha's teaching in The *Brahmajala Sutta* (D I 1), verses 1.5 and 1.6, the Buddha advised his disciples to remain tranquil when other people praised or insulted their Teacher, the Teaching, and the Order. The reason was that if they ran after either one by feeling excited or angry, they would not be able to see whether what people had said was true or not. The right attitude was to clearly discern the truth as it is, whether it is true or untrue, correct or incorrect. Based on this pure understanding, the disciples would confirm or reject it. With this tranquility, the Buddha was able to avoid the trap of being arrogant and biased when being trusted and praised by others. In heated debates, he was able to see the problem in his opponent's argument and eventually turn the situation upside down. This is the principle that the Buddha embodied when he was challenged to debate and when he faced attitudes of hostility, disrespect, insult, and aggression from his dialogue partners.

The fourth principle that the Buddha embodied in his dialogue was attentive listening and careful understanding before responding, and patience in explaining the truth. The Buddha always listened to the other's view carefully and clarified it when necessary. Sometimes he asked for confirmation from the other if his understanding was correct to the third time (D I 3, 13). Being attentive in listening in order to get the right understanding of the other's view does not only show respect to the other but also help oneself know well how to respond correctly to the problem. Besides being attentive in listening, the Buddha was very patient to clarify and explain his view step by step and in various ways until the other was satisfied such as his dialogue with a Jain lay-leader in *Upali Sutta* (M II 56). Being patient, knowledgeable, and skillful in explaining truth to satisfy the other's intellectual quest is also a key to transform the other's attitudes from negative to positive.

Conclusion

In conclusion, with the purpose of searching for good ways to deal with difficult interreligious dialogue from the ancient Buddhist wisdom, particularly the Buddha's dialogue skills in the *Dighanikaya* and the *Majjhimanikaya*, this study has found five groups of difficult dialogue ranging from dialogues that involve politics and conflict resolution to those that involve defending one's religious doctrine, settling doctrinal disputes, criticizing other's religious beliefs and practices and dealing with aggression, hostility, insults and challenge to debate.

The Buddha's four conduct principles for dealing with those difficult dialogues can be a starting point for further reflection, discussion, and dialogue skill competency training to empower people for more effective dialogue in our time.

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05 - Title Political Culture and Clashing Narratives in the Ukraine Identity Politics

Rey Ty

Problem Statement: People take sides in the Ukraine but neither know nor analyze the internal clashing narratives

Purpose of the Study: The purpose of this article was to describe the two divergent arguments about the Ukraine crisis

Literature or Theory: Political Culture, Identity Politics, Monoculturalism, Multiculturalism

Research Methods: This article used the qualitative case study research design which investigated the public policies of Ukraine in current history and utilized thematic analysis to identify trends.

Summary of Findings: There are two clashing views about Ukraine: Ukraine is monocultural vis-à-vis Ukraine is multicultural.

Conclusion: Ukraine is at a stalemate now as there are two simultaneous clashing narratives about the identity of Ukraine.

Keywords

1 Ukraine

2 political cultures

3 identity politics

4 government and politics

5 Public Policy

Area: Justice and Peace; Culture

06 - Human Rights and Peacebuilding: Addressing the Potential to Synthesize these Two Contending Perspectives

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Abstract

This review of literature asserts that there is tension between human rights and peace practitioners when they work in the operation fields. Human rights tend to be focusing more on justice but peacebuilding orients toward often more forgiving for tending to support reconciliatory approaches. This paper addresses the different perspectives of human rights and peacebuilding together with the term “conflict resolution” in the peace studies field. It presents an integrative literature review of two perspectives that provides a theory of human rights and peacebuilding, relating to addressing the different cases of conflict. The paper contributes to highlighting the problems between the two areas and presents some proposed solutions to integrate them.

Key Terms: Conflict Resolution, Human Rights, Justice, Peacebuilding, Perspectives

Introduction

Problem Statement

This paper addresses the problem in which human rights and peacebuilding approach a given conflict situation in contrasting ways. Hence, there is a clash of perspectives which complicates solving conflict.

Research Questions

This paper addresses the following questions.

1. What are the perspectives on human rights and peacebuilding?
2. What are the tensions between human rights and peacebuilding perspectives?
3. What are some solutions to integrate the differences between human rights and peacebuilding perspectives?

Research Purpose

This paper aims to address the tensions between the human rights theory and peacebuilding theory and provide potential solutions to synthesize them.

Methodology

This paper employed the qualitative method to explore the problems and potential solutions between human rights and peacebuilding fields (Creswell & Poth, 2016) in different literature. The literature is categorized in a classification of (1) the perspective of human rights and peacebuilding, (2) the tensions between human rights and peacebuilding perspectives, and (3) some proposed solutions to the problems between human rights and peacebuilding perspectives. The next section, the Current State of Literature, responds to the research questions as the results and the findings in each subheading.

Current State of the Literature

Human rights and conflict resolution works for peacebuilding have been traditionally perceived as two different areas, sometimes they are in competitive positions at both the conceptual level and operations on the ground. They are in tension and occasionally with contradictory approaches toward sustainable peace (Julio & Drumond, 2017).

The perspective of human rights and peacebuilding

Paralevliet (2018) clarifies human rights that it is understood here as norms that express expectations about appropriate behavior and capture ideas about the equal moral worth of all human beings. In addition, human rights norms are also largely reflected in international treaties. On the other hand, conflict resolution for peacebuilding is used as a generic term to cover the whole range of nonviolent conflict handling and the field itself. Practically, it includes both settlement and transformation aspects. From the perspective of human rights organizations and practitioners, there is no peace without justice, in the form of criminal prosecutions for past abuses, and impunity cannot be tolerated, even if the pursuit of justice prolongs the conflict. On the contrary, from the perspective of peace practitioners, are oriented toward conflict resolution as priority. Their approaches are based on more forgiving, tending to support reconciliatory approaches and nonpunitive measures, such as amnesty, as a means of ending the conflict as quickly as possible (human rights dialogue, 2002). These two contested concepts cause problems at that implementation level in the operation fields although the link between human rights, conflict resolution, and peacebuilding was already set into the preamble of the 1948 Universal Declaration of Human Rights as a policy and research (Julio & Drumond, 2017, p. 3).

Tensions between human rights and peacebuilding perspectives

When human rights norms have become a critical component of the global policy framework for thinking about and dealing with peace and conflict works, concerning protecting civilians in all stages of the conflict, and multiple declarations and reports highlight the importance of connecting human rights, conflict resolution, and peacebuilding. The lines between human rights and peace work have also not been clear because of rising ambitions, expanding conceptions, and diversifying practices in these fields (Parlevliet, 2018). When the specialists from both fields work on the real ground, their expertise and practice hold the specific ways of seeing, being, and doing peace works. Human rights actors think and perceive the world in binary ways of right and wrong, black and white. However, peace and conflict resolution practitioners recognize the ambiguity and capitalize on the areas of grey which exist in the real ground. The problem among them is that human rights groups have trouble within their framework in engaging with the grey area. The professionalism of both practitioners in the field is another problem when implementing the projects together. These professionalisms induce them to see one way as tunnel vision, willing to keep their professional identities, and desire to prove their relevance in operations. In terms of representation of the specific party, human rights advocacy is easily seen as supporting one specific party, since rights standards are meant to protect the weak from power abuse by the stronger one. Differently, conflict resolution and peacebuilding processes that treat parties evenhandedly, without recognizing a possible asymmetry in abuses or the special responsibility of the state to protect citizens' rights, can be suspected from a human rights perspective. Although the two contested areas seemed could not cooperate effectively for lasting peace, scholars argued and endeavored to incorporate these two areas. Vuco argued that traditional human rights concepts and policies are inadequate. They need to cooperate with peace concepts and practices (Vuco, 2002).

Proposed solutions to integrate the human rights and peacebuilding perspectives

Preventing violent conflicts and human rights violations requires strategies that incorporate perspectives from both human rights and peacebuilding fields. However, a collaboration between the two fields does not always come easily. Furthermore, both have no formula that is sufficient to meet the needs of achieving peace or protecting human rights in conflict settings or preventing future abuses. The first potential solution is that both professions acquire to develop their capacity to deal with the meaning and values of another profession constructively. Human rights actors could develop their capacity to deal with conflict cases while doing human rights work. Conflict and peace practitioners, on the other hand, need to develop and understanding of human rights for their work and to gain the ability to address the human rights violations (Parlevliet, 2002). Lutz also reinforces the cross-disciplinary understanding and collaboration between the human rights and conflict resolution fields to help local and internationally oriented practitioners in each field better understand the priorities, norms, techniques, and processes of their counterparts to achieve their shared goal of peace. However, it is important to note that it is for collaboration, not for merging (Lutz, 2002). Paralevliet argues to adopt a multi-dimensional understanding of human rights principle in conflict resolution and peacebuilding process such as addressing the underlying causes of conflict and rights violations (Paralevliet, 2018). For example, the conditions relating to inequality, inequity, injustice, and insecurity. Lutz reinforces in critically accessing the causes of conflict to solve more effectively as in some volatile conflict situation, human rights advocates could be more effective if they expanded their tool kits beyond naming, shaming, and seeking remedies in judicial forums to include conflict resolvers' broader array of negotiation and diplomatic techniques. Peace actors could better ensure that negotiations lead not just to a ceasefire but to a permanent peace if they were more willing to assert basic norms of international human rights and humanitarian law (Lutz, 2002).

See the tables below that summarize the results and findings of the all-research questions of this paper, such as different perspectives, problems and potential solutions of human rights and peacebuilding.

Table 1. Organizing and summarizing the findings from the literature (Different Perspectives)

No	Human rights perspectives	Peacebuilding perspectives
1	Express expectations about appropriate behavior and capture ideas about the equal moral worth of all human beings	Cover the whole range of nonviolent conflict-handling and the field itself. contains both settlement and transformation dimensions
2	No peace without justice, in the form of criminal prosecutions for past abuses, and impunity cannot be tolerated, even if the pursuit of justice prolongs the conflict	Oriented toward conflict resolution as a priority, based on more forgiving, tending to support reconciliatory approaches and nonpunitive measures, such as amnesty, as a means of ending conflict as quickly as possible

Table 2. Organizing and summarizing the findings from the literature (Problems and solutions)

Ref.	Problems	Potential Solutions
1	Rising ambitions, expanding conceptions, and diversifying practices	Develop the capacity to deal with the meaning and values of another in a constructive manner.
2	Expertise and practice represent the specific ways of seeing, being and doing in peace works. Binary terms of right and wrong, black and white Vs. the areas of grey	Cross-disciplinary understanding and collaboration for better understanding of the priorities, norms, techniques, and processes of their counterparts to achieve their shared goal of peace.
3	Professionalisms induce tunnel vision, willing to keep their professional identities, desires to prove their own relevance especially when they face competition for policy influence or resources	Focusing attention on important underlying conditions relating to inequality, inequity, injustice, and insecurity for a certain quality could be an option for solution to the different perspectives.
4	Human rights advocacy aids a specific party, to protect the weak from abuse of power by the strong, while conflict resolution and peacebuilding process that treat parties evenhandedly	Human rights advocates could be more effective if they expanded their tool kits beyond naming, shaming, and seeking remedies in judicial forums to include conflict resolvers' broader array of negotiation and diplomatic techniques.

Summary, Conclusion, and Recommendations

Summary

The different orientations of human rights, peacebuilding and conflict resolution have contested natures when working in the fields when human rights norm became part of the peace works for justice. Principles and professionalism of both practitioners are challenging factors when working together and requiring compromise in the fields. Human rights and peace authors endeavor to explore the solution for effective integration. Although two areas have limitations in operation fields for lasting peace, the potential solutions for effective collaboration were developed to cooperate with peace concept and practice in the peace and conflict works.

Conclusion

Peace becomes increasingly linked to the notion of justice. Conflict resolution was no longer measured simply by the absence of bloodshed but by the moral quality of the outcome. Both human rights and peace groups have their own problems in their policies and practices when working together, however, focus on sustainable conflict transformation. Integrating both principles could depend on case, place, and time.

Recommendations

Adopting cross-disciplinary and multi-dimensional understanding in both human rights and peacebuilding fields is no doubt a possible solution for current peace works. There is no better way than that until now. It is recommended to critically access and formulate the

more appropriate peace process design by researching the degree of collaboration in particular place, time, and local context as case by case.

A Case Study of Aung San Suu Kyi: Reconciliation, Not Retribution

When we focused on sustainable conflict transformation and peacebuilding, it is necessary to looking for the way how to integrate the two principles, Human Rights and Peace. This case is highlighting the Burmese human rights activist and politician Aung San Suu Kyi in terms of her way to integrate the rights and peace, of herself and how she tried to convince the country. Her life was changed forever after her return to Myanmar for caring of her mother in 1988. The then-dictator of Myanmar Ne Win imprisoned protesters who protested to his administration. Aung San Suu Kyi against the authoritarian government of Myanmar at that time and started a nonviolent resistance to achieve democracy in Myanmar. She believed and emphasized democracy as the precondition for the Burmese freedom. However, she was placed under house arrest and spent many years in custody. She declined to many compromising initiated from the military-based administrative authority of the country. She was oppressed by the military government in many ways and sentenced for the things that she did not do as well as long suffering. Aung San Suu Kyi had chosen the way towards reconciliation with her opponents, especially the military. She took in positive way even for her house arrest. She replied to reporters that she had a chance to stay at home and had time to read. She believes that the country needs to choose the reconciliation instead of retribution for moving toward democracy. She also claimed that forgiveness is essential for everyone to understand and recognize (Ashe, 2014). In 2011, the National League for Democracy (NLD) led by Aung San Suu Kyi re-registered to run the election and she formally registered to run for a seat in parliament. She had won the election and took the office. She had a long vision for the country and seemed to be planted the root of democracy in the countryman, especially in the young generation. She herself showed her forgiveness to the one who were once responsible for the persecution of her and the members of her party. She urged her fellow elected candidates from her party to join hands with those who persecuted them before. In this point, we can see that she did not ask for that she could not do. She showed her forgiveness and let others do like she did. She also told them that forgiveness is a necessary step toward national reconciliation. She urged her party representatives to show that they do not have desire for revenge against the opponents who are responsible for the persecution of them before, but doing nothing wrong at the present, and they can work alongside for the betterment of the country. Her efforts intended to release the ones who worried for being retributed for their past oppression to the democratic activists and communities. She also said her party will give equal legal protection to everyone and would not oppress those who do not agree with the party's ways of doing. She also met with the elected representatives and urged them to work for peace and rule of law to end civil wars in ethnic areas. One of her remarkable speeches depicted the importance of second chance. She said "whatever mistake they have made in the past, we need to give them the chance to change, instead of seeking revenge. If they are doing nothing wrong at the present time, they can join hands with us." to her party representatives of the upper Myanmar, in 2015. On the other hand, one prominent political analyst argued that he was admirable Aung San Suu Kyi for her seeking to heal longstanding political divisions of the country, however, it would take long time for those who suffered under military rule to come to terms with the past. He continued that it would be hard for the victims although she had urged forgiveness. It might need time, negotiation and the trust building (Mann, 2015).

Discussion on case

As above case, we have learned that Aung San Suu Kyi had chosen the nonviolent and peaceful way to resist the unjust by her belief and principles toward democracy for Myanmar. She was in very long imprisonment and house arrested in her life. She tried to sacrifice all her life to her country, Myanmar for the reconciliation and peace. Although she admired the democracy standard and human rights, she tried to balance the principles of both rights and peace. She tried to forgive the ones who were wrong doing to her and her followers, as well as to lead her followers to try to forgive and look for the long-term vision of democratic peaceful country. And she had joined the government system and had seat at the parliament and her party was ruling the country for five years until early 2021. Aung San Suu Kyi made a lot of success for the development of Myanmar. Foreign Direct Investment were increasing and Myanmar became re-connected the world. Overseas Myanmar citizen tried to come back to Myanmar and contributed their knowledge and expertise for the development of the country. Myanmar got brain-gain back. Getting the state power by landslide victory in 2015 election was the reward of her decisions and efforts by joining hands with others, deciding to re-register for the election in 2011, trying to forgive, and looking forward for reconciliation and long-term vision of peace for the country. The people of Myanmar had a chance to taste the essence of democracy and freedom even in partiality, during her administration. That contributed to choosing the right decision to respond to the unjust military coup in February 2021. People of Myanmar were not willing to going back to the dark age of military ruling and resist the military coup in many ways until now. In overall, it can be concluded that this is the fruit of Aung San Suu Kyi planted before to choose the reconciliation way to take state power even for one term-five years- of her government time in ruling the country, by integrating the rights approach and peace approach. She had tried to forgive and look forward to restoration, instead of retribution. One should not forget and hide the moment of lighting up the country in her five years of almost fully administration, and her attempted to join in the government system before her landslide victory as the consequence of her endeavor to integrate the rights approach and peace approach.

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07 - Child Forced Marriage among Muslims in Thailand

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Abstract

This paper addresses the problem of Muslim Thai child forced marriage. It aims to describe the current social norms regarding Thai Muslim child forced marriage and generate recommendations for addressing social norms in preventing child forced marriage among Thai Muslims. The method used is empirical literature research and the theoretical is the theory of "social norms" (Bicchieri et al., 2014). The findings are that Thailand has a plural legal system where Muslims' religious norms rule their followers regarding matrimony matters. However, this situation bypasses the Thai criminal code that considers the age of consent for sex as 15. Due to the "permissive" of a child forced marriage among Muslims in Thailand, this research identified harmful cultural norms such as dowry, the role of a housewife, and tradition. This paper recommends 1) raising awareness about the consequences of a child forced marriage among religious leaders and the Thai population; 2) the promotion of cultural norms to increase women's value in society, since patriarchy values still strong among Muslim-Thai community (Sateemae et al., 2017, p. 81).

Key Terms: Child Forced Marriage, Muslims, Social Norms, Thailand

Introduction

This paper addresses the **problem** of child forced marriage. It raised these **research questions:** 1. What are Muslim Thai social norms about child forced marriage? 2. What are recommendations to end Muslim Thai child forced marriage? **The research purpose includes** 1. To describe the social norms regarding Muslim Thai child forced marriage. 2. To generate recommendations for addressing social norms in preventing child forced marriage among Muslims in Thailand.

Literature Review

Child marriage is as a global problem considering the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC) paradigm. Article 1 of the CRC establishes that a child is any person under the age of eighteen. Therefore, according to the CRC, child marriage is an act that unites an individual below eighteen years old to another child or an adult. Forced marriage occurs when one of the spouses enters the relationship against their will or is not free to leave the alliance. Forced marriage has been interpreted to encompass child marriage since children cannot inherently consent to matrimony. The United Nations, for instance, voices that "children, given their age, are not able to give free, prior and informed consent to their marriage partners or to the timing of their marriage" (United Nations, 2012, p. 27 and 34). Early marriage may also enclose trafficking, where girls are traded or forcibly wedded in the circumstances often characterized by poverty and violence.

In Thailand, anyone over 15 but not yet 18 is considered a minor. The Criminal Code establishes the age of consent for sex as 15 (*Thai Criminal Code | Thailand Law Library, Sec. 277*). The law prescribes that sexual intercourse with someone under 15 years old "and not being his own wife" is a crime. Since 2003, under Thailand's strict child safeguard laws, no one under 17 can wed. Nevertheless, in the southern provinces of Thailand – Narathiwat, Pattani, and Yalla, which are prevalence Muslim – a legal loophole permits Muslims to apply

Islamic law to family matters, and infants under 15 years old are allowed to marry (Ellis-Petersen, 2018a).

Child forced marriage opens the door to many human rights violations, especially of girls and can be considered forced confinement and rape because it is sexual abuse with an infant. Also, it is human trafficking when the parents coerce the girl to marry for economic reasons. Girls forced to marry may be committing themselves to a marriage analogous to slavery for the rest of their lives. They experience domestic servitude and sexual slavery, suffer violations of their right to health, education, and non-discrimination, and experience physical, psychological, and sexual violence. Also, by child forced marriage, youth women are deeply impacted by early pregnancy. Cultural norms and traditions are aspects that drive child marriage in South Asia (*Addressing the Patterns of Child Marriage, Early Union and Teen Pregnancy in Southeast Asia*, 2018).

Methodology

This paper uses empirical literature research to study child forced marriage among Muslims in Thailand. The theoretical framing used to explore this phenomenon is the theory of "social norms" (Bicchieri et al., 2014, p. 4,5), a suited traditional method to understand human behaviors that support the practice of child forced marriage (preferences, options, and creed they have about these choices).

Findings

1. What are the current social norms regarding Muslim Thai child forced marriage?

Thailand is on the 19th ranking of the highest number of women married or in a union before the age of eighteen globally – 537,000 (Brides, 2022). Those wedded until the age of fifteen in Thailand make up three percent, and those married by eighteen range up to twenty percent. The rate of women between twenty to forty-nine years who were first united or in marriage before fifteen years and before eighteen years has stayed consistent across all age cohorts over time (National Statistical Office of Thailand, 2020, 37).

Legally, consent to sex is assumed as a natural outcome of matrimony. Hence, it is crucial that the law also establishes a minimum age of sexual consent and that the minimum age of marriage is not designed to be lower than the minimum age of sexual consent since a valid marriage needs to be consummated (*Violet Odala*, p. 3). Discrepancies in this regard can be seen in Thai Muslim provinces, where girls are allowed to marry at puberty for Muslim marriages, while the age of sexual consent prescribed in Thailand is 15. The application of Islamic law for family affairs and inheritance allows the marriage of young girls after their first menstrual cycle with parental approval. Hence, while the minimum legal age to marry in Thailand is 17, a Muslim younger than 17 may marry with a written court order or parental consent (United States Department of State, n.d., p. 33). Considering that the criminal law in Thailand prescribes that a young person under 15 cannot consent to sex, marriage under 15 years old should be considered a modality of forced marriage since the child does not have the capability to consent.

Child forced marriage is allowed in the southernmost provinces of Pattani, Yala, Narathiwat, and Satun, governed by Islamic family law and inheritance. Besides the southern provinces, child forced marriage among Muslims could happen all over Thailand since the religious views, practices, and customs of Muslims are defined through the mosque committee of each village. Islamic family law expands to Muslims outside the southern provinces, yet legally, Muslims beyond the four southernmost areas may wed underneath civil law (Marddent, 2009).

The Central Islamic Council of Thailand (CICOT), issued a national regulation on child marriage, urging local mosques not to allow matrimony under seventeen except in extraordinary cases (Buranajaroenkij, 2019, p. 75). The decision came after a wave of general anger at the wedding of an eleven-year-old Muslim Thai girl and a forty-one-year-old Malaysian man. Even with the new regulation, child forced marriage is still allowed by Islamic court's approval, or the parents document consent at the regional Islamic board office or the provincial police placement. For instance, the regulation permits parents to approve their child to be wedded: the case that initiated the change in the law had the parent's consent (ASEAN Post Team, 2019).

A Muslim member of the National Human Rights Commissioner informed that the CICOT's action was insufficient to prevent child forced marriages cases because there are no punishments for transgressors (AsiaNews.it, 2018). Hence, the current legal framework perpetuates child forced marriage. In countries with plural legal systems, combating child forced marriage can be difficult because religion plays a central role and highly influence the population's opinion. Therefore, implementing anti-child-forced-marriage social norms could be crucial for ending the practice (Plan International, 2018, p. 17).

Cultural norms are the unofficial rules of attitude in a collective mass, characterized by shared beliefs that certain conducts are usually accepted and considered natural (Bicchieri et al., 2014, p. 3). Therefore, they drive which comportment is suitable for what is "normal" in that society of reference. In-depth prejudiced visions, social norms, and expectations about gender positions and power references can promote violent practices (UNICEF, 2016, p. 52). Addressing cultural norms is essential for promoting peacebuilding activities (Avruch, 1998). Detrimental behaviors associated with child forced marriage are commonly related to what people do and what individuals think should be made, established by social norms, such as dowry, the role of housewife and tradition, as will be explained in the following paragraphs. Among Thai Muslims, the following detrimental social norms are related to child forced marriage:

Dowry: For parents who do not have the finances to support girls' studies, marriage is a way not to have the "burden" to provide food for a girl (National Statistical Office of Thailand, 2020, p. 215). Poverty is one of the drivers of child forced because marrying a daughter earlier means one less person to feed (Plan International, 2018, p. 12).

In Thailand, Muslim parents usually marry their daughters to receive a dowry, the amount paid by the groom to the bride according to the marriage agreement. For instance, in Thailand, there are cases where Malaysian Muslim men cross the border to contract polygamous marriage because the approval in Malaysia is very long. Potential spouses, or their families, who desire a bride pay for that. Usually, an affluent man offers the bride's parents money in trade for a girl to marry (ASEAN Post Team, 2019). A man who negotiates cross-border matrimony says, "Business is booming: instead of applying to a sharia court in Malaysia and answering all their difficult questions, the shortcut is to come to Thailand." Imams in Thailand demand a payment four times more for Malaysians than the residents of their district. Activists blame imams for earning funds through this practice (Ellis-Petersen, 2018b).

Child forced marriage can be a root and a result of school dropout. Children in the south, where the Muslim culture are dominant, are out of school at vastly more elevated indices over the country. Five to eight percent of lower secondary school-age children in Narathiwat, Songkhla, Pattani and Satun provinces are absent, exceeding the nationwide average of three percent of the school. This difference broadens with nineteen to as high as thirty-six

percent of upper secondary school-age kids in Pattani, Songkhla, and Narathiwat provinces absent of school. The national rate is eighteen percent.

The Role of a Housewife: According to research investigating preferences for patriarchal values among Muslim university students in southern Thailand, traditional cultural norms view girls' goals as getting married, raising kids, and doing household work (Sateemae, Abdel-Monem, and Sateemae 2017, p. 92). Child forced marriage is rooted in gender imbalance and the belief that females are lower in status than males (Laeheem & Boonprakarn, 2017). Traditionally ascribed gender roles, jointly with dominant cultural norms, diminish the value of a woman's education and her position outside the home. Indeed, Muslim females in the southern provinces have been marginalized by male-dominated organizations (Sateemae et al., 2017, p. 86).

Tradition: How sexuality is considered, experienced, and restrained is related to the observance of traditional practices in the community (Plan International, 2018, p. 14, 16). According to cultural tradition, girls are allowed to marry as soon as they start their period. Usually, the community does not know the harmful consequences child forced marriage can bring. A girl who lives in Thailand's Pattani province was forced to marry when she was fifteen years old with a man ten years older. According to her: "Here, if a girl is not married by the time she is 16, it is already felt to be too late and that no one will want to marry her" (Ellis-Petersen, 2018b). Especially on the situations at the lack of groom, the parents prefer to marry the daughter as soon as possible to prevent her from being single. Keep the purity seems to be a crucial source of value for Muslim women in southern Thailand (Win, 2011).

2. How can social norms be promoted to prevent child forced marriage?

Early marriage is entrenched in customs, directed by behaviors that support the practice (preferences, options, and creed they have about these choices) (Bicchieri et al., 2014, p. 4,5). Pinpointing the target reference network actors and their function in society allows one to pick out the essential players setting the rules in child forced marriage, for example.

Education: Muslim Thai parents should understand the importance of education for girls to expand their life skills and attain their full potential as human beings. Raising awareness among Muslim Thai parents about the value of education is crucial to diminish the occurrences of child forced marriage. Hence, economic incentives should be designed for girls and their families— like educational scholarships or monetary help from the government, international organizations or religious communities for families that keep their children in school (Plan International, 2018).

The Role of a Housewife: One of the goals is to train Muslim Thai parents in equity-based methods of decision-making and family governance, addressing unfair and damaging masculine and feminine roles (Girls Not Brides, 2022), mainly due the preponderance of support for patriarchy among a sampling of religious Muslim university students in Southern Thailand (Sateemae et al., 2017, p. 81). Conversations by NGOs and peacebuilders with Muslim parents should emphasize the harmful effects of child forced marriage on a girl's schooling, health, and well-being. Such talk should refrain from stigmatizing parents because, as this research demonstrated, they usually believe that the practice is for their daughter's best welfare (Plan International, 2018, p. 33). Norms that raise the value of women in society should be encouraged as was demonstrated predominant support for patriarchy values among Muslim-Thai (Sateemae et al., 2017, p. 81). For instance, find employing Islamic-themed self-help books for direction on Islamic matters and values: since women are in charge of their kids' education, mothers should be educated and scholarly (Eliyanah & Yannuar, 2022).

Tradition: Since religion and Muslim practices, like religion, are essential for society, the religious leader is at the heart of their network. Therefore, programs must be developed to address the religious leader in order to promote behavior change. Religious leaders can use their area of worship as a platform to reproach child forced marriage. In Thailand, Islamic committees began joining government agencies to increase awareness and contain child forced marriage underneath Islamic customs (Plan International, 2018, p. 33). Public awareness campaigns to emphasize the nature and damage caused by forced marriages and community programs to help detect, advise, rehabilitate, and shelter when necessary are essential to combat early marriage effectively.

Summary, Conclusion, and Recommendations

Summary: Thai Muslim cultural behavior allows underage rape under the guise of a religious wedding. The practice is related to "Why-Educate and Dowry," "Housewife," and "Tradition." Hence, address harmful cultural behaviors, increase women's value in society by reinforce the value of woman's education, and raise awareness about the consequences of child forced marriage.

Conclusion: There is a cultural belief among Thai Muslims that there is no problem that Muslim Thai girls getting married young. Addressing cultural norms by raising awareness of the consequences of child forced marriage impacts decreasing the practice.

Recommendations: Raise awareness about the consequences of child forced marriage among religious leaders and the Thai population. Also, develop awareness among families about the importance of the girls' education. Promote cultural norms to empower girls to advocate on their behalf, for instance develop possibilities to sustain Thai-Muslim girls to hold their opinions listened to and to participate meaningfully in provincial Muslim discussions and endeavors to finish child forced marriage – including policy reform and security and monitoring procedures (Plan International, 2018, p. 33). Also, raise awareness about the consequences of child forced marriage among religious leaders and the Thai population.

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08 - Mediatized Expressions of Religious Authority and Diversity in South Africa

Lee-Shae Scharnick-Udemans

This presentation explores the ways in which religious authority and religious diversity have been mediatized through public broadcast television and social media in South Africa. By positioning public broadcast television within its historical and institutional context I will illustrate how religious diversity and pluralism have been mediatized through constitutional mandates, institutional policies, and traditional religious authority. I argue that the public broadcasting approach has produced limited representations of religious diversity while continuing to favour one tradition over others. On the contrary, I suggest that through social media, individual actors are producing more expansive representations of religious diversity, usurping the primacy and power of both traditional media and expressions of religious authority. In conclusion, I argue that for the researcher of religion, social media presents an opportunity to encounter and engage in expressions of religious diversity that go beyond official discourses and reflect the nuances that characterise the conditions of religious co-existence in pluralist societies.

Introduction

The study of religion and media has long been established as a legitimate sub-field in Religious Studies. In lieu of the politics of knowledge production, this field of inquiry looks to what might be considered non-traditional sites and sources of religious knowledge, expression, and experience in order to make sense of the expansive functionality and utility of religion across time and space. Following a Durkheimian approach, this position suggests that religion, as a conceptual framework for understanding how human beings align themselves with both that which is considered transcendent and/ or sacred, is essentially produced and enacted through human interactions with a variety of technologies and techniques, including those proffered by electronic and digital media.

The protection and promotion of religious diversity and pluralism are essential for building safe and just societies where difference is not only acknowledged but also accepted, affirmed and appreciated as a reflection of the multifariness of human existence and experiences. South Africa is a multi-religious, semi-secular democratic state with a liberal constitutional framework that protects religious freedom and promotes religious diversity as a celebrated feature of the post-apartheid socio-political context. The national public broadcaster, the SABC, has played an important and enduring role in ensuring the production and dissemination of broadcasting material through the forms of radio and television, that meets both an editorial and constitutional commitment to promoting religious diversity (SABC Policy Document, 2020). The institutional authority of the SABC as the national broadcaster is entrenched in national policy. In a country marred by income inequality, the SABC remains the most accessible if not reliable source of information for the majority of South Africans. The institution commissions a range of content which includes programming that is specifically religious in its orientation. It is also a space where traditional religious authority is mediated to conform to broadcasting policies and circulated, nationally under its endorsement. This presentation forms part of the pilot study for a larger project on Religion and Digital Culture in Africa.

Conceptual and Theoretical Framing

The following concepts underpin this study. First is religious diversity and its co-constituent of religious pluralism. The distinction between religious diversity and religious pluralism is often described as the former, being the social reality of religious difference and the latter as the value as a culturally, religiously, theologically, or politically informed value, orientation towards religious diversity which sees the existence of difference as positive and valuable. Following the example of sociologist Nancy Ammerman (2010, pp.155) who questions the assumptions that have produced an easy, taken-for-granted almost uncritical distinction between religious diversity and religious pluralism asserts that “...*religious pluralism is the normal state of affairs. Religion itself is multi-dimensional, and the several dimensions of religious and spiritual experience can be combined in myriad ways across individual lives.* I take the position that religious diversity does not only include diversity as the presence of religious differences but also extends to internal diversity within religious groups such as the presence of various denominations, minority groups, sectarian groups and the diverse ways in which individuals interpret and experience religions based on their social locations and positionality. This position also reveals the limitations of religious pluralism as a marker of the acceptance of religious diversity precisely because of the tendency to categorise religious “diversity” as only the acceptance of religious differences between groups. This in turn allows for an undoing of simplistic understanding of what religious pluralism is and how it operates within the context of not only multiple religions but also along intersectional axes of power and privilege.

The second concept is religious authority as considered within the context of Digital Religion Studies which presupposes that the ongoing growth of religion in digital spaces has indelibly altered the ways in which religious authority is produced and circulated as well as by whom it is embodied. As leading scholars of Digital Religion, Campbell and Bellar (2023) explain, the familiar Weberian explanation of traditional authority, charismatic authority and legal-rational authority may be identified through the novel context of digital religions. Campbell and Bellar assert that religious authority is ascribed to one of four sources including, 1) religious leaders, 2) sacred texts, 3) religious structures or organisations, and 4) specific theologies of religious teachings. The affordances and logics of digital media provide novel spaces where these sources of authority may be re-constructed, circulated, and challenged.

Finally, ‘mediatising’, derived from the concept of mediatisation is connected to the ways in which “high-tech media logic” determines and transforms the content and materials with which it engages. Mediatising may then be considered in its common usage, the way in which things, ideas and places are known through media logic and technologies. Following this assertion, the SABC may then be considered a site for the mediatisation of South African society. It is against this background that I first explore ways in which religious diversity has been mediatised through the institutional position and practices of the South African broadcasting co-operation as a source and site of traditional media

Discussion

The SABC recognizes the following as “major” religions, Christianity, Islam, Judaism, African Religions and Hinduism. While South Africa is in fact a constitutional democracy that does not have an official religious character, the statistics of the country show that Christians constitute the numerical majority. These statistics require much further scrutiny since they do account for the many ways in which multiple religious belonging, the overlap of religion and culture, and indeed personal religious diversity are in fact not quantifiable via questionnaires. Therefore, while it is not possible to claim that South Africa is legally or

constitutionally a Christian country, it is fair to conclude that Christianity enjoys a number of socio-political and cultural privileges (Scharnick-Udemans, 2020). In terms of public broadcast media, especially television, there is far more faith-specific Christian content than the collective content of other religions. For example, Islam, Judaism, African Religions, and Hinduism collectively account for an estimated average of three hours per week whereas Christian-oriented programming is nearly three times that amount. Unnamed micro-minority religious groups such as Wiccans, Sikhs, Hare Krishna and the Baha'i Faith may be featured on multi-faith programming which is more topical in nature and do not enjoy specific timeslots or regular airtime.

The faith-specific programmes mediatise all modes of religious authority mentioned previously and are generally accepted by the traditional religious authorities and institutions who often feature on the programmes and participate in the national religious broadcasting panel (RBP) According to the policy, "The relationship between the RBP, the Board, management and the religious community should be one of co-operation, while recognizing that the SABC Board is ultimately responsible for matters of policy." All the content of these faith-specific programmes is subjected to the terms and conditions that the SABC sets out in its religious broadcasting policy which claims to:

"In its religious programming, the SABC seeks to correct gender, racial, religious and resource allocation imbalances associated with religious broadcasting in the past. Further, it seeks to ensure that the distinctive identities of the religious traditions are broadcast in a way that facilitates the religious and moral objectives of justice, social harmony and the common good. Religious programming should play a meaningful part in the moral regeneration of South Africa" (SABC Policy Booklet, 2020). Religious broadcasting is therefore also, a political tool, that mediatises traditional religious authority through the institutional authority of the SABC as the national broadcaster.

Social Media

Digital Religion studies may be considered a sub-discipline of Religion and Media studies. Its proponents suggest its genesis is connected to the rise of the field of study called Internet studies. The genealogy of Digital Religion Studies seems to imply an evolutionary theorisation of religion and digital media, one which assumes that one mode of media, or one set of media logics replaces another. However, as African scholars of religion and media have shown, in the varying contexts of technological developments and accessibility on the continent, media technologies and techniques appear to develop alongside each other. This may explain why in South Africa there still exists a strong culture of public broadcasting alongside the rise of social media. Social Media sites such as Instagram, Twitter, and TikTok represent spaces where religious diversity and difference may be encountered, expressed, and experienced in hitherto unavailable ways and means. It also provides a space to observe the varying ways in which religious pluralism might be enacted by a variety of individuals based on the responses and comments that come from other social media users.

While the genesis of digital religion studies does not necessarily apply to this context, the theory of the shifting religious authority which is thoroughly identified and theorised in Digital Religion Studies offers a critical lens for discerning how religious diversity and religious authority may be expressed and enacted on social media platforms.

In response to the limitations of public broadcast media which is highly institutionalised and regulated through the policy frameworks of the SABC, the constitutional mandates which govern the entire enterprise of public media and the limitation of the media affordances, social media offers a more accessible and democratic space for individuals to express their religiosity. Social media is a lens through which to view the everyday experiences of the

individuals who use it. This is not to imply that social media is a wherein there are no limitations, indeed each social networking platform has its norms and structures which dictate the kinds of content that can and cannot be posted and circulated. By the same token, users are able to subvert challenges to exercise their free expression by deploying creative means such as replacing a number with a letter in order to use profanity or utilising non-written or verbal communication such as emoticons or gestures to still communicate what might be considered unacceptable or even harmful content. Here I share one example of shifting religious authority and religious diversity encountered on social media.

In South Africa, as in the Global North Muslim women content creators feature significantly and are leaders in the genre of digital lifestyle content creation. Digital lifestyle content is mainly associated with the social media platform Instagram which was originally developed as a photo-sharing platform but later evolved into a multi-modal application for audio-visual sharing and real-time engagement. Historically, Instagram has been associated with the presentation of well-curated visuals and the showcasing of fashion of all varieties. While there are not yet extended studies of Muslim lifestyle content creators in South Africa, close observation suggests that Muslim lifestyle content creators may or may not explicitly self-identify as Muslim or be recognized as such through their chosen dress code observances. While the majority of Muslim content creators are women, they do not present homogeneously and the mainstay of the content that they produce is not defined by its religious character and covers a number of areas of interest and concern including fashion, fitness, mental health, parenting, politics, wellness among others. Therefore, the prefix Muslim must be carefully considered and not conflated with the notion of Islamic, because it does not define the nature of the content but rather speaks to the religious identity of the content creator. Muslim content creators express their religious identities, beliefs, and practices patently as they see appropriate and it may be implied through their lifestyle choices and this is shared, via the everyday depiction of their lived realities through the capabilities that Instagram as their chosen platform allows and the conventions that content creators are expected to follow. Whereas Warren working on the UK context claims that Muslim lifestyle media is characterized by “Muslim women producing content for other Muslim women” and suggest a focus on content that is informed by notions of Muslimness and womanhood, the ways in which Muslim women’s lifestyle content creators engage on their platforms contest this assertion.

A South African* Muslim content creator who runs a business on Instagram which is listed as a Holistic Health Service regularly posts content related to women’s menstrual health and fertility and the ways in which the Feminine Divine is embodied in all women. She encourages women of religions to unlock their femininity through a range of practices including yoni-steaming, menstruation rituals, the consumption of herbal teas and yogic breathing practices. All her content engages her identity as both a healer and a Muslim.

During the month of Ramadan, she took to her platform to discuss issues of menstrual shame and shaming those Muslim women experience especially when they are religiously exempt from the fast while menstruating. She used her platform to provide a theologically sound and affirming explanation for why the exemption from fasting on account of menstruation or illness of any kind should be treated as mercy from the Divine and should not invoke practices of shaming from society or internalised shame. Her explanation included the invocation of religious scriptures, together with reflection on her own experiences. Many followers shared her video and commented that they found it extremely helpful in understanding and accepting the religious underpinning of the exemption. Others shared that her message had helped them to release the shame through socially imposed menstrual taboos by her provision of a religiously informed explanation. In this example, we

see both charismatic and legal-rational religious authority at play and although this kind of engagement might not be endorsed by traditional religious institutions, the responses of her followers tell another story. While this woman is indeed a Muslim content creator, she does not deliver sermons, provide formal religious advice or claim traditional religious authority yet her example demonstrates that in sharing their lives within the genres, conventions and parameters of social media platforms space for the encounter and observation of shifting, deinstitutionalised religious authority and expansive religious diversity.

Conclusion

It is evident that social media provides more opportunities for members of minority groups to express and mediatise their religious beliefs and practices thereby enhancing opportunities for encountering religious diversity than is available through traditional media formats. Under the media logic and affordances of social media, we see more diverse representation in terms of not only ‘what’ is represented but also ‘who’ is representing. It is through the media logic and affordances that shape the content that is produced by content creators as opposed to institutional policies that traditional religious is reconfigured in digital contexts.

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09 - Energy, International Cooperation, and Sustainable Peace Nexus: A Case Study of Morocco

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Abstract

This article explores the nexus between energy, international cooperation, and sustainable peace in Morocco. It analyzes the country's efforts to promote renewable energy as a means to enhance sustainable development, reduce carbon emissions, and foster regional cooperation. Using secondary sources, the study shows that Morocco has made significant efforts in implementing its energy policy objectives, particularly in developing solar and wind power plants and engaging in international partnerships to mobilize resources and expertise. The article argues that Morocco's energy strategy can contribute to sustainable peace by promoting international cooperation between Africa and Europe, as well as by mitigating the risks of climate change and reducing dependence on fossil fuels. The study concludes that Morocco's experience offers valuable insights for other countries seeking to promote sustainable development, renewable energy, and peaceful international cooperation.

Keywords:

Energy, international cooperation, sustainable peace, renewable energy, Morocco

I. Introduction

The global energy landscape is undergoing a significant transformation, primarily driven by the urgent need to mitigate climate change risks and promote sustainable development. Renewable energy sources, including solar, wind, and hydroelectric power, have emerged as alternative solutions to address these challenges. Beyond their environmental benefits, renewable energy sources also offer opportunities for international cooperation and sustainable peace, enabling countries to collaborate in developing and sharing resources, knowledge, and technologies.

Morocco, a North African country, has emerged as a leading example that has embraced renewable energy and international cooperation to enhance sustainable development and promote peaceful relations. As such, this article explores the nexus between energy, international cooperation, and sustainable peace in Morocco and its implications for other countries. Specifically, the article focuses on the North-South energy cooperation between Morocco-Spain and Morocco-UK, which has set an example of a win-win partnership in meeting energy needs and achieving sustainable development.

Therefore, this article contributes to the discourse on renewable energy, international cooperation, and sustainable peace, with Morocco's experience serving as a case study. It highlights the importance of North-South energy cooperation and equitable distribution of benefits in achieving a just energy transition and sustainable development. Finally, the article concludes with a discussion of the broader implications of energy on international peace and cooperation.

Context

In 2009, Morocco has set a goal to achieve 52% renewable energy in its electrical mix by 2030, reflecting its commitment to transition towards a low-carbon economy. The country plans to achieve its 2030 renewable energy target by generating 20% of its power from solar energy, 20% from wind energy, and 12% from hydro energy. In order to accomplish this, the

country intends to increase its renewable energy capacity by roughly 10 GW between 2018 and 2030, which will include the addition of 4,560 MW of solar capacity, 4,200 MW of wind capacity, and 1,330 MW of hydropower capacity.

Political stability in Morocco is a key factor that supports the energy transition process, and the government of Morocco has introduced policies to encourage renewable energy investment, such as tax incentives. These policies have attracted both domestic and foreign investment in the renewable energy sector, contributing to the country's progress toward its renewable energy goals. Despite geopolitical challenges posed by the Moroccan Western Sahara issue, Morocco's focus on renewable energy remains steadfast, supported by its stable political environment and commitment to sustainable development.

Figure 1. Gas Maghreb Europe Pipeline Route

Source: Natural Gas World, 2021

For Morocco, which heavily depends on foreign energy sources, this move presents a significant challenge to its energy security and economic development. Therefore, reducing its dependence on imported energy sources is an existential must.

An Overview of Xlink Power Project and Energy Cooperation

The Xlinks Morocco-UK Power Project is a groundbreaking electricity generation initiative that aims to produce zero-carbon electricity using solar and wind energy. The project will be in Guelmim Oued Noun, a region in Morocco known for its abundant renewable energy resources. The electricity generated from this facility will be exclusively connected to the UK through 3,800km (Figure 2) of sub-sea cables designed for High Voltage Direct Current transmission. The project is expected to generate 10.5GW of zero-carbon electricity using solar and wind power and will provide 3.6GW of reliable energy for an average of 20+ hours a day.

This capacity is sufficient to power over 7 million homes in the UK by 2030, making it an attractive low-cost and clean energy option. Once complete, the project is projected to satisfy 8% of Great Britain's electricity needs. In addition to its consistent output from solar panels and wind turbines, the project will feature a 20GWh/5GW battery facility onsite that

will offer ample storage to guarantee a dedicated, near-constant source of clean energy for the UK.

This facility is designed to supplement the renewable energy already generated in the UK. During periods of low winds and short sun hours, the project will take advantage of the long hours of sun in Morocco and the consistency of its Trade Winds to provide a firm yet a flexible source of zero-carbon electricity.

Figure 2. The Proposed Route of the Xlink Power Project

Source: Own elaboration based on PV Magazine Group, 2022

The Xlinks Morocco-UK Power Project represents a significant advancement in renewable energy generation and has the potential to significantly reduce carbon emissions in the UK.

Problem Statement

Morocco is a non-petroleum country and thus relies on foreign sources to meet 90.5% of its energy demand. As part of its National Strategy of Energy Efficiency, Morocco has reduced its energy dependency ratio from 97.5% in 2009 to 90.5% in 2020. Despite these efforts in energy transition, a reduction of only 7% in 11 years is not sufficient to achieve the Ministry's goal of increasing the share of renewable energies in the electrical mix to over 52% by 2030. Thus, the problem is how to leverage international cooperation to address the national energy crisis and achieve sustainable peace.

Purpose

This article aims to examine the nexus between energy, international cooperation, and sustainable peace in Morocco. Specifically, it analyzes the country's efforts to promote renewable energy as a means to enhance sustainable development, reduce carbon emissions, and foster regional cooperation. The study also discusses the implications of Morocco's energy policy for sustainable peace and international cooperation.

II. Concepts

Renewable Energy: Renewable energy, according to the International Energy Agency (IEA), refers to energy obtained from natural processes that are replenished more quickly than they are used up. Solar, wind, geothermal, hydro, and biomass are some examples of renewable energy sources mentioned by the IEA. Unlike fossil fuels, renewable energy sources do not emit greenhouse gases and have lower environmental impacts.

International Cooperation: International cooperation has been widely discussed in the field of international relations, where scholars have debated the emergence and continuity of cooperation in a global system without a governing authority. A common definition of cooperation is when actors modify their actions to match the real or anticipated desires of others. Thus, cooperation, especially on an international level, pertains to interactions aimed at achieving shared goals when the preferences of actors are not entirely congruent (harmony) or completely conflicting.

Sustainable Peace: Sustainable peace refers to any efforts made by both global and local players aimed at reinforcing and sustaining peace within a particular social framework. Sustainable peace is not just the absence of violence but also includes positive social, economic, and political developments that promote social justice and human security. Sustainable peace is a long-term process that requires ongoing efforts and commitment from all stakeholders involved.

III. Methodology

This study is based on a review of secondary sources, including academic literature, government reports, and media articles. The sources were selected based on their relevance to the research questions and the credibility of the authors and publishers. The data were analyzed using a thematic approach, focusing on the key themes of renewable energy, international cooperation, and sustainable peace.

IV. Findings

Morocco's energy policy is centered on expanding renewable energy to enhance sustainable development, reduce carbon emissions, and promote regional cooperation. The country has set a target of generating 52% of its electricity from renewable sources by 2030, with a particular focus on solar and wind power. To achieve this goal, Morocco has launched several initiatives, including the Noor Solar Complex, the largest solar power plant in the world, and the Tarfaya Wind Farm, one of the largest wind farms in Africa. Morocco has also developed partnerships with international organizations and countries, such as the European Union and China, to mobilize resources and expertise to support its energy transition.

Morocco's energy policy has several implications for sustainable peace and international cooperation. Firstly, the expansion of renewable energy can reduce dependence on fossil fuels and mitigate the risks of climate change, which can be a source of conflict and insecurity. For instance, droughts and water scarcity, which are exacerbated by climate change, can lead to competition over resources and trigger conflicts between communities.

By promoting renewable energy, Morocco can contribute to regional stability and reduce the risk of conflicts related to energy and environmental issues.

Lastly, Morocco's energy strategy has the potential to improve regional collaboration and unity. Due to its location at the crossroads of Africa and Europe, Morocco can play a crucial role in renewable energy development as a regional center. Morocco and Spain's collaboration on natural gas and the ongoing innovative initiative between Morocco and the UK are both excellent examples of promoting regional energy cooperation, which promotes sustainable peace and stability in the region.

V. Conclusion

In conclusion, the benefits of energy cooperation go beyond just energy security and access. It is a multidimensional concept that is interconnected with other sectors such as job creation, economic opportunities, and technology transfer. The examples of successful energy cooperation initiatives between Morocco, Spain, and the UK demonstrate how this can lead to sustainable peace and stability in the region.

The article concludes that instead of engaging in conflict with Algeria, Morocco has chosen to focus on enhancing cooperation with other countries that share the same goals of promoting sustainable development, renewable energy, and peaceful international cooperation. This approach not only reduces the risk of conflict but also provides opportunities for mutual benefits, such as building energy security, and increased economic growth. Overall, the article highlights the importance of prioritizing cooperation and collaboration over conflict and competition in the pursuit of regional development and stability.

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10 - Interculturality as a Paradigm to Promote Social and Environmental Flourishing in the Present Milieu

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Abstract

In our globalized and interconnected world with multiple social and ecological concerns, promoting social and environmental flourishing requires a paradigm of cultural interaction that can respond to the present milieu. This study examines the relevance of interculturality as a paradigm for this task, drawing from social sciences, religious studies, and environmental philosophy with particular focus on the themes of interculturality, multiculturalism, and culture-nature relationship. Through a qualitative analysis, this study explores how interculturality can promote social and environmental flourishing. Interculturality emphasizes mutual exchange, enrichment, collaboration, and transformation while opposing negative social tendencies like ethnocentrism, narrow nationalism, and the zero-sum mindset. As culture is embedded in nature, interculturality can raise awareness of the integral connection between culture and nature, promoting greater appreciation for environmental conservation. This study also examines how the Society of the Divine Word (SVD) employs interculturality as a core value in both its approach to communal living and missionary work. This paper demonstrates that while often considered a model for socio-cultural interaction, interculturality also has an environmental dimension that warrants further exploration to highlight its positive impact on the contemporary world.

Keywords: interculturality, cultural interaction, social flourishing, environmental flourishing

1. Introduction

The world is in constant flux due to various reasons, including migration for work, business, and escape from natural calamities. Advances in digital communication technology have also enabled billions of people to connect globally. At the same time, humanity is facing numerous challenges such as geopolitical tension, interreligious conflicts, fake news, infodemics, and environmental degradation. Interculturality can serve as a relevant concept for current contexts and can be effectively used as a paradigm of cultural interaction to promote social and environmental flourishing. This essay proposes that interculturality has both social and environmental implications that can positively impact the world.

2. Literature Review

Culture is an essential component of human life and is examined across various fields. It can be defined in numerous ways, with different nuances and emphases. Louis Luzbetak (1988), a cultural anthropologist, defines culture as “a socially shared design for living.” However, this design is not universally shared, which is why in some places, simply leaving one’s home province can result in a significant cultural shift. As societies become increasingly multicultural, it is crucial to promote positive interactions between people of different

backgrounds. Interculturality, a concept dating back to the mid-20th century, has become increasingly vital in recent decades in both secular and religious spheres. Cultural exchange can vary depending on multiple factors. New migrants to a country may assimilate to the dominant culture voluntarily or by force, which can lead to cultural homogenization and loss of diversity. A better process is cultural integration, where minority groups adopt aspects of the dominant culture while retaining their original culture, creating a multicultural reality.

Interculturality in recent years has become a paradigm advocated by social scientists as a practical approach to cultural encounters. It prioritizes relationships based on exchange, dialogue, and mutual transformation. According to Daniel Pietrzak (2006), interculturality is an ongoing process of development through interaction between members of different cultural groups. It promotes mutual respect and reciprocity, rejecting the idea that one must give up their identity to become like the dominant group. Similarly, it rejects the notion that cultures are so different that no common ground can be established among them. While each culture is unique, there are also cultural overlaps that make them different and the same (Kisala, 2009).

Multiculturalism has become prevalent in today's world, with many organizations and communities comprising members from various cultural and national backgrounds. In these settings, coexistence and tolerance are often emphasized for social harmony. Interculturality goes beyond affirming cultural diversity to emphasize the dynamic exchanges taking place among people of different cultural backgrounds. Interculturality promotes mutual exchange between cultures that can lead to transformation and enrichment for all involved. Stanislaus and Tauchner (2021) assert that interculturality results in mutually reciprocal relationships among cultures, where people learn and grow together, enrich each other, and challenge one another's cultural values and practices towards mutual transformation.

3. Methodology

This paper is a qualitative examination of interculturality and its importance in fostering social and environmental flourishing. Various works in the fields of social sciences, religious studies, and environmental philosophy are utilized for this analysis. Specifically, the study explores intercultural communication, multiculturalism, and the interplay between culture and nature as presented in the literature. By considering these themes, the paper aims to shed light on the significance of interculturality in promoting a harmonious relationship between society and the environment as well as the well-being of both. The paper also examines how the Society of the Divine Word applies this paradigm to its communal life and missionary work.

4. Discussion

4.1. Interculturality and Social Flourishing

Interculturality promotes social flourishing by seeking mutual transformation rather than mere co-existence or tolerance. Through active engagement and learning from one another, interculturality can lead to the realization that certain cultural elements may conflict with values of peace, justice, and equality (Stanislaus & Ueffing, 2015; Stanislaus, 2022). It offers the possibility of a new synthesis resulting from mutual gifting during cultural exchanges, facilitating collaboration while countering negative tendencies like the zero-sum mindset, ethnocentrism, and narrow nationalism. The zero-sum mindset is the perception that one group's gain necessarily denotes another's loss. This mindset erodes trust and promotes hostility, leading to anti-cooperative and aggressive means to advance one's interests (Fearon et al., 2021). In contrast, interculturality assumes that inclusive and collaborative

engagement can lead to mutually beneficial solutions that build a harmonious and sustainable society.

Second, interculturality can be a powerful tool in promoting social flourishing by addressing ethnocentrism. Ethnocentrism refers to the belief that one's own group is the center of everything, with all other groups being scaled and rated with reference to it (Sumner, 1906). While not inherently negative, ethnocentrism often leads to the perception that one's own race, ethnicity, or culture is superior to others. This belief can severely limit cultural exchange among members of the society. At its most extreme, ethnocentrism can result in acts of persecution, exploitation, and violation of human rights by one group against another. Throughout history, there have been countless instances of genocide resulting from extreme ethnocentrism. In contrast, interculturality fosters an appreciation for a diversity of cultural values, practices, and perspectives, which contributes to building a more inclusive and peaceful society.

Third, interculturality aims to counter the negative effects of narrow nationalism, which involves an excessive and exclusionary focus on one's own national identity to the detriment of others. While a healthy sense of national pride can be positive, narrow nationalism often leads to hostility towards other cultures and nations. This can manifest as discrimination and exclusionary attitudes towards members of different cultural groups within the same country. Ethnic identity may be conflated with national identity, and the presence of other cultural or religious groups may be seen as a threat to national welfare and purity. Interculturality promotes a global mindset that encourages people to move beyond self-interest and solipsistic thinking. By fostering collaboration and mutual enrichment, interculturality helps to counteract the negative effects of narrow nationalism, building a more inclusive and harmonious society.

4.2. Interculturality and Environmental Flourishing

Interculturality goes beyond social and cultural aspects, and also has significant environmental implications. By adopting this model, it is possible to deepen our understanding of the relationship between culture and nature and recognize the need to prioritize environmental well-being as part and parcel of social and cultural promotion. Pope Francis (2015) highlights the interconnectedness of social and environmental flourishing in his concept of 'integral ecology,' which resonates with the thought of liberation theologian Leonardo Boff (1997) who broadened the scope of liberation theology to include the natural environment. By integrating environmental concerns into intercultural interactions, we can work towards a sustainable future that benefits both humanity and the natural world.

To start the discussion on how interculturality promotes environmental flourishing, it is crucial to examine the relationship between nature and culture from a philosophical viewpoint. Despite various scholarly disciplines such as sociology, anthropology, and environmental philosophy having debated the distinction between culture and nature, a consensus is yet to be reached. Holmes Rolston III (1999) highlights that nature and culture differ in their transmission methods, as genes transfer information in nature and humans transmit cultural knowledge neurally. While there may be similarities between certain aspects of human culture and nature, such as the law of aerodynamics being applied in the motion of both birds and planes, it is incorrect to equate these two intrinsically different phenomena.

Rather than perpetuating the dichotomy between humans and nature, J. Baird Callicott (1992) urges for humans to be integrated back into nature through a new dynamic and systemic postmodern concept of nature. Similarly, Marc Bekoff (2000) envisions a worldwide community where humans perceive themselves "as a part of nature and not apart from her."

These sentiments echo that of Deep Ecology which sees nature as a unified totality inclusive of every creature, and humans are but a single node on the gigantic tree of life. Additionally, J.M. Schaeffer (2007) emphasizes that the social and cultural aspects of humans do not disconnect them from their biological reality, and he calls for an end to the human exception by recognizing that humans are just one among many living beings since “the social and the cultural are deeply dependent on the biological.”

Religious leaders have also affirmed the intimate connection between humanity and nature. Pope Francis (2015) asserts, “Nature cannot be regarded as something separate from ourselves or as a mere setting in which we live. We are part of nature, included in it and thus in constant interaction with it.” The late Vietnamese monk Thich Nhat Hanh (1988) remarks, “We should deal with nature the way we should deal with ourselves! We should not harm ourselves; we should not harm nature...Human beings and nature are inseparable.”

While the phrase “part of nature” is commonly used, it can have different meanings depending on one’s worldview and ethical beliefs. However, there is a growing consensus that the dichotomy between humans and nature is false. Human beings are part of the natural world, and as such, human culture is intricately connected to nature. As Freya Matthews (1991) notes, “culture is an emanation of Nature.” Over the past 50 years, environmental literature has consistently highlighted anthropocentrism as the primary cause of the modern environmental crisis. Industrial and technological developments have led to human alienation from nature, and the remedy is for humans to recognize their connection to the natural world. This connection becomes particularly apparent when humans find themselves in the position of prey or predator, as is the case with other animals. Therefore, it is necessary to move away from the notion that humans are exceptional and instead embrace our place as one among many living beings. Dramatic encounters with nature can serve as powerful reminders of the inextricable connection between humans and nature. While nature can thrive without human beings, humans cannot exist without nature, which has been present for billions of years before the arrival of humans. As Holmes Rolston III (1999) observes, “Nature is the womb of culture, a womb that humans never entirely leave.” Consequently, the construction of culture will always be influenced by nature in some capacity.

The connection between human beings and nature is not limited to biological dimensions, but also extends to spiritual ones. Many millions of people worldwide believe that natural features such as mountains, rivers, forests, and individual trees are inhabited by spirits that must be respected. This belief is part of the animistic worldview, which holds that the spiritual and physical worlds are intrinsically linked and that all material phenomena have agency. Animism is a construct of anthropologists studying cultures and religions, rather than a concept articulated by indigenous people themselves. Nonetheless, many cultures continue to hold such beliefs even after formally adopting a religion.

For many cultures, the importance of nature extends beyond its sacredness to encompass its vital role in their way of life. For people living in forests, all animals and vegetation are essential to their lifestyle and cultural identity. The forest resources provide food, medicine, clothing, furniture, and entertainment. Nature is also incorporated into people’s cultural practices. While it may seem that modern culture has abandoned its roots in nature, this is not the case for every culture. Holmes Rolston III (1999) argues that nature is the “womb” of culture, and while culture has evolved out of nature, it has not left it entirely behind. While some cultures influenced by the Enlightenment mentality view nature as merely objects of scientific investigation and control, the convergence of culture and nature can still be seen in values, religious beliefs, spirituality, language, traditions, and livelihoods worldwide.

Interculturality, as a paradigm of cultural interaction that prioritizes environmental concerns, can bring about three main benefits: (1) increased awareness of the continuing importance of nature to culture; (2) deeper cultural understanding of the environment; and (3) the re-establishment of an ecological culture and civilization.

Firstly, interculturality can help individuals and communities recognize the ongoing significance of nature to culture. Through mutual exchange and enrichment, intercultural engagement provides an opportunity to learn from indigenous people around the world who have adapted their lifestyles in harmony with the environment (Pope Francis, 2015). By acknowledging the knowledge derived from the natural environment (Castro, 2021), intercultural exchange can foster empathy and understanding towards nature-oriented cultures, leading to actions that promote the flourishing of both culture and nature.

Secondly, interculturality can promote a deeper cultural understanding of the environment. The interdependence between culture and the environment means that any impact on one system will affect the other. Access to existing ecological knowledge and practices in various communities can provide insights into successfully navigating within available means and avoiding environmentally destructive practices (Pretty and Pilgrim, 2008). Intercultural dialogue also reduces the likelihood of development projects that exacerbate power imbalances, ignore environmental responsibilities, and fail to distribute benefits equitably.

Thirdly, interculturality can contribute to the re-establishment of an ecological culture and civilization. In societies where the exploitation of nature for technological development has led to alienation from nature, intercultural engagement can inspire reconnection with the natural world. Recovering the connection between culture and nature is crucial in developing a global ecological culture and civilization that recognizes humans as part of nature. Not doing so renders the claim meaningless and fails to guide the direction of future development.

5. Interculturality in the Society of the Divine Word

To demonstrate how interculturality can be promoted in specific contexts, this section explores the case of the Society of the Divine Word (SVD), a Roman Catholic missionary congregation established in 1875. The SVD operates globally, with over 6,000 members from more than 60 countries serving in over 80 countries. The SVD's commitment to interculturality is a fundamental aspect of their life and work and is enshrined in their Constitution. According to former General Superior Antonio Pernia, interculturality is intrinsic to the SVD's DNA and is essential to their self-understanding (Nguyen, 2013). As a result, many SVD scholars have published on the topic of interculturality, including some that have been cited in this essay, namely, Stanislaus, Ueffing, Tauchner, Nguyen, Kisala, and Castro.

In addition to academic discussions, the SVD's intercultural approach is evident in the cultural composition of its communities, which is intentionally diverse to reflect the global church's reality and to promote mutual learning and respect across cultures. Members of the congregation undergo extensive cross-cultural communication training before being sent on mission. In their community living and mission work, the SVD stresses the importance of intercultural living and cultural immersion. The experience of intercultural exchange and dialogue within the community builds solidarity, fraternal communion, and a shared vision.

Interculturality is also a core value of the SVD in its missionary approach, emphasizing the fostering of relationships through dialogue in the local context. SVD members seek to understand and respect the local cultures and traditions of the people they work with,

learning the local language, customs, and beliefs to build relationships based on mutual understanding and respect. This intentional effort allows SVD members to live and work effectively in various mission contexts worldwide. For example, the nearly 100 members in the Province of Australia, which includes Australia, New Zealand, Thailand, and Myanmar, come from 19 different countries and live and work in smaller intercultural communities ranging from several members to nearly 20 members. They work with indigenous peoples, migrants, refugees, asylum seekers, the marginalized, and people of other faiths and cultures (AUS Provincial Chapter Documents, 2023). The SVD Australia Province's vision and mission statement, adopted in March 2023 at the Provincial Chapter, affirms that intercultural living enables them to join hands with dialogue partners to "foster a culture of encounter and care for creation." Thus, the SVD's efforts to promote interculturality in community living and mission are a valuable model for promoting social and environmental flourishing in the present milieu.

6. Conclusion and Recommendations

Addressing the challenges facing humanity requires an understanding of the complexity of the issues, which necessitates a multifaceted approach. This means that environmental concerns cannot be addressed without considering social concerns and vice versa. The paradigm of interculturality, which is discussed in this essay as a model of cultural exchange, can contribute to promoting both social and environmental flourishing by promoting dialogue, reciprocity, and transformation while debilitating negative social tendencies. As cultural interactions become more prevalent than ever, a healthy model of engagement is imperative to ensure that flourishing is accessible to all – humans and nature. The SVD's efforts in this regard are a promising step, and this model should be widely adopted, not only in religious communities but in all contexts of intercultural engagement. Thus, interculturality can be applied in particular organizations, groups, communities, in an intentional manner. Through its widespread application in these contexts, interculturality can gain momentum and become the operative paradigm in the larger society and the world. It is important, therefore, that organization and community leaders explore interculturality with its related aspects such as intercultural communication and intercultural living in order to better understand and apply this paradigm to their specific contexts. Moreover, it is important to give attention to the environmental aspect of the paradigm to fully utilize its potential towards the common good.

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11 - Examining the Pedagogical Content Knowledge in World History of Pre-service Teachers

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ABSTRACT

This descriptive qualitative study aims to identify the gap in the pedagogical content knowledge (PCK) in World History that are learned from the university and in field study by pre-service teachers. The participants of the study were composed of 6 participants who were chosen using purposive sampling method. Interview was used to gather data which was analyzed using thematic analysis. As practiced in the school, the PCK in World History includes independent learning to make students content masters, technological transformation of content, contextualization and localization of lessons, and collaborative learning to clarify and refine concepts. In the field study, the PCK were lesson contextualization and localization, interactive activities for fun and informative lessons, differentiated instructions to address students' needs, Socratic teaching to develop high order thinking, pragmatic teaching to condition students and teacher-centered teaching to encourage understanding. Independent learning to develop inquiry and interpretive thinking is not religiously practiced in high school while interest-based teaching that allows for development of history fluency is neglected in the university.

Keywords: field study, history, pedagogical content knowledge, Social Studies teachers

Introduction

Pre-service teachers must master pedagogical content knowledge (PCK), which integrates pedagogy and content to teach the "what" and "how" (Shing, Saat and Loke, 2015). Pre-service teachers need PCK to link global historical events, from the biggest to the smallest, to construct compelling narratives for themselves and their students in social studies and world history (Harris and Bain, 2010). Thus, pre-service teachers must master PCK throughout teacher training to build successful teaching and learning settings (Blömeke and Delaney, 2012) and become effective history instructors. The Philippine Commission on Higher Education (CHED) Memorandum Order No.75, s. 2017 mandates students in the Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSEd) program majoring in Social Studies to receive multi-disciplinary content and pedagogy training. Likewise, Department of Education (DepEd) Order No.35, s. 2016, states that teachers must continually enhance their material and pedagogical knowledge, practice, abilities, and attitudes to provide a true teaching-learning environment for students.

Since teaching World History is difficult, the university and cooperating school should provide pre-service teachers meaningful experiences to develop appropriate PCK (Kathirveloo et al., 2014). However, many pre-service teachers lack pedagogical training which lead to their struggles to build and model their knowledge to students (Lee, 2014). They failed to complete all pedagogical duties (Khoza, 2017). Although very important in teaching-learning process, the PCK of history teachers is understudied (Tuithof, 2021). There is also no evidence linking pre-service teachers' practical teaching experiences to their

university education. (Coddington, 2020). Thus, this research seeks to discover any PCK gap in world history of pre-service teachers before and after field study immersion.

The problems that this paper addressed were the following:

1. What are the pedagogical content knowledge in World History that the preservice teachers learned in the university and gained from field study?
2. What are the pedagogical content knowledge gaps between what the pre-service teachers learned from the university and what they observed in their field study?

The purpose of this study is to identify the pedagogical content knowledge in World History that the pre-service teachers learned in the university and gained from field study. It also aims to examine the pedagogical content knowledge gaps in both circumstances of field study.

Literature Review

Tuithof et al. (2021) proposed four subject-related historical reasoning PCK components. These include (1) representing history, or how teachers communicate the nature and structure of historical knowledge to students; (2) transforming history, or how teachers transform historical content in lessons and materials that target historical understanding and thinking; (3) attending to students' ideas about history, including misconceptions and prior knowledge; and (4) framing history or selecting and arranging topics into a coherent story thereby framing a history curriculum that illustrates significance, connection, and interrelationships. However, Shulman identified two key PCK elements: (1) instructional strategies and representations, or how the teacher transforms subject matter knowledge, and (2) knowledge of students' understanding, or the learning process and content-related problems of students (Verloop, Van Driel, and Meijer, 2001). Successful content teaching requires pedagogical content expertise. PCK transforms topic knowledge into pedagogical products and teaching techniques for students (Solis, 2009). Thus, pre-service teachers, particularly those teaching World History or related Social Science courses, need it.

In order to blend pedagogy and content, which involves both the "what" and "how" of teaching, pre-service teachers need to have a solid understanding of PCK in university (Shing, Saat, and Loke, 2015) and in the field study (Harris and Bain, 2010). Pre-service teachers need PCK in order to link global historical events, ranging from the most significant to the most insignificant of them all, in order to build captivating narratives for both themselves and their pupils. According to VanSledright (2014), PCK in history should include expressing, reframing, or altering historical events while also listening to the perspectives of students. Therefore, pre-service teachers need to be skilled with PCK in order for them to become successful history teachers (Blomeke and Delaney, 2012). PCK is required to construct effective learning and teaching environments. Pre-service teachers should be given meaningful experiences that will equip them with relevant PCK which is essential to teaching and learning (Kathirveloo et al., 2014). These experiences should be provided by the university as well as the cooperating school where students will practice teaching. This is because teaching World History is tough.

Methodology

This study utilized the descriptive qualitative research method developed by Husserl (Conelley, 2010) which is used to create meanings of the individual's experience (Creswell, 2007). It used constructivism as the philosophical underpinning because it sought to understand PCK from the gathered data and from the views of the participants using semi-structured interview. In selecting the six participants, purposive sampling was used, and the following inclusion criteria was applied: (1) 4th year college student; (2) enrolled in a field study course; (3) willing to participate in the study and were already deployed 2 to 3 months in cooperating schools and (4) handled World History in their practice teaching. Those who were not assigned to teach World History were excluded. After transcribing the interview, MaxQDA software was used to encode the data and use the six-phase guide developed by Braun & Clarke (2006) for thematic analysis which included (1) data familiarization; (2) generating initial codes, (3) searching for themes, (4) reviewing themes, (5) defining themes, and (6) writing the paper. The goal was to identify themes or patterns in the data on PCK and used these themes to address the research gaps.

Findings

Pedagogical Content Knowledge in World History that Preservice Teachers Learned in the University

As practiced in the school, the PCK in World History includes independent learning to make students content masters, technological transformation of content, contextualization and localization of lessons, and collaborative learning to clarify and refine concepts. Since college students are expected to be independent learners, it is apparent from the experiences of the six participants that an independent learning approach was used in teaching World History in the university. Their teachers allow them to study a specific topic/lesson on their own, look for resources to substantiate it, and prepare the materials for classroom presentation. Independent learning lets students set goals and measure progress while taking ownership of their education (Vimmikas, 2022). Since students wrote their own lessons and made their own materials, it motivated and empowered them (Meyer, Haywood, Sachday, and Faraday, 2008).

Furthermore, teachers must become technologically savvy to incorporate technology into their World History teaching. During the pandemic, Juhi and Sakshita (2018) found that technology in the classroom improves instruction because it causes fundamental structural changes and improves university teaching and learning. Pre-pandemic lesson discussions include technology. World History students use technology to display their work.

Contextualized and localized education also improves Social Studies, especially World History. Localization connects curriculum-specific learning material to regional data and resources in the learners' community (Hasibuan, 2019), while contextualization promotes comprehension by focusing teaching and learning on real-world applications (Lorbis, 2019). For instance, many teachers discuss local heroes and events since students learn faster and remember more when topics are presented in context, making education relatable and practical. (Kitiashvili, 2020). University history teachers need localized examples, exercises, and illustrations.

In addition, collaboration may enhance learning when students get along (Scager, et. al., 2016). It clarifies topics and aids students. It boosts self-confidence and higher-order thinking. They also learn to work with various learners (Gates, 2018). Teachers divide students into groups to discuss issues. Brainstorming helps them learn and present material. They may brainstorm together by sharing their expertise.

Pedagogical Content Knowledge in World History that Preservice Teachers Gained from Field Study

In the field study, the PCK were lesson contextualization and localization, interactive activities for fun and informative lessons, differentiated instructions to address students' needs, Socratic teaching to develop high order thinking, pragmatic teaching to condition students and teacher-centered teaching to encourage understanding.

The resource teacher's contextualization and localization assist cooperating students at school grasp history. Contextualized and localized education improves classroom performance (Reyes, et. al., 2017). Thus, high school teachers pursue localization and contextualization, like universities. Since it's hard to make history fun, participants said their resource teacher contextualized and localized it. Interactive classroom activities improve critical thinking, engagement, and learning control (Clarke, 2022). Interactive games helped pupils concentrate and pay attention during discussions at cooperating schools. Gamification, GBL, and educational games can assist students enjoy conceptual learning and express their creativity. Game-based learning improves learning at all ages. (Azawi et al., 2016). Gamification in teaching improves student engagement.

Cooperating schools encourage students' ability to learn the subject. Differentiated instruction emphasizes that students learn best when teachers can determine their current levels of functioning and learning preferences and use this information to move them to higher levels of learning (Reis and Renzulli, 2018). Participants said high school has a by-category division where students in each grade level are divided into groups or sections with a sufficient class size. The previous year's grades were used to classify youngsters. They were grouped with like academics.

Cooperating schools also employ Socratic technique to help students understand. An exit ticket is utilized when the teacher offers a discussion question to assess student comprehension. Exit tickets increase learning by fostering active student engagement, knowledge links, self-reflection, and a goal for future learning (Toli and Kallery, 2020). It improves academics and behavior. Exit tickets seem to provide new learning possibilities.

Further, the cooperating school uses operant conditioning to motivate students by rewarding them for answering questions. Operant conditioning shows that rewarded behavior is more likely to be repeated than punished behavior (Renard, 2020) whereas conduct that is penalized is less likely to occur. Rewards were given to the learners who shared their learning from the discussion. Teachers increasingly provide information in teacher-centered learning. They organize all class activities. Participants said their resource teachers utilized just modules or books, a teacher-centered approach.

Gaps in PCK in World History between the University and Cooperating School

The research found two significant gaps: (1) autonomous learning to build inquiry and interpretative thinking is not properly performed in high school and (2) interest-based teaching to create historical fluency is disregarded in the university. Helping students become autonomous learners maximizes their classroom potential. Independent learning is key to a university education because college students are engaging in autonomous learning modes and thinking (Al-Maani, 2019), taking responsibility for their own learning, being self-directed, and choosing what to focus on and how much time to spend learning. Most institutions, including the study's participant, emphasize individual learning. Students are free to research and construct their own materials on prescribed subjects. Hence, university students are expected to have at least a higher level of independence in their learning once they enter higher education.

On the other hand, teaching based on students' interests involves teachers determining what students are interested in and then using those interests to guide and direct students' educational experiences. Students are encouraged to study by the use of their own intrinsic motivation, which allows teachers to spark students' enthusiasm for learning through the use of interest-based teaching (Juhi and Sakshita, 2018). This may be accomplished by associating historical events and ideas with learning experiences that are significant, current, and fascinating. The method of doing so allows teachers to customize the learning process in such a way that it caters to the interests of the students (Toli and Kallery, 2020), which may lead to improved academic performance in the classroom (Djudin, 2018). On the other hand, teachers of history at universities often ignore their students' passions and ignore this fact while teaching history lectures.

Conclusion

In the university, it is apparent that student-teachers are taught in a World History classroom using independent teaching method so that they become critical minded learners. This, however, is not usually the practice in secondary schools where students are spoon fed about the lessons most of the time. Hence, many of these students do not become independent critical thinkers. On the other hand, interest-based teaching in history classes is practiced in the secondary schools so that individual interest and skills of the students are tapped and enhanced. However, interest-based teaching in history classes is not practiced by teachers in the university due to fact that more independent learning methods are used by them to teach the course.

Recommendation

Teachers of history courses in the university should utilize interest-based teaching approaches to enhance the motivation of pre-service teachers in learning and understanding the courses. Pre-service teachers may be able to learn these approaches so they can apply it in their practice teaching and professional practice. Meanwhile, teachers of history courses in the secondary schools should utilize independent teaching approaches to prepare high school students for higher education while developing their interest in the subjects. Pre-service teachers may be able to learn these approaches so they can apply it in their practice teaching and professional practice. University and secondary school teachers should exchange best practices in PCK in history or even Social Studies classes through in-service trainings and seminars so that gaps in PCK identified in the study may be addressed.

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12 - Padan as A Religious Tolerance Relations Concept

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Abstract

This paper discusses Padan as a religious tolerance relation concept. Tolerance is essential in interreligious relations, but the problem is increasingly difficult to determine the concept of relation. What is the idea of a tolerance relationship as a standard principle that can be accepted and used collectively? Through this research, we offer a concept of relation tolerance that is Padan as a religious tolerance relation. The discussion uses qualitative and quantitative through literature, questionnaires, and interviews.

Keywords: Concept, Padan, Relation, Religion, Tolerance

Introduction

Problem Statement

Tolerance is essential for humans. It directs people to respect differences, accept each other's, appreciate existence, and understand that every human has differences. We tolerate others in their presence, views, and rights as a human (Eisenstein, 2008, p. 4; Erlewine, 2010, pp. 183-184; Hamonangan & Imamah, 2021, pp. 186-188; Stanton & Stroumsa, 1998, p. 357; Tyler, 2008, p. 86). Unfortunately, it is increasingly difficult to determine the religious tolerance relation concept as a standard principle that can be accepted and used collectively, neutral and balanced.

Research Question

Based on the abovementioned problem statement, what concepts can we offer for religious tolerance relation, the neutral (balanced), mutually taken in differences?

Purpose of Study

The study offers the concept of tolerance adopted from *Padan*, the idea of Batak people's relations for religious tolerance relations concepts.

Literature Review

Tolerance

In Bahasa (KBBI), tolerance (/to-le-ran-si/ n) is (1) the character or attitude of tolerance: two groups of different cultures are fully interconnected --; (2) measuring limits for additions or subtractions that are still allowed. In English Cambridge Dictionary, tolerance (/tɒl.ə'reɪ.jən/ US/'tɑ:.lə'reɪ.jən/) is a willingness to accept behavior and beliefs that are different from our own, although we might disagree with them. From these meanings, we can state that tolerance is the willingness to accept behavior or beliefs that differ from us, although we disagree.

It is also the same as conveyed by scholars, as implied by Andrew R. Murph, that tolerance is an attitude that admits the possible validity of seemingly contradictory viewpoints and hesitancy in passing value or truth judgments on individual or group belief (Murphy, 1997, p. 594). Furthermore, the tolerance range is wide. Tolerance is not only related to religious

perspective as Jay Newman's statement (Newman, 1978. p. 10) that tolerance corresponds to the verb tolerate. It means a man can handle all sorts of things, as a teacher can take the student's stupidity or lousy manner, a wife can tolerate the husband's eccentricities, and so on. But, still, there is yet to be a clear standard. Suppose we look at this from Christianity's perspective of love (tolerate). Love itself has no clear boundaries. We can love others as we love ourselves and should love our enemies (Matthew 5:43-44). Even if our tolerance neglect, we must love and forgive seventy times seven (Matt. 18: 21-22) (Hamonangan & Imamah, 2021, p. 186; Jewett, 1982, pp. 23-28). We do not have a concrete form as the standard principle of tolerance relations.

The Batak and The Concept in Batak

The Batak tribe is the third largest ethnic group in Indonesia after the Javanese and Sundanese. If we call the Batak concept, it means a principle or wisdom held and practiced that uses ideas, the image of custom or culture, or the direction of life that regulate relationships as a set of inherited beliefs approved by the ancestors that govern all life. One concept from Batak is *Padan*, a promise relation (Causey, 2007, p. 275; Nyhus, 1987, p. 3; Pederson, 1970, p. 35; Siahaan. B, 2011, pp. 10-15; Situmorang M. E., 2018, p. 33; Situmorang. S, 1981, p. 40; Hamonangan, 2015, p. 100; Harahap, 1960, pp. 24-77; Napitupulu, 1972, p. 21).

The *Padan* is a promise between the two clans bound by the ancestors long ago and binds the descendants until now. The story of the agreement's formation (*Padan*) varies. The story of each family is different. Each has its own story. Some of them: are: 1. Child exchange, 2. Competition, 3. Aid or help, 4. War or conflict, 5. Cooperation, and else. For example, *Padan* occurs through the exchange of children. Clan A did not have children; due to this condition, B's child took to become A's child. Because of this, A could continue the lineage. A promise makes that A and B are *Padan*. Or *Padan* occurs through the conflict (war); in conflict condition, A helps B, and then they make a *Padan* that they are the same.

The Concept of *Padan* Relationship

Padan is a promise. Simply, there are three points of *Padan*. First, the concept of *Padan* is a promise that makes the same. Second, the idea of *Padan* prioritizes one another over another. Third, comparable defines what to do and what not to do.

First, clan *Padan* is a relationship bound by promise, namely *Padan*, which forms the same relationship pattern. They are two different clans but are the same in the *Padan* relationship. They are the same but not the same clan or the same family. The two are brothers; both are sisters. Nothing higher. The concept of *Padan* positions clans that promise to be equal or the same. The relation *Padan* is equivalent. The idea is bound and connected in the same level

of promise. They do not position one superior to the other or vice versa. Their relationship is standing the same height and sitting the same low. Contracts are held together and carried out together. Nothing lower. Nothing higher.

The relationship concept differentiates who is the old brother or young brother. The older brother is the host if A goes to B's house. And vice versa, if B goes to A's house, then A is the old brother, the host. Then, who is the senior brother or the young brother? The concept of *Padan* formulate both are the same. Whomever the host is, the older one. He is the older brother. Then, if one met in a public place! How? If on neutral ground, their relationship is equal and balanced. They call each other Ampara. For example, if Ranto met Jhon in public, we would call each other Ampara. However, the age aspect is also a consideration. If we know that the person is older than us, we prefer to call the older brother, but he will respond to us with Ampara. The relationships that respect each other and feel the same.

The second is mutual priority. The concept of *Padan* takes precedence over one another. For example, if two children come to Ranto's house simultaneously, namely A and B. A is Ranto's biological child, and B is a child from a clan with *Padan* with Ranto. They both asked for salt. In this condition, Ranto had to give the salt to B's child. Ranto put his child first because of *Padan*. Their relationship is like more than siblings. Put others first. It also applies vice versa. The *Padan* concept regulates mutual priority. The relationships prioritize each other. These are the answers obtained from interviews and questionnaires. Some assert that *Padan* is stronger than the law. The Batak language is called "*togu urat ni bulu, toguan urat ni Padang, togu na nidok uhum, toguan ni dok ni Padan.*" It means: "Strong bamboo roots, firmer grassroots; The firmer the legal bond, the firmer the bond of promise." Here, you must prioritize one over the other.

Third, some things can and cannot do in the *Padan* relationship. What has to do? It is to remember, maintain, perform, and pass on *Padan*. From generation to generation until today. The Batak people continue to apply this in life. *Padan* relationships must help each other, even without being asked. The thing that is not allowed is to violate *Padan*. Promise *Padan* should not break. They must respect each other and be the same. Because promises bind both, they are not allowed to marry. Relationship *Padan* may not allow a marriage. Marriage is forbidden in *Padan* relations. It is worse than mating with one blood (incest). Marriage is prohibited in *Padan* (Simanjuntak, 2006, pp. 92-92).

Methodology (Library, Questionnaire, Interview, And Boundaries)

The author uses qualitative and quantitative research methods with descriptive analysis (Marshall & Rossman, 1989, p. 9; Dixon, Jr, & Straits, 2016, pp. 5-10; Devi, 1997, p 238)—the right type in identifying a condition or idea in social. As the Batak are part of society, they can study. Primary and secondary data are collected using literature, questionnaires, and interviews (Miller & Dingwall, 1997, p. 51). The bibliography uses Indonesian, English, and Batak language references. Because the discussion is local-cultural (Batak concept), references from local languages are highly prioritized (Riyanto, 2020, p. 9). There were no references discussing *Padan*. Thus conduct a questionnaire and interview. Questionnaires use to obtain direct, primary data (25 questionnaires). The questionnaire used was an open-end question with nine question points (seize/sequence of the question) related to *Padan* (True, 1983, p. 208). Questions should be as simple as possible thus that they are easy to understand in one sheet (appearance). Inquiries are made from general to specific (clarity). Questions focus on issues (catching interest), are easy to understand, and obtain accurate responses (Devi, 1997, p. 293). Interviews use to gather data orally. The Toba Batak tribe is a tribe that adheres to an oral tradition, passing it down from generation to generation (language, customs, genealogy, stories, and else) (Rodgers, 1988, p. 74-75). Oral tradition is

the text of life (Huda, 2005, pp. 195-196). Oral (*Hata*) in Batak culture is held tightly. What humans have been their words (Sibarani, Isa, & Susilo, 2003, p. 111; Sihombing, 1986, p. 132). The limitation of this research is only on the issue of the *Padan* concept in general, not specifically on the *Padan* narrative story in each clan—limited research for five months, August, September, October, November, and December 2022. Structured interviews were limited to 5 people, and 25 questionnaires out of 50 distribute. The total number of informants is 30.

Findings

***Padan* As a Religious Tolerance Relations Concepts**

The problem with inter-religious tolerance relations is that a tangible form of tolerance must formulate. Religions that are diverse and different from each other require a formulation of a state of tolerance. Religious differences make it challenging to choose a path or formula that must be balanced. The concept (form, model) must be neutral, not because one religion is the majority and the other minority. Or one religion is more powerful than the other. Or it is using one religious dogma for the tolerance concept, pressing the other religion to obey one (doctrine) religion, or using one idea that benefits one religion. We need religious tolerance relation concepts that are balanced. For this reason, the *Padan* concept offer for tolerance. The idea of the relationship is 1). *Padan* is a promise that makes it the same but still different. 2). Prioritizing one over the other. 3). Some things can and cannot be done in the *Padan* relationship.

The Promise That Makes You Same but Different

Padan can be a binder of tolerance relations between religions. With *Padan*, the relationship with one another takes care of each other. It creates a common ground for mutual respect for one another. Different religions can be one, but still further. They are the same but not the same clan, family, or religion. The two are brothers; both are sisters. Nothing higher. The concept of *Padan* positions clans that promise to be equal or the same. The relation *Padan* is equivalent. The idea is bound and connected at the same level of promise. They do not position one superior to the other or vice versa. *Padan* is a promise that has the same position. The agreement was made not to pressure, intimidate or persecute. But a deal that maintains relations with each other to protect each other. Promises that make the same, but still different, and respect the differences. That promise made those bound by *Padan* equal.

Padan is an equal relationship that makes the value of tolerance a common ground. One religion to another religion is similar. It is an offer in interreligious relations. It does not mean to negate inclusive, exclusive, or pluralism. But it is looking for a middle way without cornering one against the other. With this pattern, equality recognizes collectively. One and others consider themselves as one. Not higher, not lower. In this equality, the design of siblings intertwines. Everyone can be an old brother and a young brother. When A comes to B's house (party, event, celebration), B is a senior brother.

On the other hand, when B comes to A's party, A, as the host, is the big brother. If the invitee does not arrive, he is not worthy of inviting, and he is not worthy of being an old brother or young brother, and he's immature. This equality gives the two the authority of the different one over one other. Different religions have an equivalent *Padan* bridge in their respective existences. Equality does not corner or demean others; they acknowledge each other's existence.

Prioritizing One Over the Other

Putting one another first is the *Padan* principle. This concept can adapt to the idea of relations. If one puts the other first, and the other does, too, there is a pattern of mutual care. Relationships will establish. Each other prioritizes each other to build a way of mutual respect, respect, and care for each other. In *Padan*, the concept of *Padan* takes precedence over one another. For example, if two children come to Ranto's house simultaneously, namely A and B. A is Ranto's biological child, and B is a child from a clan with *Padan* with Ranto. They both asked for salt. Ranto had to give the salt to B's child. Ranto put his child first because of *Padan*. Their relationship is like more than siblings. Put others first. It also applies vice versa. The *Padan* concept regulates mutual priority.

Padan offers the concept of tolerance relations between religions. *Padan* emphasizes that relationships are built by prioritizing each other. Every religion prioritizes one over the other. It continues to be done from generation to generation. Thus, tolerance happens if everyone can prioritize one over the other. It is not a matter of what we give but what we can do within limitations. Put others first (give something) even if we need it, like the analogy of two children who need (ask for) salt. In *Padan*, we must prioritize children from our *Padan* relationship, not give them to our children. Of course, it must be known and seen by our children. They see and know he also has the same rights (to each other) in the child's family, who get salt. With this, the relationship between religions will be very close because the relationship is a mutual priority.

The Things Can and Cannot be Done

Padan implements what to do and what not to do. What we must remember, maintain, perform, and pass on *Padan*. The concept of *Padan* reactions is to help each other even without being asked. It may not violate, but if you can't (able to), it is not a mistake. The point is in helping each other rather than in ability. The *Padan* relationship must be maintained and applied from generation to generation. And there is one thing that is not allowed in *Padan* relationships; namely, *Padan* relationships are not allowed to marry.

Padan offers the concept of tolerance relations between religions. *Padan* emphasizes that the relationship continues to build. *Padan* must remember, maintain, and perform. From generation to generation until today. It is essential in religious relations. Good relations must be recognized and passed on from generation to generation. One religion to another must continue to maintain, care for and continue the *Padan* relationship. Especially in a country that does not allow interfaith marriages, *Padan* is a solution. In *Padan*, marriage is not allowed to happen. Because promises bind both, they are not allowed to marry. Relationship *Padan* may not allow marriage. Marriage is the thing not to do in *Padan* relations. It is worse than marrying with one blood (incest). It keeps them distinct yet the same and not separate.

Conclusion

We are indeed different, but we can be the same regarding *Padan*. *Padan* is one of the related concepts in the Toba Batak tribe, which is an offer in religious tolerance relations. The idea of a tolerance relationship bound a promise called *Padan*. With *Padan*, we recommend different religious ties by a shared commitment. Those who have *Padan* are the same. *Padan* is a promise that exalts everyone in the relationship—a promise to be the same, yet different. We are putting each other first and respecting differences. Help each other and cannot be bound in marriage. Remain forever different but cannot be separated.

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13 – International Exchanges: Impacting Research and Teaching

Martin, Staci

Thongsan, Nuch Sara

Problem Statement: When governments, such as Thailand and USA, invest in scholarship such as the Fulbright, it can offer lasting connections that support a global network that create spaces to exchange ideas, research, and codevelop global/local solutions.

Purpose of the Study: The purpose of the presentation is to explore how Fulbright international exchanges can impact education and research.

Literature or Theory: Critical Hope (Freire, 1994; Martin, 2018)

Research Methods: We will apply a first narrative of our own experiences of being Fulbrighters in the USA and Thailand. Selected Findings: We will focus on how Fulbright promotes international goodwill through learning, teaching, and research. We will also highlight our experiences and how we went about applying for the program.

Summary of Findings: We will focus on how Fulbright promotes international goodwill through learning, teaching, and research. We will also highlight our experiences and how we went about applying for the program.

Conclusion: When these partnerships or connections are created with mutual understanding between countries, we are able to co-create new or strengthen existing knowledge across communities, as well as, improving lives around the world.

Keywords

1 International Partnerships

2 Hope

3 Higher Education

4 Peace-building

5 Scholarship Exchange

Area: Culture; Justice and Peace; Education

14 - Hybrid Second International Conference on Religion, Culture, Peace and Education Factors Contributing to Poor Adoption of Family Planning service among women in Northern Nigeria

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Abstract

Globally, the burden of unmet need for family planning is high, half a million women, nearly all of them in the developing world, die each year in pregnancy or childbirth, one of the most effective cost-effective ways to preventing these maternal and infant mortality is by the adequate knowledge and attitude towards the use of family planning services. In Nigeria, these deaths affect the northern regions than other regions. Family planning can effectively ease maternal mortality by reducing the number of unintended pregnancies. Knowledge of practice, socio-economic and cultural determinant among other factors have contributed to poor adoption of these services. This study is a review paper, relevant literature addressing each issue were discussed. Failure in addressing the poor adoption of family planning services, will further lead to maternal deaths and women opportunities to thrive contribute to their country's development distorted. Theories of planned behaviour and reasoned actions were adopted in considering factors contributing to poor adoption of family planning service. In conclusions, family planning allows couples to decide on their children, empowers those children thrive in a proper environment with proper attitude and perceptions. Proper adoption of services will reduce maternal deaths and engage development in northern Nigeria.

Keywords: Adoption, Family Planning, Women, Northern Nigeria

Introduction

Several attempts to control population upsurge are as old as humanity. Nearly 923 million women worldwide wish to avoid pregnancy worldwide and 30% of maternal deaths can be reduced annually yet 218 million women still have unmet need for planning (United States Agency for International Development USAID, 2022). Globally, 257 million women have unmet need for a modern family planning method (United Nations Populations Funds, UNFPA, 2022). African has suffered, in Nigeria, northern regions are affected due to low knowledge and access to planning services. Access to safe, voluntary family planning is a human right, and this is central to gender equality and a key factor in reducing poverty, yet in developing regions about 257 million women who want to avoid pregnancy are not using safe and effective family planning methods (UNFPA, 2022). The burden of unmet need for family planning is high in Sub Sahara Africa, compared with other regions of the world as in these regions the risk of pregnancy complications and unsafe abortion in tragedy remains high. Unmet need for family planning is lowest in Europe and Central Asia compared with other regions (UNFPA, 2022).

An estimated 35% of women in Latin America and the Caribbean, 28% in Africa and 23% in Asia cite health risks and side effects for not using family planning services (Sedgh & Hussain, 2014). In these regions diverse complications arising from use of planning services

have lowered the use of these services. More than half a million women, nearly all of them in the developing world, die each year in pregnancy or childbirth, one of the most effective cost-effective ways to preventing these maternal and infant mortality is by the adequate use of family planning services (Lule, Hasan, & Yamashita-Allen, 2007 and Apuke, 2017). Poor and inefficient health systems are known to characterize family planning and maternity care services delivery across regions such as Asia and Africa. In West Africa and South-Central Asia, male partner opposition to women's use of family planning accounts for high reported levels of unmet needs (30% and 31% respectively) in both regions (Sedgh & Hussain, 2014). In Nigeria where the review paper is studied there is no difference, as there are no met needs across regions as northern women are affected by numbers of factors affecting their health choices Maternal, Newborn and Child Health Programme (2018).

The paper with a view to understanding factors contributing to the adoption of family planning services some research questions were raised as are their adequate knowledge and use of family planning services among women in northern Nigeria? What are the economic factors that influence family planning services among women in northern Nigeria? Are there cultural practices that affect family planning services among women in northern Nigeria? The specific aim of the study to factors that affects adoption of family planning use among women in northern Nigeria, the specific objectives are, to determine the knowledge and use of family planning services among women in northern Nigeria. To determine economic factors that influence family planning services among women in northern Nigeria. To explore cultural practices that affects family planning services among women in northern Nigeria. Factors Contributing to Poor Adoption of Family Planning service: Northern Nigeria is faced by diverse barriers that affects women in adequately utilizing family planning services, one of such factors are cultural and socio-economic this paper enlightens the factors.

SOCIO-ECONOMIC INFLUENCE ON FAMILY PLANNING

FP can effectively ease maternal mortality by reducing the number of unintended pregnancies, the number of abortions, and the proportion of births at high risk and it has been estimated that meeting women's need for modern contraceptives would prevent about one-quarter to one-third of all maternal deaths, saving 140,000 to 150,000 lives per year (WHO,2022). Another million suffer serious, sometimes permanent pregnancy-related injuries. Much of this suffering and death could be prevented through effective family planning engendered by modern contraception. FP use protects women from the health risk of unwanted pregnancies and gives women control over their lives. The principal effort in population control is family planning, which aims at communicating to a society the desirability of limiting family size for economic, social and maternal health reasons.

Economic factor in northern Nigeria serves a major factor influencing family planning decision among spouse and socially it influences the women in utilizing the family planning services Mairiga, *et al.*, (2010). The strongest motivating factors for practicing contraception were economic and completion of desired number of children. According to Nwosu, Eke, & Chigbu (2011) carried out a study to identify socio-demographic and economic factors influencing the practice of modern family planning in rural communities of Abia State, Nigeria. The study revealed that Practice of family planning was highest among single ladies, unemployed and married women with 7 or more living children and lowest among illiterate mothers, farmers, mothers with less than 4 living children and the mothers from the poorest families whose monthly income were below N20,000. Similarly in northern Nigeria women have low level of income earners especially farmers, illiterates, housewives, those with only Islamic education, petite business traders as to these women alone cannot take decisions pertaining any family planning methods. Improved education strategies and better access to

services are needed to solve these problems. Education is a determinant to effective utilization of family planning service and also a major determinant to control the size of the family. The present study will be conducted to know other socio-economic factors that affects and influence the use of family planning services in northern Nigeria among women.

CULTURE ON FAMILY PLANNING SERVICE ADOPTION

Family planning (FP) has attracted global attention due to its importance in decision making about population growth and development issues (Nigeria Health watch, (NHW) 2016). FP allows couples to decide their children as well as empowers them to ensure those children are thrive in a proper environment Family planning use is still low in many developing countries, including Nigeria, where 23.7% of currently married women had ever used one method to reduce childbirth. Childbearing and the use of contraceptives are some of the most important decisions on reproduction that could be taken by couples to curtail the number of children they want to have. Therefore, the issue of family planning and its methods has led many married women to either accept family planning or reject it (Suntai & Apuke, 2016). Key reasons for not practicing contraception were traceable to cultural imperatives, ignorance and religious belief among women in northern Nigeria.

The cultural barriers in northern Nigeria among the women influences on the decisions making of the women in utilizing family planning services. Culture is a major determinant to family planning services especially in African. In Nigeria different cultural beliefs affect families in utilization of family planning services. In a study, Undelikwo, Osonwa, Ushie & Osonwa, (2013) carried out a study to investigate family planning behaviours and decision-making among couples in Cross River State, Nigeria. The findings show that spousal communication and the involvement of men in family planning methods enhances the chances of fertility control and increases couple's chances of happier life. In northern Nigeria only the woman cannot decide on matters affecting her health hence she needs the consent of her spouse before any or major decisions are taken, as such family planning are not engaged by women whose spouse disapproves or reject. In other studies conducted, revealed practice of contraception was low while traditional birth control methods were highly preferred in northern Nigeria are mostly the withdrawal or abstinence methods.

Several others studies demonstrated that despite a high level of awareness, practice of contraception was still very low. In addition, Reshma (2015) carried out a study investigating the awareness in women perception for family planning among 25 married women aged 18-50 years, conducted in Baliyana village, Rohtak, most respondents were aware of the use of family planning but only 12.0% had ever visited a family planning clinic. It implies that despite the knowledge of family planning services the usage was low. Perceived constraints to the use of family planning methods included husband's opposition, fear of complications and perceived insufficient knowledge about family planning methods. In northern Nigeria similarly in studies undertaken by Yakasai & Yusuf (2013), in Kano state, it concluded that there is a knowledge practice gap in use of family planning methods among married women, northern women suffer knowledge gaps especially among the uneducated women with low economic status.

THEORY OF PLANNED BEHAVIOR AND REASONED ACTIONS

Factors contributing to poor adoption of family planning services as in the study, knowledge gap, socio-economic and cultural determinant affects the use of family planning services among women in northern Nigeria, theories that look at perception and attitude of the women are used for this study. Theory of planned behavior (TPB) and reasoned actions explains the factors contributing to adoption of family planning. In this theory of planned behaviour, behavior is explained by behavioral intention, which is influenced by attitudes

toward a specific behavior, subjective norms (SNs), i.e. perceived social pressure to perform the behavior and perceived behavioral control (PBC). That is, both internal and external factors can facilitate or hinder behavior (Montano, Kasprzyk & Taplin, 1997) while theory of reasoned actions was developed by Martin Fishbein & Icek Ajzen in 1975. The theory is based on the assumptions that human beings are usually quite rational and make systematic use of the information available to them. People consider the implications of their actions in a given context at a given time before they decide to engage or not engage in a given behaviour and that most actions of social relevance are under volitional control (Ajzen,, 1980 cited in Rachel,, 1999).The theory of Reasoned Action specifically focuses on the role of personal intention and knowledge in determining whether behaviour will occur, the strength of others' exerts influence on individuals' behavior, making them do what others want them to do and it tends to make them act in accordance with others. This implies that external or internal factors could lead us to take a certain decision. People could take a certain decision because they feel is beneficiary to them while some take it because others superior to them wants them to take such decisions.

The both theories are applicable to this study as it looks at the perception and attitude of women on the use of family planning. As the theory postulate, internal and external factors could influence decision making, this could be seen in factors influencing adoption or acceptance of family planning such as having knowledge on family planning, husband rejection of family planning, illiteracy, culture and tradition as affecting use of family planning services. In northern Nigeria women are not major decision makers they depend on their spouse and other elder women in the family to make health decisions for them as such issues affecting their health is influenced either by internal or external factors and she will be unable to use any family planning service without proper consultation of other family members who can largely give quack or traditional methods and her health is largely at risk.

Discussions

Nigeria is the 3rd most populous country in Africa, with more than 88 million people, it also has a high annual population growth (3.5%) and a total fertility rate of 6.0 lifetime birth per woman Federal office of Statistics, Nigeria Demographic and Health Survey, (2017). Despite the population growth several factors contribute to the adoption of family planning services among women in northern Nigeria. Socio-economic factors such as the low usage of available FP methods, lack of access to information on family planning services usage, lack of support from spouse and communities, cultural barriers have threatened women's ability to build a better future for themselves, their families and communities in northern Nigeria. Adeleye, Akoria, Shuaib & Ogholoh (2010) carried out an investigation to study elicit barriers and knowledge gaps regarding the benefits of family planning among women in Irrua, Edo State, Nigeria, the study discovered that family planning was of no benefit. No statistically significant association was demonstrated between educational levels and the knowledge of family planning benefits. In northern Nigeria previous knowledge, socio-economic factors such as education, type of job done by spouse or their age in marriage influences use of family planning service. This review paper discovered socio-economic factors encountered by women or their spouse affects their use of family planning services in northern Nigeria as other cultural belief indisposes them not to utilize FP services.

The study discovers adequate knowledge on the practice of family planning is significant to the practice of usage of the services, women need to be knowledgeable of the help to their health that these services accrue to them the theory of planned behaviour is based on the assumptions that human beings are usually quite rational and make systematic use of the information available to them. People consider the implications of their actions in a given context at a given time before they decide to engage or not engage in a given behaviour and

that most actions of social relevance are under volitional control (Ajzen, 1980 cited in Rachel, 1999). The theory of Reasoned Action specifically focuses on the role of personal intention in determining whether behaviour will occur. The paper sees information and awareness on population matters that address issues such as cultural barriers to utilization of family planning services, unwanted pregnancies and contraceptives importance and its use. It is envisaged that these will encourage social modernization, specifically family planning, and in turn encourage a small family norm thus helping to reduce the population expansion problem. Specifically, activities that focus on the experience people have in talking to their partners about sex and contraceptive use, the positive and negative beliefs about adopting family planning use, and the types of environments that enhance the use are influenced by the knowledge and practice of the use of family planning service.

In conclusion

In this study on factors contributing to adopting family planning services, knowledge, cultural and socio-economic factors largely affect a woman decision in utilizing family planning services and this in turns affects her ability to thrive properly in their society and the world at large. When women are adequately knowledgeable on the practices of family planning and are properly empowered socially and economically various cultural barriers will be broken as such northern women will know their right over their body as well as the right to make health decision specifically on issues relating to their fertility. The study will recommend nursing education, voluntary community mobilization team in northern Nigeria to emphasize programs on creating awareness on practices on family planning, encourage socio-cultural aspects of contraceptive practices by local communities in northern Nigeria.

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15 - Evaluation of functionality, adequacy and electrical lecturers' preparedness in utilization of multimedia micro teaching laboratories constructed by TET Fund in colleges of education in northern Nigeria

Nasiru Bello Mohammed

Ahmed, Ibrahim

Problem Statement: Students performance in colleges of education is low.

Purpose of the Study: To determine the adequacy, functionality and preparedness of lecturers

Literature or Theory: Dale come of experience

Research Methods: Descriptive survey

Summary of Findings: The micro teaching laboratories are adequate, functional but not utilized by lecturers in the colleges

Conclusion: Lecturers are to be motivated to use the laboratories

Keywords

1 Micro teaching laboratories

2 Multi Media

3 Teaching

4 Micro

5 Laboratories

Area: Education

16 - Buddha's Basic Teaching Approach to Peace

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ABSTRACT

This paper provides a view of the Buddha's fundamental teachings apply to peaceful and harmonious living. The teachings of Buddha offer valuable insights and guidance for achieving peace and harmonious living. At the core of Buddha's teaching is the Four Noble Truths, which is the nature of suffering and the path to end it. The path to the end of suffering is called the Noble Eightfold Path. These teaching can be applied to achieve peace and harmonious living by encouraging individuals to cultivate a sense of detachment and non-attachment to the world around them. The paper has highlighted the terms of peace and then analyze the Buddha's basic teaching approaches to peace revolves around the concept of the emphasizes the Four Noble Truths and following the Noble Eightfold Path. The conclusion of the paper is the Buddha's teaching on peace is understanding the nature of suffering, developing a way of life that promotes inner peace and ethical behavior, and ultimately attaining enlightenment. Through these teaching and practices, individual can find peace and harmony within themselves and in their relationships with others.

Keywords:

Buddha, Buddha's Teaching, Peace, The Four Noble Truth, The Noble Eightfold Path

INTRODUCTION

The Buddha's fundamental teachings offer a profound insight into the nature of human existence and provide a way to attain inner peace and harmony. At the core of these teachings is the recognition that suffering is an inherent part of human life, and that our attachment to desire, ignorance, and craving is the root cause of our suffering. The Buddha's teachings offer a path to overcome this suffering and attain inner peace through the Four Noble Truths and the Noble Eightfold Path. The Four Noble Truths state that suffering exists, the cause of suffering is craving and attachment, suffering can be overcome, and the path to overcome suffering is through the Noble Eightfold Path.

The aim of the paper is to provide a comprehensive overview of how Buddha fundamental teachings can guide individuals and societies towards greater peace and harmony. Buddha's basic teachings approach to peace can be summed up in the Four Noble Truths and the Noble Eightfold Path. These teachings provide a framework for understanding suffering and its causes. The primary data related to the Buddha's basic teaching approach to peace included his original teachings of the Four Noble Truths and the Noble Eightfold Path. Secondary data included scholarly articles and books that analyze and interpret the Buddha's teachings and their relevance to peace and conflict resolution. Both primary and secondary sources helped deepen understanding of the Buddha's basic teaching approach to peace, and how we might apply these insights in our own lives and in the pursuit of greater global peace.

The research finding suggest that the Buddha's basic fundamental teachings can have significant implications for promoting peaceful and harmonious living. By cultivating mindfulness, compassion, contentment, and ethical behavior, individuals can contribute to a more peaceful and just society and lead more fulfilling lives.

In this article, the term Buddha refers specifically to Siddhartha Gautama, the historical figure who founded Buddhism and developed the teaching on the Four Noble Truths and the Noble Eightfold Path. The term "Buddha's teaching" in the context of the Buddha's basic teaching approach peace refers to the core teachings and principles developed by Buddha. These teaching emphasize the importance of cultivating inner peace, compassion, and wisdom, and developing a way of life that promotes harmony and peaceful coexistence with others.

LITERATUR REVIEW

What is peace?

Peace is a state of harmony characterized by the absence of conflict, violence, and war. It involves mutual understanding, respect, and cooperation between individuals, communities, and nations. Peace can exist on different levels, including inner peace, social peace, and global peace. Inner peace refers to a sense of calmness, serenity, and tranquility within oneself. It involves being at ease with oneself, accepting one's strengths and weakness, and find a sense of purpose and meaning in life. Social peace refers to the absence of conflicts, discrimination, and injustice withing a society. It involves ensuring that all members of a community have equal rights, opportunities, and access to resources, regardless of their race, ethnicity, gender, religion, or social status. Global peace refers to the absence of war, violence, and terrorism among nations. It involves promoting cooperation, understanding, and mutual respect among different cultures, religions, and nations to prevent conflicts and promote a peaceful coexistence.

According to the K.N. Jayatillake (Jayatillake, 2018), definition of peace is a state of inner tranquility and harmony that arises from a deep understanding of the interconnectedness of all things. It involves cultivating inner peace and extending that peace to others, promoting understanding and dialogue, and working towards social justice and equality.

Johan Galtung's definition of peace is a state of harmony characterized by the absence of direct, structural, and cultural violence. Direct violence as physical violence, such as war or terrorism. Structural violence refers to the ways in which social structures, such as poverty or discrimination, harm individuals and communities. Cultural violence refers to the values, beliefs, and symbols that legitimize and perpetuate violence. He believes that positive peace is achieved by addressing the root cause of violence and conflict, rather than just treating the symptoms (Galtung, 1996). Moreover, Johan Galtung mention in the mini-peace theory, peace is entropy, Nirvana is entropy – hence, in a certain sense peace is nirvana and nirvana is peace. (Galtung, 1985)

According to Thich Nhat Hanh, peace is not merely the absence of conflict or war, but a way of life that is grounded in love, understanding, and interdependence. He sees peace as something that is achievable in our daily lives, through our interactions with others, our relationship with nature, and our own inner spiritual practice. He believes that true peace beings with inner peace, which is result of being fully present and attentive to present moment (Hanh, 2005)

Buddha's fundamental teachings

The Four Noble Truths are a foundational teaching of Buddha, which was first articulated of his first sermon, and is considered to be the core of Buddhist philosophy and offer a roadmap for understanding the nature of suffering and how to overcome it. The Noble Eightfold Path is one of the central teachings of Buddhism and is the path that leads to the cessation of suffering and the attainment of enlightenment.

The Four Noble Truth

The first Noble Truth states that suffering is an inherent part of life. The second Noble Truth asserts that the cause of suffering is craving and attachment, which are based on ignorance and delusion. The third Noble Truth holds that is possible to overcome suffering by removing its causes, and the fourth Noble Truth offers a path for doing so, known as the Eightfold Path.

Numerous scholars and practitioners have written about the Four Noble Truth, offering various interpretations and insights.

Walpola Rahula provides a clear and concise overview of the Four Noble Truths, drawing on traditional Buddhist teachings and commentary. He explores the implications of the Four Noble Truths for contemporary life, emphasizing their relevance of addressing social and environmental issue (Rahula, 2007). Bhikkhu Bodhi's offers a detailed examination of the Fourth Noble Truth, which outlines the Noble Eightfold Path as a means for overcoming suffering. Bodhi provides a comprehensive analysis of each step of the Eightfold Path, drawing on a range of Buddhist texts and commentaries (Bodhi, 2010). Thich Nhat Hanh offers a contemporary interpretation of the Four Noble Truths that emphasizes their practical application in daily life. He offers insights on how to apply the Four Noble truths to cultivate mindfulness, compassion, and insight (Hanh, 2008). Damien Keown offers a concise overview of the Four Noble Truths, situating them within the border context of Buddhist philosophy and practice. Keown discusses various interpretations and criticisms of Four Noble Truths, as well as their influence on other religious and philosophical traditions (Keown, 2013)

The Nobel Eightfold Path

The Eightfold Path consists of eight interdependent factors that work together to cultivate wisdom, ethical conduct, and mental discipline.

Bhikkhu Bodhi provides a detail analysis of each of the eight factors of the path, drawing on a wide range of Buddhist texts and commentaries. He explores the practical application of each factor in daily life and offers guidance on how to cultivate them (Bodhi, 2010). Thich Nhat Hanh offers contemporary interpretation of the Eightfold Path that emphasizes its relevance to modern life. He explores each factor of the path and offers insights on how to apply them in the context of mindfulness, compassion, and engaged action (Hanh, 2008). Peter Harvey offers a comprehensive overview of Buddhist ethics, including the Eightfold Path as a means for cultivating ethical conduct and mental discipline. He explores the historical and cultural context of the Eightfold Path and offers a critical analysis of its key concepts (Harvey, 2000). Rupert Gethin offers a scholarly examination of the Eightfold Path, situating in within the broader context of Buddhist philosophy and practice. Gethin provides a detailed analysis of each factor of the path and explores its relationship to other key Buddhist teachings (Gethin et al., 1998)

METHODOLOGY

The first step was conducted the literature review. This involves reviewed and analyzed various primary and secondary sources, including Buddhist texts, historical records, and scholar articles, that discuss Buddha's teachings on peace. After conducting a literature

review, a qualitative analysis conducted to examine the key themes and concepts related to Buddha's teaching on peace. To clarify and supplement another way is to explore by conducted interview two Buddha's practitioners.

FINDINGS

Buddha's teaching on peace is based on the concept of Four Noble Truths and the Noble Eightfold Path. The Four Noble Truths describe the nature of suffering, its causes, and they way to end it, while the Noble Eightfold Path outlines the steps one can take to achieve enlightenment and liberation from suffering. The first Noble Truth states that suffering exists and is fundamental part of the human experience. The second Noble Truth identifies the cause of suffering as craving and attachment, which lead to greed, anger, and delusion. The third Noble Truth offers the possibility of liberation from suffering, known as Nirvana or Enlightenment, which can be achieved by removing the causes of suffering. The fourth Noble Truth outlines the path to liberation, known as the Noble Eightfold Path. This path consists of eight interrelated practices: right understanding, right intention, right speech, right action, right livelihood, right effort, right mindfulness, and right concentration. Buddha taught that the practice of the Noble Eightfold Path can lead to inner peace and harmony with others, which is essential for creating peace in the world. He emphasized the importance of compassion, loving-kindness, and non-violence in one's relationship with others. Furthermore, Buddha taught that the root of all conflict and violence is in the mind, specifically in the delusions of attachment, anger, and ignorance. Therefore, he emphasized the practice of mediation and mindfulness to cultivate a clear and peaceful mind. Overall, Buddha's basic teaching approach to peace emphasizes the importance of understanding and addressing the root causes of suffering, cultivating inner peace through ethical conduct and mental training, and promoting compassion and non-violence in all relationships.

According to the interview by online with the Buddhist practitioners, they often meditate to calm the mind and cultivate inner peace. They practice mindfulness in their daily lives by being present in the moment, paying attention to their thoughts and emotions, and cultivating a non-judgmental awareness of their experiences. They practice compassion towards themselves and others, recognizing the interconnectedness of all beings and the suffering that arises from ignorance and attachment. They practice right speech and action by speaking and action in ways that are truthful, compassionate, and ethical. They study the Buddha's teachings to gain a deeper understanding of the nature of reality and to develop wisdom. These practices helped Buddhist practitioners to experience inner peace, cultivate compassion, and develop wisdom. Moreover, helped to reduce suffering and promote harmony in their relationship and communities.

CONCLUSION

The root cause of suffering and conflict is attachment, desire, and ignorance. According to Buddha, the ultimate goal is to attain Nirvana, which is the state of liberation from suffering and rebirth. The path to peace involves following the Eightfold Path, which consists of right understanding, right intention, right speech, right action, right livelihood, right effort, right mindfulness, and right concentration. By practicing these principles, one can develop wisdom, ethical conduct, and mental discipline. Compassion and loving-kindness are essential components of Buddha's teachings on peace. By cultivating empathy and kindness towards oneself and others, one can overcome negative emotions and foster harmony and understanding.

In summary, Buddha's basic teachings emphasize the importance of self-awareness, ethical behavior, and mental development in achieving inner peace and harmony with others.

Through the practice of mindfulness, compassion, and wisdom, one can cultivate a peaceful mind and contribute to a peaceful society.

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17 - Political Philosophy and Political Economy on Justice and Peace

Rey Ty

Problem Statement: The problem is that “justice” and “peace” do not have fixed meanings. But, how is that a problem? What happens when the meaning of those terms change? That is the problem. Is the problem that philosophers have tried to contextualize peace and justice by drawing on bygone concepts? Is political economy a better way to understand justice and peace?

Purpose of the Study To show that “peace” has had different meanings throughout history and in political economy.

Literature or Theory: This paper distinguishes several related terms which have very different meanings: political philosophy, political thought, political theory, and political economy.

Research Methods This article is qualitative in nature, reviews the literature, engages in document analysis to reveal the emerging trends.

Summary of Findings: Compare peace and justice in 5 different time periods as well as employing political economy as a tool of analysis with surprising complex findings, which defy simplistic categorization.

Conclusion: “Peace and justice” are still changing. But how does this understanding of the way philosophy evolves help solve the problem? How different and useful is the understanding of justice and peace from the perspectives of political philosophy and political economy?

Keywords

1 Political Philosophy

2 Political Theory

3 Political Thought

4 Political Economy

5 Justice

Area: Peace

18 - Impact of TikTok as the Form of UGC on Thai Music Industry During COVID-19 Pandemic.

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Abstract

This paper explores an impact of TikTok application with the powerful algorithm technology that is the users frequently sees the content of the similar label and feels the homogenization of the content. The purpose of this paper was to study about an impact of TikTok as the form of User Generated Content (UGC) on Thai music industry. The literature and theory that guides this research was the TikTok application, the User Generated Content (UGC), and Thai music Industry. The method employs Netnography. The researchers found that the TikTok algorithm technology worked very well so that the users frequently consume the similar content which was Thai style music. Then the users have lost other variety contents. According to UGC, we founded that during COVID-19 pandemic, women are more participate with Thai style music via TikTok than men. The central idea of chorus or hook of the music are touching the TikTokers. It drives TikTokers repeating the Thai style music that they found interesting. In conclusion, TikTok was the application that youth and young-adults used a lot during COVID-19 pandemic. It is the way out for youth and young adults because they cannot hang out with other people.

Key Terms: TikTok, Thai style music, TikTokers

Introduction

The great leap forward of technology has encouraged mobile phones (smart phones) and modern devices that can connect to the Internet (smart devices) to become convenient to listen to music. This results in a 42% revenue growth for the music business in 2015-2020, according to IFPI (International Federation of the Phonographic Industry), (site in Stone, 2020). Later, The COVID-19 pandemic has also become a major force for the global music industry to look for the ways to survive in their business. Originally, record labels and artists may have earned their income from both merchandising and organizing concerts to engage with their audiences. Nowadays income can come from live streaming, which is an online form of broadcasting. It can be used in the online industry, there are a variety of games, special events, TV shows, and many more. In addition, part of the income will be received from subscriptions on platforms or online channels that facilitate the users to listening to the music and create a phenomenon for a song to become a popular song more easily.

In September 2016, “TikTok” application was released as a music creative short video social software. Although it emerges from the founders in China, this application is the world’s prominent destination in Asia, United states and other parts of the world. TikTok is accessible in over 150 marketplaces and in 75 languages (e.g., Hallanan, 2018; Mushtaq, 2018, cited in Jaffer, Riaz & Mushtaq, 2019). The application is allowed users to make and share 15 to 60-second short video. The user can select the background music, motion editing and special effects processing for making the short video. Moreover, “TikTok has also creates a distinctive music community, with music as the center for content category division, and also launched the “dance dance machine” with the “human key detection technology” (Xu, Yan & Zhang, 2019 p.59). Jaffer et al. (2019) stated the additional benefit of

TikTok is that collaboration which is a major motivation where the users can do a “duet” with others by responding to their video which results in a limitless chain of responses.

The TikTok algorithm technology is the powerful tools arousing users to spent time on this application. Hern (2022) revealed that TikTok algorithm consists of various signals such as hashtags used, songs liked, and the device that the person used. The general process of TikTok algorithm is

“When a new video is uploaded, TikTok’s system shows it to a small set of users. TikTok has already determined that these users would probably like the video. This is based on the past videos that they liked before. The video is considered “liked” when it is shared to others, when it is viewed completely, and if the creator is shared with other people as well. When that takes place, TikTok then begins to share it to more people. This creates a sort of feedback loop, that when it continues on, creates viral sensations.” (Thai, 2021).

TikTok application considers as the form of User Generated Content (UGC) like other application for example Facebook and Instagram, that is users are content producers themselves while the product owner or organizations do not have to pay for the production of the content. According to the main theme of TikTok is music, this research focused on Thai music on TikTok during COVID-19 pandemic.

Thai music industry

Liked other country all around the world, Thailand has variety of music genres. However, Thailand has a distinguish music style that is mainly gives a fun feeling in Thai style. In this research are specific to “Wan or Jo” music. Wan in Thai word is a kind of slang are used to defined Thai boys or girls who always ride a loudly motorcycle and disturbing the community. ‘Dek Wan’ is the misbehave children who like to race on public roads. Therefore, the gathering of Van children who are often abandoned by society is to 'build identity' and create 'recognition' from the action they think that their awesomeness (Kriangwattana, 2007). The researchers view this phenomenon as creating an identity in this way is in the same direction as the Putnark article (2018), only their 'projection' has a different tool, namely 'motorcycle' versus 'TikTok app'. But then at present, there is a phenomenon that shows the relationship between the TikTok app and the songs that are dubbed 'Wan songs' or what we originally knew of these songs' characteristics as upbeat songs.

“Wan music” or pleng Wan started from comedian “Jazz Chuan Chuen”, who played a character like a Wan child in many movies and dramas. Jazz turned to release the first single with the Jazz Spooknick Papiyong Kookkook band called "Wan Fo Lo Phew" (2015) and this song became a hit song and trended at the annual New Year's Eve event in 2016; every event must play this song loudly. Up charging the New Year's song rankings (sanook.com, 2015), at that time this type of music was called 'Jo Song' or ‘Wan music’.

TikTok application and Thai music industry

In Thailand, the growth of TikTok users is not limited to teenagers, students and working age anymore. This corresponds to the statistics of Thai people using TikTok, where users of Gen Y (aged 22-38) and Gen Z (aged 17-22) have grown in similar numbers. Its users are 75% female and 25% male (Prakai, 2020). Ms. Laksamee Jong, Campaign and Content Manager TikTok Thailand reported on [MARKETINGOPPS](https://www.marketingopps.com) website (2020) that short videos are in trend throughout the year 2020 can be divided into 5 types of content:

- 1.Talent is a video that shows a special talent or skill.
- 2.Comedy is a funny show create hilarity for the audience.

3. Food & Drink & Travel is a show of eating, cooking, making drinks, and reviews of various tourist attractions.

4. Basic Dance is a dance show whether it is a full skill, dancing with a serious system. or learn how to dance.

5. Beauty & Fashion is a review of fashion products, clothes, bags, shoes and cosmetics.

Zhi (2018) makes a summary of 3 main elements that make TikTok special and different from other video apps:

1. Music is the main theme of TikTok. The application is it easy to use.
2. The effective management and analysis of big data. This makes it easy for users to choose what they like.
3. The basic video time set at 15 seconds is designed to suit the fast-paced life of young people.

According to Zhi's research, music marketers in the digital age understand the nature of listeners to listen only to the music they like. The release of a new song by an artist thus becomes the release of one song at a time. Also known as releasing a new single instead of releasing a full album which includes the trend of choosing to promote music through the TikTok application as well.

User – Generated Content (UGC)

Driscoll, Brizee, Salvo, and Sousa (2008) defined User-Centered Theory as a theory of design that places users at the center of technology development in an iterative, recursive, and collaborative process. User – generated content (UGC) or also known as electronic word – of – mouth (eWOM). Manap and Adzharudin (2013) stated that UGC spreads input through an online medium. Everyone can create material uploaded to the Internet by non–media and it has a greater influence on people's consumption. The contents created by anyone are generally be shared on social media such as on Facebook, YouTube, Twitter and Instagram. Hennig-Thurau, Gwinner, Walsh, & Gremler (2004) defined eWOM/UGC as follows "...any positive or negative statement made by potential, actual, or former customers about a product or company, which is made available to a multitude of people and institutions via the Internet". Consumer perceived UGC as more credibility more trustworthy, useful and unbiased. UGC contents are based on consumers' own experiences approve. Thus, the consumers have a potential to trust the content generated by other users because they perceive the users do not have any commercial interest (Mir & Rehman, 2013).

Research question

The purpose of this research was to study about an impact of TikTok as the form of User Generated Content (UGC) on Thai music Industry. TikTok application platform, Thai music industry, and User Generated Content (UGC) was lead this research as qualitative research that focuses on explaining the phenomenon in a cultural context to understand a way of life through the perspective of the owner of that culture, who is a TikTok user with music that is defined as Wan music.

RQ: How TikTok as the form of User Generated Content (UGC) impact on Thai music industry?

In order to answer the research question, the researchers used a research methodology called Netnography or an ethnographic research method. Netnography originate by Rebert V. Koniznets (2010), professor of public relations strategy, business communication, consumer culture digital marketing strategy and social media analysis from the University of

South California at Annenberg, USA, which is derived from the words ‘Net’ or Internet and Ethnography. The real world and the virtual world have almost become the same world. Likewise, research terminology such as Webnography, Network Ethnography, Digital Ethnography, Online Ethnography, Ethnography on the Internet, Cyberethnography, and Virtual Ethnography are all applications of an observational approach to ethnographic research and engagement to understand social interactions in the context of online spaces or digital communications described by the following set of terms: cyberspace, virtual communities and virtual world.

Methods

The researchers adapted the design process of Digital Ethnography Research to explore the behavior of Tiktok users and impact on Thai music industry as follows.

1. Identification of issues, we explore the engagement of TikTok users in Thai Wan or Jo songs.
2. Defining and selecting communities. This research is a group of TikTok Thailand users.
3. Participatory observation. The researchers observed the lives of TikTokers (TikTok users) for 3 months, from August 1 to October 31, 2021, by joining the application and interviewing three teenage users who were linked with the genre of music which is Wan or jo songs
4. Data analysis and interpretation of research results.
5. Writing, presenting research results and theoretical findings and their application.

Findings

After 3 months which was August to October 2021, the researchers’ participatory research and observations of TikTokers’ engagement behavior with ‘Wan songs’ on TikTok, we spent observing every day, averaging 30 minutes per day.

The researchers’ observation founded that females have about 90% of the proportion of making video clips by dancing and lip syncing to music or audio clips. Most of them make clips alone and a few have 2-3 other friends do it together. On the other hand, males are only about 10%. The production processes or activities of the TikTokers with ‘Wan song’ are start by watching other people’s clips and finding out who is the original singer of the song in their own favorite clip. Then download that song to reproduce for their own version until it becomes a group of fans who love that song or sound and carry out activities together by putting # followed by the name of the song or a keyword that shows that they are in the same group. In order to show appreciation for that song or sound. The researchers took notes from scrolling to view content and found a clip that reproduced the ‘Wan song’ that exceeded 20K users per #, a total of 13 #, i.e. ‘I want a good lover’, ‘You better like me’, ‘Wearing gold to drive a wan’, ‘Waist around’, ‘Fun-loving ladies’, ‘Nang nang’, ‘Hearts pounding for oxygen’, ‘Sharks land’, ‘Bowling wants to eat chicken’, ‘Can’t hold back’, ‘Raises the glass’, ‘Device’, and ‘Will be shot by gun’.

Song	Artist	Number of Videos Created by Users (Data as of December 31, 2021)
1.I want a good lover	LiLTY	28.4K
2.Wearing gold to drive a wan	Jazz Spooknick Papiyong Kookkook	235.4 K

3. Waist around	Prim Lai Thai	517.2K
4. Can't hold back	Vangoe	853.4K
5. Device	Bangmin	1.4M
6. Will be shot by gun	Namemt & 1 Flow	116.6K
7. You better like me	Owen	4767K

Table 1: From 13 # can find out of the person who created the first post of # or the song is the artist himself, consisting of 7 songs

The results of the research in terms of content linked to Wan music, can be divided into 4 types:

1. The original songs were used in a ready-to-use manner and had a Wan rhythm already in place by excerpting some parts of the song that is chorus or hook. The hashtag (#) is still followed by the name of the song, for example, songs in the order 1-6.

2. A remix is a song that an independent artist brings an old song or a song that may not have the rhythm of the original version, such as the song 'You better like me' posted by the original artist, OWEN, which has a slow tempo. There are only 4,767 users create content from original, but independent artists mix original songs with 'Wan music' to make them more fun and can be more successful among TikTok fans than original songs. For example, the user named 'Seafood Kon Dee' remixed the song 'You better like me' to make the beat more 'Wan rhythm' then has users re-create content up to 169.6K Videos.

3. Some songs that have been cut, such as the Joker Family's Song 'Hurt Jang Tee Rak Khwai'. It was cut the lyric 'Raise a glass and throw it down your throat' and made into a clip by a TikToker who loves this part of the song with the word after hashtag '#raise a glass' became a popular search term instead of the original song title.

4. The song mix with voice speech similar to a DJ playing music in a pub. This may reflect the emotional pressure that pubs and bar have been closed for more than a year during this time because of the COVID-19 pandemic. The TikToker nostalgic for the atmosphere of a night out.

The researchers also founded that popular Tiktok users created clip can be re-shared via the Instagram platform at the same time. It also causes the publicity of the song for artists across platforms.

Conclusion

Figure 1: The guideline of UGC on Thai music Industry

According to User Generated Content, we founded that during COVID-19 pandemic, women are more participate with Thai style music via TikTok than men. The central idea of chorus or hook in the music are touching the TikTokers portrayed through the account of artist's social media, artist's Fanclub, and artist's affiliate. It drives TikTokers repeating the Thai style music that they found interesting. UGC runs through Tiktok, which also can be shared via Instagram and Facebook. Specifically, 'Wan songs' with joyful and hilarious lyric and rhythm contribute the contents in various forms, such as covering song, dancing, remixing music, and using music as a background of their contents.

In conclusion, TikTok was the application that youth and young-adults used a lot during COVID-19 pandemic. It is the way out for youth and young adults because they cannot hang out with other people. TikTok has impact on Thai music industry because this application theme is primary focus on music. Once the chorus or hook in the songs are touching the TikTokers, the user will be generated and share the content not only on TikTok platform but across other platforms as well. This phenomenon affects the way of promoting a new single of artist and the way of how record company enhance a song to be famous.

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19 - The Karo-Batak Traditional Calendar as a Practical Guide of Church Eco-theology: The Case of Karo Batak Protestant Church (GBKP) in Indonesia

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Abstract

The paper addresses the problem of the using Karo-Batak Traditional Calendar in the context of Karo Batak Protestant Church (GBKP) in Indonesia. Officially, GBKP prohibits the use of it with consideration that it was a product of paganism. On the other side, Karo-Batak Christians (the most church member of GBKP) still use it in their daily life, especially for special occasions and interests. This paper aims to relieve the tension and conduct a creative reconstruction of it to produce a significant and comprehensive contribution of Karo-Batak Christians in GBKP without choosing between their culture or Christian faith. But giving more contribution to the special issue of ecological crisis. This paper uses a cultural eco-theology from a Christian perspective and uses a qualitative research approach with a hermeneutic method. The results of this paper show that the Karo Traditional Calendar is useful as a medium/practical guide for the implementation of GBKP eco-theology for Karo-Batak Christians. GBKP can even use the calendar as part of her ecological-evangelical mission to strengthen her contribution to the sustainability of livable life.

Key Terms: Cultural Eco-theology, Environmental Crisis, GBKP, Karo-Batak Traditional Calendar

Introduction

Problem Statement

There is a foundational tension between culture and Christian faith values in the context of the use of the Karo-Batak traditional calendar amidst Karo-Batak Christians' daily life in Indonesia. Karo-Batak Christians, mostly which are located in North Sumatra Province, Indonesia, use the Karo-Batak traditional calendar, *Wari Sitelupuluh* (WS), especially for their special occasions and interests. But on the other side, Karo Batak Protestant Church (GBKP) prohibits its use by the reason of paganism. Officially, GBKP acknowledges that WS is the Karo-Batak traditional calendar, and its usage is a product of paganism and "automatically" contrary to the Christian faith. The tension that I mentioned before lies in the selection between culture (as a cultural identity) and church (as a faith identity) by Karo-Batak Christians who mostly are church members of GBKP. The tension has two potential domino effects: a presumption that every Karo-Batak Christian is not pure Christian and decreasing the GBKP church member contribution, especially with the general issue nowadays, the ecological crisis, where GBKP truly has to respond it in the light presenting and taking action to sustain our livable life.

Research Questions

Based on the problem statement above, this paper has three significant research questions:

1. What is GBKP and Karo-Batak Christian?

2. What is Karo-Batak traditional calendar and how it's using is officially prohibited by GBKP?
3. How did the Karo-Batak traditional calendar become a practical guide of church eco-theology for GBKP in light of ecological crisis issues nowadays?

Research Purpose

This paper aims to relieve the tension that I mention before and conducts a creative reconstruction of the new use of WS as the Karo-Batak traditional calendar to produce a significant and comprehensive contribution of Karo-Batak Christians in GBKP without choosing between their culture or Christian faith. But giving more contribution to the special issue of ecological crisis. With this paper, I am trying to open a new academic opportunity for GBKP to officially review a Karo cultural treasure (it means WS) and to put use it as a practical guide of GBKP church eco-theology.

Research Limitations and Definition of Terms

The study of WS as the Karo-Batak traditional calendar is limited by some limitations and definitions of terms such as (a) on the meaning and the use of it for daily life of both traditional and modern Karo-Batak people (especially Karo-Batak Christians) occasions and interests. (b) The term practical guide used in this paper doesn't aim to make a practical guide step by step but only explains that WS can become a practical guide. The practical guide of church eco-theology, step by step, will discuss other opportunities. (c) Christian faith means an explanation of faith by the GBKP official Christian doctrines, especially on Karo culture and products. (d) cultural eco-theology means an eco-theology that accommodates culture and cultural insights to strengthen and contextualize the idea of it as relevant as possible, especially in pneumatology.

Picture 1: *Wari Sitelupuluh* (WS) in combination with the modern/Gregorian calendar in Indonesia. Each day of WS is inserted below the date and each month of WS is inserted beside the month of the Gregorian calendar. WS has no year.

Literature Review

The only theological academic literature on the Karo-Batak traditional calendar, WS, in Indonesia was *Dimensi Spiritualitas Ekologis Kalender Tradisional Karo* (Ginting, 2022). In this paper, WS was researched on its ecological spirituality dimensions with the lens of the Christian ecological spirituality idea of Leonardo Boff. This paper was successfully presenting that WS contains ecological spirituality dimensions and shows that WS contains two specific theological implications on Christian spirituality dialogue: the sense of

penggejapen (meaning: to feel) and the consciousness of rest. This paper also mentioned that Karo-Batak Christians can use WS in combination with the Gregorian calendar for their daily life because of the ecological-theological implication that WS has which become a helper for their ecological awareness (Ginting, 2022). Other kinds of literature on the Karo-Batak traditional calendar are non-academic and theological literature but cultural literature such as (Bangun, 1990), (E. P. Ginting, 1999), (Prinst, 1996), (Sitepu et al., 1996), and (Tarigan, 1990). All of these are written in Karonese and Indonesian languages. My point is *The Karo-Batak Traditional Calendar as a Practical Guide of Church Eco-theology: The Case of Karo Batak Protestant Church (GBKP) in Indonesia* is the first theological academic research on Karo-Batak traditional calendar that study it through the ecclesiological perspective that needs reinterpretation upon WS through pneumatology. It means that this research could contribute to giving new insight to the reader and open further research opportunities for other theological researchers.

Methodology

The research in this paper runs in four steps. The first step is reading and analyzing WS as the Karo-Batak traditional calendar specifically on the meaning and use of it in the daily life of the Karo-Batak people, especially for Karo-Batak Christians. The process of reading and analyzing is helped by the sources of Karo cultural works of literature (literature research with the hermeneutic method) and produces some significant data to be analyzed. The second step is reading and analyzing the official Christian doctrine of GBKP on Karo culture and products. This process runs through reading and analyzing the official documents of GBKP such as GBKP Church Order, GBKP Confession of Faith, and GBKP Ecclesiastical Trial Reports. In this step, significant information is collected to be analyzed together with the previous data. The third step is analyzing the collected data from a cultural eco-theology perspective. This perspective provides a measurable explanation of Christian ecological conversion as a mission and calling by the church in light of ecological crisis issues nowadays. As I mention above this perspective comes from the light of ecclesiology especially the interpretation of pneumatology. The last step is making and describing the conclusion and recommendation on the research. All of the steps run with the strong motivation that a product of Karo culture (*Wari Sitelupuluh*) can strengthen GBKP church mission.

Findings

GBKP and Karo-Batak Christians

GBKP is an acronym of *Gereja Batak Karo Protestan* (Karo Batak Protestant Church). GBKP born in 1889 through a Dutch Missionary Society (Nederlands Zendelinggenootschap) (Kipp, 1990). GBKP whose 317.060 church members (the majority is Karo-Batak people) (GBKP, 2019) is spread out in Indonesia and Malaysia and is also a member of some ecumenical organizations. The significant point that I want to mention here about GBKP is the system of church governance (church polity) is reformed or presbyterian with the official church order to arrange and manage all of life church organization and members (GBKP & Cooley, 1976, pp. 25–26). The significant finding in reading and analyzing GBKP (by official documents) is *the kind of church polity that GBKP has is still influenced by the West (colonial) perspective*. The foundational evidence of this argument is the pattern of church order that GBKP adopted nowadays similar to the oldest church order designed by Dutch ministers in 1941 (Gintings, 2015, p. 649). On the other side, Karo-Batak Christians are Karo-Batak people who received the Christian faith. Before Christianity came to Karo-land, the native religion and faith of the Karo-Batak people was *Pemena* or *Perbegu* which means "the people who believe in the existence of evil spirits". According to the research, that term was suggested by missionaries

(Rae, 1994, p. 18). Regardless of that, *Karo-Batak people (whether Christian or not) uphold a sense of balance between God, human beings (Karo society), and nature where they live*. For this reason, Karo-Batak people have a unique cultural system and product in their lives (Bangun, 1986, pp. 35–49). The sense of balance is like "the DNA" of the Karo-Batak people. The foundational difference between traditional/primal Karo-Batak people and Karo-Batak Christians lies in way of thinking. Primal/traditional Karo-Batak people have a bold mythical way of thinking but not for Karo-Batak Christians (Gintings, 1999, p. 13).

Wari Sitelupuluh (WS): The Karo-Batak Traditional Calendar

The Karo-Batak traditional calendar is *Wari Sitelupuh* (meaning: days of thirty). derived from *wari* (day) and *sitelupuluh* (thirty—the sum of the days). WS is a lunar calendar and it has 12 months in a year. Every month has 30 days on average. Both name of each month and each day has a special meaning to determine "the good day" or "the bad day" for occasions and interests (Rae, 1994, p. 32). In the modern world, WS is combined with the Gregorian calendar (see picture 1). The interesting finding about WS is this traditional calendar has no year. *It means that the life of the Karo-Batak people doesn't lean on time (year) but on how they treat their daily life in the light of a sense of balance. Whenever nature exists, the Karo-Batak people also exist*. This is the deep meaning of the use of WS. The problem with the use of WS is that traditionally, WS is run by *guru si beluh niktik wari* (shaman who can count the days). The shaman has believed to have magic power and an ancestor spirit that tell him how to use WS according to the situation, occasions, and interests (Ginting, 1999, p. 57). By this traditional situation and usage, WS is believed as a product of paganism and automatically contrary to the Christian faith by the church (GBKP).

Era before 1966, GBKP still hold the Dutch colonial missionary mindset about traditional Karo culture was the product of paganism and that is why GBKP has to avoid its aspect especially related to daily activity conducted by a shaman (*guru*). After this era, GBKP began to open the window for positivity of the culture by receiving some Karo cultural products like traditional music instruments (Ginting, 2015, p. 175). Through GBKP General Assembly in 1979, the use of WS in the daily life of church members was allowed (GBKP, 2016b, p. 5). Unfortunately, through GBKP General Moderator Assembly in 2002 and 2011 the use of WS in the daily life of church members was prohibited because of paganism and syncretism (GBKP, 2016b, pp. 113, 205). These trial decisions were seen also in GBKP Church Order Book 2005-2015 (GBKP, 2010, p. 76). In GBKP Church Order Book 2015-2025, the issue of the use of WS has not mentioned anymore (GBKP, 2021). *Conclusion: the position on the issue of the use of WS now is the same as before, the product of paganism and syncretism, and that is prohibited*. This conclusion is strengthened also with an explanation of GBKP confession of faith in culture (GBKP, 2016a, p. 30).

Toward New Using of Wari Sitelupuluh: a Practical Guide of Church Eco-theology of GBKP

In the study of Christian eco-theology (church eco-theology), there is part of Christian praxis with aiming to treat the environment wisely as a mission of Christians and the church. This part is practical. Denis Edwards mentions this area with the term "Christian ecological conversion" (Edwards, 2014, p. 152). Ernst Conradie mentions six levels of church practical eco-theology outcome and one of them is "local Christians communities can become ecologically conscious communities" (Conradie, 2006, p. 173). *Making Karo-Batak Christians can become ecologically conscious communities may happen if they are not uprooted from their cultural roots*. In my opinion, *using WS through a new paradigm can make Karo-Batak Christians have ecological consciousness*. Why ecological consciousness? Because of the real situation like nowadays, Karo-Batak Christians together

with other friends in the world are facing the issue of ecological crisis (environmental crisis). I believe that as human beings we have to contribute something our way to reduce the negative effect and resources of ecological crisis, and for me, it begins with ecological consciousness: it is a must.

The use of WS is prohibited by GBKP because this church argues that WS and the process of reading the time (day) are the product of paganism and syncretism where the evil spirit exists in it. GBKP maybe think that there is a magical power that can influence the church members. I acknowledge that in the official document of GBKP Confession of Faith, especially on culture, GBKP confesses that culture is a human product and in the light of God's Word, culture can use properly (GBKP, 2016a, p. 23). But I find the weakness of this confession: there is no explanation about the position of the Holy Spirit as a Giver of life and creation. *My point is, WS can become a practical guide of GBKP church eco-theology if GBKP confesses that Holy Spirit also works upon Karo-Batak people's ancestors in producing WS as a Karo culture product. In other words, GBKP confesses that WS is a gentle fruit of the Holy Spirit that works in human beings* (in this case: Karo-Batak people). Without this, it is difficult to receive WS as a part of the church's ecological mission in responding to the issue of ecological/environmental crisis. How it can happen?

GBKP has to try to reinterpret her theology of the Holy Spirit (pneumatology). In her pneumatology, Holy Spirit is just for human beings and not for other creatures. There is no explanation for how the Holy Spirit works upon human beings especially the product of human beings that produce by them. In my opinion, Leonardo Boff is right when explaining this topic. He says, "The Holy Spirit penetrates everything, embraces everything, exists beyond all limitation" that is why, Boff explains, "God is not tied down, but breaks in at will, upset human plans, act with irresistible power, reveals a wisdom that confounds all human understanding" (Leonardo Boff, 2015, pp. 60–61). For me, WS is a part of the gentle wisdom of the Holy Spirit given to Karo-Batak people so that they can arrange their daily life wisely with nature and environment like the "DNA" of theirs, the sense of balance: God, human beings, and nature.

Boff also speaks about shamanism (where the traditional use of WS was also conducted). He says, "Shamanism comes from the interpretation of reality as energy. ... shamanism is perhaps the oldest cosmovision of humanity, through which human beings gave meaning to the forces of nature and felt deeply united with them" (Leonardo Boff, 2015, p. 50). Boff's opinion is right when I was trying to understand WS. At the primal stage of Karo-Batak people's lives, as Simon Rae mentioned, there was no systematic way of life and belief or faith (Rae, 1994, p. 18). To arrange the society shaman existed and interpreted even though modern Karo-Batak people argue that interpretation is paganism. In my understanding, as modern Karo-Batak Christians, we can use the WS as an ecological-practical guide for our daily life because we reinterpret WS as not a product of paganism but a gentle wisdom of the Holy Spirit that works upon us nowadays. This gentle wisdom opens the room of our environmentally conscious as a concrete action of GBKP church eco-theology. Beginning now, Karo-Batak Christians do no need to choose between culture (as a cultural identity) and church (as a faith identity) but they can hold both. Even, the two potential domino effects as I mentioned above, don't need to happen.

Summary, Conclusion, and Recommendations

Summary

GBKP is a presbyterian church in Indonesia whose majority of the church member is Karo-Batak Christians. Up to now, GBKP still holds the tradition, at least on one or two parts, of Dutch missionaries' paradigm on running the church polity. This point is seen when talking

about the use of WS. Officially GBKP prohibits its usage because it is argued as a product of paganism and syncretism. Through cultural eco-theology, especially in pneumatology, GBKP is considered to reinterpret the meaning of the Holy Spirit's existence in Karo culture. The new interpretation presents a new insight and paradigm that WS is a gentle wisdom of the Holy Spirit works.

Conclusion

Wari Sitelupuluh (WS) can become a practical guide of GBKP church eco-theology if GBKP can confess that Holy Spirit also works upon Karo-Batak people's ancestors in producing WS as a Karo culture product. GBKP confess that WS is a gentle fruit of the Holy Spirit works in human being (in this case: Karo-Batak people). With this WS can become a part of the church's ecological mission in responding to the issue of ecological/environmental crisis. GBKP has a better potential to become ecologically conscious communities

Recommendations

This research recommends other theological researchers, especially those concern with Karo culture, to design a daily new alternative church liturgy based on *Wari Sitelupuluh* for concrete action for sustainable life. With this alternative liturgy, church members will have a deeper meaning and better ecological consciousness.

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20 - The Nexus Between Religious Tolerance and Peaceful Co-Existence in Democratic Nigeria

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Abstract

Living peacefully among the citizenry requires understanding Nigerian society's complexities and pluralism. Religious tolerance requires knowing and understanding other people's faith with the human connection to bring peace and development to the community. This study will examine the nexus between religious tolerance and peaceful co-existence in democratic Nigeria. Information will be derived from journals, articles, government publications, and internet sources through secondary data. The theory of toleration will be use in explaining the need for peaceful living among diverse religious group in Nigeria, while proving the essence for understanding and development in the country. Observation remains that Nigeria has passed through various ethnic and religious crises even before and after the military regime. But it is essential to coordinate a link between religious tolerance and peaceful co-existence among the people. Understanding the pluralistic issues in the Nigerian community will allow for interreligious dialogue, which will benefit everyone. Conflict resolution and other methods to curb the up rise in the cases of clashes among the people should be critically examined. More so, there have been calls for a united country and shun the difference that might occasionally arise in the country, which has created many gaps in the nation's development. Therefore, this paper concluded and recommended that religious tolerance must be preached. The teaching of peaceful co-existence must be part of the goals of every spiritual leader and stakeholder in the affairs of the country's policies.

Keywords: Religious tolerance, Peace, Conflict resolution, Nigeria

Introduction

Problem Statement

Tolerance is very important for Nigeria to build the nation to achieve the goals of a social welfare, justice, and prosperity state (Jegede, 2019). A nation constantly preoccupied with ethnic or cultural, and religious conflicts will be unable to increase industry, trade, foreign business networks, professional work, and all economic activities as the basic capital of a prosperous country. The diversity of ethnicity, culture, and religion that characterizes Nigerians has become a reality since independence. Nigeria's founding nationalist is confident in building a country with a variety in the same spirit to achieve the golden goal of social welfare, justice, and prosperity for all citizens. They believe these goals can be achieved by maintaining cohesiveness, harmonious relations, bureaucratic services, defense and state services, and mutual respect in religion, culture, and the arts.

However, promoting peaceful coexistence between different ethnic groups and adherents of other religions and cultures is not an easy task. Strong regulations, intelligent management, and ongoing government oversight are needed, as the active participation of religious

leaders and the wider community (Rosyada, 2017). In addition to its history of increasing coherent relations between all ethnicities and adherents of religions, Nigeria has very important experiences related to religious tolerance, ethnic relations, and cultural appreciation. Despite the above provisions, it is very important to mention quickly that freedom "permits" anyone to "abuse" or "ignore" the religious beliefs or tendencies of others; for no religion is accepted as higher than another before the law; and because of that the country is called a secular state (Oise-Oghaede, 2022). Therefore, this research will examine the nexus between religious tolerance and peaceful co-existence in democratic Nigeria.

Purpose of the Research

This study examines the nexus between religious tolerance and peaceful co-existence in democratic Nigeria. While the specific objectives will be considered:

1. To investigate how religious tolerance will serve as an antidote to the religious crisis in democratic Nigeria.
2. To examine the effects of religious intolerance on peaceful co-existence in Nigeria.
3. To discover the challenges of religious tolerance and peaceful co-existence in Democratic Nigeria.
4. To proffer suggestions on promoting religious tolerance and peaceful co-existence in Nigeria.

Concepts

Religious Tolerance: Tolerance requires that all that is different in the community respect each other and let others carry out their religious traditions as they believe. Tolerance also requires that all citizens of different religions, ethnicities, and cultures respect each other in all civil rights as human beings, access to all facilities and opportunities, education, professional jobs, etc. The main goal of tolerance is unity and harmony in diversity. According to Raji, Abdullateef, Araba-Yusuf, & Festus (2015), religious intolerance occurs when a group in society deliberately and hard tries to eradicate what is considered wrong by its members in religious thought and practice. In short, religious intolerance occurs when a group refuses to accept or accommodate the views and opinions of adherents of opposite religions.

Coexistence: Coexistence requires that all diverse communities strengthen togetherness, respect each other, work together to maintain the harmony of life, prevent conflicts between communities, and resolve conflicts. Coexistence also requires cooperation between government and non-governmental organizations to prevent conflicts resolve conflicts, and develop and even strengthen multicultural societies (Hartoyo, Sindung, Teuku, and Sunarto, 2020).

Peace: Peace is more than the disappearance of war. It is also the "upholding of an orderly and just society" organized to ward off violence or extortion by the aggressor and only to ward off exploitation and abuse by the strongest (Howard, 1971, p. 226). For Christians and Muslims, peace is not simply the absence of war or organized violence. It is also the existence of justice and the creation of status in which citizens can develop their full potential. Human nature is peaceful, and violence comes from our upbringing, not nature. Bad education separates us from our compassionate nature. Deception depicts people as inherently evil and selfish. This is the essence of violence (Yazdani, 2020). Building a culture of peace is an immediate task of our time, far more important than in the past.

Methodology

This research study used secondary data from articles, publications, journals, newspapers, and internet sources to analyze contents empirically. The need to understand the various reports on religious tolerance and peaceful co-existence prompted literature on the subject matter.

Findings

1. Religious Tolerance: The Antidote to Religious Crisis in Democratic Nigeria

Nigeria has an estimated population of over 200 million from various ethnic groups (Gulloma, 2023). Religion often coincides with an ethnic group, but not always. Most Hausa-Fulani in the north are Muslim, and most Ibo in the southwest are Christian. However, the Yoruba in the Southwest is both Muslim and Christian, with a slight Muslim majority and many mixed marriages. In addition, the National Education Policy (2009) expressed concern about the "erosion of core values and growing cynicism in society". He advocated making education a "powerful tool for cultivating social and moral values." Education must "promote universal and external values directed towards the unity and integration of our people" (Ibukun, and Aboluwodi, 2010).

Religion must enlighten, inspire, and unite people in every society. Ironically, this often breeds dissension, intolerance, and hatred among religious groups in Nigeria today. The danger posed by religion has reached such frightening dimensions that it cannot sustain any meaningful development underneath. According to Okoro (2008: 105), religion and its institutions are suspected in some quarters to be the main cause of violence, crisis, and conflict in modern history and the history of human social development.

To further promote religious intolerance and peaceful coexistence, Ojie (2003) suggests that concerted efforts should be made to achieve intercultural awareness among the citizens of this country. Therefore, studying the Nigerian people and their religion should be mandatory in our education system. Efforts should also encourage greater interaction between different religious groups. The need for dialogue also makes sense to promote religious tolerance and peace in Nigeria. The dialogue will help create religious consensus, understanding, and peaceful coexistence among the country's diverse religious communities. The purpose of dialogue should not be to erase the identity of each participating group. Instead, the aim should be to address various areas of religious disagreement (Davies & Egbuchu, 2019). Christianity and Islam recognize dialogue as a legitimate way of resolving conflicts. For example, the Islamic dialogue model allows recognizing opposing groups' positions and accommodating their views.

2. Effects of Religious Intolerance on Peaceful Co-existence in Democratic Nigeria

It identifies religious intolerance as the main cause of conflict, senseless destruction of life and property, and lack of sustainable development in the country. "One of the problems causing problems in this Nigeria is the high level of religious intolerance, namely the false worship of God. If God doesn't want religion, He can stop it (James, 2022). In the case of Nigeria, the frequency of religious conflicts in the north has so far left a negative effect on the socio-economic composition of society. During these conflicts, Christians sometimes took up arms against Muslim attacks, claiming they did so in self-defense.

Religious intolerance is a major threat to human rights. Human rights apply to everyone, regardless of skin color, sex, gender, religion, health status, clothing, socioeconomic status, etc. This threat is not only due to fundamentalist groups' real actions, which can be identified as clear standard human rights violations; the real threat comes from the political goals or political projects underlying fundamentalism, which essentially consist of changing the way

identities are ascribed and negotiated. Human rights issues are about having rights as human beings (Ojo, 2017).

Another area that has experienced a serious decline due to conflicts stemming from religious intolerance in Nigeria is Nigeria's economic life country. Religious violence and insecurity resulting from intolerance continue to affect the country's economic prosperity. Various activities of religious fundamentalists and rebels continue to negatively impact economic and business activities in most parts of the country, particularly in northern Nigeria. It is vital to note that most of the parts of the Northeast that are most affected by the activities of religious fanatics and terrorists are the agrarian communities whose agricultural produce is transported to other parts of Nigeria for sale and consumption (Çancı, and Odukoya, 2016). The activities of religious fanatics and rebels have no doubt drastically reduced the country's income and gross domestic product, thereby hampering Nigeria's economic growth and development (Atoi & Babale, 2021).

3. Challenges of Religious Tolerance and Peaceful Co-existence in Democratic Nigeria

From the above point, it is vital undertaking various works of literary works and viewpoints; the following are identified as the challenges of religious tolerance and achieving peaceful co-existence in democratic Nigeria:

Poverty: The problem of poverty, especially in urban areas, seems to cause most of the violence (ethnic or religious), originating from problems such as unemployment, inadequate housing, and physical and social infrastructure (Obateru, 1994; Sulaiman & Ojo, 2013).

Wrong religious orientation: People learn differently in different religions. When adherents of certain religions are indoctrinated incorrectly, religious obsession often occurs, leading to violence.

Religious literacy level: Every Nigerian belongs to one religion or another. However, only a few people get an education in Nigeria because people often believe what their religious leaders tell them; illiterate people are easily manipulated to achieve selfish or other goals because they are uncritical and illogical.

Selfishness on the part of religious people: Some religious leaders, regardless of their calling, tend to be selfish. They use this method to commit religious violence, knowing the ruling government will invite them to seek approval. Therefore, they joined the government for their interests (Sulaiman, 2016).

Conclusion

This research study focuses on the nexus of religious tolerance and peaceful co-existence in Democratic Nigeria. With the wave of religious crises and other challenges in achieving a peaceful society, there is no more important issue than finding lasting solutions to building a better and united country. The call for the harmonious living among the different ethnic and religious bodies, including African religious people, will create sustainable development for the country. The various past and recent issues of inter-religious conflict in Nigeria have made the country lose out on being part of a developed nation. On this note, a united country is needed and builds a brighter future for the coming generation.

Recommendations

1. There is a need to protect freedom of religion in Nigeria.
2. It is important that promoting religious tolerance and acceptance of opposing views should be enhanced both onsite and in the media for all religious people to be aware.

3. The government and international community's support Nigerian human resource development via training and job provision.
4. Spreading the message of true friendship and true love among the Nigerian people will curb ethnoreligious conflict.
5. Secular Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) and Religious Organizations (FBOs) must redouble their efforts as dialogue facilitators and conflict mediators between conflicting parties.

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21 - Impact of Religious Institution in Peacebuilding: The Role of the Naga Shisha Hoho in the Formation of the Forum for Naga Reconciliation (FNR)

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Abstract

Nagas in the North Eastern part of India have been in violent conflicts for more than seventy years. The conflict began as a fight for independence from the Union of India but deteriorated into a cycle of factional fighting within the Naga political party, which has engulfed society in a wave of animosity, suspicion, and retaliation. Religious organizations, specifically Naga Shisha Hoho (Christian religious institution), drive the creation of the Naga Forum for Reconciliation during such a difficult time. This peace initiative in Nagaland by religious institutions is put into perspective in agreement with the peacebuilding scholar's argument on the positive impact of religion in peacebuilding.

Key Terms: Forum for Naga Reconciliation (FNR), Naga Shisha Hoho (SH), Religious peacebuilding, Nagaland, Religious Institution

INTRODUCTION

Problem Statement

The Nagas have been immersed in one of the world's longest but least-known violent battles for nearly seven decades. The Naga conflict began as a struggle for Naga independence but has now devolved into a cycle of factional and inter-tribal feuds that have engulfed Naga civilization in a vortex of hatred, bloodshed, and retribution. The murder among Naga factions came to a halt until after the creation of the FNR. Going back in time, it was the religious group, Shisha Hoho, that played a vital part in the founding of the FNR, putting an end to the bloodshed in Nagaland (P. R. J. Schreiter & Jorgensen, 2013). However, no extensive work has been done on the function of the Christian prayer center, Naga Shisha Hoho, in the development of FNR, which played an important role in peacebuilding among Naga insurgent factions.

Research Questions

1. What was the role played by the Christian prayer Center – Naga Shisha Hoho (religious institution) in the formation of FNR?
2. How FNR was formed and contribute to the peace in Nagaland?

Research Purpose

This paper attempted to contribute to the continuing scholarship on religious peacebuilding by highlighting the importance of Naga Shisha Hoho, the development of FNR, and its contribution to peacebuilding in Naga society. The work will be significant because there is insufficient research on the topic; hence, it will be of additional value and a new resource in the field. The lack of research on the origin and function of FNR may be due to its being disregarded in the larger context of the conflicts in North East India.

Background and Context of the Nagas

Nagaland is a state in North-East India bordering Myanmar to the east. Many Naga scholars believe they migrated from southwest China through Myanmar during the Great Wall construction or, at the end, following different directions and places (Changkiri, 2015; Dozo, 2017; Iralu, 2009; Jamir & Lanunungsang, 2005). Under the British annexation in the late nineteenth and beginning of the twentieth century, they came under British rule. After India gained independence from the British, Naga Hills territory was simply transferred to India. Under these circumstances, the Nagas became a part of it (Chaise & Hazarika, 2009). The Indian administration faced stiff opposition from the Nagas, who did not want to become a part of India. Notwithstanding the tension, Naga statehood was signed by the Indian government and the Naga People's Convention, and a tiny group of Nagas functioned as government officials in the Assam administration (Chasie & Hazarika, 2009; Iralu, 2009). Previous to all of this, the Nagas created the Naga Club in 1918. The Naga National Council (NNC) was formed in 1946, to unite all Naga tribes and ensure their freedom. With the passage of time and the division of viewpoints, another side developed in the 1980s, notably the National Socialist Council of Nagaland (NSCN), which was later divided into two parties, the NSCN(IM) and the NSCN (K). The division and split between them grew, and there are now more political groups in Nagaland. There was a lot of bloodshed and political unrest in the state due to all of this (Iralu, 2017; Jaiswal, 2021; Saikia, 2014). Against the backdrop of Nagaland's violent context, the development of FNR through the religious group Shisha Hoho is crucial.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Library and bookstore shelves are filled with critiques of the negative impacts of religion in conflict scenarios. Many scholars have long challenged and stereotyped religion as a source of conflict. However, at the same time, some contemporary scholars are on a positive note that religious institutions play a crucial role in peacemaking (Abu-Nimer & Garred, 2018; Appleby, 2000; Broadhead & Keown, 2007). The dynamics of religion are that it can be very violent, and on the other pole, it can be a pacifist. Appleby named that dynamic as 'militance' bearing double meaning. By 'militance,' he means the willingness and, under certain conditions, even an eagerness to sacrifice oneself, one's family, one's loved ones, and one's most precious possessions in the service of a noble cause that is perceived to be transcendent, sacred, beyond time and space, engaging at the deepest level of humanity (Appleby, 2000). In the words of Rudolph Otto, this dynamic is "*mysterium tremendum et fascinans*," a mystery of the radical other, which is tremendous in the sense of soul-shaking and ultimately fascinating, intriguing, and compelling (Otto, 2017). This sacredness is a source of ethical behaviors and interpretations, from suicide through homicide to martyrdom to self-sacrifice. Religions legitimate this range of activity under the canopy of experiencing the sacred (Appleby, 2000).

Religion and violence

The study of religion and violence shows two prominent types of violence associated with religion (Appleby, 2000). The first type is *ethnoreligious or ethnonationalism violence*. Here the power and militance of religion are brought to bear in a cause that is, strictly speaking, not religious, or not primarily for religious goals. In ethnoreligious violence, religion itself claims that its institutional self-understanding and prerogatives are implicitly or unconsciously subordinate to a different ideology, such as the nation-state or the ethnic group. Nationalist and ethnic leaders recruit religion to make sacred their struggles and therefore legitimate. This kind of dynamism and activity includes martyrdom and suicide, as well as acts of sacrifice and compassion for fellow countrymen and women or other co-

religionists. It is an extreme form of religious militancy that legitimates violence and sometimes sees violence as a sacred duty or obligation. The second type of religious violence is *religious extremism* which is often called “fundamentalism”. Fundamentalists believe the solution to problems besetting society is the building up of religion as a viable alternative to secular society, which has replaced religion or rivals it.

Religion and Non-Violence

There are numerous pieces of literature that discuss the negative impact of religion in a conflict scenario. However, there are several academicians (Appleby, 2000; Coward & Smith, 2004; Creamer et al., 2015) who suggest that religious organization play critical role in conflict than simply negative one. Faith-based organizations, and their workers, are often found on the frontlines of conflict throughout the world, conducting conflict management and resolution activities as well as advancing peacebuilding initiatives. In the words of Appleby those who engage in peacebuilding works are “nonviolent religious militant” and “religious virtuosi” – holy monks and gurus, learned rabbis and mullahs, dedicated priests and ministers, and devout laity, are the people who place themselves in jeopardy by working in conflict zones among the poor and dispossessed (Appleby, 2000). These are the people who make themselves available as conflict mediators, and they take responsibility for rebuilding the institutions of war-ravaged societies. Religious actors dedicate to pursuing justice and peace through non-violent means operate at various distances from life-threatening conflict, in various relations to the religious community and its official structures need to take seriously. For nonviolent religious militancy becomes politically effective over the long term. Furthermore, political effectiveness is not the only measure of social potency, but it is critical to accomplishing sustainable peace in the society.

Since the aftermath of ‘9/11,’ greater international attention has been paid to the role of religion in conflict. Popular perceptions about religious fundamentalism have led, to both a widening gap between different religious communities and to an increasing awareness among (secular) policy-makers that religion can play an instrumental, potentially problematic role in local, national, and international conflicts. At the same time, there is a growing appreciation among practitioners of the fact that religious actors also have great potential to resolve conflict and decrease tensions. This holds true, particularly for post-conflict settings, where religion can contribute to a wide range of peace-building activities (Ali & Mans, 2006). The combination of moral authority and the ability to create a genuine commitment to peace among large parts of the population makes many international policy-makers regard religious communities as important ‘drivers of change’ in peace-building. An increasing number of scholars in the field of international relations have come to devote their attention to phenomena such as ‘religion as a conversation starter’ (Merdjanova & Brodeur, 2009), ‘the global resurgence of religion and the transformation in international relations’ (Thomas, 2005), ‘making peace with faith’ (Mohammed Abu-Nimer & Garred, 2018). Learning to take cultural and religious pluralism seriously is essential for foreign policy in the 21st century (Thomas, 2005). Many recent academic writings describe religion as a key factor for peace-building: religious actors have some distinctive features that make them particularly valuable as peace-building agents. In her edited publication, *Bridge or Barrier*, Gerrier ter Haar argues that “... religious actors tend to enjoy institutional legitimacy, have an available methodology, and possess the structures and networks necessary for the mobilization of people” (Haar & Busuttill, 2005). However, the spiritual dimension of peace-building is largely neglected by secularists, who consider this more as a technical process. Religious actors can play a positive role in a post-conflict setting by combining spiritual guidance with organizational capacity. However, religious peace-building is far from being a monolith exercise. Appleby emphasizes that there is a clear ambivalence: on the one hand,

it is important to note that “with the advent of ... coalitions across religious, cultural and geographic boundaries, unprecedented possibilities arise for developing the peace-building skills of religiously inspired actors.” On the other hand, “too many religious leaders continue to pursue narrow sectarian or ethnic agendas, think only of the needs and rights of their own people and fail to oppose the demonization of the other” (Appleby, 2000). The literature therefore seems to suggest that religious actors should be considered with some caution, but policy-makers should also acknowledge the potential for religion to build a sustainable peace.

METHODOLOGY

This research work applied historiography and reviewing the FNR documents, publications, and books, newspaper articles and digital data posted on social media shall be considered secondary resources. Employing Qualitative research, the researcher interviewed key leaders, members of the FNR committee, and leaders of Shisha Hoho through WhatsApp and messenger calls.

FINDINGS

RQ1 Christian prayer group Shisha Hoho – A Force in Naga Peacebuilding

The ‘Shisha’ means ‘doing in obedience’, while ‘Hoho’ is a word representing an organization or a conference. Shisha Hoho was started in a small village, Kutsapo under the Phek district of Nagaland. This small village was one of the last villages to accept Christianity in a predominantly Christian state. Although Christianity arrived in Kutsapo in 1948, the spread was slow. Even up to the 1990s, when Christianity had entrenched itself fully in many parts of Nagaland, in Kutsapo village only 30% of the population was Christian. In 1991, something dramatic happened that saw an increase in Christian numbers. It was down to one man name Chosayi Lohe and the Naga Shisha Hoho prayer house (Kraft et al., 2020; Naga Shisha Hoho Prayer Centre, 2016).

In the 1990s Naga Shisha Hoho prayer center was started. It was established at a crucial time. In the late 1980s and early 1990s, factional violence between the NSCN-K, NSCN-IM, and the NNC was at its height. It was a time when the situations of the Naga Political Groups (NPG) were in a state of epic weariness because of the situation between the various factions. At this juncture, the so-called NPGs sought the help of the church and the village where they could come together and energize their spiritual growth and also get physical aid. It is also to be noted that, at this point in time, there was no other prayer center in Nagaland. The prayer center became a place where irrespective of position, or profession, whoever has the heart and burden for society comes together for prayer and fasting. During this period Chosayi hears the voice of God for the Nagas to come together. But he was unsure how to put this into practice. God then instructed him to go to the various nationalist leaders and “say to the leaders that they must stop killing each other” (P. Khusoh, personal communication, December 2022; Kraft et al., 2020; Naga Shisha Hoho Prayer Centre, 2016).

Although Chosayi had no background in dealing with nationalist leaders, God directed him to speak. Some believed while others doubted Chosayi’s intentions. Violence continued amongst the various factions, but eventually, they realized the futility of it and people started to believe in him. Chosayi’s role as God’s emissary allows him to travel to different Naga political group leaders and different locations (P. Khusoh, personal communication, December 2022; Kraft et al., 2020).

RQ2 How FNR was formed and contributes to the peace in Nagaland?

The Forum for Naga Reconciliation (FNR) was formed at a time when Naga society was torn apart with intense “interfactional” violence, suspicion, distrust, and divisive political rhetoric (Hindustan Times, 2008; Singh, 2006). FNR was formed in principle on February 24, 2008, as one of the outcomes of the Naga Peace Convention organized by the Naga Shisha Hoho in Dimapur. It was christened on March 25, 2008, at Kohima with the support of 39 Naga frontal organizations, the Nagaland Baptist Church Council (NBCC), and the Council of Naga Baptist Churches (CNBC). In 2008, the forum comprised of 14 members where Wati Aier, a prominent Naga theologian, was the founding convener (Morung Express, 2017). Chosayi and Wati are one of those religious virtuosi in whose dedication and commitment FNR was founded and the violence among the Naga factions came to a halt (Morung Express, 2019).

Members of the FNR represent Naga churches, tribal councils, and civil society organizations. FNR is a neutral organization that is not linked with or supportive of any Naga political group or party active in Naga politics. It continues to strive for Naga reconciliation in an impartial and fair manner, with the Naga people's interests and rights as its core principle. The FNR has been involved in the following activities since March 2008 (Aier, 2019; Morung Express, 2011, 2017, 2019, Naga Shisha Hoho Prayer Centre, 2016). Notwithstanding the lack of hope, timely mediation and back-channel diplomacy were pursued. On August 21, 2008, members of Naga political groups, frontline Hohos, churches, and civil societies signed a 10-point 'A Covenant of Shared Hope' in Chiang Mai, Thailand. FNR's efforts led to the signing of the "Covenant of Reconciliation", which reduced killings due to factionalism. Only after the Naga factions signed a peace agreement did the killing halt. It is noteworthy how crucial the Christian concepts of reconciliation and concept are in this situation. The Forum for Naga Reconciliation, a civil society organization, has been the key player in the peace movement outside of the bargaining table (Baruah, 2020).

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The Naga Shisha Hoho prayer center was established in the 1990s to help the NPGs energize their spiritual growth and get physical aid, as there was no other prayer center in Nagaland. The Forum for Naga Reconciliation (FNRN) was formed in 2008 to work for Naga reconciliation in an impartial and fair manner, with the interest and rights of the Naga people as its primary principle. A Covenant of Common Hope was adopted at the Naga Peace Summit III in 2008, which became the basis for the subsequent "Covenant of Reconciliation".

In Nagaland, religious institutions have played a vital role in promoting peace. If religious virtuosi like Chosayi and Wati Aier's commitment to promoting peace is absent, there will be factional fighting and bloodshed among the Nagas, which could have been worse. It is worth noting the role NSH, FNR, and the Nagaland Baptist Church Council played in the 1960s in pressing for a bilateral cease-fire agreement between the GOI and the NNC. These actions are motivated by a strong belief in Jesus' message of love and forgiveness, which is evident in their activities.

Religious extremism and religion amalgamating with ethnic interests have create havoc in society in many places. However, in the case of Nagaland active participation and involvement of the religious institution have brought peace.

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22 - Epistemic Injustice in Protest Policing Online: The Case Study of the Polish Women's Strike

Rak, Joanna

Problem Statement: Epistemic injustice included in protest policing influences the development of civil disorder.

Purpose of the Study: The study aims to determine an extent of epistemic injustice of protest policing online for the Polish Women's Strike.

Literature or Theory: The study links the theories of epistemic injustice and protest policing.

Research Methods: The study uses content and thematic analysis of tweets released by Warsaw police responsible for policing Women's Strike protests.

Summary of Findings: The study shows the relationships between exclusion and silencing, as the characteristics of epistemic injustice, and the development of civil disorder. Epistemic injustice is indicative of partisan policing.

Conclusion: The study contributes to the studies on procedural justice by showing the role of epistemic injustice in protest policing and its consequences for public order.

Keywords

1 Epistemic injustice

2 Protest policing

3 Procedural justice

4 Poland

5 Social movements

Area: Justice and Peace

23 - The Silent Hagar: A Feminist Intersectional Perspective on the Biblical Narrative Reflecting the Context of Women Migrant Workers

Yuliana M. Benu

Abstract

Migration in the Asian context has inevitably been represented by women. It is not only representing the quantity, but also its vulnerable condition. Women migrant workers are mostly mistreated, violated, and abused. This writing 'The Silent Hagar' aims to portray and reflect the plight of women migrant workers who are trapped into modern slavery. It has begun since ancient society, which was recorded in the Bible narrative in Genesis 16:1-16.

Key Words: Feminist, Intersectional, Women, Migrant, Workers.

Introduction

Trans-national crime and international organized crime are the serious **problems** in the migration process (Jurnal Perempuan, Ed. 94, 2017). These criminals are possessed with groups or networks which works systematically from local to global levels to recruit, transport, and transfer persons by use of coercion, abduction, fraud, deception, the abuse of power (cf. Palermo Protocol, 2002). Persons, especially women and girls, in plight due to poverty, climate crisis, low income, debt bondage, less education, victims of gender-based violence are the most targeted by the mafia. They are placed by the mafia to work mostly in informal sectors such as domestic workers, palm oil laborers, and sex workers. Unfortunately, working with less protection caused human rights violations against women workers.

Research **questions** in this paper are (**RQs 1**) how to identify multiple faces of violence that are experienced by women migrant workers since ancient to modern society? (**RQs 2**) How to build community resilience to provide safe space for women workers to speak up about human rights violations they experience? This paper **aims** to describe women migrant workers' conditions in the past and current situation and to give alternative solutions for the community to provide safe space for women to speak up.

This writing is motivated by the anti-human trafficking movement in Timor, Indonesia and my background as a theologian. As a young female theologian, I am reflecting from the Biblical narratives of Hagar in Genesis 16:1-16. Hagar's experience is similar to women migrant workers who face stigma, discrimination, and exploitation in patriarchal society and from their employers in the working workplace. The women workers situation will be identified from my own context in Timor related to migration and women migrant workers. This writing is not aimed to convince you to fully follow my thoughts, as each context and experience have its own characteristics. You can encounter this writing by your thinking and experience based on your own context. However, in action against human trafficking, we can work together.

Literature Review

Migration is simply understood as people move within or beyond a country in search of a better life. Many people migrate to seek for study, living with family, and economic opportunities, while others escape from conflict, war, and persecution (UN, 2020). Based on IOM World Migration Report 2020, per June 2019 international migrants were approximately 272 million globally. Around two thirds were labour migrants (UN, 2020).

Today, in the global market, women are the most demanded as informal workers. According to data released by WIEGO and ILO in 2019, there were 76 million domestic workers globally and 76 percent of them were women (WIEGO, 2022). The majority of workers came from developing countries as explained 62,2 million or 82 percent. Indonesia was one of the sender countries. This figure demonstrates what it is called ‘feminization of migration’. The term emerges from the issue of the escalating number of women domestic workers and trafficking in persons recently, especially in developing countries (Jurnal Perempuan, Ed. 94, 2017).

This paper uses feminist and intersectional theories as well as biblical hermeneutics. These perspectives will try to identify and understand women workers’ situations from the past until the current situation, specifically the multiple burdens that women have faced.

Methodology

In this paper, a case study method is used to describe the past situation of women workers which is taken from the Biblical narrative, Genesis 16:1-16. This case study will be a guideline to describe and understand women workers context recently.

Findings

(RQs 1) The past— Intersectionality of Women workers. In Christianity, narrative stories which is recorded in the Bible (Old and New Testaments) in the ancient time of Israel and Roman empire did not mention directly the term of domestic worker. However, in practice, the term closely related to servant/slavery. This practice thrived in ancient patriarchal society. Masters/mistresses are people who come from high social status, rich economically, possess power and high position in the society. While slaves are opposite from masters. They come from lowest social structure, poor people, descendant of slave, prisoners of war, and those who are trapped in debt bondage. A master can have dozens of slaves which legitimate his status as a wealth person (Mangililo, 2006).

In the context of slavery, there is power abused between master/mistress and slave. Slaves have no rights as they are owned by their master/mistress. They are seen as property of their master/mistress. Hence, being slaves means to devote their entire lives to their master/mistress. Slaves can be freed if their master/mistress releases them. Children, men, and women can be slaves, however women experience extremely heavy suffering due to the patriarchal system in the society. Female slaves can be used as ransom if the family is unable to pay debts (Susan E. Hysten, 2018).

The Bible narrative in Genesis 16:1-16 described the live of Abram, Sarai, and Hagar in Canaan. These three actors lived in ancient patriarchal society which placed them into different social status that bring advantages or discriminations. **Abram**, as a man, had a privilege in many aspects of life such as in religion, economy, politics, and social. **Sarai**, Abram’s wife was a middle-class woman, however she still faced society standard where women should give birth and rise children. Sarai faced stigma and discrimination as she did not had child yet. **Hagar**, an Egyptian slave who work as a servant for her mistress, Sarai. As a foreigner, Hagar had no relatives or friends whom she could talk to or assist her in difficulties. As a woman, Hagar lived in a patriarchal society in which male domination was a high privilege over women. As a slave and poor person, Hagar was economically dependent on her mistress. She had to submit passively to her mistress as her live and death were under the control. (Mangililo, 2006). These multiple burdens demonstrated Hagar’s vulnerability living in the lowest social structure of the ancient society. In this context, we could understand **the Silent Hagar**.

Social class and status created a huge gap between Abram-Sarai and Hagar. Abuse of power was clearly shown when Sarai gave Hagar to Abram so Hagar could bear her a child. Later on, Hagar conceived a son from Abram. Hagar was voiceless as she could not decide whether she agreed or not. However, for the sake of Sarai, Hagar sacrifices herself. **Here we understand that ‘The silent Hagar’ had no authority over her body as a woman.**

Instead of being happy, Sarai was envious when she knew that Hagar conceived. Sarai complained to Abram that Hagar despised her. Abram asked Sarai “Your slave is in your hand, do with her whatever you think best.” But Sarai mistreated (it could be violence, torture, punishment) Hagar even though she was pregnant. Here **‘the Silent Hagar was a powerless woman.’** She couldn’t fight against her mistress.

Living in suffering and desperation, Hagar fled from Sarai. Only two possible choices: living or dying. Staying with Sarai and Abram meant living in a nightmare or even death but leaving means choosing to still be alive. Here **‘the silent Hagar had courage try to rescue her life and the baby.’**

Without a clear destination, Hagar ran away from Sarai. But the Angel of the Lord found her near a spring in the desert. I would like to highlight the word “found”. As I said before that, Hagar perhaps had no friends, no family to tell the suffering stories, but there in her loneliness in the desert, God found her. **Here we learn that “God heard Hagar's silent voices. God is with the marginalized people.”** God promised Hagar that He will increase her descendants so much that will be too numerous to count. This promise brings hope to Hagar, as **she knew that God heard her misery, so God will protect and empower her** (Mangililo, 2006).

The Current— ‘The silent Hagar’ in the context of women migrant workers. Today, there are countless stories of women migrant workers stories like ‘the silent Hagar’. The similar situation based on their multiple identities as women, single mother, migrants, poor, and victims of gender-based violence. Living in patriarchal society has put them as second class persons and places them in the lowest social structure. It has defined them as powerless women with lack of protection. Marginalized women who live in poverty, and debt bondage are at high risk in the context of modern slavery.

In 2017, the World Bank estimated there were around 9 million Indonesian domestic workers working overseas and around 4,2 million domestic workers inside the country. East Nusa Tenggara (NTT) province has been recorded as one of the highest-ranking provinces in Indonesia to send workers overseas and related to cases of trafficking in persons, NTT is at the first position (Tempo.co, 2015).

Thousands of cases have reported that victims are threatened like animals, violated, passports confiscated and sexually abused by the employers and agency, not allowed to interact with other people outside the employers’ house, denied holidays, long working hours, less or no salary, and murder. Pregnant women migrant workers died when giving birth due to limited access to health facilities in the plantation. Workers in fishing vessels are forced to work overtime, not allowed to be sick and if they die, their corpses will be thrown away to the sea. In the past 8 years, more than 600 workers died in their working place and not all of them were returned to NTT.

(RQs 2) Build community resilience. The plight of migration in Asia is an irony. Building community resilience to provide safe space for women is one of effective strategies to end crime against humanity. Here are some suggestions that are needed to build a safe community for women.

First, in patriarchal society, women should be treated equally as men in terms of fulfilling their rights. Women have equal opportunity to get high education as men, have chance to speak up and be involved in the decision-making policy. **Second**, domestic work which is mostly represented by women is counted as a job that has same level with other work in public sector. Promote equality means no discrimination based on gender and working class. It is needed legal protection by government to avoid women working from violence and exploitation in their working place. **Third**, networking plays important role to work hand in hand combating every form of human rights violation, including human trafficking and modern slavery. Build network from local, national, regional and global is an action combating trans-national crime and international organized crime.

Summary and Conclusion

The Silent Hagar represents thousands of women migrant workers in patriarchal society who experience various forms of violence both in private and public areas. In search of a better life, they left their hometown, families, and children to get proper work overseas. Unfortunately, they are trapped in the human trafficking mafia as they are the most targeted group by the mafia to supply global market demand on cheap labor. We are called to stand together overcoming the culture of silence which literally normalized violence in patriarchal society. We stand in solidarity with women workers by providing a safe place promoting equality and gender justice, protection, and networking.

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24 - Environmental Consequences of Myanmar Coup on Karen's Forest and Nature Reserves: Violence Monitoring Perspective

Anwar, Riyad Febrian

Problem Statement: As environmental degradation is interrelated with armed conflict, we suggest that NGO's violent monitoring initiatives could go beyond to also highlights events that led to environmental destruction.

Purpose of the Study To what extent violence monitoring method to document instances of violence could be used to identify direct or indirect environmental destruction within the violence monitoring reported area?

Literature or Theory: This article would build upon two theories: 1) Efficacy of citizens' journalism in times of conflict. The article will also reflect on Center for Integrity's usage of Violence Monitoring Archive in Rakhine State and 2) the mutual relationship between natural resource and armed conflict. (Berhe AA (2022) On the relationship of armed conflicts with climate change. PLOS Clim 1(6): e0000038. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pclm.0000038>)

Research Methods: Exploratory research on quantitative methods on documenting instances of violence.

Summary of Findings: CSI's violence monitoring does not only accumulate human or property losses, to give more contextual understanding to the public, it also documents other background snippets such as what causes such violence, when the violence occurred, and who perpetrated the violence. These background snippets are useful, not necessarily to estimate environmental damage, but to associate known environmental loss in the area with the violent incident that precede it.

Conclusion: Our observation on CSI's violence dataset suggests that the violence monitoring is ill-equipped to become sound evidence to estimate environmental damage yet it might be functional enough to inform public on the danger of armed conflict to the local environment at large.

Keywords

1 Violence Monitoring

2 Myanmar Coup

3 Karen State

4 Environmental Activism

5 Environmental Degradation

Area: Justice and Peace

25 - Marginalizing the Faithful: The Assad Regime's Use of War on Terror Language to Suppress Religious Dissent in the Syrian Civil War

Shah, Sama

Problem Statement: Although religion has played a significant role in the Syrian Civil War, the Assad regime has employed War on Terror language to delegitimize and marginalize religious protestors as radical extremists, raising the issue of how the regime's rhetoric and policies have impacted religious dissent in the country.

Purpose of the Study: This research paper examines the role of religion in the Syrian Civil War and argues that the Assad regime has employed War on Terror language to delegitimize religious protestors as radical extremists.

Literature or Theory: This study will draw on literature from the fields of political science, religious studies, and critical discourse analysis.

Research Methods: The paper will use qualitative methods, including critical discourse analysis of official speeches, media reports, and government policies.

Summary of Findings: This paper is expected to find that the regime has employed War on Terror language to suppress dissent and entrench its authoritarian rule during the war.

Conclusion: This paper's conclusion highlights the need for greater attention to the complex role of religion in the war, underscoring the importance of distinguishing between genuine religious movements and terrorist groups in efforts to promote peace in the region.

Keywords

1 Syria

2 Islam

3 War on Terror

4 Authoritarianism

5 Dissent

Area: Religion; Justice and Peace

26 - Social Work Education: An Instrument for Conflict Resolution and Peace Building

Baily Vincent

Abstract

This paper includes the results of a study designed to identify the role of social work education in conflict resolution and peacebuilding.

Social workers play a crucial role in the lives of individuals, groups, and communities whom they serve, and the responsibilities of social workers include conducting assessments, providing counseling, and connecting clients with various resources, in order to create better living conditions, reducing the existing conflicts and initiate peacebuilding, hence make social workers ambassadors of peace. The research questions studied were to find the connection between Social Work Education, conflict resolution, and Peace, the methods, tools, and skills employed by them in resolving conflict and achieving peace. A key aspect of the study was to understand emotions, perceptions, thoughts, and ideas about Conflict resolution aiming toward peacebuilding.

Introduction

Peacebuilding is determined to entail participation in the struggle for social justice. Peace is a lack of violence. Peacebuilding is described as participation in the battle for social justice. Peace is defined as the absence of conflict and fear of violence among various social groups. The absence of conflict or violent hatred is often defined as peace. As a result, it begins with attentive active listening and communication in order to develop and build true mutual understanding. Galtung, the father of peace studies, regularly mentions the difference between 'negative peace' and 'positive peace'. Negative peace refers to the lack of violence. If a ceasefire is imposed, for example, a bad peace will result. It is negative because something undesirable has stopped happening (for example, violence has stopped, oppression has finished). Positive peace is packed with positive content such as relationship healing, the development of social structures that serve the needs of the entire people, and the constructive settlement of conflict. Peace does not imply the absence of all strife. It entails the absence of all types of violence and the constructive resolution of conflict.

According to UN 2023, India still being in a developing status, and people in India still experience a lack of basic amenities, lack access to education, and healthcare. Conflicts among individuals, groups, and communities are raising day by day based on the change in the demands of their lives and lifestyles. Social workers continually work in areas where conflict is prevalent on a daily basis. Few examples of conflicts among

- Individuals – Problems with self-awareness, Conflict between person to person (needs, values, interests) which leads to emotional disturbance and malfunction.
- Groups – Working in groups/teams is a key area of any organization, and if there are conflicts that are dysfunctional it leads to disruptions (goals, interests).
- Communities – Caste-based Discrimination (rights, positions, familial, religious, and political)

The importance of social workers in peacekeeping and resolving conflicts is growing (Parker, 2013). "Social work is a practice as well as an academic field that fosters social

transformation and growth, social cohesion, and the empowerment and liberation of people." The ideas of equitable society, rights of humanity, communal responsibilities, and heterogeneity underpin social work. Based on social work theories, the social sciences, humanities and social sciences and indigenous knowledge, social work engages individuals and institutions to address life challenges and increase well-being (IFSW, 2014). Social Workers are dedicated to bringing about social change, whether they work directly with individuals or groups, coordinate community-based activities, or lead policy-making efforts. Social Work Education is a structured learning path created by the greater practitioners of social work.

Social work education and practice in the context of peacebuilding and conflict is established for years and, albeit still under research. Social workers demonstrate a variety of skills for working in micro, mezzo, and macro environments. Social work has always been about conflict and resolving conflict. Social workers traditionally tend towards learning and practicing the skills of conflict management for the sake of reducing unnecessary conflict. Negotiating conflict is an essential skill for social workers in multiple arenas. Conflict resolution (CR) may be defined as any process used to manage, determine, or settle differences that may arise among individuals, families, groups, organizations, communities, nations, or any other social unit. According to Mayer (2013), Conflict resolution is a core competency of social workers, and social workers have contributed greatly to this thriving field. Conflict resolution as a field of practice includes mediation, facilitation, conflict coaching, dispute system design, management, and arbitration. Conflict professionals provide preventative, restorative, substantive, procedural, and decision-making services to people in conflict. According to Zumeta (2000), there are five basic mediation models, facilitative (also called the settlement-driven model), directive, evaluative, transformative, and narrative. However, Heitler (2010) suggests a sixth "therapeutic model." Each of these models typically adheres to several core values, and all models look to create win-win outcomes for the parties(table-1).

Table-1: Conflict Resolution Models Based on Social Work Perspective

Mediation/ Conflict Resolution Models based on Social Work Perspective			
Models	Setting	Philosophical Assumptions	Description
Facilitative (also known as Settlement driven model)	Social Work, Family, Community, Neighbourhood, Labour, School-based	Conciliation, Problem-Solving	Parties are encouraged to negotiate based on their needs and interests. Used to create a better understanding
Directive	Family, Community, Neighbourhood, Organizational, Labour, Civil court	Problem-solving	The mediator uses a directive approach to convince parties of the best solution and control the process
Evaluative	Social Work, Family, Community, Organizational, Labour, Civil court	Conciliation	Assumes the need to provide direction based on law, industry practice, or technology

Transformative (also known as the mutual-aid model)	Victim-Offender, Family, Neighbourhood, Community, Organizational, Workplace	Relationship building and restoration	Parties are encouraged to deal with underlying causes with a view to repairing their relationships as the basis for settlement. Seeks empowerment and mutual recognition. Settlement is not important.
Therapeutic	Social Work, Family, Psychology, Individual, Conflict Coaching, Therapy	Relationship building and restoration, treatment, follow-up	Focuses on underlying causes with a view to improving future relationships. Has a twofold goal: Emotional Healing plus agreement on a plan of action with follow-up.
Narrative	Neighbourhood, Community, Organizational, Supervision	Conciliation, Problem-Solving	Seeks to uncover conflict causes through storytelling and attempts to identify cultural differences that cause conflict.

Deutsch, Morton (1973), This frequently referenced text defines a conflict typology and explains how people with less power can use nonviolent means to persuade those with more power and establish social justice. Allan E. Barsky (2015) introduces social worker learners to five basic conflict resolution approaches: power, privileges, interests, therapeutic, and transformation, and demonstrates how each of these methods can be applied in a variety of contexts, including family conflict, disputes at work, ethical quandaries, cross-cultural interaction issues, criminal law, and health care. Using competence assessments and practical exercises, students may put theory into exercise.

Mayer (2013) indicates that “mediation is the natural outgrowth of social work practice because its goal is to help empower people in conflict to solve their own problems, and because it builds on core social work theory and skills such as problem analysis, communication, and systems intervention” (p. 2). If this is true, social worker expertise would be enhanced by developing skills in mediation/conflict resolution. social workers are trained in areas such as identifying and analyzing underlying interests, developing resources, and generating options, social workers would be well suited to handle issues related to mediation/conflict resolution.

Conflict resolution is a core competency of social workers, and social workers have contributed greatly to this thriving field. Conflict resolution as a field of practice includes mediation, facilitation, conflict coaching, dispute system design, management, and arbitration. Conflict professionals provide preventative, restorative, substantive, procedural, and decision-making services to people in conflict. According to Kruk (1997), areas, where mediation/conflict resolution skills are beneficial, include divorce, postdivorce parenting, parent and child relationships, adoption, aging, healthcare, and mental 7 health. In addition, Mayer (2004), Keefe and Koch (1999), Irving and Benjamin (2002), and Heitler (2010) indicate that conflict resolution skills can be adapted to disability issues, community problem-

solving, education, workplace harassment, criminal justice, social policy, and intercultural disputes.

The research question of this study was to find out from the perspective of social work students if there is a connection between Social Work Education, Conflict Resolution, and Peacebuilding? and to analyze the methods, tools, and skills employed by them in resolving conflict and achieving peace.

Methodology

This study used the Qualitative approach to research and it was a Semi-structured, Mixed method approach. The participants were students with Social Work Backgrounds- Participants consisted of students currently enrolled in an MSW program at a college in Chennai, Tamilnadu, India. A total of 10 students participated in the study. An email describing the study was sent to all MSW students, and interested students were asked to contact the researcher directly. A non-random, purposive, maximum variation sampling frame was used. Maximum variation sampling involves selecting participants who vary widely along dimensions of interest (Patton, 2001); dimensions of interest were religious affiliation, age, gender, sexual orientation, race, and family. The study had a focused group discussion, with open-ended questions that were based on the methods of social work and the way each method helps in conflict resolution and aims towards positive peacebuilding.

Results

Data were analyzed using Google form metrics. Findings included that social work education has imparted knowledge on conflict resolution and peacebuilding. The methods, both direct and indirect have a direct relationship in dealing with the problems of individuals, groups, and communities. Professional dedication is reinforced by the fundamental knowledge base of the profession, its values, ethics, and core skills, including the commitment to human, relation-based practice and methods and practices curated from different disciplines. The figure below shows the six methods of Social Work practice and the core areas it works on.

Figure-1: Methods of Social Work Practice

On a daily basis, social workers meet people who experience multiple problems like discrimination, poverty, oppression, and family problems that lead to domestic violence and individuals who are anxious, and depressive. Social work commonly emphasizes empowerment, self-determination of the client, use of a systems perspective, focus on process and a commitment to social justice.

Conflict resolution skills are utilized and applied in areas related to community, education, workplace, criminal justice, and families such as divorce, aging, mental health, child/parent relationships, adoption social policy, and intercultural issues. Social workers use these

conflict resolution skills: negotiation, mediation, advocacy, group facilitation, family group conferencing, healing circles, and evaluation.

Discussion

Conflict is common in practice and in our personal lives; conflict resolution assists the social worker in discovering new ways to examine and evaluate client concerns, personal difficulties, and professional issues. Social workers can get new insights into the root causes of conflicts, the manner in which individuals should act in conflicts, what individuals are competent in, what constitutes an efficient or successful conflict resolution, and the steps it takes to settle a conflict.

As in the Council on Social Work Education (2008), professionals in social work are aware of human behaviour throughout life; the numerous social systems in which individuals live; and the ways in which social systems encourage or hinder individuals from maintaining or attaining their well-being and health. Social workers use liberal arts concepts and expertise to explain natural, cultural, societal, emotional, and spiritual growth. "To understand the person and the environment, social workers need to critique and apply knowledge" (IFSW, 2014).

From the results obtained the study finds the connection between Social Work Education, conflict resolution, and Peace, the methods, tools, and skills employed by them in resolving conflict and achieving peace. It is proved from this study that there is a link between Social Work Education, Conflict Resolution, and Peacebuilding, hence it can be proved that Social Work Education is an Instrument for Conflict Resolution and Peacebuilding.

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Presented at the Hybrid second annual international conference on Religion, Culture, Peace and Education, Department of Peace Studies, Payap University, Chiang Mai, Thailand, April 27-28, 2023.

27 - How Feminist and Disability Theory Relate: A Case Study of Afghanistan Women and a US Lecturer

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Abstract

This was an autoethnography, qualitative case study that explored both feminist and disability theory. It found that female university students who grew up in Afghanistan had a strong drive and persistence to prove their worth and success and that instances of oppression and suffering could increase this desire. This is compared to the researcher's experience who taught and advised Afghanistan students and noticed a similar personality trait in his students, especially female students, that he felt in himself, that being the need to overcome adversity from his disability and to prove his worth and success.

Problem Statement

Since the Taliban has taken over Afghanistan women no longer are able to attend education after sixth grade. Their hopes and dreams are squashed and no longer encouraged like they were when they were able to learn from lecturers and professors who overcame their own life barriers, similar to my own, epilepsy.

Research Questions

This Research has two purposes:

1. To examine the level of motivation by Afghanistan female students and
2. Addressing women empowerment as compared to disabled lecturer empowerment and how these inspire and understand each other that may be unique in their behavior and mindsets.

Literature Review

In an article published forty years ago Joan Scott, a Professor Emeritus at Princeton University, stated how difficult it was for historians to take gender seriously when it was difficult due to the belief that women had a history separate from men, 'therefore let feminists do women's history which need not concern us' (Baynton, 2005, p. 562).

Disability arguments were prominent for slavery in the nineteenth century and after its demise. One of the most common arguments for slavery was simply that the intelligence of African Americans was impaired to such a degree that they were unable to live in freedom on an equal basis with white Americans (Baynton, 2005).

The "first-wave," feminist movement in the United States began in the late 18th century when Mary Wollstonecraft published her book, *Vindication of the Rights of Woman*, where it stated that "the education of women has, of late, been more attended to than formerly; yet they have still reckoned a frivolous sex, and ridiculed, or pitied by the writers who endeavor by satire instruction to improve them" (Wollstonecraft, n.d./1796, p. 8). The primary issue for first-wave feminists was to campaign for the recognition of women as human beings and not the property of men (Brown, 2019, p. 98).

In general, there is a long history spanning many centuries of women's oppression and suppression in developing countries. With this regard, Afghanistan possesses a deep and fundamental gender divide that has existed for an extended period. The status, position, and

role of women in Afghan society have been different under varying regimes and time periods (Diyarbakirlioglu, 2017). Afghanistan is a mosaic of various ethnic and linguistic communities ... the fact that patriarchy and its prevailing culture and traditions dictate moral codes of conduct for women” (Emadi, 2002).

The Taliban Takeover of Afghanistan

Since the Taliban takeover of Afghanistan in 2021, “Afghan women and girls have suffered a severe rollback of rights, from denial of education to restrictions on movement to a lack of participation in the economy” (Farid & de Alwis, 2023, p. 1). On Sept. 7, the Taliban announced an interim caretaker government made up exclusively of male Taliban members and later that month the government added representatives from different religious and ethnic minority groups, but none were women (Farid & de Alwis, 2023).

Since August 2021, the government has issued 36 Sharia-based decrees and instructions regarding the rights of women and girls. Many of these decrees specified so-called acceptable behaviors for women, such as segregation from men, dress code, and the requirement for women to be accompanied by a male chaperone when traveling more than 72 kilometers from home. (Farid & de Alwis, 2023).

Women and Education in Afghanistan

In the 1950s purdah (gendered separation) was abolished; in the 1960s a new constitution brought equality to many areas of life, (Amnesty International [AI], 2022) including education where males and females shared classrooms at Kabul University for the first time which was the only institution of higher education in Afghanistan (Kazem, 2005).

In 2001, when the Taliban’s first regime fell, there was officially not a single girl in elementary school and only a handful in secondary school — that is in the entire nation of Afghanistan. Less than 20 years later, there were 3.6 million girls enrolled in primary and secondary school, and around 90,000 in higher education (Basij-Rasikh, 2023). When the Taliban took over Kabul and the country in October of 2021 many of this progress was lost but the desire for women to achieve and thrive has not. “Hearts may break, but spirits do not” (Basij-Rasikh, 2022, Global Opinions section).

Afghan women have revealed the capacity to engage in resilience processes amidst tremendous risks. Previous research with women members and supporters of the Revolutionary Association of the Women of Afghanistan, RAWA. RAWA is an underground, volunteer, Afghan women’s resistance organization founded in 1977 with the goal of using humanitarian and political means to assist, educate, and encourage others to resist oppression and to advocate for peace, democracy, and women and, more broadly, all human rights revealed that resilience is a process, not an outcome (Brodsky et al., 2011).

Disability Overview

People who battle with disabilities every day are humans first and they share a common aspiration for inclusion, success, and personal dignity.

The exclusion of children with disabilities in public education was not barred until 1975, the precursor to the Individuals with Disabilities Education Act (IDEA), the “Education of All Handicapped Children Act” (Blanck, 2019). In 1975, over half of the more than eight million American children with disabilities were excluded from suitable and integrated educations, and one million of those children were prohibited entirely from public schools (Blanck et al., 2013).

“One billion people, or 15% of the world’s population, experience some form of disability, and disability prevalence is higher for developing countries. Persons with disabilities are more likely to experience adverse socioeconomic outcomes such as less education, poorer health outcomes, lower levels of employment, and higher poverty rates” (Disability Inclusion Overview, 2022, p. 1). It should not be surprising to anyone that poverty may raise the risk of disability through malnutrition, insufficient access to education and health care, unsafe working conditions, a polluted environment, and poor access to safe water and sanitation (Disability Inclusion Overview, 2022). There is a class of people who live on the sidelines, practically as being invisible. Not only are they the physically disabled but rather socially and economically disabled. Society has yet to learn the virtues of tact and courtesy while dealing with them. By not accepting them as a part of the mainstream of society, we hurt and violate their human rights at every step. They have been suffering not only because of their physical condition but also due to the emotional harassment that they are subjected to (Bedi, 2019).

Findings

I have had tuberous sclerosis and epilepsy since I was twelve years old. I always felt the need to be better than others due to my marginalized status in society and most likely the reason I obtained two master’s degrees and most of my dissertation for my doctoral degree among other prove-you-wrong accomplishments. To explore my experience as a disabled educator who felt an affection for as well as a reciprocal one from Afghanistan university students I taught and advised and to add my voice to the various bodies of literature on international feminism and disability theory, I chose to use a case study autoethnography. Autoethnographies “are highly personalized accounts that draw upon the experience of the author/researcher for the purposes of extending sociological understanding” (Sparkes, 2000/2000, p. 21).

When I decided to go to the American University of Afghanistan (AUAF) in August 2017 it was not initially my first choice. Even though I was the only student asked to teach or co-teach eight graduate classes at Northern Illinois University, the school where I was obtaining my doctorate degree and obtained a lot of experience in various areas, and different cultures was a focus of mine, landing positions were not happening. So, I saw a position that was open in Kabul, Afghanistan at the American University of Afghanistan and I applied and then was hired. Prior to that I had little health insurance and was put on a medication not conducive to my type of epilepsy but the doctor at the time was performing, perhaps, malpractice and I had seven interviews and seven seizures during them, one in a campus board room so desperation called for going to a warzone and hopefully starting my career. I have always been someone who seeks adventure and a challenge so going to Afghanistan became exciting. Disability Studies in Education (DSE) frames disability as a valuable form of diversity rather than a deficit (Collins & Ferri, 2016). I was quite open about my condition except during job searches. I was acting in almost every job interview instead of freely being myself because of the stigma epilepsy brings even though friends and colleagues thought I should state my unique background and accomplishments.

Much of this background is why I felt so comfortable, teaching and advising Afghanistan first-year university students, especially females. I knew they battled on a much tougher, more difficult, dangerous level than I ever did or will, but they inspired me, and I also saw some of them in me. When I started the CHAMPS Peer Mentor Program at the American University of Afghanistan for first-year students to be mentored by third- or fourth-year students, I saw the drive the students had, especially the female students who became mentors. 68% of the mentors I hired were females. No doubt that was the first time they held a position of any sort of power because they were mentoring groups of 10-12 male and female students.

Interview

One of the primary mentor leaders of the CHAMPS Peer Mentor Program was a female student named Haidari. She was a Senior student at AUAF who took off with the program that grew to 330 students in a year and a half. She was mentoring a group of twelve mentees, but she also was the leader for the entire group among the mentors in many respects. She started a Facebook page for the group and on a regular basis posted how she had been mentoring her mentees, events that she was planning and clever learning documents she shared. This young lady was truly a leader and I saw a lot of her in myself and the ones who took part in this Facebook site. Here is an example of one posting for an event that Haidari shared on March 5, 2019 “This is to let you know that it’s a great opportunity to join tomorrow’s event the Special Envoy for Regional Consensus on Peace and CEO of the High Peace Council. Please remember that your participation points will be added; if you join the event tomorrow.” Haidari also came up with other ideas such as a Leadership Event where the mentees were to build on their networking and public speaking skills. She had a lot of creativity, energy, and drive that I was so proud of. Female students working extremely hard to succeed could have many reasons. I can speak for myself initially. I took on as many different and challenging experiences as possible and gained as many degrees as I could to show that the problem with my brain did not affect my ability or intellect and that I was as good or better than others. This may be true for female students in Afghanistan. A study that focused on women university graduates’ access to employment in Afghanistan stated a subject considering her experience, she now decided to stand on her own feet and believe in herself. “Women themselves must do their best and utilize their talents and skills...they should always be creative. They have to create opportunities for themselves” (Payne et al., 2021, pp. 101–102).

Another student at AUAF who was in my First Year Success Program that I taught and Directed the Curriculum for was named Shogofa. She was from Kandahar Province in Afghanistan and graduated with a Business Administration degree. She and her family were lucky to flee Afghanistan and move to the United States when the Taliban took over Kabul on August 15, 2021. Shogofa received the AUAF Presidential High Honor Award twice and is a professional artist. She is a writer and a poet whose focus is on women and children. She has also written five preparatory books for Kankor (college entry exams). (Rogers, 2020) In an interview I did with Shogofa she stated her passion for education and success.

The commitment to education was so ingrained in me ... I was given poisonous chemicals by some antagonists in schools, but I was so devoted to studying and making it to the university that I even sacrificed my sleep, relaxing time, which I eventually became ill. But the sleep deprivation and poisonous chemical had overwhelmed me, and I could not seriously study for almost two years. I was taken abroad for treatment and now I feel much better. The health issue and the sense of revenge from the antagonists of school encountered in my life left a grave impact on me which was the turning point of my life and ended up leaving me with a burning desire in my heart. I will carry it for the rest of my life, NOW! Education is not a necessity, it is my PASSION, it is my burning desire (Rogers, 2020, p. 5).

Another Afghan female who is in the United States and learning cooking now. Hanifa was asked how much her persistence and drive to learn increased because of the oppression of women in Afghanistan? “That sensation impact (s).my life and made me more strong to achieve my goals. (I) try hard to make more confident to not give up and try (to) work hard and happy to learn more. And feel bad for those women in in my country they don’t have this.”

I spoke to a former student of mine, Laila, whom I helped herself and her sister get out of Afghanistan last year and who went to Ghana. Asked if Laila felt a need to do better to show her achievement because she is a female? “Well, definitely I would like to show practically all the achievements (skills and learnings) which I had in Afghanistan by working on it and getting the outcome of it. Laila also stated, “Losing my self-confident and faith in myself could influence my desire to achieve.”

Conclusion

When people are marginalized by society the drive to prove they are as good or better is strong and is proven by women in Afghanistan when given the chance to learn and succeed and it is mirrored by a disabled educator whose brain may have been hindered in the view of some but he has fought to have a seat at the table of success like many Afghan women fight for as well. .

Recommendations

It is recommended that more research be done on oppression/suffering and how it equates in its drive to succeed. This topic is not thoroughly explored at all in scholarly research.

Also, it is recommended women in Afghanistan or other developing countries who are given the chance to learn should be studied fully in a quantitative study to see their academic, co-curricular and extracurricular activity when compared to males to see what their statistical numbers show.

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28 - Bulgarian Immigrants' Educational Experiences in U.S. Higher Education

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Abstract

This paper explores the educational experiences of Bulgarian immigrants in U.S. higher education institutions. Although the participants in the study appreciated their Bulgarian education, their education degrees from Bulgaria were not recognized in the U.S., and they needed to obtain an evaluation of their degree or start their education again in the U.S. They discussed their motivation for obtaining a U.S. higher education degree and their challenges with studying in the U.S. as well as their support and successes in the U.S. higher education system.

Keywords: Education, Higher Education, Bulgarian Immigrants, U.S. Higher Education Degrees, Semi-Structured Interviews

Introduction

One reason for most immigrants to have difficulty finding jobs is due to lack of formal education from their host country (Boeren, 2011; Harrison & Lloyd, 2013). Additionally, most immigrants' educational and professional credentials, gained prior to migration, may not be recognized (Lee & Westwood, 1996). Therefore, there is a need to investigate immigrants', in this case Bulgarian, perception of educational experiences in the United States (U.S.).

This paper is guided by the following research questions:

1. How do Bulgarian immigrants perceive their educational experiences in U.S. higher education?
2. What are Bulgarian immigrants' aspirations for education?

The purpose of this paper is to explore the educational experiences of Bulgarian immigrants in U.S. higher education institutions. This study is informed by the literature on immigrant students in U.S. higher education, including immigrants' access to higher education, their challenges and transitions.

Literature Review

Today's global economy requires people to have higher skills and training (Kim & Diaz, 2013a). Thus, it is important that individuals have access to higher education. As the number of immigrants in the U.S. increases, educating them in U.S. institutions becomes a priority. However, immigrants face barriers that limit/hinder access to higher education (Kim & Diaz, 2013b). These include "race and ethnicity, cultural values, language and literacy level, socioeconomic status, country of origin, and length of residence in the United States" (Kim & Diaz, 2013a, p. 47).

Kanno and Grosik (2012) pointed out that there was not enough research on the experiences of English learners (ELs) who wanted to make a transition from the high school level to the college level. The authors identified some challenges that prevented immigrant ELs' access to higher education. Those included linguistic issues, such as not knowing how to write essays at the college level, low verbal scores on the exam for college admission, and not meeting the requirements for reading and writing at college. Other challenges for the ELs are

related to insufficient financial resources to enroll in the desired academic institution and lack of support from their teachers and counselors in high school. Kanno and Grosik (2012) also noted that the approach to English as a second language (ESL) education and the college climate also influences the experiences of ELs. Treating ELs as a group with deficiencies contributes to students' negative experiences, whereas having ESL requirements incorporated into a writing program that is part of the first-year curriculum as well as having a diverse college environment influences ELs experiences much more positively (Kanno & Grosik, 2012).

One of the challenges immigrants' experiences is with their English language acquisition. Policy makers assume that immigrants have to know the language of their host country to be able to integrate into the society (McHugh, Gelatt, & Fix, 2007). ESL programs aim to help immigrants with their integration by providing opportunities for immigrants to gain knowledge about the culture of their receiving country and improve their language skills (Louw, Derwing, & Abbott, 2010).

Derwing and Munro (2013) compared the development of speaking skills between Mandarin and Slavic-language speakers in Canada. By comparing the two groups, the authors found that the Slavic-language speakers improved their comprehensibility and fluency of the English language by looking for more opportunities to communicate in English. Derwing and Munro (2013) suggested that the willingness to communicate (WTC) framework (MacIntyre, 2007; MacIntyre, Dörnyei, Clément, & Noels, 1998, as cited in Derwing & Munro, 2013, p. 167) could explain the differences with respect to motivation, culture and interaction in the improvement of oral English language skills between the two groups of learners.

More longitudinal studies on immigrants' progression with their English language skills are needed. These can inform policy makers about how to distribute resources for language training of immigrants. Integration into the host society is challenging for immigrants, and language programs can help them acquire the needed language skills and, thereby, their integration (Derwing & Munro, 2013). Swaminathan and Alfred (2001) believed that institutions of adult and higher education can help immigrants in their transition into the different cultural contexts in the receiving country. Further, postsecondary educational institutions can help immigrants obtain an education that can increase their income and economic integration into U.S. society (Teranishi, Suárez-Orozco, & Suárez-Orozco, 2011).

Teranishi et al. (2011) argued that community colleges can address the educational needs of immigrants. These institutions are less expensive compared to four-year institutions, admit applicants openly, and can accommodate nontraditional students who have work and family responsibilities. On the other hand, immigrants are looking to enroll in a higher education program, increase their English language skills, and find a job (Teranishi et al, 2011).

Kanno and Grosik (2012) argued that more English learners needed to enroll in four-year educational institutions to increase their chances of better paid work. On the other hand, the authors had the view that more people need to graduate from college for the U.S. to continue to be competitive with other developed countries. The ELs who wanted to pursue college degrees needed special attention because this group of students was the fastest growing in the system of K-12 (Kanno & Grosik, 2012; Wolf, Herman, & Dietel, 2010).

Hazen and Alberts (2006) pointed out that many international students decide to stay permanently in the U.S. after graduating with their degrees. Various factors play a role in these decisions (Hazen & Alberts, 2006; Szelényi, 2006). Students' motivation and aspirations influence their evaluation of the possibility to migrate (Szelényi, 2006). In their migratory decision making, they consider their desire for achievement, talents, professional

ties, and perceived opportunities in the country they look to potentially settle in. While economic and professional considerations may influence the decision of international students to stay, personal and societal factors act in favor of returning to their home countries (Hazen & Alberts, 2006). For example, Hazen and Alberts (2006) found that the Europeans in their sample of participants perceived better job or career opportunities as a main U.S. advantage. However, the Europeans pointed out friends or family and better quality of life as the top two advantages of their home countries. Further, the decision to come and study in the U.S. is different from the decision of potential staying in the U.S. after completion of one's study. While considerations about one's professional advancement and education influence the decision to study in the U.S., individual reasons mostly influence the decision to return to the home country (Hazen & Alberts, 2006). For some international students, changes in their decisions about career and family will lead them to immigrate permanently in the future (Hazen & Alberts, 2006).

Methodology

Semi-structured, open-ended questions were used to collect data. I completed face-to-face interviews, phone and Skype interviews. I collected data for this qualitative study by interviewing participants, writing memos (from the interviews), and keeping a reflective journal during the process of data collection and data analysis. The participants were Bulgarian immigrants from the Chicagoland area. I chose pseudonyms for my participants.

Findings

Education in this study refers to education of adult immigrants in U.S. institutions of higher education. In this study, Bulgarian immigrants, who are first-generation immigrants, shared their perceptions of their experience with their education obtained in formal institutions, such as college and universities, in both Bulgaria and the U.S.

The Bulgarian immigrants in this study discussed the recognition of their credentials in the U.S., their motivation for obtaining a U.S. higher education degree and their challenges with studying in the U.S. as well as their support and successes in the U.S. higher education system.

Immigrant appreciation of their Bulgarian education

Some of the immigrants valued their education in Bulgaria. For example, Diliانا believed that she received a good education in Bulgaria, which together with her life and work experiences prepared her for both the Bulgarian and the U.S. labor market.

Another participant, Vasil, also believed that he began his employment preparation in Bulgaria. He stated with respect to his training:

The most important thing that I passed was a CISCO certificate. It is called Certified Network Associate of CISCO. This is the first of a couple of certificates that means that if you passed it, you are allowed to work with CISCO equipment and do things with computer networks. And, in general I have preparation from Bulgaria. I have earned a Bachelor's degree in computer information systems in Bulgaria. This has helped me a lot to study for the exam for the certificate to prepare for it.

Vasil acknowledged that his studies in Bulgaria helped him prepare for the certificate exam in the U.S.

Recognition of Bulgarian immigrant credentials in the U.S.

Bulgarian immigrants shared that they could not start work immediately with only their degrees from Bulgaria. For example, after coming to the U.S., Ralitsa realized she would not

be able to continue working as a dentist unless she passed some exams. Another immigrant, Diana also could not work as a pediatrician regardless of her Bulgarian education in this field and many years of work experience there. She also had to pass exams, for which she needed time, which she currently did not have because of her work commitments.

Coming to the U.S., Denitsa found out that although she had graduated as a surgical nurse in Germany, she could not start working immediately at the same level with her diploma. Being in the same profession as Denitsa, Bisera commented that her Bulgarian diploma was not recognized in the U.S. and she had to study again to be able to work as a nurse. Diliانا was the only immigrant who stated that she had an evaluation of her Bulgarian diploma done, which was equated to a master's degree in the U.S., and she found work with it at a bank.

Motivation for obtaining a U.S. higher education degree

Bulgarian immigrants had different motivations for deciding to pursue a U.S. educational degree. For example, Vesela, who was a single mom, identified the need to study something quickly because by juggling a couple of long-hour and low-paid jobs she was not able to support her child. Other immigrants believed they were too old to study or there was no need.

Some of the participants expressed their regret that they did not study in the U.S. Looking back at his career decisions, Krum reflected with regret:

If I came to America now, I would do something to study something. I regret that I have not done that before. Um, I was searching for a job, I was looking to make money, and I did not think that much. Now, I understand that for your future good when you invest in education, no matter how long this study would be, the important thing is to graduate. You will have a profession, and then you can have a career.

Krum saw the value of education for “your future good.” However, coming to the U.S., he had to start working to make his living.

Immigrants who established their own businesses in the U.S. did not study a major again in the U.S. They believed they were successful at what they did in the U.S.

Challenges with studying in the U.S.

Some immigrants had difficulty navigating the U.S. educational system. Like other immigrants, Boyana was growing up and doing well in the Bulgarian education system. Coming to the U.S., she expected the method of instruction and taking exams to be similar to what she was used to in Bulgaria. However, coming to a different system, it took time for her to learn it.

One of the immigrants, Snejana, who was young and recently came to the U.S., shared that she wanted to continue her education. However, she experienced difficulties with learning the financial aid system; she missed the deadlines for financial aid and did not enroll in college.

Vesela shared that she had not been oriented at the beginning of her studies. Not having a clear direction to follow made Vesela to lose her motivation in school. In her own words, she explained, “And, because I am not motivated, um, I am a tired, single mom. I worked at two jobs at one point.” Vesela learned about academic performance after the fact. She believed that her many obligations affected her negatively.

These examples from Boyana, Snejana, and Vesela illustrate that Bulgarian immigrants had to learn to navigate the U.S. educational system, which was a new system for them and different from the Bulgarian system with which they were familiar.

Some of the immigrants shared that they had to work while studying. Out of the nine participants who studied or currently study in the U.S., only one did not work while studying because her husband supported her.

Support – Administration, friends, and family

To overcome challenges in the U.S. higher education system, Bulgarian immigrants relied on support, including administration, friends, and family.

Vesela explained how she was helped by a counselor:

God sent me this woman, who was my counselor. For 20 minutes this woman opened my eyes so much that she turned my life around, the direction of everything I was doing, you see. She turned my whole direction around. First, she very delicately, very tenderly, very carefully, with a great respect, she scolded me for the GPA that had dropped. And after that, she asked me what the reason was for my GPA dropping because when she looked at my history, it had not been like that. So, I told her, “I am tired. I cannot anymore. I cannot endure, and I don’t know what to study.” And she, the woman, sat and explained to me: “The educational system works like that in America. You have to do this like this and that like that...And the woman gave me such simple advice, such practical advice. And, she opened my eyes so much that, I became embarrassed a lot at first. And then, however, I became encouraged. And, in fact, I understood that first, I still have a chance, and second, I actually know how to use this chance.

The counselor helped Vesela to understand her situation and the system. Vesela felt hopeful that in the future she can overcome challenges and be successful.

Boyana received support from a friend. She recalled that when she received the results that she had been admitted, she was not aware she had to take pre-requisite courses in her program. A friend helped Boyana by advising her how to make a reasonable course schedule and manage her time while working full time.

A few of the immigrants received financial support or financial aid for their studies. For example, Vesela took financial aid to pursue a bachelor’s degree. Another participant, Kamen, thought that providing financially for his wife’s studies would help her improve her work situation. He believed that “while one is working, the other can study. In my case, it took five years for my wife to study to get her diploma. And, now she is better.” Kamen paid for his wife’s education in the U.S.

Success in U.S. higher education system

Bulgarian immigrants perceived they were successful when they graduated, got their diplomas, and obtained certificates or licenses in their professional fields in the U.S. Some of the participants had future plans to obtain certificates or license and thus to continue professionally developing their careers.

To conclude, this section explored the educational experiences of the Bulgarian immigrants in U.S. higher education institutions. Findings from this section are the following:

1. Education degrees from Bulgaria (a specialist degree, bachelor’s, and master’s) for the participants in this study were not recognized in the U.S., and they needed to obtain an evaluation of their degree or start their education again in the U.S.

2. These Bulgarian immigrants wanted to find their place and believed that having a U.S. degree would help them achieve that. However, a Bulgarian degree was sufficient for the immigrants who established their own businesses in the U.S.
3. Motivation to pursue education and obtain a U.S. higher education degree depended on the immigrants' perceived personal circumstances.
4. These Bulgarian immigrants experienced challenges, including navigating the new and different U.S. higher education system and combining work and study.
5. These Bulgarian immigrants overcame challenges in the U.S. higher education system by receiving support from administration, friends, and family.

Conclusion

Despite their challenges, Bulgarian immigrants studying in the U.S. had support and experienced successes in the U.S. higher education system. The findings with respect to some of these immigrants who enrolled in higher education programs point to the need for researching how immigrants manage in higher education. Various factors, such as not being familiar with the foreign educational system, lack of information, individual motivation, income, and support (e.g., mentoring) might have played a role in these immigrants' educational experiences/outcomes. A study that goes into more depth to explore the factors that affect immigrants' student achievement and shape their educational experiences will be beneficial for higher education professionals.

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29 - Clan Feud: Its Impact to the Academic Performance of Tertiary Students in Cotabato City

Nuñez, Rachel Anne |Taboada, Alfred| Fernandez | Harold, Lumibao | Mark Anthony

Problem Statement: The study aimed to find out the impact of clan feud to tertiary students' academic performance in Cotabato City which sought to answer the questions, how does clan feud influence and affect tertiary students in terms of attendance, behavior, grades, participation, and psycho-social well-being.

Purpose of the Study: The study generally aimed to find out the impact of clan feud to tertiary students' academic performance in Cotabato City.

Literature or Theory: The study is anchored on the study of Torres (2008), Kreuzer (2005), and data from the international conflict alert data.

Research Methods: The study is anchored on the study of Torres (2008), Kreuzer (2005), and data from the international conflict alert data.

Summary of Findings: Based on the results from the researcher made survey, clan feud had occasionally both influenced and affected students' academic performance specifically in students' attendance, class participation, and school grades.

Conclusion: The researchers were also able to generate themes on the effect of clan feud in the psycho-social well-being of the students such as feelings of fear, trauma, anxiety, and persistent stress.

Keywords

- 1 Clan feud
- 2 Rido
- 3 Academic performance
- 4 Tertiary students
- 5 Conflict alert data

Area: Culture; Justice and Peace; Education

30 - Jesus' Principles for Peace and Intractable Conflicts

Ottenhof, Robert

Problem Statement: Jesus' teachings, in their historical setting, are typically not interpreted in the context of peacebuilding.

Purpose of the Study: How do Jesus' ideas about peace for his society in first-century Palestine contribute to present-day conflict studies? This study explores Jesus' ideas about peace in their historical context.

Literature or Theory: The study interconnects Jesus' strategy for peace with Peter Coleman's dynamical systems approach and Daniel Bar-Tal's socio-psychological infrastructure model for intractable conflicts.

Research Methods: Jesus lived in a time of socio-political protracted conflict, under Roman occupation, and among conflicting Israelite factions. Jesus' teachings are viewed within the framework of conflict studies.

Summary of Findings: The study shows that Jesus' strategy for peace include the principles of an uncompromised vision of peace, a reorientation of the collective emotional attitude, pragmatic ethics, and a universal peace-oriented ingroup. How can these principles contribute to the study of intractable conflicts?

Conclusion: The study shows how Jesus' strategy for peace brings fresh ideas to modern peace theory that addresses intractable conflicts.

Keywords

- 1 Intractable conflicts
- 2 Jesus of Nazareth
- 3 First-century Palestine
- 4 Dynamical systems approach
- 5 Socio-psychological infrastructure

Area: Religion; Justice and Peace

31 - Post-Religious Conflict Peacebuilding Strategy in Mareje, West Lombok, Indonesia

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Abstract

The burning of Buddhist houses in Mareje, West Lombok, Indonesia, by Muslims in May 2022 has been resolved through customary deliberations and the signing of a peace agreement mediated by the village and West Nusa Tenggara provincial governments, yet there remain unresolved issues pertaining to their shared aspirations for sustainable peace. This conflict may also reflect issues of social inequality, education, and political interests, which, if left unaddressed, can cause other problems and violence may reoccur. Therefore, this study aims to analyze the dimensions of the conflicts and offer strategies for promoting a more sustainable peace between both communities. In examining conflicts and strategies, I employ conflict analysis theory, basic human needs, and civic engagement. I conduct this research through thematic analysis of qualitative (interviews) and documented (newspaper and journal articles) data. I argue that sustainable peace and mutual progress can be achieved by strengthening shared spaces at weddings or traditional events, sharing cultural narratives related to the claim of one lineage, and bolstering formal and informal civic engagement (interreligious youth organizations and conflict resolution task forces). Thus, the community and local government must adhere to shared aspirations by conducting joint activities for the equal progress of Mareje.

Keywords: interreligious conflict, religious tensions in Mareje Village, sustainable peace strategy, post-religious conflict

Introduction

Mareje Village is located in the Lembar District of West Lombok, Indonesia, where 70% of the population is Islam and 30% Buddhist (Saparwadi, 2016). Many years have passed during which they have coexisted on the same piece of land. The community here is not only administratively interdependent, but also actively involved in a variety of activities. Also, the two religious communities respect each other's beliefs and the traditions of the conducted activities. As a form of respect, it is common for people to give non-celebrators of the holiday a variety of foods and then they wish them well on the holiday's commemoration reciprocally (B, Personal Communication, March 12, 2023). This practice demonstrates the harmonious and peaceful relationship between the two religious communities.

Initially, social activities, such as mutual cooperation, weddings, community service, and customs, highlighted the harmony between the two religious communities. Tolerance is truly upheld and shown in relation to activity participation, therefore the majority of social activities are carried out communally without religious identity embellishments. Despite the apparent achievement of social peace, religious disputes continue to be inevitable in this place. Religion is a sensitive issue for the people of Indonesia; therefore, tensions are quite high and it is easy to incite conflict in the name of religion—despite the fact that this is unrelated to religion— included in Mareje.

The conflict between Muslims and Buddhists in Mareje Village led to the burning of Buddhists' homes and an attack on Ganjar Village. A cursory reading of the news indicates that the source of the major dispute was a little matter, namely firecrackers and the emotional distress of the misunderstood teenagers. Takbiran night, which is the night Muslims celebrate victory day, is associated with firecrackers, but the firecrackers aimed towards the cattle pens of one of the locals appeared to incite three days of intense religious violence. Muslims from Mareje and those from outside Mareje attacked Ganjar Village and other Buddhist-inhabited hamlets by burning homes and vehicles and threatening to force the Buddhists out. As a result, the Buddhists had to be evacuated by the West Lombok Police and the West Nusa Tenggara Police, and they ran to the nearby forest.

Although conflict in May 2022 has been resolved through customary deliberations and the signing of a peace agreement mediated by the village and West Nusa Tenggara provincial governments, there remain unresolved issues pertaining to their shared aspirations for sustainable peace. This conflict may also reflect issues of social inequality, education, and political interests, which, if left unaddressed, can cause other problems and violence may reoccur. Therefore, this study aims to analyze the dimensions of the conflicts and offer strategies for promoting a more sustainable peace between both communities. This purpose is encouraged by concern regarding changes in the harmony of relations between the two religious communities and the strategies by which they can reshape and sustain the harmony that has existed for years.

Literature Framework

The religious conflict in Mareje is considerably more complex, including presumptions of political tension after the election of the village chief and the accompanying social inequity. In analyzing the outer and inner layers of the conflict, I employ the onion diagram analysis method to determine the needs, interest, and position of both parties. Deeper then, conflicts emerge from dissatisfaction with basic human needs such as survival needs, well-being needs, identity or meaning needs, and freedom needs, which can also affect the fluctuations of violence or conflict (Galtung, 1990, 292). I assume that by elaborating on these fundamental needs, we will be able to explain the conflict's roots and provide a sustainable peace strategy. Then, to reconstruct the harmony of the two religious communities, I highlight the shared cultural narrative and civic engagement (Varshney, 2002) of the community in current or potential activities or organizations, so the conflict can be transformed (Lederach, 2003). Hence, the theories will be able to identify the multiple layers and underlying causes of the conflict, as well as provide a comprehensive framework for peacebuilding strategies that encourage communal progress.

Methodology

This paper will examine the roots of the conflicts that lead to interreligious violence and offer strategies for building sustainable peace. To be able to explain this subject systematically, I did research employing thematic analysis with qualitative data from interviews and case-related documents such as news articles and journals. Thematic analysis is a method within qualitative research that involves identifying, analyzing, and interpreting a set of patterns from cross-data (Clarke & Braun, 2017; Kiger & Varpio, 2020). This method may include a systematic process of data coding in order to identify the key themes and subthemes that arise from the data sources. In the context of the Mareje conflict, an analysis of themes relating to the causes and triggers of the conflict, post-conflict situations, and peacebuilding strategies for both parties is provided. Using thematic analysis in combination with qualitative data and documents may offer a broad understanding of the religious conflict in Mareje.

Discussion

Muslims-Buddhists Religious Conflict in Mareje

The conflict that happened in Mareje Village on the night of Takbiran, 1 May 2022, began with tensions among youths and finally escalated into interreligious violence. Basically, firecrackers on Takbiran night are a real phenomenon and part of the 'right' of Muslims to do so on a holiday. Unhappiness occurs when the rights of a certain community are violated or impeded. Based on the information, a Buddhist reprimanded the youths who set off firecrackers without bringing religious overtones, because they have already reached the disturbing stage, rather, they are merely pursuing a normal social life to create mutual comfort between neighbors. The advice was not to prohibit firecrackers, but rather to request that they not be directed at cattle pens or houses, as doing so could cause panic and even fire. The violation continued the following day, when one of the passing young Buddhists was subjected to a personal attack. Afraid, the Buddhist youth hurried to another Buddhist's house where a group prayer was taking place to look for help. But, the Muslim teenagers guilty for the earlier violence went towards the mosque and announced over the loudspeakers that he had been attacked by Buddhists. Muslims from nearby villages began to arrive with attacks directed against Buddhists in Mareje especially Ganjar and other places, as the news of this conflict spread (A, personal communication, November 28, 2022; Putra, 2022). The attack in the form of burning Buddhist houses and vehicles, as well as threats to relocate, exemplifies the 'position' of Muslims against Buddhists, which has resulted in violence.

The movement, which occurred quickly and involved a significant number of Muslims from several areas of West Lombok, is believed to have been deliberate and planned (B, personal communication, March 12, 2023). This is due to the accumulation of tensions on both parties as a result of difficulties unrelated to religion; hence, this conflict has become a ticking time bomb that threatens to disrupt the social conditions of the community members. Even while the Mareje can coexist with the existing diversity, there is a natural tendency to prioritize their group, referring to the role of religion in Indonesian culture as a whole. Even religious diversity that is peaceful will always be accompanied by conflict or invisible obstacles, such as superiority and inferiority. So, regardless of the quality of social relationships, people will keep developing their own communities. Similarly, the social conditions that exist in the village of Mareje, West Lombok, in the form of an unseen exclusivism that engenders social envy, are characterized by the same traits.

As seen by the growing number of Buddhists who are able to pursue postgraduate and even PhD degrees (Saparwadi, 2016), the social standing of Buddhists is continually improving. The improvement of education itself is designed for the advancement of Buddhist religious education in the village. Muslims, who represent a majority of the population, do not experience the educational opportunities afforded to the Buddhist community, where competition is high and the number of available positions is shrinking. Opportunities to obtain a higher education influence other changes, such as facilitating the ability to obtain a respectable career, enhancing family welfare, strengthening relationships, and enhancing dignity. In addition to their personal development, Buddhist religious groups also grow physically and psychologically. Certain monasteries, like the Girisena Monastery, the Avalokitesvara Monastery, and others that are undergoing progressive repairs, are stunning. These buildings represented the development of physical communal welfare for the Buddhist community in West Lombok as a whole. The mental progress in this regard can be seen in the solidity of Buddhists, religious knowledge, and the way Buddhists respond to issues related to religion—for example, religious marriages, which often result in a reduced

population of Buddhists, begin to be considered and responded to through increased education.

Some Muslims, who do not experience communal progress, view the Buddhists' development as a threat since it causes dissatisfaction. Muslims' dissatisfaction with their human basic needs (Galtung, 1990) led to unavoidable tensions and the encouragement of religiously-motivated violence. In addition, tensions grew due to political interests as a result of the election of the Mareje village chief (A, personal communication, November 28, 2022; Kurniawan, 2022; Redaksi, 2022), which they thought violated the collective agreement, and there was a feeling of being betrayed. Hence, the 'interest,' or what Muslims actually want, behind the violence that was perpetrated was not only offense, but rather unmet needs, a sense of being threatened, and the disappointment of political agreements. Deeper still, attacks, repression, and pressure on Buddhists to relocate are an expression of dissatisfaction with social inequality and unfulfilled political goals, which is a type of structural violence (Galtung, 1990) and 'needs' that Muslims must obtain.

Post-conflict Peacebuilding Strategy

The burning of Buddhist houses in Mareje, West Lombok, Indonesia, by Muslims has been addressed through Gawe Rapah customary deliberations and the signing of a peace agreement mediated by the village and West Nusa Tenggara provincial governments (Wijanarko, 2022a). Customary deliberations can be held peacefully with the intervention of the village authority, the Regent, and the West Lombok Governor as a third party. The traditional process is over until the reading of Ikar Sopoq Tundun, which states that the community is a single lineage, at which time it is vital to preserve the traditions of harmony and peace (Wijanarko, 2022). This commitment is an expression of a shared cultural narrative (Varshney, 2002) in which people feel they are descended from an inbred lineage and that it is inappropriate for them to fight. The conflict is resolved by a peace agreement carrying legal penalties for its violation and in response to this incident, the local government established a task group to manage future problems (Kurniawan, 2022).

Apparently, all activities and social life have resumed in Mareje Village after the end of interreligious violence (Jingga, 2022; Wijanarko, 2022b). Yet, some people keep experiencing post-conflict sensitivity, as indicated by their refusal to attend weddings of different religions, their uneasiness in social circumstances, post-traumatic, and others (A, personal communication, November 28, 2022; B, personal communication, March 12, 2023). Even, after the signing of the peace agreement on May 4, 2022, an unidentified group pelted a monastery in Lenong, West Sekotong, with stones and set fire to the *berugak* (a small hut in the courtyard of the monastery), as a result of the attack in Mareje, which spread to other Buddhist-populated areas in West Lombok, however, the action was successfully halted by the locals. (Mulyana, 2022). This shows that the implemented peace strategy is insufficient in certain areas. Although it is noticeable that the conflict's climax has been resolved, have its root causes likewise been identified and addressed? The answer is "no."

According to Varshney (2002), formal or informal civic engagement is a strategy of conflict resolution. Through unstructured associations, the community engages in a form of informal civic engagement. Because the community of Mareje initially shared places and moments together, this must be reaffirmed through a sound strategy from the community's leaders. Residents are accustomed to gathering for festivals such as weddings and other customs; therefore, this place will be ideal for re-establishing their relationship. I argue that formal or associational civic involvement can be achieved in the transition by forming youth organizations that include members of both religions in the planning of communal progress. In addition, the establishment of a conflict resolution task group by the administration of

West Lombok is a good step as a platform to meet citizens' aspirations and resolve issues without resorting to such drastic measures.

If such ambitious societal aims go ignored and this struggle between religious communities continues, the situation will be a ticking time bomb that could explode at any moment on a larger or lesser scale. The community and government must examine various measures for maintaining peace in the village. Lederach (2003) argues that conflict is unavoidable in social connections, but it may also be a tool for mutual growth; so, its resolution must address the fundamental area, namely human relationships. In addition to addressing these violent incidents between religious groups, village or provincial governments must investigate in considerable detail what causes tensions between the two. Both aspirations for social inequality and political interests require an equal and equitable resolution. If the government and people of West Lombok can view the conflict positively, it can serve as a catalyst for change. With government-supported programmes, the community can collaborate with the government to enhance economic development, political stability, education, and religious knowledge. Buddhists who have previously had access to education should inform Muslims about scholarship opportunities and other educational programs. Thus, conflict can be transformed (Lederach, 2003) into a mutual progress without competitiveness or rivalry between the parties, which might lead to future conflict.

Conclusion

The local authorities, conflict resolution personnel involved, and media have declared that the violence that occurred in Mareje was not a religious conflict (Kurniawan, 2022; Putra, 2022; Redaksi, 2022), yet it is apparent that the tension that erupted was between the two religious groups, regardless of the trigger. This should then urge the initiative to dig deeper into the roots of the conflicts that arose between the formerly peacefully coexisting parties. This is due to the inclination for exclusivism among the two religious groups, particularly in terms of communal progress, which causes the problem to arise without being recognized. As a result of competitive tensions and other circumstances, social, educational, and financial inequalities lead to dissatisfaction on the part of some Muslims, whose basic needs are not met evenly. The emergence of this problem is also triggered by political interests that are seen as inadequate. Hence, conflicts do occur amongst religious communities, but, as said previously, the underlying causes are quite complicated, therefore suitable measures are required to truly resolve it. Hence, for the development of Mareje Village, the community and local government must evaluate their different aspirations in harmony and engage in community-building activities. Furthermore, I argue that sustainable peace and mutual progress can be achieved by strengthening shared spaces at weddings or traditional events, sharing cultural narratives related to the claim of one lineage, and bolstering formal and informal civic engagement (interreligious youth organizations and conflict resolution task forces). Thus, the community and local government must adhere to shared aspirations by conducting joint activities for the equal progress of Mareje.

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32 - A Local Voice: Life Experiences and Reflections of a Woman Human Rights Defender in Thailand

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Abstract

Ngamsuk Ruttanasatian, a local woman human rights defender and lecturer at Mahidol University's Institute of Human Rights and Peace Studies (IHRP), also studies for a PhD on Peacebuilding at Payap University. Her engagement as both academic (teacher and student) and practitioner, as a female activist on human rights issues, forms the background for interviewing Ngamsuk and writing this paper. I explored materials on the 'local turn' in peacebuilding, the role of Human Rights Defenders in Thailand, particularly women, and relevant NGO and media sources relating to the cases Ngamsuk has been engaged with. The paper focuses on her personal experiences, relations, and issues that motivate her involvement as a frontline human rights activist and as a peacebuilding researcher. It reveals how family, place, and community (she comes from Thailand's 'deep south' which has a long history of tension with the state, political and military violence) have influenced her involvement as a human rights defender, and feed into her perspectives about international peacebuilding agendas, such as resolution of long-standing ethnic conflicts along the Myanmar-Thai border.

Keywords: Women Human Rights Defenders. Local Peacebuilding. Grassroots Activism

Introduction

Building upon the 'local turn' literature in peacebuilding, I seek to understand what motivates individual actors to become engaged in defending human rights and become 'local peacebuilders'. This paper is driven by one overarching question: What lessons can we as fellow students of peacebuilding learn from a local woman human rights defender's life experiences and the multi-scales engagements that stimulate and sustain peacebuilding?

The 'local turn' and 'critical yeast' in peacebuilding

The 'local turn' in peacebuilding studies is the summation of the responses to the failure of top-down approaches, and an effort to transform both research and the practice of peacebuilding through a deeper understanding of how external structures and forces play out at local levels and through a better understanding of local agents and actors. Leonardsson and Rudd (2015, p.832) observe: 'Found within both NGO activism and academic writing, the peacebuilding-through-local-emancipation approach implies both an ambition to include local voices and a critique of what has been done so far.'

Ginty and Richmond (2013, p.763) focus 'on the epistemological consequences of the recourse to localism in the conceptualisation and execution of peace building.' Their argument is that local activists and defenders have been able to 'tap into' networks and social platforms which strengthen their voices and reach targeted audiences. There are debates about what the 'local' means for conflict resolution and peacebuilding (Richmond, 2011). In practitioner realms there has been growing recognition of the relevance of incorporating local knowledge and practices within peacebuilding, including notions of 'bottom-up peacebuilding' (Paffenholz, 2003).

The ‘local turn’ also points to local actors, agents, and ideas involved in peacebuilding. What motivates them? Why do they become peacebuilders? Have personal experiences of conflict and violence led them into the peacebuilding arena? Where do they draw their strength to sustain their peacebuilding endeavours? Lederach (1998, p. xvi) argues that working with and through local peacebuilders ‘empowers the resources for reconciliation from within that society and maximizes the contribution from outside.’ He argues that local actors should be supported in their peacebuilding roles. They are vital to the ‘critical yeast’ of ‘relational spaces, intersections, and interactions’ of the growing web of actors engaged in peacebuilding at and across different scales (Lederach, 2005, p. 100). ‘Women’s groups in Nepal, Guatemala, and Sri Lanka, for example, have promoted gender issues, women rights and minority rights for indigenous groups or lower castes’ (Paffenholz, 2013, p.11).

Local peace activists like Ngamsuk herself have studied and reflected on the works of Galtung and Lederach. However, to such persons, peacebuilding is about the everyday of conflict and of living. For example, Ngamsuk’s lived experiences in Thailand’s “Deep South” (Chambers, Jitpiromsri, and Waitoolkiat, 2019) are things that awakened her to broader issues of inter- and intra-communal conflict. Thus, academic notions of protracted social conflict, ‘structural violence’ and ‘cultural violence’ (Galtung, 1969; 1990; Jones, 2011) are things that she has been exposed to in the context of everyday life before she began studying what peacebuilding is about. Less obvious influences underlying her personal activism came out in interviews with her, including family tensions and the role that spirituality plays in her life.

One key aim of this paper is to better appreciate the *personal* drives and influences upon a human rights defender may feed into the development of “critical yeast” within broader relational webs that are fundamental elements of peacebuilding.

Methods

The paper is based upon face-to-face discussions in July 2022, and a three-hour video-recorded meeting with Ngamsuk on July 25, 2022, followed up with shorter clarification correspondence by email. To better enable me to contextualize what she says in the interviews, I researched on the contexts, organisations, and human rights issues that she mentions from various online sources. All of the information in this paper is given with Ngamsuk’s permission, including the use of her name throughout. Her forthright and fair-minded responses to many questions, plus her determination and dedication to defend human rights, have helped inspire this paper.

Family feelings and the need for reconciliation

Ngamsuk shared how troubled family relations led her to seek solace in Buddhism, and how that helped her towards peaceful reconciliation within the family. She recalled how badly troubled she was when her mother had “to accept what my father did to her... I needed my mother to fight back.... I felt that she was a weak woman, and I did not like her weak behavior. That is why I was always angry.” That patriarchal power relations between her father and mother not only generated the violence directed at her mother but also produced pain and stress in Ngamsuk’s young mind. At the age of thirteen, she told her parents that she had to leave home, and she moved to Songkhla Province to focus on her education. She kept her strong feelings against the direct violence that occurred and the relationship of submissiveness and aggression for many years.

Whenever she meditated upon her own feelings, reactions, and motives, she felt that “it was not good to be angry with my mother. If I believe in the non-violent way, why do I treat her aggressively instead of being kind and gentle - I have made her suffer too.” Through practicing

Buddhist mindfulness of forgiveness and acceptance, while seeking a change of behaviour, Ngamsuk demonstrates how she learnt to reconcile with her family members as her consciousness and reflexivity develops. This helped her to develop ideas about broader forms of reconciliation in her front-line HR activities. She had gone through anger, realization, and forgiveness in her personal life, which helped influence her life as an activist and researcher.

Women in protracted conflict and as peacebuilders

Women peace activists have played pivotal roles in peacebuilding activities in the Thailand's "Deep South" (Pattani, Yala, Narathiwat and four districts of Songkhla comprising Thepa, Chana, Na Thawi, and Saba Yoi), Ngamsuk's homeland and places where she has been actively engaged in practical and academic activities relating to peacebuilding. In these southern provinces, the confrontation between the military and opposition movement has often led to incidents of violence, which has sometimes been perpetrated in markets, hotels, schools, places of worship, and other public spaces. Traditional practice in the South often means that women are typically expected to be in the private sphere and households. According to Buranajaroenkij (2019, p.69) 'Gendered social norms determine that women and men have an unequal level of influence, decision making power, and access to and control of various resources concerning peacebuilding policies, which in turn define the direction of conflict resolution policies and measures.'

The development of the Women's Peace Network has put some women activists in closer touch with international organisations and NGOs interested in local peacebuilding activities in the South. Women peace activism has helped challenge traditional gendered norms, created gender awareness about women within the conflict, power relations, and peacebuilding (Buranajaroenkij, 2019, p.73). Women have helped create informal "advocacy spaces" (Moser and Clark, 2001) for discussing and negotiating everyday human rights issues affecting their communities, families, men and women. Ngamsuk's calls for the creation of greater political space for advocates to defend human rights and freedom of expression goes hand in hand with her thoughtful feminist attitudes.

A woman HR defender facing off corporate power

Ngamsuk worked with other women human rights defenders courageously for the defence of their own rights, and for the defence of the rights of others. This readiness to speak out was witnessed when she reposted a Fortify Rights (2019) news release on a Facebook page of International Federation for Human Rights (IHRP). The Thai poultry company, Thammakaset Company Limited, had earlier arrogantly snubbed at the National Action Plan on Business and Human Rights (NAP), initiated by the Royal Thai Government (RTG) and ignored the international human rights law obligations and the United Nations Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights (UNGPs). The company filed at least 17 criminal and civil defamation cases against at least 23 human rights defenders since 2016; and when another criminal defamation lawsuit was filed by the same Thai poultry company against Nan Win and Sutharee Wannasiri, two other human rights defenders involved in promoting labour rights in Thailand, Ngamsuk reposted the Fortify Rights news release to protect defenders of human rights against corporate power.

Regardless of such adverse publicity, the poultry company sued Ngamsuk for criminal defamation under Articles 326 and 328 of the Thailand Criminal Code. If convicted of criminal defamation she would have faced up to two years in prison and up to 200,000 Thai Baht (US\$6,500) in fines. Fortify Rights took the position that these actions violated domestic and international law. Ngamsuk steadfastly worked with Fortify Rights to publicise her case and brought attention of her plight to a wider circle of friends and sympathisers in both the

academic and civil society. The Bangkok Criminal Court which could not find any criminal act, dismissed the complaint against Ngamsuk Ruttanasatien on September 18, 2019. Reluctant to accept that ordinary people have rights to freedom of expression, Thammakaset appealed to the Supreme Court for Strategic Litigation Against Public Participation (SLAPP) against her. This court suit took another year to deliberate before the Court of Appeal upheld the Criminal Court's decision and the Supreme Court finally confirmed the decision of both lower courts that Ngamsuk had not committed any crime when she spoke out through sharing a Fortify Rights news release by IHRP's Facebook page. In the meantime, Fortify Rights continues the campaign to protect human rights defenders against SLAPP, many of whom are women HR defenders, who like Ngamsuk, are often engaged in the struggle against localized human rights violations. (see, Fortify Rights, 2022).

Burma Issues and NGO advocacy work

Ngamsuk had ten years of service with an NGO, the Burma Issues, doing fieldwork, investigating, collecting, writing and distributing information about the atrocities committed against the people of Myanmar, including refugees and internally displaced persons along and across the Thai border. In an article she co-authored with a fellow activist, Ngamsuk related what she witnessed in Tham Hin Camp, a refugee camp (Rurranasatian, and Doherty, 2004). There were 9000 refugees mostly Karens, clamped into a restricted space of 6400 square meters. Aside from the spatial restrictions and overcrowding, she saw a variety of difficulties in their day-to-day lives. Camp regulations meant that refugees could not work to earn their living and were entirely dependent on NGOs operating in the camp for food, shelter, and medicine. There was limited access to education and healthcare. She advocated greater freedom for the Karen living in camps to govern themselves with cooperation between refugees, NGOs working in the camps, and Thai authorities.

Abduction

The story of Ngamsuk's abduction alongside an Australian colleague working for *Burma Issues* made the *Bangkok Post* (According to the Border Patrol Police, the pair were forced to cross the Moei River border from Mae Sot district into Karen State 'to take photos of the DKBA's Yoar Kyi camp' which had previously been attacked by the Karen National Liberation Army, a military branch of the Karen National Union (KNU). During the late-1990s fighting between the rival Karen factions had intensified, and the KNU viewed the Democratic Buddhist Karen Army (DKBA) of being used by the Burmese army, the Tatmadaw, to further weaken the Karen strongholds along the borderland.

The following extended quote from the recorded interview relates to Ngamsuk's direct experience of violence on the Myanmar-Thai border. The extended quote is kept as it reveals an event that was physically, emotionally, and mentally challenging for her. It is another example of the dangers that frontline human rights activists sometimes experience. Further, it reveals how conflicts often entangle individual peacebuilders under stressful, dangerous, and challenging circumstances.

'In 1998, I experienced a kidnapping incident in Chiang Rai. The Democratic Buddhist Karen Army (DBKA) kidnaped me and my friends for five days. The first day was the most serious. My friend asked me for the last words that I would like to say. We were handcuffed then and was under a tree together. I kept thinking about my mother because I never take care of her and just think about the other people. I felt then that if I was freed and still alive, I would take care of her. They kept us for about ten days. I took one year to recuperate because after the incident, I could not sleep in the night. I suffered from nightmares from the traumatic experience. From what I had studied about the Burmese army, its history and how it treated

the prisoners, from the texts I have read before, I was very agitated. Even when some soldiers tried to assure me and not to kill myself.’

The trauma of this abduction event and the pain that Ngamsuk went through was a great test to her resolve as a frontline HR defender. However, we can see that she has reflected upon this in different ways. First, her thoughts returned to her relationship with her mother, and the incident seems to have led her to seek peace with her mother whom she felt she had neglected. Thus, an unrelated act of direct violence against Ngamsuk triggered a resolve to reconcile with her mother. Another key issue that this reflection provides is the difficulty she had in coming to term with this personal trauma. It was a horrific experience for anybody to go through, raising anxieties about whether she would live or die. She suffered for a long time after this event, and when recalling what happened to her nearly 25 years ago, a sense of the anxiety this violent personal experience still has on her comes through. The fact that she was able to ‘recuperate’ and return to frontline HR work is testimony to her strong convictions and sense of social injustices, and her accumulated experiences of what conflict and violence means at varying scales, from embodied, deeply personal levels through to geopolitical violence in the Deep South or along the Myanmar-Thailand borderlands. Ngamsuk even shows compassion for ordinary rebel army soldiers, such as the ones who abducted her.

‘I also realized how soldiers suffered from the war for I was kidnapped for five days, yet I have to spend one year to heal myself. At that time, I could not talk. I cannot tell people because I was not calm. My attitudes towards the soldiers changed, especially the lower ranking ones – how they relate to the people. I saw the Burmese soldiers from the border suffered. They were asking food from us and lacked food. They had to travel with us to the check point. I understand why they had to steal when they went to the Karen village. I understand the feelings of the soldiers... the military brainwashed them... From this experience, I can better relate to the situation in the border, than before. I have to listen to them even when I do not want. They are also suffering.’

Personal and Social Peacebuilding

Ngamsuk came through her abduction, and this violent event triggered a long period of reflection and necessary recuperation. It further developed in her an awareness of the multiple ways in which violence is not confined purely to the victims, and that there is a need to consider the different ways it may cause suffering, even to those carrying guns. Through her example we may see how personal experiences of violence at different scales have led to reflection on the deeper meanings of peace, helping to energize an abiding commitment to peacebuilding across scales.

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33 - Mapping and Preserving the Cultural Properties of Balanga City, Philippines

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Abstract

The city of Balanga, with its colorful history, is a rich repository of tangible cultural properties dating back from 18th century which need to be mapped and preserved as it mirrors the cultural identity of the place. The purpose of this study is to map the tangible movable and immovable cultural properties of the City of Balanga, Bataan, its significance, current condition, integrity problems and measures necessary for its preservation. Focused ethnography was used as research method with interview as the primary data gathering instrument. The data gathered were analyzed using participatory cultural mapping method. The tangible immovable cultural properties that were mapped include 6 houses, 1 church and 2 government structures and tangible movable properties include 7 religious images, 4 works of industrial / commercial arts, 1 artwork and 7 archival holdings. It is recommended that formal training on preservation of tangible immovable and movable cultural properties should be given to local communities especially owners and caretakers so that awareness and accountability maybe institutionalized.

Keywords: tangible properties, cultural mapping, Balanga City, ethnography

Introduction

The Philippines has been under Spanish colonization for 333 years, 50 years under the Americans and 3 years under the Imperial Japan. It has remained an independent country after the Second World War until present while standing proud as a member of community of nations. The years of colonization have left many cultural heritages in the country which range from tangible to intangible. These cultural heritages have historical, archival, anthropological, archaeological, artistic and architectural values which mirror the cultural identity of many facets of society. To preserve and conserve these heritages, the Philippines passed Republic Act 10066 or the Heritage Law which encourage local government units (LGUS) and its instrumentalities to “conduct an inventory of their cultural treasures and to provide Filipino communities with the resources they need to maintain, preserve, and promote their local and national heritages in their efforts to do so”. This inventory will serve as basis for LGU and local communities in the conservation and preservation of their cultural heritages.

The Philippine law states that cultural heritages should be maintained, developed and improved through time which include private and public cultural properties. The preservation and conservation of these properties are very important since these are handed down from one generation to another and reflect much of the cultural identities of places (Modern Heritage Matters, 2013) that were formed since these properties were conceived. One of the cultural heritages that need to be preserved are the movable and immovable tangible cultural properties that have survived years of colonization and events that changed the course of history. The city of Balanga, which is the heart and capital city of Bataan, a province known for its crucial role in the Death March during the Second World War and Japanese occupation of the Philippines, is a historically rich community which was founded in 17th century and home to many tangible movable cultural properties. However rich the city

is, there are only four registered tangible properties in the Philippine Registry of Cultural Property (PRECUP), a repository of all information pertaining to cultural properties in the Philippines being maintained by National Commission for Culture and the Arts (NCCA). These include Bataan Provincial Capitol Building, Provincial Government Building of Bataan, Cathedral of Saint Joseph of Balanga and the Bataan Provincial Capitol Grounds.

Hence, it is the aim of the present study to map more tangible movable and immovable cultural properties in the city with the aim of creating a more updated and exhausted inventory of all cultural heritage so that necessary preservation measures may be put in place before it becomes too late. This study also aims to add more properties that can be listed under PRECUP to help the city on its effort of continuously providing good governance by looking after its cultural heritages as important building block in community building. These cultural properties are important elements in the lives and identities of communities as part of its cultural legacy (Giddy and Webb, 2016), as tourist destinations (Mousavi, Doratli, Mousavi and Moradiahari, 2016) and has the potential to build lasting peace and promote resilience (European Union, 2021) among people and communities. There is also a need to map these tangible cultural properties because many are in disarray and the original owners who have the knowledge about these heritages continue to decline in numbers over the years.

Research Questions

This study addresses the following research problems:

1. How may the tangible immovable cultural properties of the city be described in terms of history, year constructed, ownership, status, condition and integrity of the structure, declaration, and significant stories?
2. How may the city's tangible movable cultural properties be described in terms of history, year constructed or created, type of acquisition, physical condition, condition and integrity of the object, ownership or jurisdiction, dimensions, declaration, and significant stories?
3. What are the problems or constraints that affect the cultural properties and the conservation measures installed to maintain the good conditions or desired wellness of the cultural properties?

Methodology

The data for this research were gathered and analyzed using participatory cultural mapping method which included six (6) phases namely: Scoping and Negotiation Phase, Social Preparation Phase, Training of the Local Team Phase, Data Gathering Phase and Data Validation Phase, and Finalization of Local Culture Phase based on Cultural Mapping System of the National Commission for Culture and the Arts' Cultural Mapping Toolkit (2019). This cultural mapping method is an approach used to identify, record, and use cultural resources and activities for building communities (Cook and Taylor, 2013), identify where the resources are, what resources they have and where they want to be (Municipal Cultural Planning, 2011). Thus, the researcher collaborated with locals such as barangay officials and caretakers, as well as municipal tourism officers, to identify and analyze the city's tangible movable and immovable cultural treasures using the NCCA's Cultural Mapping Toolkit.

The results of the interviews were analyzed using Braun and Clarke's (2006) phases of thematic analysis which include Phases 1-2: Familiarization and coding where the researchers immersed with the data to become intimately familiar with their content through reading and re-reading all data items, and making notes in the process and Phases 3-5:

Theme development, refinement and naming where codes were organized and data were coded into candidate themes, reviewing and revising those candidate themes, and developing a rich analysis of the data represented by the finalized themes. Trustworthiness of the research process which include credibility, dependability, confirmability and transferability (Lincoln and Guba, 1984) was used to assess the robustness of the study. Ethical considerations were also observed through the use of informed consent form

Findings

The tangible immovable cultural properties mapped include 6 houses, 1 church and 2 government structures tangible movable cultural properties that were mapped by the researchers in the city of Balanga. On the other hand, the movable cultural properties mapped include 7 religious images, 4 works of industrial / commercial arts, 1 artwork and 7 archival holdings.

The nine (9) immovable and nineteen (19) movable tangible cultural properties in the city of Balanga that were mapped are deemed significant and important in the historical and cultural construct of the city and the province in general. However, the age of these properties and the challenges brought by the climate change are imposing an even bigger challenge of conservation among the its caretakers, the community and the local government units (LGUs). Significance of the Identified Tangible Cultural Properties. The role of 6 houses, 1 church and 2 government structures in the historical and cultural construct of the city lay on the meaning they represent and their functions in the past and present society.

For instance, the 6 houses in the study which became home to powerful and prominent families and politicians in the city and the province breath so much history which can be used as basis for studying the life and exploits of each important person who live in that house. The items that are kept in the houses may very well serve as crucial primary sources (Ouz, 2011) in order to get a knowledge of how the lives of these notable individuals impact others and how their lives are influenced by others. According to Hornedo (2000), artifacts are lifeways that represent a significant amount of knowledge that may be studied and discussed. These homes are living records of the political, social, religious, and even economic events that have taken place inside the communities. A person may build history and make connections between facts by utilizing the abundance of knowledge that is kept in these homes, which is accessible from the perspective of these dwellings. (Tuna and Saral, 2018).

Meanwhile, the tangible movable cultural properties that were mapped by the researchers include 7 religious images. These are saints that play an important role in the faith of the Catholic people in the city. These images are works of arts and have stood some tests of time over the years. Hence, the significance of these images can be measured on the religious and value system of the people who revere and believe in the miracles it brings in their lives. This is another interesting significance of the religious image since they shape people's faith and act as intermediaries between God and the people. Balanga has a strong foundation of Catholicism because it has the church, the saints and the tradition of Lenten and fiesta which provide them the opportunities to constantly renew their faith. As such, the religious images are important because it can be studied and its relation to community values and ideals can be studied as well.

While the city prides itself of its rich tangible movable and immovable cultural heritage, conservation measures remain a link that is missing in the people's efforts preserve their culture. Many owners of the tangible movable heritage have no basic skills in conservation of the cultural properties they take care of. There was no formal or informal training that they

become part of which could have taught them how ensure the integrity and historicity of the cultural properties under their supervision and ownership. For religious images, they rely on the role of encarnador who does the Encarnacion or the repainting of the santo in which natural or commercial paints and dyes were used. If the encarnador is not knowledgeable enough about the history of the image and the importance of conserving its original appearance, then alterations on the originality of the images maybe made.

The difficulty of conserving cultural treasures also applies to those who are responsible for their upkeep or who possess physical, immovable cultural artifacts. They, like the owners and caretakers of moveable cultural property, have little understanding on how to conserve these properties, which may have implications for the role they play with regard to the preservation of these items. In the event that inappropriate conservation measures are put into place, the authenticity of the tangible movable and immovable cultural properties will be put in jeopardy. As such, thorough protection of these cultural properties should be carried out since cultural heritage is a driving force behind and a prerequisite for urban development that is sustainable (Pintossi et al., 2021). Every individual is responsible for ensuring that the cultural assets and values that civilizations have will be preserved for future generations (Karadeniz, 2020). Awareness is one of the essential elements that must be present in order to effectively safeguard cultural heritage.

Conclusions

In this initial effort to map the tangible cultural properties of Balanga, nine (9) immovable and nineteen (19) movable tangible cultural properties were identified. The tangible immovable cultural properties include 6 houses, 1 church and 2 government structures while the tangible movable cultural properties include 7 religious images, 4 works of industrial / commercial arts, 1 artwork and 7 archival holdings. These tangible cultural properties are living heritage of the city and the province that warrant proper conservation and use for historical and cultural writing purposes. Regrettably, most of the caretakers and owners of these tangible cultural properties have no to limited knowledge and skills in conserving these properties which put them in a compromised position.

Recommendations

The study recommends that continuous mapping of the remaining tangible immovable and movable cultural properties of the city be made before it becomes too late for old properties. Tie up with Provincial Tourism Office of Bataan and its instrumentalities and NCCA should be continuously pursued to ensure that the IEC materials maybe used by both the university and the government for educational and tourism-related purposes. Informal training on conservation of tangible immovable and movable cultural properties should be given to local communities especially owners and caretakers so that awareness and accountability maybe institutionalized. Establishment of the Center for Bataan Studies maybe pursued to centralize all the mapping efforts and ensure continuity of funding. Schools should have syllabi in place that promote tangible and cultural heritage of the city.

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34 - Devadasi or Indian Temple Prostitution System – A Form of Human Trafficking in Disguise

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Abstract

Devadasi system is a religious practice in India that involves sexual exploitation of minor girls from the poorest fractions of the society. Young girls get dedicated as 'Devadasis' forcibly and are subsequently compelled to provide sexual services to the community under duress, which is a form of forced labour associated with commercial sexual exploitation. The aim of

this paper is to explain and establish how the combination of religious undertone, economic necessity and societal pressure has masked the Devadasi system from being considered as human trafficking. This study will use qualitative analysis approach using the data collected through secondary tools, such as, the published journals, articles, news, reports, and legal acts to be. The analytical findings will demonstrate that belonging to the socio- economically backward sections, superstitious beliefs and poor implementation of legislative framework have made it difficult to denote the Devadasi system as a violation of human rights. Devadasis are the victims of child trafficking and to abolish this deep-seated institution of sexual exploitation of women and children in the name of God and culture, it is necessary to spread awareness and strict enforcement of laws.

Keywords: Devadasi, Human Trafficking, Religious Exploitation, Sacred Prostitution, Sexual, Exploitation of Children

** All the names of the Devadasis are pseudonyms to protect their identities.

Introduction- Devadasi System Still Prevails

From the era of burning the widows alive on the funeral pyres of their deceased husbands in the name of religious tradition, to the days when the women have become key players in empowering India's advancement, the country has come a long way. From 2010, the female literacy rate has increased by 14.4% in 2021 (Shield Square Captcha, n.d.). They have started to hold significant and central positions in the professional as well as the public spheres while making their names in every field, be it science, research, space, technology, politics, defence, literature, or arts. Persons like Mrs. Pratibha Devi Singh Patil (President), Mrs. Draupadi Murmu (President), Mrs. Indira Gandhi (Prime minister), Mrs. Meera Kumar (Speaker of the House of the people), Isha Basant Joshi (first woman IAS), Kiran Bedi (first woman IPS), and many others have adorned high offices and respectable posts (Srivastava, 2019). According to the EY report 2022, 5% of the NIFTY 500 companies have female chairpersons and 95% of those companies have at least one female person amongst their board of directors (Women's Representation on Indian Boards Has Tripled in 10 Years: EY Report, 2023).

Even after women are holding such high positions in the country, flying fighter planes and commercial aircraft, leading Army battalions at Kings Way during the Republic Day parade, serving as officers in important government departments of India, the discrimination against them still prevails, and it is even more tragic for women from the underprivileged group and lower castes (Thapa, 2020).

According to a statement given by the UN Resident Coordinator in India Renata Dessallien, the women and girls from impoverished social groups of India encounters more vulnerabilities and are at greater risk of crime and violence (India, 2020). The females from the poor socio-economic section and inferior castes are most susceptible to human trafficking, or to be precise, sex trafficking (Parker, 2022). A study by Reuters has expressed that 16 million women and girls amongst the approximate 20 million commercial prostitutes in India are the victims of trafficking. The Legal Services in India have also confirmed that, in India, four girls enter into prostitution every hour and three of them would be forced into it (Habibullah, 2021). One of the main reasons associated with the trafficking of these Indian women into prostitution is the religious customs of prostitution. According to the provided data, it has been proven that, every year, almost 20,000 women get trafficked internally in India, and pretty much 50 per cent of them belong to the states with the prevalence of religious prostitution (Acharya, 2011, page-95).

Religious Prostitution or more precisely Temple Prostitution in India is a centuries-old ritual in Hinduism to devote young girls of lower castes to the deities in the Hindu temples, to make them subservient to satisfy the carnal desires of the priests as well as the men from the upper castes and these girls mostly are known as Devadasi. Devadasis were originally viewed as the protectors of art, who would learn classical Indian forms of music as well as dance to perform in front of the deities, some of them would be literate enough to compose poems, and hence people esteemed them as auspicious persons. Nevertheless, that is ancient history, modern Devadasis are straightforward sex workers. As reported by William Dalrymple of the New Yorker, present-day Devadasis get exclusively trafficked from the underprivileged section and lower castes such as Dalit Madar caste (Nast, 2008).

In 2016 the Indian Supreme Court instructed the states to implement strict laws to abolish the Devadasi system altogether as it has turned into an atrocious act of forcing young girls into a lifetime of sexual slavery (Devadasi System: Historical Background and Supreme Court Stance - GKToday, 2016). But unfortunately, the association of the term 'religious' with it, oppression from the upper caste men, superstitious beliefs and ignorance to the illegitimacy of the act, share the accountability to keep the Devadasi practice still prevalent in the Indian society, which serves as the problem statement for this paper. The key-question that the paper is going to analyse is whether, the factors 'religious practice', 'social compulsion' and 'poor economic situation' together have camouflaged the crime of trafficking associated with the Devadasi practice, and if yes, then to what extent. To uproot this evil act completely from the Indian society, it is necessary to confront this issue as a form of sex trafficking, so as to save the little girls from getting forced into prostitution in the name of 'serving the God' and that serves as the motivation for this paper (Devadasi System - Origin, Tradition & Beliefs Involved in the System, 2023).

The introduction has briefly discussed the concept of Devadasi in India. Following the introduction a literature review has been conducted to elucidate on the history of the Devadasi tradition, the degradation of the Devadasi system from being a sacred ritual to modern sexual slavery as well as the detection of traces of trafficking from the experiences shared by the Devadasis. The findings from the literature survey have shown that the religious superstitions, the negative socio-economic position and the societal pressure together have created the atmosphere for the Devadasi system to be still prevalent in India. The conclusion refers to the legislative initiatives taken by the Indian government as well as recommends the steps to be taken to completely eradicate this vice from the Indian society.

Literature Review: The Transition from A Sacred Tradition to Modern Vice

The word 'Devadasi' is a Sanskrit term, 'Deva' means 'God' and 'Dasi' means 'female servant', hence the whole expression intends for 'the female servant of God' ("Devadasi | Indian Society | Britannica," 2020). It is presumed that the origin of the Devadasi tradition traces back to the Keshari Dynasty in the 6th century A.D. in South India (Shingal, 2015). This Hindu tradition then used to be perceived as a sacred ritual of dedicating young pubescence girls to the provincial temples by marrying them off to the deity (Dkhar, 2015). The ceremony of marriage signified that they would be traditionally immune to the state of widowhood (Explained: Who Are Devadasis, Their History and Current Status, 2022) and they would be prohibited from marrying someone else as well (Dkhar, 2015). During those days, Devadasis used to get respected as auspicious females as they were attributed to partake in the temple ceremonies by performing Indian classical music and dance so as to mediate between God and His worshippers as well as to act as temple-keepers (Explained: Who Are Devadasis, Their History and Current Status, 2022). But not all the Devadasis had the privilege of taking part in the temple rituals, only those from the upper caste could perform them whereas the ones coming from the lower caste had to take care of chores like washing, cleaning the

temple, and fanning the deities. Devadasis were also used to get classified into categories depending on whether they were offered by the parents, or were kidnapped and forcibly made Devadasis, or were sold to the temple, or they willingly chose to be Devadasis (Ganeriwal, 2020). From a modern perspective, this classification process can be regarded as instances of coerced trafficking of minor girls into sexual slavery (Sex Slavery | Slavery | Britannica, 2023).

Nevertheless, despite the ancient glory, the tradition started losing its dignity around the Medieval Sultanate and Mughal era, as the vandalism of the Hindu temples led them towards their degraded exploitation by the upper castes in the society. The final stroke happened during the British period that transformed the Devadasi practice completely into the religious prostitution in temples persisting till date (Shingal, 2015).

At present it has become a medium of trading and trafficking the young girls from the underprivileged segments of the Indian society to sexually exploit them. Sometimes the parents hold an auction to trade the girls off to the highest bidder who would become her first 'client' and afterwards they generally get trafficked to the red-light areas in Mumbai as the city is infamous for its brothels (Top 10 Largest Red Light Areas in India | Famous Red Light Areas in India, 2023). Parvatamma, a Devadasi, shared her experience in an interview where she recounted that once she had reached puberty, the Devadasi tradition compelled her virginity to be sold to the highest bidder and once she had her first daughter at the age of 14, she was traded to the red-light district in Mumbai ("Devadasis Are a Cursed Community," 2011). Another Devadasi, Rani Bai stated that she was tricked by her parents and aunt to be offered to a man for INR 500 at the age of 14. She pleaded with her mother and aunt to let her go, but they compelled her, saying it's her duty as a Devadasi and left her alone with the man who forced himself on her despite her protests. She also narrated that when she was 6 years old, the ceremony of becoming a Devadasi happened, she was then too little to know the consequences and was only told that they were going to make a lot of money afterwards, which made her happy as they were really poor, so she did not really ponder about how the money would come. She was later got sold to a brothel in Mumbai by her aunt as well (Nast, 2008).

Methodology

The chief purpose of this paper was to account for the fact that variables like 'sacred tradition' and 'negative socio-economic circumstances' have prevented the Devadasi system from being regarded as a device of human trafficking. The core-question that the paper has analysed is whether, the factors 'religious practice', 'social compulsion' and 'poverty' together have camouflaged the crime of trafficking associated with the Devadasi practice, and if yes, then to what extent. The source analysis delves into secondary sources and the source corpus includes, published journals and articles related to the history of the Devadasi tradition, the social evils associated with it and the modern transition of the system; reported narratives of the trafficking Devadasi victims; and news-reports about the initiatives taken by the Indian government and legal acts to abolish the Devadasi system.

Findings

The objective of this paper was to demonstrate that belonging to the underprivileged socio-economic sections, irrational religious faiths and inadequate legislative framework together have made it challenging to establish the Devadasi system as human trafficking. According to the Article 3 of UN protocol, human trafficking for prostitution can be defined as the [induction](#) by force, fraud, or coercion of a person to engage in the sex trade (United Nations, 2000), which makes the association between the trafficking in persons for prostitution and the Devadasi system more prominent as the young Devadasis also get sold

or forced to join the service often by their poor parents and families belonging to the lower castes who would know that they are not actually sacrificing their daughters to God but coercing them into sex-trade. There are more than 40,000 Devadasis living in Karnataka, many of whom are reported to be victims of human trafficking. While, on one hand, superstition has led Kalpana's grandmother to sacrifice her to the God, believing that the deity is angry with them and punishing them by giving a smaller number of boy child. On the other hand, some Devadasis, like Aswamma and Gowri's mother got trafficked due to the financial necessities of their families ("Devadasis in Karnataka: Pushed off Mainstream by Social & Economic Factors," 2022). The relevance to 'sacred tradition' draws the distinction between the Devadasis and the commercial sexual workers, which prevents the dedication of Devadasis from being suspected as a trick to procure pre-pubescent or teenage girls for trafficking into prostitution. The experiences shared by the Devadasis have suggested that 95% of them got trafficked, yet, because of the term Devadasi is associated with them, neither of them has been treated as trafficking victims and provided with compensation or rehabilitation, nor there has been any case registered against the perpetrators under Indian Penal Code (Bengaluru, 2023).

A careful observation in the modern transition of the Devadasi Tradition specifies that the present existence of the system strictly relies on, 1) the religious belief of the people, which convinces them that offering their young girls to deity would make Him happy, bring them blessings and fulfilment of their wishes such as more male children in the family or going one step upward in the social status ladder, 2) the poor financial condition, that makes the girls unwanted burden for the families, hence they become vulnerable to get sexually exploited and earn money for their families while the families just use the Devadasi tradition as an excuse to send their girls to brothels, and, 3) the societal pressure as the rigid caste system of India gives the chance to the upper caste men to coerce the lower caste people to fulfil their duties by forcing their daughters to become Devadasis. For the very poor, and the very pious, the Devadasi tradition can still be regarded as a way out of poverty while gaining access to the blessings of the deities, the exact two things that the most impoverished people yearn for.

Conclusion

The Devadasi tradition, which was introduced in the name of devotion has now become a social evil. In the patriarchal society of India, girls get considered as liabilities, mostly in the underprivileged sections of the country. This practice turns out to be a perfect ploy to convert their liabilities into assets as well as justifies their action of pimping out their daughters into prostitution. At present, the Devadasi system is generally predominant in the Indian states of Karnataka, Tamil Nadu, Andhra Pradesh, Maharashtra, and Orissa as well (Ganeriwal, 2020).

The Indian Government declared the practice of Devadasi illegal in 1924 and since then many states have tried to form laws to eradicate this evil (Sofiabhambri, 2021),

- Bombay Devadasi Protection Act, 1934
- Prevention of Dedication Act (Madras Devadasi) in 1947
- Prohibition of Dedication Act (Karnataka Devadasi), 1982
- Prohibition of Dedication Act (Andhra Pradesh Devadasi), 1988
- Abolition of Dedication Act (Maharashtra Devadasi), 2005

In 2016, the Indian Supreme Court declared strict laws to abolish the system (Devadasi System: Historical Background and Supreme Court Stance - GKToday, 2016). Unfortunately,

even after being outlawed, NHRC (2022) data has shown that there are 70,000 Devadasis living in Karnataka, 80,000 in the states of Telangana and Andhra Pradesh. Declaring the Devadasi practice as a serious issue of violation of Right to Life, Dignity and Equality of these victim women, in October, 2022, NHRC has issued notices to the secretaries of Union Ministry of Women and Child Development and the Ministry of Social Justice and Empowerment, and the chief secretaries of Karnataka, Kerala, Tamil Nadu, Andhra Pradesh, Telangana, and Maharashtra, asking them to give a detailed report containing supporting data mentioning the steps taken/proposed to be taken by the authorities to prevent the Devadasi system as well as to provide the Devadasis rehabilitation and social security so that they could lead their lives with dignity. It should also mention whether any local laws have been enacted in the States to prevent such social evil, and if not, what steps have been proposed to be taken to eradicate it (NHRC Issues Notices to Centre, 6 States Seeking Report on Devadasi System, 2022).

At the age of going to schools, these young girls get ensnared into hellish world of prostitution in the name of 'sacred tradition' as the dedication ceremonies happen pre-pubescent. Illiteracy, economic vulnerability, and ignorance to the illegality of the Devadasi system push them off to this dark world. Empowering the girls is necessary for which proper steps should be taken to ensure that they get access to education, skills development, employment opportunities and rehabilitation schemes. The frequency of the awareness campaigns to enlighten everyone about the illegitimacy of the Devadasi practice and the vices associated with it requires to be increased as well. Strong enforcement of the legal acts, stern actions taken by the authorities together and harsh penalties should be implemented upon the perpetrators.

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35 - Esoteric Elements as Ascribed in Buddhist *Charyapada* in India

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Abstract

This study aims to discuss divine aspects of Buddhist tantra from the point of view of Charyapada. Charyapada is the first literary evidence of Old Bengali Literature. The application of these songs basically depended on the tantric Buddhist philosophy. This Charya does not exist simply in the form of a musical and poetic devotional song but it is also a medium of instilling the enthusiasts and devotees into the philosophy of prajana (knowledge) Karuna (compassion) and Prajnaupaya (ways of knowledge). Through the knowledge, of pragyaparamita spiritual adepts are fully immersed in spiritual thinking and external truth. In this context, Charyapada is one of the elements which is very much important in this external and internal tradition. Moreover, the right path to achieve the great blessing is also described in these songs.

Keywords: *Charya, guru, siddhacharya, ignorance, great blessing*

Research Purpose & Problems

When we work on esoteric elements as ascribed in *Charyapada* in India, and then some relevant questions arise in our mind. The questions are- 1) to find the meaning and classification of *Charyapada*, 2) to discuss the significance of this collection of songs in Buddhist tantrism, 3) to disclose the function of nerves, wheels breathing and in esoteric pursuits, and 4) to publish how to realize the ultimate blessing. This article is planned to solve all the theoretical questions, which is mentioned above.

Methodology

Every research paper explores some new findings or thinking. As per methodology, this paper would be exactly written based on analytical and descriptive methods. To make a corpus of this paper, data was collected from primary sources like the books of *Hajar Bachorer Purano Bangala Bhashay Bouddha Gan O Doha, Charya-Samgrahah, Charyagiti Parikrama*, etc... Side by side some of the ideas and information gathered from a secondary source such as various journals, literary critics, Indian religion Buddhism and history related books.

Literary Reviews

Many eminent scholars just mentioned and discussed various aspects of *Charyapada* and give us the right outline to understand it. All those books and researches are such as '*Hajar Bachorer Purano Bangala Bhashay Bouddha Gan O Doha*' by Haraprasad Sastri, *Charya-Samgrahah* by Bhaktimal Dey, *Charyagiti Parikrama* of Nirmal Das, *Charyagiti Padabali* by Sukumar Sen, etc... The main theme of all those frameworks is a delineation of the substance of these *charya*-songs and literary evolution. But this matter has not been specifically highlighted. This lacuna is the main source to plan this framework.

Findings

After reviewing all the songs of Charya, it is cleared the religious allusions, description of the hidden practice methods, and various terminology, those mediation in *Charyapada* that the main background of these songs is Buddhism, but not the original form of Buddhism, but a modified form of Tantra.

Introduction

Since ancient times worship of goddesses and spiritual practices was divided into two sections. The first is, to achieve the grace of Deities through sacrificial rites (*yajna*) and the other is to gain the grace of the goddesses by awakening the inner power by restoring to multifarious activities. Here, the first is a sign of Vedic religion and the other is the character of *Tantrism*. But if we profoundly observe it, then it assumes that when primitive man lived in a forest or cave, then they applied magical power due to self-protection and riding of various fears such as anxiety of serpent bit, fear of animal's attack, the anxiety of hidden enemies' attack, fear of cataclysmic natural power, etc. Again, along with the evolution of human civilization, achieving the miraculous power of man was added as one of the aims of Tantraism. So, it can be easily assumed that practices of Tantra or magic have been started from the beginning of human civilization. 'Tantra' has been used as the meaning of 'system'. The term 'tantra' is usually derived from the Sanskrit verbal root of 'tan' means 'to spread' and 'tra' means 'to save'. Hence 'tantra' is 'that which saves' (Augustine, 2008, p.20). In the religious world, the term 'tantra' may be understood as 'that which spreads knowledge' (Dasgupta, 1974, p.2). Perhaps in the 7th century, tantric religion and esoteric rituals entered into Buddhism like the Hindu religion. In general Tantra in Buddhism is divided into five classes, such as *Pitri-tantra*, *Matri-tantra*, *Kriya-tantra*, *Charya-tantra*, and *Advay-tantra*. *Charyapada* is a collection of mystical Buddhist songs, which is part of tantric *Vajrayana* and *Sahajayana* (vehicle of *Vajra* and vehicle of *Sahaja*). In 1907 A.D. Mohamohopadhyay Haraprasad Sastri, a renowned scholar of oriental studies and historian discovered the manuscript of *Charyapada* from the Royal Library of Nepal and at first attracted the attention of educational society through The Asiatic society in Kolkata. In 1916 A.D. he published it in a single volume named '*Hajar Bachorer Purano Bangala Bhashay Bouddha Gan O Doha*' from the organization of Bangiya Sahitya Parisad. Basically, that incomplete manuscript was the Muni datta's commentary of fifty's *charya* songs. *Charyapada*, the first literary evidence of Old Bengali literature, is very significant in the Buddhist occult world. The word *Charya* is derived from the root 'Char' by adding 'yat' and 'yap' as suffixes, which means 'conduct'. The meaning of Charya in a broad sense is the regular performance of all kinds of customers and sacraments. In Buddhist tantrism, the meaning of *Charya* is the conduct of esoteric practices. It is known as '*chacha*' in the regional language. *Charya* in Buddhist culture is divided into two classes, like, *Guhya-charya* and *Bahya-charya*. Of *Guhya-charya* has two divisions, like *Ati-Guhy Charya* and *Guhyatguhya Charya*. On another side, *Bahya charya* is split into five classes such as general *Pooja* (worship) *charya*, *Khyoah charya*, *Laskar-jatra charya*, *Nritya (dance) Charya*, and *Nritya Sahit Pooja charya*. These songs are performed secretly in the rituals of *Aagam Poojas*. As per the *Vajrayana* philosophy, *Charya* songs are also called *Vajrageets* (*Vajra* Songs) as they were adopted from *Vajrayan*. In general, *Charya* is composed of dancing with singing in front of tantric adorable deities. It is remarkable that without those people who have taken *Vajrabhisheka*, other general people are not allowed to hear the song and see the dance. Only the people of *Vajrabhisheka* have the right to participate in this ritualistic ceremony. Now below the esoteric aspects of *Charyapada* are discussed in the light of tantric Buddhism.

Discussion

The composers of *Charyapada* were introduced in society as a Buddhist tantric part. So, it is natural to reflect the thought and self-realization of Tantra in their compositions. All the

Tantric Buddhists imagined the different *tattvas* (doctrines) in their own corporal structure. The resting place of absolute happiness is the temple of the body. Basically, Buddhist *siddhacharyas* believe the body (*Kaya*) is the container of all types of occult practices. According to the Bhiksus, 'the body is called the *nikaya*' (Farrow & Menon, 1992, 11:4:64.). *Siddacharyas* strongly believe that all things which are present in the universe are in our body. Only if it is possible to know the inner secrets of the human body, then it will be possible to know the universal cosmology and its all kinds of mysteries. As a result, the realization of great blessing is not possible without the body. In the Buddhist tantric world, three types of body (*Kaya*) have been envisioned, such as body of *Dharma* (*Dharma-kaya*), body of enjoyment (*Sambhoga-kaya*), and body of transformation (*Rupa-kaya* or *Nirmanakaya*). (ibid, 11:4:54.) Again *Sambhoga-kaya* divided into two parts as *Parasambhoga-kaya* and *Swasambhoga-kaya*. According to *Hevajatantram*, it is not possible to attain great happiness without the body (ibid, p.56). The universe is hidden in the body and can only be known through the *yoga* system. As the *siddhacharyas* of *Chraya* were aware regarding this universal law, that's why Sarahapa allegorically said in his song that '*paramatattva* (ultimate metaphysical principle) is at your home (body). You are asking out for it. You have seen your beloved within, but you are searching for him in the neighbor' (Dasgupta, 1976, p.105). Regarding the importance of the body in *sadhana*, Kanhapa said in his song (song no. 11) that 'the *yogin* Kanha has become a *kapali*, and has entered into the practices of *yoga*, and he is supporting in the city of his body in the non-dual form' (Das, 2010, p.141).

In the Tantra world, the total number of *nadis* (nerves) and sub-nerves in the human body is three and a half lacks. Not only in Buddhist tantras, but also in Hindu tantras and *Yoga-Upanishads* recognized the existence of these number pulses. *Bhagavan* declared regarding these nerves that 'the *nadis* are all transformations of the three realms of existence (Body, Speech, and Mind), which encompass all that exists' (Farrow & Menon, 1992, 1:1:21.). Among these numerous pulses, thirty-two are the main nerves, because these thirty-two nerves bear *bodhicitta* and flow into the Centre of Great Bliss. Again, of those, three nerves are directly associated with the practice of tantra in Buddhist Tantra, known as *Lalana*, *Rasana*, and *Avadhuti*. In order to *Yogaratanamala* 'these entire nerves are conceived of as possessing characteristics of phenomenal things. Therefore, particular phenomenal qualities are conceived of in a particular center as the nature of *Lalana*, *Rasana*, and *Avadhuti*' (ibid, p.14). In the Hindu tantric tradition, they are respectively called *Idá*, *Piñgalá*, and *Susumná*. *Lalana* is believed to be on the left, *rasana* is believed to be on the right, and *avadhuti* is in the middle. In this context, S. B. Dasgupta clearly said that 'Lalana is believed to start from the neck and enter the navel region from the left side. *Rasana* starts from the navel and enters the neck from the right. Within these two, and passing through the lotus in the heart is the *Avadhuti*' (Dasgupta, 1990, p.154-155). In *Charyapada*, *Lalaná* and *Rasaná* together are named as *sunyatá-karuná*, *prajñá-upáya*, *áli-káli*, moon-sun, left-right, *gráhya-gráhaka*, *dhamana-chamana* etc. Likewise, *Avadhuti* nerve is called *devi*, *yagin*, *sahajasundari* i.e. in *Charyapada*. Of those, '*Lalana* is of the nature of *Prajna* (wisdom), and *Rasana* remains as *Updya* (means) (Shasti, p.158), and '*Avadhuti* remains in the middle as the abode of *Mahasukha*' (Dasgupta, 1950, p.107). In *Jnanodaya Tantra* stated that reconciliation *Prajna* and *Updya* is possible when *Lalana* and *Rasana* both are united in the nerve of *Avadhuti* by intake and rotation of breath and with this union the adept can realize the bliss in his body, which is called *Sahajananda* (Rinpoche & Dwivedi, 1988, p. 10). Sarahapa, in his song (Song no. 5), indicates the way how to achieve the *Sahajananda* of the metaphor of river and bridge and said 'the body is allegorized by a river, of which two streams named *bamaga* (*lalana*) and *danga* (*rasana*) and in the middle of the river has bridge (*avadhuti*). When climbing the bridge, do not go left or right, because *Bodhi* is near you' (Das, 2010, p.124). Likewise, *Siddhacharya* Kukkuripa said (Song-2), 'that the *Bodhicitta* (sharpen

Power) is purified when the movement of Lalana and Rasana are united and stopped. If *Bodhicitta* is generated upward into the way of *Avadhuti* by the *Kumbhaka* yoga, Then the ultimate bliss can be realized (ibid, p.115).

The esoteric adepts imagined several wheels in the body. In Buddhist Tantra, the number of wheels is four, named as *Nirman-chakra*, *Dharma-chakra*, *Sambhog-chakra*, and *Mahasukha-chakra*. Although, the Hindu tantras identify seven plexuses in their system, of which name is *Muladhara-chakra*, *Svadhithana-chakra*, *Manipura-chakra*, *Anahata-chakra*, *Visuddha-chakra*, *Ajna-chakra*, and *Sahasrara-chakra*. *Siddhacharyas* identified that the first wheel named *Nirman-chakra* is locked at the navel and here presenting deity is *Lachana*. The second wheel named *Dharma-chakra* is locked at the heart and its presenting deity is *Mamaki*. The third wheel named *Sambhoga-chakra* is locked at the neck and its dwelling deity is *Pandura*. And the last wheel *Mahasukha-chakra* is locked at the flat of the head and here dwelling deity is *Tara*. Indeed, the *siddhacharyas* were experts in *Hatha-yoga*. Through the process of *Hatha-yoga*, they produce the *bodhicitta* in *Nirman-chakra* and gradually move it upwards. When it passes through *Dharma-chakra* and *Sambhoga-chakra*, then an adept realizes the great blessing. The feeling that occurs when *bodhicitta* produces in *Nirmanchakra* is called *Ananda*. Chronologically, when *Bodhicitta* resides in *Dharmachakra*, there is a filling, its name *Paramananda*. When *Bodhicitta* resides in *Sambhogchakra*, there is a filling, its name *Biramananda*. At last, when *Bodhicitta* resides in *Mahasukhachakra*, there is a filling, its name *Sahajananda*, which is the ultimate goal of an adept.

The tradition of the guru is more ancient and it exists in almost every religion. Ever since the advent of tantric religion, *tantrickas* (adepts) believe that this mystic spiritual practice is not possible without the guru. In the term of guru, the first letter 'gu' is an indicator of the darkness of ignorance and the second letter 'ru' is the protector of the darkness of ignorance. Hence that is the guru, who can able to remove the all darkness of ignorance and shows the light of absolute knowledge. Because of being always respectable and adorable by the disciples, the guru is regarded as one of the main doctrines in the Hindu and Buddhist tantric literature. To determine the significance of the guru in Tantrism, eminent scholar Tomy Augustine has rightly said that "tantrism proves to be a dangerous path for those who are uninitiated and unaccompanied by a competent Guru. No *sdhaka* should attempt it by him. The Guru is identified with the principal deity and the initiate is expected to abide by the Guru's directions" (Augustine, 2008, p.40). Compared to the other scriptures with tantric scriptures, the guru is depicted in tantric scriptures as equal to god, and sometimes even he or she has gotten a higher position than the goddess. For example, it is said to *Kularnava Tantra* that 'only Guru can rescue his disciple of ire of Siva, but when the guru is angry, there is no way to get rid of him' (Das, 1383, p. 294). As per *Bhairavadamar Tantra*, 'it is not possible to understand the fundamental principles of Tantrism without the active role of the guru' (Chattapadhyay, 1958, p.156). Only the guru can able to fully explain the symbolic terms used in the tantric world. It is recognized that the practices of *siddhacharya* are very esoteric subjects. In these esoteric subjects, there are some complex physical and mental processes, that can't be practiced without the proper guidance and assistance of someone with prior experience. Therefore, the significance of a guru has been repeatedly echoed in their songs. As regards this matter Lūipā has stated in his song (Song no.1) that "strengthen the quantity of great bliss, ask and learn from the Guru" (Das, 2010, p.113). Likewise, *siddhacharya* Cāṭilapā said in his song (Song no. 5) that 'how to cross the materialistic world, ask to *anuttarsamee* (guru) Chatil' (ibid, p.125). Again, in another song (Song no. 38), Sarahapā stated the significance of guru through the allegoric of the boat ride "in the small boat of body form, the mind is its handle and hold on it in the methods prescribed by the great guru" (ibid, p.201). So, above these excerpts indicate that only the guru's advice can

save the mind from various thinking hindrances, which are the main obstacles in *sadhana* (spiritual practices). Here it is proved that composers of *Charyapada* have strongly believed that ultimate reality (*sahajananda*), which is out of the senses, even isn't to know by the reading of scriptures. Only this knowledge can be achieved through the quality of service to the guru.

In the esoteric world, the main but primary duty of a *sadhaka* is to keep the five senses and six vices, named lust, anger, greed, sense of me, attachment, and partiality. Because these are the main enemies of a *sadhaka* (spiritual adept). That's why *Kularnava Tantra* (13/91-92) clearly stated that "hatred, doubt, fear, shame, disgust, race, disposition and cast, these are the eight bonds of human beings. Bound by these bonds one is a (*pasu*). Liberated from these bonds one is *Siva*" (Das, 1383, p.329). In this context, *Ajdevpa* (Song No. 31) stated that 'the adepts always need to remove fear and hatred' (Das, 2010, p.187). As these bondages are the cause of ignorance and restlessness of mind. Therefore *Luipa* (song no.1) said that 'due to the restlessness of mind, time enters' (ibid, p.113). *Kala* (time) is the cause of all sorrows. Only *pancaskandha* (five Aggregates) can be burned and entry of time can be prevented only by the advice and grass of the guru. And *Bhusukapa* (Song no. 49) said, when five Aggregates is burned, then the senses are automatically destroyed' (ibid, p.221).

Conclusion

In conclusion, achievement of great blessing is the highest goal of all adepts. *Sahjananda* is the form of ultimate joy and happiness. Therefore, adepts are always active to achieve or realize this great blessing and being free from all kinds of sorrows. In order to the belief of tantric society *prakriti* (female power) and *purusha* (male power), both are all times present in the human body. Achievement of salvation or realization of great blessing is just then possible when an adept can reconcile between *prakriti* and *purusha* by breaking through the six wheels (*sathachakra*) through the awaking of serpent power (*kundalini sakti*). Those corresponding doctrinal concepts are reflected rhythmically in the verses of *charyapada*. According to Buddhist tantra, the realization of ultimate blessing is possible only by the union of *sunyata* (emptiness) and *karuna* (compassion). 'Mainly *Mddhyamika* teaches that *bodhicitta* is a unique blend of *sunyata* and *karund* (Intellect and Will)' (Mdd Murti, 1955, p. 264). Here *Sunyata* is *prajana* and *karuna* is the active principle of compassion. *Charyapada* is the medium of the revealed form of that esoteric theory. As well as many mystic aspects with complex rituals had been having to do with. Therefore, it is no exaggeration to call that the composition of *Charyapada* is the song of the hidden doctrine of esoteric practices.

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36 - Communal Tension and Social Cohesion in India: Pathways for Positive Praxis

Yasin, PP Mohammed

Problem Statement: rising religious tensions in India in the background of attempts to replace democracy with religious fascism

Purpose of the Study: to investigate the possibilities of inter-disciplinary action and policy practice in ensuring social cohesion and national unity.

Literature or Theory: Durkhemian ideas of social cohesion and collective effervescence and the idea of 'imagined communities' as proposed by Benedict Anderson.

Research Methods: Literature review and event analysis

Summary of Findings: The utility of performance or secular performance in ensuring national unity.

Conclusion: The paper attempts to draw conclusions at the possibilities of inter-faith unity and cohesion contributing to the national development and vice versa.

Keywords:

- 1 Social Cohesion
- 2 Social Policy
- 3 Interfaith Action
- 4 Religious Conflict
- 5 Religious authoritarianism

Area: Religion

37 - Everyday Peace Discourse from the Scholar Perspectives

Ruttanasatain, Ngamsuk

Problem Statement: This paper explores the everyday peace discourse from the scholar perspectives. It is based on the existing literature during 2017-2022. The violence conflicts which have been happen in Thailand and neighbor countries may need the new knowledge and creative way in order to build peace. Everyday peace as a concept and the practice from the local community approaches to overcome violence conflict in daily life might be important to explore. According to Roger Mac Ginty argues in her paper Everyday peace: Bottom-up and local agency in conflict-affected societies that everyday peace can be an important building block peace formation, especially as formal approaches to peacebuilding and state building are often deficient.

Purpose of the Study: To address the concept and discourse of everyday peace from the scholar perspectives that might help to reduce the limitation of knowledge in building peace in Thailand and neighbor countries.

Literature or Theory: This paper is based on the everyday peace by Pamina Firchow and Roger Mac Ginty, and make the linkages from the peace, violent, and conflict theories of John Paul Lederach, Sung Yong Lee, Oliver P. Richmond, Peter Wallensteen, Michael Ignatieff, Sarah Maddison and Johan Galtung.

Research Methods: The literature reviews is used as a research method.

Summary of Findings The concept and discourse of everyday peace that have been discuss in the scholar world. Their work might show the strength and weakness and also the gap that will help to do further research.

Conclusion: The expected outcome of this study will be the lesson learn in theory and case studies from the scholar perspectives.

Keywords

1. everyday peace
2. discourse
3. scholars
4. knowledge
5. violence conflict

Area: Justice and Peace

38 - Globalization, Identity Politics and The Ethics of Solidarity: An Indonesia Perspective

Komimbin, Alfian Rico

Problem Statement: Globalization divides the world into a binary opposition between the strong and the weak, the victorious and the losers. Global authorities are becoming new giants pressing for local sovereignty. In turn, identity politics is one of the dominant strategies in response to globalization that tends to suppress locality. In the context of politics in Indonesia recently, identity politics has transformed into the politicization of identity which is even more dangerous than the political threat of buying and selling votes (money politics).

Purpose of the Study: To construct an alternative idea as a counter ideology to identity politics in Indonesia

Literature or Theory: I will use Olúfẹ́mi O. Táíwò's theory of "Elite Capture" and Anselm K. Min's theory of Solidarity of Others

Research Methods: I will use Systematic Literature Review

Summary of Findings: Using Systematic Literature Review as a research approach, this article elaborates the prospective idea of solidarity into a counter ideology of identity politicization in the stage politics in Indonesia. Using literature studies as a data collection technique, this article offers the idea of rhizomatic solidarity as a result of the construction of the idea of solidarity of others and rhizomatic identity.

Conclusion: The idea of solidarity of others (not solidarity with) can be an alternative to counteract identity politics

Keywords

- 1 Globalization
- 2 Identity Politics
- 3 Solidarity of Others
- 4 Counter culture
- 5 Counter ideology

Area: Religion

39 - The Role of The Evangelical Christian Church in Papua Land to Achieve Sdgs No Poverty in Papua Province

Makuba, Elvira Hubertina

Tasik, Ayomi

ABSTRACT

This research is research to examine the role of the Evangelical Christian Church in Papua Land to Achieve Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and No Poverty in Papua Province. Based on the data of the Indonesian Statistical Bureau poverty rate in Papua Province is the highest in Indonesia. Since the time before SDG's exist, churches have roles on the its service to people which relates to SDGs. The Evangelical Christian Church in Papua, as one of the faith actors has some roles to achieve SDGs No Poverty. Theory that is used to explain the church's roles is functionalism theory from Talcot Parson which has been used as role theory. The research succeeded in gathering information on service activities carried out by The Evangelical Christian Church in the Land of Papua which related to targets and indicators to achieve SDGs "No Poverty "in Papua Province. Primary and Secondary data have been collected and analyzed. The result shows that the Evangelical Christian Church in Papua Land has significant roles in achieving SDGs "No Poverty" in Papua Province. Activities carried out by The Evangelical Christian Church in the Land of Papua in its service to people related to targets and indicators to achieve SDGs "No Poverty "in Papua Province. Primary and Secondary data have been collected and analyzed. The result shows that the Evangelical Christian Church in Papua Land has significant roles in achieving SDGs "No Poverty" in Papua Province.

Introduction

The State of Indonesia was involved in the work of preparing and determining the Sustainable Development Goals and has made government regulations related to the determination of SDGs. The first of the 17 existing Sustainable Development Goals, the first Goal is Zero Poverty. Dealing with poverty, in 2021 the number of poor people in Indonesia was 27.54 million. Papua Province is the poorest province in Indonesia with its poverty rate 26.86 percent (BPS data as of March 2021) of a total population of 4,303,707 residents (Data of Statistical Bureau of Indonesia per March 2021). In the work of alleviating poverty, of course first the focus is always to the role of the government, but in the work to reduce poverty, many parties can actually help the work to eradicate poverty; One of that parties is religious community. Based on the data from the Central Bureau of Statistics Indonesia, the number of population in Papua Province who are Christian protestant in 2017 is 2,128,233 where the total population in that year is Rp. 3,265,202. According to the regulations of government each province in Indonesia has its Plan of Action to achieve national target of SDGs. Papua Province has set Plan of Action (Rencana Aksi Daerah) as well as has done evaluation of achievement for the year 2015 – 2017.

The Evangelical Christian church in Papua land is still carrying out its role in the development fields including services which relates to the efforts to alleviate poverty. and thus, playing a role in achieving SDGs on No Poverty. The research question is what the role of the Evangelical Christian Church in the Land of Papua in achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) No Poverty in Papua Province? The research was conducted to gather information on the activities of GKI services in Tanah Papua in their ministry which are

closely related to TPB Without Poverty starting from history before the church was founded until the period of the Evangelical Christian Church in Papua Land services in Tanah Papua in 2017-2022. The research was conducted at the history of the church's role and achievements in the Province of Papua which already has its provincial Action Plan to achieve SDGs. The Province of Papua referred to in this research is the Main Province before the division of the Province of Papua into 4 Provinces.

Some of the previous research that became the source of this research was research from Haustein and Tomalin (2019) which conveyed the role of faith actors in supporting the preparation and achievement of SDGs. This study emphasizes the role of each faith actor as explained by Haustein and Tommalin. In relation to the role carried out by the Evangelical Christian Church in Tanah Papua it is closely related to all the roles of the types of faith actors described above.

Tujuan Berkelanjutan di Indonesia (Sustainable Development Goals in Indonesia) describes the concepts, targets and strategies as well as the implementation of Sustainable Development in Indonesia. This book specifically explains how Indonesia is pursuing the target of achieving SDGs supported by economic, social and environment. Starting from this research, this research tries to elaborate further on the role of the church which is specifically related to the social dimension. Murdiana and Mulyana (2017) researched the Analysis of Poverty Alleviation Policy in Indonesia where this research explained the poverty alleviation programs that had been implemented by the government.

The Document Called to Transformation Ecumenical Diaconia published by the WCC and Act Alliance (2022) is a source of literature that provides information about the role that can be played by religious communities and how the religious community is involved in carrying out this role. In more depth it is explained about the role of Faith Based Organization in the work of achieving SDGs by focussing at the indicators. The roles described are in accordance with what this research intends to describe in the context church services in Papua Province. and moreover, these roles are explained in accordance with the GKI service activities in the Land of Papua according to the indicators.

Other main library sources used in this study are the Sustainable Development Goals documents issued by the Ministry of National Development Planning the National Development Agency. These documents are very important because they are a reference for all stakeholders to participate in achieving SDGs within the regional scope which will contribute to achieving SDG targets nationally which in turn will contribute to achieving SDGs at the international level.

The role theory that is used as a reference in writing this research is related to the theory of functionalism put forward by Talcot Parson (1951). Functionalism theory was used as a role theory in the early days of the theory's appearance. The theory provides understanding on how a society which has different parts operate to accomplish their purpose.

Poverty line is a standard to define standard of living of population in a country. Poverty line in Indonesia is set by Statistical Bureau of Indonesia both the international poverty line and national poverty line is used to determine number of poor people in Indonesia.

The definition of Sustainable Development Goals is development that maintains the community's economic welfare on an ongoing basis, development that maintains the sustainability of people's social life, development that maintains the quality of the environment and development that ensures justice and implementation of governance that is able to maintain an increase in the quality of life of one generation to the next.

The Evangelical Christian Church in the Land of Papua was established on October 26, 1956. The vision of the Evangelical Christian Church in the Land of Papua, which is called the Theological Vision, is the Kingdom of God. The mission of the Evangelical Christian Church in Tanah Papua is to manifest the signs of the Kingdom of God in fellowship, witness, service of love and justice. This operational mission is visible in the General Affairs, Theology, Resources and Funds programs as a manifestation of the implementation of the Church's Tri Callings. Because of that, GKI in Tanah Papua is to manifest the signs of God's kingdom or the signs of shalom which cover all fields, including the economy, health, peace education and others.

All data related to the description of Papua Province was taken from the 2019 Regional Medium Term Development Plan Document. Papua Province is located in the eastern part of Indonesia. The area of Papua Province is 32,027,839 hectares. The administrative area of Papua Province consists of 28 districts and 1 city, which is divided into 470 districts and 4,378 villages. Administratively, Papua Province is bordered by

In terms of measuring poverty in the Sustainable Development Goals, the agreed concept of poverty is a condition in which a person's expenditure is below \$1.25 (World Bank Standard) according to the document Transforming our World: The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development Goals. Shortly after setting the 2030 Agenda, the World Bank raised the poverty standard to \$1.90 which was officially announced in October 2015.

Method

The research has been done by using qualitative method. The data used in this study were collected through in-depth interview techniques and secondary data collection obtained from literature review data or library research. Primary data has been collected from 15 informants that is through in-depth interviews and library research.

Research Interview Informant Data on the Role of GKI in Tanah Papua in Achieving SDGs Without Poverty in Papua Province

No	Informant	Total
1	Synod worker	7
2.	Presbytery worker	2
3.	Worker at congregation	4
3.	Workers at church Institution	2
4.	Members of Parliament	1
	Total number of informants	16

The Role of the Evangelical Christian Church in Papua Land to achieve SDGs No Poverty

GKI in Tanah Papua supports the achievement of TPB Without Poverty achieved through the role of all divisions within the church organization. And this role is one part of the many roles played by various institutions in government and non-government institutions. In carrying out this role everything is communicated to the institutional parts of the GKI in Tanah Papua both at the synod, class and congregation levels as well as institutions within the GKI in Tanah Papua where communication is conveyed to individuals within the institution to be forwarded to individuals in the congregation and society.

1. The role of the Church in education to alleviate poverty

The church is the main institution (social intuition) in Papua land which started the education through the work of missionary. Until this recent time the church still runs the education institutions started from preschool to university level. Below are data of school and number of students, teacher as well as other staff.

YPK Kindergarten, Elementary and Middle School Data for the 2017 – 2018 academic year.

Level of Education	Number of schools	Number of schools	Number of schools
Kindergarten	51	1854	195
Primary School	374	31,612	1049
Junior High School	23	5,485	335

Number of schools and students of YPK Senior High School and Vocational High School for the 2018 – 2019 Academic Year in Papua Province.

SMA (Senior High School)					SMK (Vocational High School)			
Academic year	Number of schools	Number of students	Number of teachers	Administrative Worker	Number of schools	Number of students	Number of teachers	Number of administrative workers
2018 – 2019	17	1845	164	49	9	1933	177	22

2. The Church encourages participation of people at the grass root level to participate in their own development.

3. GKI in Tanah Papua plays role as a Partner of the Government, NGOs and Churches.

- GKI Church in Tanah Papua as a partner of the Central Government
- GKI in Tanah Papua as a partner of the Provincial, Regency/City Government and Village Level Government.
- GKI in the Land of Papua as a Legislative Institution Partner
- The Evangelical Christian Church in Tanah Papua acts as a partner for non-religious-based non-governmental organizations (NGOs)

- The church plays a role as a partner of churches - both domestic and foreign churches.
- 4. GKI in Tanah Papua becomes a Mediator for the NGO
- 5. The Church plays a role in reaching Vulnerable Communities
- 6. The Church plays a role in reaching people live in remote areas
- 7. The Church's role as a provider of Funds
- 8. The Church's role in the health Sector.
- 9. The Church Acts as a mentor.

All the roles explaining above relates to the target and indicators SDGs No Poverty that has been set nationally and Provincially by the government. All roles which have mentioned above can be summarized as below:

1. Pioneer or Initiator and mobilizer

As a pioneer or initiator of church activities since the beginning of the church was established in terms of supporting education, health, and the real economy. In terms of dealing with the disasters that occurred during the 2017 to 2019 ministry period in several disaster incidents, the church immediately took initiatives that were very useful to help the congregation and the community. For example, when a disaster occurred in Keerom Regency, the church moved.

2. Resource Provider

The church provides resources that are used to achieve SDGs such as funding, personnel, expertise. Experts of the church offices usually have a better understanding of the situation at the grassroots level. Generally, church workers understand the situation at the grassroots level very well, namely everything related to the ability of funds, assets and knowledge possessed. The assets owned can also be related to the potential of available natural resources.

3. Liaison for Stakeholders (Bridge or Channel for Stakeholders)

The church becomes a bridge for partners in terms of implementing partner programs to achieve SDGs. There are many programs from the partners of church like World Vision Indonesia, UNICEF and churches. The purpose of all of programs mainly connects a lot with the efforts to achieve SDGs No Poverty

4. Mentors

The church can be a good companion for church members because basically church members already have a sense of trust in the church. One example as has been explained is the assistance that is always carried out by Women Training and Development Center, as well as in other programs and activities designed by the Evangelical Christian Church in Papua Land

5. Advisers

As adviser the church has a role that has been given in various forms. Both in cooperative relations with the national, provincial and district/city level governments, the church provides information and suggestions for improving community development in Papua Province and also other provinces. This also happened in meetings with the parlement.

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40 - The Vedic Hindu Law and misinterpretation: Its Relevance and Reflection on Modern Hindu Society

Kumar, Shiv

Problem Statement: In this Paper it will be shown that vedic law was scientific but due to some people it has miss used but now a days people want it for its scientific fact

Purpose of the Study: Vedic law was really good for society. Its hypothesis will be the acceptancy of Vedic law in modern society

Literature or Theory: Veda and Indian Penal coad

Research Methods: Descriptive

Summary of Findings: Vedas are the oldest literary texts in Indian history. The meaning of

Vedas is the supreme knowledge that the ancient Arya sages have come across with their keen eyes. The Vedas are the reservoir of knowledge of these four parts: Dharma, Artha, Kama, and Moksha. Acknowledging the religious greatness of the Vedas, the Manusamhita (2/6) states that the Vedas are the root of all religions. From ancient times to the present day, various laws have been introduced in society based on religion. So, the ancient Indian society was not exempt from that religious rule. The ancient Indian social system was based on the then-Vedic precepts; Which are now known as Hindu laws. In the middle, it has been misused in various ways. For example, in Vedic India women had equal rights and respect in all matters. They could participate in everything from education to priesthood and worship and other activities of society. But later they were deprived of that right. Today in the present era free minded modern society has again introduced laws aimed at women's rights. And this women's law comes from the Vedic age. There was no traditional caste system in Vedic India. The social system of that time was divided into Brahmins, Kshatriyas, Vaishyas, and Shudras on the basis of work. But in the Middle Ages that varnashrama became customary and the first three classes of society began to exploit the deprived class. In independent India, laws were made for the rights of the deprived class. In the main paper it will be discussed in a long way.

Conclusion: Vedic Law is scientific still modern era

Keywords

1 Vedic Law

2 Misuse

3 Medievalism

4 Rights

5 Modern Perspective

Area: Religion, Culture

41 - Compatible with critical peace education? A reflexive thematic analysis of the European youth programme Erasmus+

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Introduction

This paper looks at explicit and implicit assumptions and key concepts that the European Commission's youth programme, Erasmus+, brings to bear on its beneficiaries. With its emphasis on non-formal education (NFE), Erasmus+ is handy funding and support also for organisations that work with various forms of peace education (PE).

Currently, in academic circles, there is a call on peace education practitioners to reflect on how their work is positioned within critical positions and structures, such as political economy, state interests, and identity (Kester et al., 2021). This challenge builds on critical peace education (CPE), which asks us to challenge and critique the social order, question guiding concepts, and interrogate other forms of power (Bajaj & Brantmeier, 2011; Hajir, 2019).

To put the Erasmus+ programme to the test, this paper compiles a data set comprising key guiding documents of Erasmus+ to set up a reflexive thematic analysis. This forms the structure of a discussion that revolves around the driving research question: *Which tensions exist between the Erasmus+ programme and critical peace education, and what could such tensions mean to beneficiaries involved in peace education?*

Literature review

Peace education, in short, is the combination of content, pedagogy, and theory that stimulates competence development that contributes towards peace (Brantmeier, 2009; Hantzopoulos & Williams, 2017). It is interrelated to other forms of education, including human rights education and citizenship education (Hantzopoulos & Bajaj, 2021; Kester et al., 2021). Recently, the field has drifted towards a focus on structural causes of violence, known as critical peace education (Bajaj & Brantmeier, 2011; Hantzopoulos & Bajaj, 2021). CPE directs its primary emphasis to deep interrogations of power.

Many have argued that PE must be freed from the format of schools. Freire (1970) critiqued traditional, instructional forms of education, arguing that students become passive, uncritical receivers of knowledge. Harris (2002) has argued that education must be connected to a wider social reality to be effective. And Bar-Tal (2002) states that only through experiential learning can values, skills and attitudes be internalised, and behavioural tendencies challenged.

Youth work, and other organisation approaches provides one avenue for a wider social reality, through non-formal education. NFE draws on elements of both formal education and informal learning, and is construed as a holistic means of learning. Being semi-structured, voluntary, interactive, and participant-centred, it engages participants on a cognitive, practical, and attitudinal level (Brander et al., 2021) – or engaging the head, the hand, and the heart, as it is sometimes articulated.

The primary approach of NFE in European youth work, including projects supported by Erasmus+, is experiential learning. According to Kolb's (2015) cycle of experiential learning, the active experience comes first, followed by a debriefing or reflection around observations and potential take-aways from the experience. Ultimately the aim is to widen the gaze and try to generalise what the findings could mean in real life, and how they can be put into practice.

The Erasmus+ programme has supported mobility projects for young people since the 1980s. The programme currently covers 33 programme countries, with many more partner countries (European Commission, 2022). The programme primarily aims to be an instrument for lifelong learning, which will contribute to “sustainable growth, quality jobs and social cohesion, to driving innovation, and to strengthening European identity and active citizenship” (European Commission, 2022, p. 6).

Evaluation and monitoring of Erasmus+ funded projects indicate that they lead to increased participation, appreciation of cultural diversity, and a commitment to work against discrimination, intolerance, and racism, to name a few aspects (Böhler et al., 2022). But others have pointed out that the impact is often ‘soft’ due to the limited time perspective, which hardly allows for a good connection with issues of structural injustice (Brown, 2018, p. 94).

Methodology

To frame the discussion, and to identify tensions in the juxtaposition of Erasmus+ and critical peace education, I draw on a qualitative, critical framework of reflexive thematic analysis (TA) (Braun & Clarke, 2022). The data comes from the official programme guide of Erasmus+, and official European Union (EU) strategy documents that in some way inform or instruct Erasmus+. This review reveals guidelines, prompts, and incentives provided through the funding scheme. Within the Erasmus+ programme guide, I limit my inquiry to the two project types that cover youth exchanges and training courses.

Having worked closely within the framework of Erasmus+ for nearly a decade, I bring with me a high level of familiarity with the data material. However, I have selected and read programme documents carefully, and coded the relevant bits after several passes at the material. The coded segments that remain, capture the essence of what particular bits of the documents are about (Braun & Clarke, 2022), and the codes contribute to the patterns that form the final themes around which the discussion revolves.

Subjectivity is unavoidable in deciding what to highlight in the data material, but in reflexive TA, this is considered a desirable trait (Braun & Clarke, 2022, p. 12). Seeking to provide an understanding of the realities that spring from the dataset, I lean actively on my situated knowledge as a practitioner of the field, applying a contextual epistemology to see what I see based on my own experience (ibid, 2022, p. 185).

Findings

The review and coding of the selected data material have led to three themes that relate a coherent and concise story of Erasmus+ that merits scrutiny when held up against CPE.

T1: Building participants' life skills to cope in a changing world...

At its core, Erasmus+ is about improving the competences of its participants (European Commission, 2022, p. 4). It mentions specifically social and intercultural competences, critical thinking, and media literacy (European Commission, 2022, p. 10), with a further aim of empowering people to participate in democratic life and civic platforms of engagement.

The programme also prioritises competences linked to green change and digitalisation, and states that participants are the ones who are to become actors for social change. This acknowledges the fluid nature of society and encourages participants to stay in the loop of what is current in the continent and beyond. Erasmus+ promotes lifelong learning, with emphasis on language skills and other competences that facilitate international cooperation.

T2: ...by including as many diverse people as possible...

Diversity is heavily emphasised as a strength of the overarching European project. This also shows in the prioritisation of the Erasmus+ programme., which aims to incorporate a plurality of voices, including young people with fewer opportunities, whether social, economic, geographic, or other (European Commission, 2022, p. 139). There is also a nod to migratory phenomena, adding to the diversity.

The other side of the diversity coin is inclusion. Erasmus+ contains various mechanisms to facilitate young people's inclusion, despite being at a disadvantage financially, geographically, in need of language assistance, accompanying persons, or other challenges. Support is also offered to organisations that are involved in work with young people who require something more than the norm.

T3: ...to create unity and cohesion.

A key part of the rationale of Erasmus+ is that the competences in focus, and the ensuing empowerment, benefit the EU as a whole. In other words, it is an investment into the future of the union. The programme guide holds that a deepened understanding of the EU and what it represents, fosters a sense of ownership or belonging among participants (European Commission, 2022, p. 10). A sense of European identity is an important building block to help the regional body function better (ibid, 2022, p. 4).

The logic goes that active participation leads to a sense of ownership, which in turn means that people will be invested in the idea of a regional block of exchange, cooperation, and integration. With formulations like 'EU common values' (ibid, 2022, p. 4; 14), and 'common priorities' (ibid, 2022, p. 12), Erasmus+ deals a full hand of universalisms to its beneficiaries.

Discussion

Critical theories, in a wide sense, can be considered as "all theories of society that subject its object to critical examination" (Keet, 2020, p. 21). They are meant to clarify the emancipatory potential in the object in question. This thinking has grabbed hold of peace education too over the years. CPE raise issues including neoliberal rationality (Gruber & Scherling, 2020), post-structural violence (Kester & Cremin, 2017), and a general mitigation of asymmetrical power relations by centring context and agency (Hantzopoulos & Bajaj, 2021, p. 28).

Competence development is a key aspect of European youth work, in general (T1). By competences, we typically refer to values, attitudes, skills, and knowledge (Council of Europe, 2016). But the rationale for competence development goes beyond just learning for the individual's sake. Rather, individuals are afforded such opportunities, as per the Erasmus+ programme, to become better equipped to participate actively in democratic life (T3). As a form of grease for the cogs of a transnational, regional appliance.

Beneficiaries, such as organisations, tend to be in it for a different impact, such as increased awareness and critical reflection of participants, which will ultimately contribute to combatting social injustice (Brown, 2018). Such steps are important in that they open up a dialogue, imploring participants to reflect, and then act. However, it remains a sticking point

that non-formal PE projects funded by Erasmus+, are often one-off events, leading to 'soft' outcomes, consisting mainly of individual behavioural changes (ibid, 2018, p. 91). This limited time aspect is in tension with structurally oriented approaches such as CPE.

A core aspect of NFE is that anyone can contribute to, and benefit from a learning setting. Erasmus+ rewards involvement or inclusion of the target group in all mobility projects. This is to encourage young people to engage and learn to participate in civil society (T2), which, in turn, strengthens the cohesion of the union (T3). But there are critics of such a rosy view. Costas Batlle (2019) highlights that organisations are given to compete for funding, therefore having to shape their ideas to fit in with the criteria of the sources of funding. Cremin (2016) considers it a crisis of PE praxis that funders' agendas drive the efforts implicitly or explicitly. One of the main challenges with this, is that values and viewpoints may stand as universal. In Erasmus+, some of these leanings are quite explicit when we see mentions of 'European values' (T3).

PE is generally dominated by Western-centric thought and programming (Gittins, 2019; Kurian & Kester, 2019), manifested through the assumption that democracy, capitalism, human rights, and international law are sufficient conditions for a just peace (Kester et al., 2021). There are critiques of such universalities, however, giving caution also to regional programmes like Erasmus+. Noddings (2012, p. 56) holds that the imposition of values onto others is a failed form of cosmopolitanism, terming it, instead, a form of exceptionalism.

Bwanyire (2016, p. 22) leans the other way, arguing that 'the core values of peace education are "blind" to culture, race, religion, and gender, among other things'. He calls it a collision between universalism and cultural relativism, and argues that basic, natural, cosmopolitan values exist, largely based on natural rights all human beings have. Tibbitts (2020), reviewing both theoretical and empirical arguments for and against universal values, finds a range of common ground in between. She concludes that there is room for a hybrid approach, which she terms 'qualified universalism' (ibid, 2020, p. 115). This approach could incorporate elements both of universal and particular positions, levying more socialising influence with younger participants, and more critical and reflective styles with older participants.

Gruber and Scherling (2020, p. 21) call for CPE to engage the neoliberal rationality of education, arguing that PE may perpetuate everyday injustices unless delinked from Eurocentric capitalism. With its result-orientedness and economic metrics, neoliberalism effectively elevates the market to be the main moralising mechanism (ibid). Costas Batlle (2019, p. 429), though, finds that NFE, with its flexible nature and focus on caring relationships, offers an educational counterweight to neoliberalism.

Non-formal PE efforts construct a safe space for dialogue, and ask us to cooperate towards common goals, though allowing for many ways of *seeing*. This is an epistemological approach, which assumes that rectifying the lack of the right kind of knowledge is the necessary tonic for issues of peace and conflict (Kester, 2023, p. 5). But there is a need to look more concertedly at ontology, and allow for other ways of *being* for it to qualify as peace education (ibid, 2023). The dominant ontologies in education spring from Western epistemologies, and generally mean being a rational citizen. This is the cue of Erasmus+ too, with beneficiaries being pulled towards a way of *being* that aligns with the value base of the programme (T3). Participants are to be critically thinking so that they participate more effectively in democratic life (T1), and they are to feel ownership to European values, so that the EU becomes or remains a cohesive union (T3).

Although emphasising local context, CPE requests engagement with global phenomena like racism. Such issues of difference could be tackled head on, rather than avoided, as a pedagogy of discomfort (Kester, 2023). That they are brought up explicitly, to challenge

participants to direct their eyes at taken-for-granted assumptions of all kinds. Or, more organically perhaps, peace educators can be prepared to capitalise on teachable moments when they arise, instead of drawing them out explicitly (Verma, 2017, p. 11). Either way, the key word is interruption, to counter totalising discourses, power relationships, and binaries (Hantzopoulos & Bajaj, 2021).

Conclusion

Erasmus+ is an available and constructive platform for funding and support for NFE, including PE projects and activities. This paper acknowledges that fully, but points out, as well, that there is a need for scrutiny of the conditions PE efforts are held to when funded by this programme. As a minimum, this paper has shown that peace education efforts conducted with funding by Erasmus+, require reflexivity on norms of the field, as well as taken-for-granted practices. As pointed out by Cremin (2016), unexamined assumptions may in itself lead to structural or cultural violence, despite those being the exact things the PE effort aims to counter. And there are some weighty aspects accompanying funding from Erasmus+ that require beneficiaries to be alert. Starting off with a term like 'European values' (T3), is in clear tension with CPE.

Furthermore, the reflection journey needs to make a stop to consider inclusion a bit closer. What are the criteria to be included? And at whose expense? Reflection is an integral part of NFE, for participants too. Drawing on Tibbitts' (2020) view on hybrid approach to universalisms, beneficiaries could strive to lean ever-more on critical and reflective pedagogies. They will still be left with participants who learn and improve their competences as individuals, contrary to the overall aim of CPE. And the project basis on which such NFE work takes place still leaves us in 'soft action' terrain, with its limited time aspect (Brown, 2018).

But every journey begins with the first step. The contributions of this paper, with the thematic analysis and discussion, is to promote awareness around such issues, as well as put forward a thinking tool to help see oneself and one's work in a critical light.

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42 - The Psychotherapeutic Value of Abhidhamma Teachings: An Analysis of Emotional Conflict

Aung, Myint Myint

Problem Statement: Individuals suffer emotional conflict when they are torn between intense but incompatible emotions, such as love and hate, or fear of failure and success that results in distress and mental health problems.

Purpose of the Study: This paper is to study unwholesome mental states and overcome emotional conflicts based on the study of the psychotherapeutic value of the Theravada Abhidhamma which is applicability to contemporary societal issues.

Literature or Theory: The Abhidhamma teachings provide a theoretical framework for meditation practice and wisdom. In addition, it offers significant psychotherapeutic value in emotion regulation, cognitive restructuring, and insight.

Research Methods: The methodology involves a first-person approach, a qualitative analysis of relevant texts from the Abhidhamma canon, and a descriptive approach to explore the teachings further.

Summary of Findings: The findings suggest that Abhidhamma teachings can be a valuable tool in helping people to manage emotional conflict, and it offers practical methods to address the causes of it and cultivate positive mental states.

Conclusion: Overall, this study highlights the Psychotherapeutic Value of Buddhist teachings to enhance the effectiveness of psychotherapy and the wellbeing of individuals experiencing emotional conflict. Further research is needed to investigate mental health professionals who have used Buddhist teachings in their practice and to survey individuals who have received therapy based on it.

Keywords

- 1 Psychotherapeutic value
- 2 Emotional conflicts
- 3 Abhidhamma
- 4 Vipassanā meditation
- 5 Mental health

Area: Religion

43 - Post Traumatic Effects and Mental Health of Trafficked Children

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Introduction

Human trafficking is a worldwide offense and an abuse of human rights. Although study has shown that trafficked people have a high incidence of mental disorders and use mental health services, little is known about mental health workers' experiences detecting and caring for trafficked people.

Child trafficking is a type of modern enslavement, a quickly expanding, mutating, and multifaceted system of extreme human exploitation, violence against children, child abuse, and violations of children's rights. Modern slavery and human trafficking (MSHT) is a significant worldwide public health issue, exposing individuals to serious short- and long-term physical, mental, social, developmental, and even hereditary health risks. Human trafficking is described as the recruitment and moving of people for the purpose of exploitation, most often through deception, intimidation, compulsion, or the misuse of vulnerability. Every year, hundreds of thousands of women, men, and children are transported across and within international boundaries to be abused through forced sex work, domestic slavery, and forced labour in sectors ranging from farmland to construction, fishing and forced criminality.

According to the National Crime Records Bureau (NCRB), there were approximately 2,200 instances of child trafficking in 2019, with domestic trafficking accounting for 95% of the cases. According to government statistics, 6,616 people were trafficked, including 2,914 minors. However, advocates believe that the true figure is much higher because many victims do not report their crimes to police, owing to a lack of knowledge about the law or dread of smugglers. According to the National Human Rights Commission, 40,000 children are kidnapped in India each year, with 11,000 remaining unidentified. According to non-governmental organizations, between 12,000 and 50,000 women and children are smuggled into the country each year as part of a flourishing sex trade. Now, KSCF is fighting child exploitation in India, and people all over the globe are rallying behind us.

Review of literature

Ottisova, Livia & Smith, Patrick & Shetty, Hitesh & Stahl, Daniel & Downs, Johnny & Oram, Siân. (2018), in the study - Psychological consequences of child trafficking: An historical cohort study of trafficked children in contact with secondary mental health services stated that, child trafficking is associated with high levels of physical and sexual maltreatment, as well as extended contact with mental health agencies. The most commonly cited symptoms for kidnapped juveniles were post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) (22%), and affective disorders (22%). In this study, they also mentioned that minors who had been trafficked showed a variety of mental health signs and conditions, including high-risk and serious mental illnesses that required inpatient admission. In order to enable prompt recommendations to psychiatric treatment, post-trafficking support groups, children's services, and other organizations that work with kidnapped children should

include mental health assessment in their regular service offerings. It would be advantageous for staff at these services to be educated in how to react to indications of mental anguish and how to help clients obtain primary and supplementary treatment for their mental health **Ottisova, Livia & Smith, Patrick & Shetty, Hitesh & Stahl, Daniel & Downs, Johnny & Oram, Siân. (2018).**

Palines PA, Rabbitt AL, Pan AY, Nugent ML, Ehrman WG (2019), in their study - Comparing mental health disorders among sex trafficked children and three groups of youth at high-risk for trafficking: A dual retrospective cohort and scoping review described that the complicated trauma endured by child sex trafficking survivors can have a variety of consequences and overlap the symptomatology of numerous mental health illnesses. Survivors' adaptive reactions to complicated trauma may result in incorrect mental health condition diagnosis and therapy, delaying access to trauma-focused therapies. There is discussion of alternative explanations and therapies for this complicated dysfunction. High-risk individuals frequently have underlying complicated trauma, which only gets worse during the trafficking experience. **Palines PA, Rabbitt AL, Pan AY, Nugent ML, Ehrman WG (2019).**

Domoney, J., Howard, L.M., Abas, M (2015), in their study - Mental health service responses to human trafficking: a qualitative study of professionals' experiences of providing care mentioned that when giving treatment to trafficking survivors, mental health workers encounter a variety of difficulties, such as coping with social and legal volatility, a lack of involvement, and issues with inter-agency working. Mental health workers could better serve the needs of prospective victims of trafficking if they underwent training to raise knowledge of the problem, support safe and appropriate reactions, and educate employees about the current systems available for exploited people. Additional investigation is required to determine the generalizability of results beyond this inner circle and to examine the methods used by health experts to identify victims. **Domoney, J., Howard, L.M., Abas, M (2015).**

Kiss, L., Pocock, N. S., Naisanguansri, V., Suos, S., Dickson, B., Thuy, D., ... & Zimmerman, C. (2015), in their study- Health of men, women, and children in post-trafficking services in Cambodia, Thailand, and Vietnam: an observational cross-sectional study explained that trafficked men, women, and children were subjected to extensive physical and psychological abuse, resided and worked in exceedingly hazardous circumstances, and reported having significant health issues. the research demonstrates that victims of trafficking have a variety of health requirements, and all post-trafficking support packages should include medical evaluation and treatment to recover victims' physical and mental wellbeing. Support for mental health ought to be viewed as a crucial part of treatment. **Kiss, L., Pocock, N. S., Naisanguansri, V., Suos, S., Dickson, B., Thuy, D& Zimmerman, C. (2015).**

Oram, S., Stöckl, H., Busza, J., Howard, L. M., & Zimmerman, C. (2012) in the study on - Prevalence and risk of violence and the physical, mental, and sexual health problems associated with human trafficking: systematic review indicated that trafficking for sexual abuse is linked to violence and a number of severe health issues. The health of trafficked males, people who have been traded for other forms of abuse, and efficient health intervention strategies all require more study. Despite a sharp rise in awareness of human trafficking over the past ten years, there is still a dearth of data regarding the experiences of abuse and other physical, mental, and sexual health issues among exploited individuals. Trafficking is linked to severe health issues, suggesting that victims of trafficking will probably need a coordinated reaction from medical professionals and other support services. **Oram, S., Stöckl, H., Busza, J., Howard, L. M., & Zimmerman, C. (2012)**

Siân Oram, Mizanur Khondoker, Melanie Abas, Matthew Broadbent, Louise M Howard (2015) in their study on Characteristics of trafficked adults and children with severe mental illness: a historical cohort study stated that the most frequently reported illnesses were PTSD and affective disorders, though schizophrenia and other associated disorders. People who had been trafficked were more likely to be compulsorily committed as psychiatric inpatients and had lengthier stays once under the care of the mental health agency. Although the causes of the extended inpatient stays of patients who have been victims of trafficking are unclear, their complicated social requirements may be a contributing factor. Taking care of social and welfare requirements appears to be crucial in forecasting negative results for trafficked individuals' mental health. Those who have been trafficked and have a variety of conditions, such as psychoses, are treated by mental health agencies. **Siân Oram, Mizanur Khondoker, Melanie Abas, Matthew Broadbent, Louise M Howard (2015).**

Wood LCN (2018), in the study on Child modern slavery, trafficking and health: a practical review of factors contributing to children's vulnerability and the potential impacts of severe exploitation on health stated that child trafficking is an aggressive type of child abuse and a major public health issue on a worldwide scale. The numerous and accumulating negative effects on a child's health brought on by modern-day slavery and trafficking are especially severe due to the harm caused by psychological and physical abuse to the body and growing brain. In order to better understand child pre-trafficking vulnerabilities, victim recognition, successful interventions, and recovery paths, there is a crucial need for additional education, activism, study, and health experts. **Wood LCN (2018).**

Gezie, L.D., Yalew, A.W., Gete, Y.K (2018), in their study on Socio-economic, trafficking exposures and mental health symptoms of human trafficking returnees in Ethiopia: using a generalized structural equation modelling stated that violence-mediated socioeconomic and trafficking-related exposures were variables influencing the signs of mental illness. Therefore, in addition to helping people reintegrate economically, methods to deal with the widespread mental health issues should be developed and put into practice. People who had been kidnapped were very likely to return with more severe cases of PTSD, sadness, and anxiety. Given the high frequency of mental illness, it may be necessary to offer victims of trafficking complete reintegration and protective services, such as psychosocial counseling and mental health therapies in addition to financial and legal support. **Gezie, L.D., Yalew, A.W., Gete, Y.K (2018).**

Yvonne Rafferty (2008) in the study on The Impact of Trafficking on Children: Psychological and Social Policy Perspectives explained that major societal issues include human trafficking and commercial sexual abuse (CSE). The detrimental effects of child trafficking and CSE on children are supported by psychological studies on child abuse and victimization. Additionally, it offers advice for several exercise fields. (e.g., child interviewing, treatment for childhood PTSD, and treatment of sexually reactive behavior. However, much work needs to be done to better understand the ecological, contextual, and global factors connected to child trafficking and CSE because child maltreatment has traditionally been seen more as a clinical issue requiring diagnosis and treatment and less as a social problem. **Yvonne Rafferty (2008).**

Altun S, Abas M, Zimmerman C, Howard LM, Oram S (2017) in their study on - Mental health and human trafficking: responding to survivors' needs indicated that people who have been trafficked frequently experience mental health issues, such as melancholy, anxiety, and post-traumatic stress disorder, and at least some of these individuals seek out supplementary mental health services. Research from various nations demonstrates that among survivors who interact with shelter services, melancholy, anxiety, post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), self-harm, and attempted suicide are prevalent. PTSD, anxiety, and

depressive symptoms were all mentioned. Although traumatic experiences while being trafficked may cause or worsen mental disorders, poor mental health may also increase vulnerability to trafficking due to factors directly related to poor mental health, such as decreased decision-making capacity or understanding and increased reliance on others.

Altun S, Abas M, Zimmerman C, Howard LM, Oram S (2017).

Abas, M., Ostrovschi, N.V., Prince, M (2013), in their study on Risk factors for mental disorders in women survivors of human trafficking: a historical cohort study stated that the mental illnesses, most notably PTSD and melancholy, were likely to be affected by a variety of predisposing, precipitating, and sustaining variables. Care plans for survivors of human trafficking must be tailored to their specific requirements, and professional standards for treating PTSD and melancholy must be followed. Evidence on the efficacy of treatment for PTSD in human trafficking patients is required. **Abas, M., Ostrovschi, N.V., Prince, M (2013).**

Hemmings, S., Jakobowitz, S., Abas, M (2016), in their study on Responding to the health needs of survivors of human trafficking: a systematic review explained that human trafficking is fundamentally an illegal form of severe exploitation and abuse, from which people experience a variety of physical, psychological, and sexual and reproductive health issues. To promote healing from this crime, healthcare workers must be at the forefront of survivors' answers. **Hemmings, S., Jakobowitz, S., Abas, M (2016).**

Ligia Kiss, Nicola S Pocock, Varaporn Naisanguansri, Soksreymom Suos, Brett Dickson, Doan Thuy, Jobst Koehler, Kittiphan Sirisup, Nisakorn Pongrungsee, Van Anh Nguyen, Rosilyne Borland, Poonam Dhavan, Cathy Zimmerman (2015), in their study "Health of men, women, and children in post-trafficking services in Cambodia, Thailand, and Vietnam: an observational cross-sectional study" indicated that people who have been kidnapped will have a variety of health requirements, and that medical evaluation and treatment to recover people's physical and psychological well-being should be included in all post-trafficking support packages. Support for mental health should be regarded an important component of care. Intervention study is required to find successful types of psychological support that are readily applied in low-resource contexts and among multilingual, multicultural populations. **Ligia Kiss, Nicola S Pocock, Varaporn Naisanguansri, Soksreymom Suos, Brett Dickson, Doan Thuy, Jobst Koehler, Kittiphan Sirisup, Nisakorn Pongrungsee, Van Anh Nguyen, Rosilyne Borland, Poonam Dhavan, Cathy Zimmerman (2015).**

Conclusion

Child trafficking is a major public health problem and human rights violation. Child trafficking is described as the recruitment, transit, movement, lodging, or reception of minors for purposes of exploitation. From an analysis of previous literature and articles, researchers found that post-traumatic stress disorder, anxiety, and other mental health problems were consistently reported among child victims of trafficking. I found People with high levels of physical, mental, sexual and emotional health problems are victims of human trafficking and include not only children but also individuals who have experienced similar trauma. High levels of anxiety, depression, and post-traumatic stress disorder are the main problems seen in trafficked children. Child sex trafficking survivors are more likely to suffer complex trauma and are at increased risk of developing mental illness. In addition, studies examining the relationship between trafficking and health found that longer duration of trafficking was associated with higher levels of distress and higher risk of HIV infection. Emotional distress (especially depression) may recede from the initial level, but for many people it leaves a life-altering aftermath after a stressful time. It can affect an individual's sense of control over themselves, their future, and their ability to participate in social

situations. may be injured, develop mental health problems, or be deprived of educational opportunities.

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44 - Implementation of Peace and Gender Education Values in University Management

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Abstract

Good university management must be able to provide broad opportunities for each member of the organization to improve their abilities, recognize member status based on work performance, work according to a code of ethics, and have a high participation rate of members in the decision-making process. This concept is in line with gender values. On the other hand, the demand for peace education is getting higher, due to the awareness that humans exist in a diverse and multicultural existence. Thus, the implementation of university management must be able to implement the values of gender and peace so that the education held will be able to guarantee peaceful education, equality, and equity. If this fails to be done, then education will only give birth to anarchist next generations, which will make this earth even more chaotic and bring destruction. This study aims to analyze the values of gender education (equality, justice, access, participation) and peace (tolerance, collaboration, togetherness, creativity) in higher education management practices. The research was conducted using a qualitative case study approach. The results of this study are the practice of managing tertiary institutions at UNUGHA using the values of gender education and peace education: 1) The values of gender education appear in the form of university regulations and their practices in providing equal opportunities for men and women as leaders and administrators, equal work, equal pay, equal opportunities to be creative in developing work units, curriculum and learning management practices that facilitate tolerant, collaborative, communicative, and creative learning, always participate in the process of making management decisions, 2) value -The values of peace education in the management of tertiary institutions are tolerance, togetherness, prioritizing common interests, helping each other, as well as a creative, collaborative, tolerant, and humble learning process. Thus, at UNUGHA, a comfortable, calm, conducive work climate is created, and no conflicts are found. So, the recommendation from the results of this study is to develop findings on a management model for higher education based on peace and gender education to create a peaceful university climate to foster peace-loving next generations. Thus, the development of the human resource component of the university management plan can and must implement gender education values and promote peace.

Keywords: university management, peace education, gender, equity, equality

Introduction

Problem Statement

The main purpose of this research is to analyze the values of gender and peace education in university management practices.

Research Questions

The research question posed is how is UNUGHA university management practice in the perspective of peace education and gender values?

Research Purpose

This study aims to analyze the values of gender education (equality, justice, access, participation) and peace (tolerance, collaboration, togetherness, creativity) in higher education management practices

Research Rationalization

Good university management must be able to provide broad opportunities for each member of the organization to improve their abilities, recognize member status based on work performance, and work according to a code of ethics. This is because the ability of good members of the organization (university) will contribute to the achievement of the goals and vision of the university. Likewise, the vision of the university will make it easier to achieve its goals and vision of the university (Zulfa, 2020). Thus, universities must work hard to manage their human resources so that they become human capital for their organizations. To ensure the achievement of these goals, universities must evaluate the performance of their human resources (Byars, 1991) which is then used as an instrument to determine their status. The level of their status in the organization will be determined by their work performance (Ornstein, 2012). Apart from determining HR status based on competency and good performance (Dharma, 1985), (Rivai, 2009), what is no less important is HR working according to a code of ethics. This means that human resources must work professionally by using the minimum work standards set by the university and their expectations exceed the standards set (Wirawan, 2019).

Based on this opinion, there are three important points that can be obtained, namely: equality and access (; the contribution of each individual and performance work), fairness (; status based on work and professional performance). This is in accordance with the values of gender education. This means that a tertiary institution whose postscript is a higher education institution in its management must adhere to the values of gender itself. Without this, the university not only betrays the gender values that must be upheld by the university but also betrays the general concept of management itself.

On the other hand, to create a peaceful world, all components on this earth, including universities, must be able to spread peace. In accordance with the vision of education, universities must be able to organize peace education or internalize peace education values such as tolerance, collaboration, togetherness, and creativity. An internalization is a form of propaganda and information strategy from peace education (Morisson, 2013). whereas university management that is responsive to gender is relatively successful if it is supported by individual potential, building a strong financial system, patterns of power relations, and local culture (Mufliha Wijayati (1*), 2022).

Based on observations, educational practices are still found that conflict with the values of gender education and peace education, such as stereotypes that men are superior to women in jobs that require labor such as the field, verbal violence even under the pretext of joking, distrust of women's ability to occupy positions certain activities, conducting certain events, relatively lacking cooperation if the activity is chaired by a woman, lack of support for developing creativity. More specifically, in the management of students, there are still those who use gender bias models and gender-neutral models (Sumar, 2015).

As for gender in the context of management, the results of her research can be seen (Poppy Nurmayanti, 2021) states that organizations dominated by women at the management and administrative levels tend to practice transformational leadership. Elsewhere the success of gender mainstreaming (gender responsive budgeting) at IAIN Metro (Muflaha Wijayati (1*), 2022). To be able to realize this, the government's role is very important in making related policies such as gender mainstreaming policies. In the context of Indonesia, the President has issued a Presidential Instruction (Inpres) regarding Gender Mainstreaming (RI, 2009).

Based on this background, it shows that whatever the context, applying gender values and peace education is very important in all areas of human life. Moreover, specifically, the practice of gender-based university management and peace education based on previous research studies is still very rare. Departing from this reason, this research was conducted.

Literature Review

1. University Management

Good university management must be able to provide broad opportunities for each member of the organization to improve their abilities, recognize member status based on work performance, and work according to a code of ethics. This also means that every individual is male, male or female, old or young. Especially when talking in the context of gender and power in management, it means talking about management and transformational leadership which contrasts with transactional leadership (B. Bagilhole, 2011).

Several cases show that creating university management with a gender perspective still needs a long struggle. In Australia, South Africa, and Portugal, for example, while women as senior managers have an increased capacity to influence decision-making in managerial universities, particularly with regard to 'soft' management skills, these are not valued in competitive management cultures (Kate White, 2011).

University management is the core of university administration. While the core of university management is leadership. In leadership, the core is the policy-making process (Rifa'i, 2016). In the process of making good decisions and being able to produce effective decisions, management must involve every individual in the organization through certain work mechanisms. It is in this decision-making process that it is important to pay attention to gender values and peace education because it will affect the entire university management process starting from planning, organizing, staffing, directing, coordinating, reporting, and budgeting (POSDeCoRB) from Luther Gullick. Incorporating gender values and peace education starts from the university planning process with Gender Mainstreaming as well as planning in specific areas such as planning in curriculum management, human resource management, education financing management, management of educational infrastructure, and so on.

2. Gender and Gender Education Values

Gender is an issue that is timeless. Universities as large institutions consisting of large people, who have broad insight and a high level of awareness relatively easy to implement gender values in their campus managerial processes. Moreover, the university is an institution of higher education, so it is appropriate to carry out education from a gender perspective. This means that education on campus should implement gender values such as equality, justice, access, and participation (Khotimah, 2008), not discrimination, inclusive (Indriyani, 2021) compassion, materialism, meaning et al (Marini, 1995).

3. Peace Education

Peace Education is considered to be both philosophy and process involving skills, including listening, reflection, problem-solving, cooperation, and conflict resolution (Harris, 2002). Peace education hopes to create in the human consciousness a similar, if not greater, commitment to the ways of peace. Peace education values such as justice, non-violence (thoughts, words, attitudes, behaviors, actions, various systems and structures that protect the environment and humans), balance (justice by sharing), positive thinking, tolerance, mutual respect, fair competition, love, and so on (Santoso, 2021).

In its implementation, there are three categories, namely: peace education in intractable conflicts in the region, peace education in the region of interethnic tension, and peace education of experienced tranquility peace education in region interethnic tension, and peace education of experienced tranquility (Salomon, 2002). In the university context, the implementation of peace education falls into the third category.

Methodology

This research was conducted using a qualitative approach with case studies. Case studies are used as a qualitative research design to evaluate events or situations in real situations to gain an understanding and human behavior based on different values, beliefs, and scientific theories (Polit, 2004). Research conducted at UNUGHA Cilacap was carried out with qualitative data collection methods using in-depth interviews, observation participants, and documentation (Creswell, 2012: 212-223), and then the data were analyzed using an interactive analysis model from Miles – Huberman (Miles, 1994). The subjects of this study were divided into three categories, namely leader or manager, faculties and staff personnel of the university, and students. The subjects of the leader or manager group are student program heads, deans, vice-rectors, rectors, and heads of work units.

Findings

1. Gender Education Values in UNUGHA Management Practices

Indonesia is a country that is very concerned about gender issues. This can be seen from several regulations issued by the government, including a) National Education Office Number 84 of 2008 concerning Guidelines for Implementation of Gender Mainstreaming in the Education Sector. Permendiknas Number 84 stipulates, and b) Instruction of the President of the Republic of Indonesia on Gender Mainstreaming (RI, 2009).

According to these regulations, UNUGHA Management Practices that are in line with gender education values include planning and regulation, implementation, monitoring, and evaluation.

First. In the planning aspects of the university, for example, gender education values are found, namely a) Academic policies regulate prospective new students who must provide equal opportunities to men and women, regional origin, ethnicity, religion, disabled groups, b) awarding scholarships to groups financially disadvantaged, campus warriors, achievers, c) in the field of human resources, for example, giving equal opportunities to all members of the university, both male and female, to enter the selection market for these positions, such as positions as vice-chancellor, dean, head of study program, and unit other work as well as a career as a professional lecturer starting from the academic position of expert assistant to professor or professor, d) Development Strategic Plan and Master Plan that are globally and internationally oriented in the context of scope dimensions and international issues including gender issues, e) university budget that is does not discriminate against certain gender groups.

Second. Implementation. The leaders from the university level to the study program totaling 4 rectorate heads (1 person), 5 deans (1 person), 16 study programs (8 people), 11 work units other than faculties (6 people) there are 16 women from 36 managers (44, 44%). Besides that, in actual implementation, it is a function of organizing and actuating management. In practice, it also provides equal pay according to equal pay for equal work (Ornstein, 2012), (Rivai, 2009), and equal opportunities to be creative in developing work units, and curricula with a gender perspective, both in the form of documents based on gender-appropriate core values. , research with a gender perspective has begun to appear, although not too much (; career women's management, women's leadership, MSME community empowerment, *KRIKTo* learning models, and so on), and learning management that starts from planning lessons based on gender-congruent values, practices that facilitate tolerant, collaborative, communicative, and creative learning, and all leaders at the study program level up to the university level always participate in the management decision-making process, so that they feel involved so that awareness grows to make the results of these decisions successful for the progress of UNUGHA.

Third. Monitoring and Evaluation. Monitoring, especially through quality audits of work units and study programs, BKD assessments, assessment of academic ranks and functional positions of lecturers, and measurement of lecturer performance by students is part of efforts to maintain, oversee and justify the successful implementation of university program planning through their long arms (work units and study programs).

Based on the data display and discussion above, what has been practiced at UNUGHA in the university management process is relevant to the values of gender education. The values referred to are: all university regulations, equal opportunities for men and women to be elected as leaders and administrators, opportunities to obtain the same job, and earn the same wages, and equal opportunities to be creative in developing work units, curriculum with a gender perspective, and learning management, practices that facilitate tolerant, collaborative, communicative, and creative learning, always participate in management decision-making processes.

To realize university management practices that are relevant to gender values, or the endemic term is the implementation of Tri Dharma PT with a Gender perspective is relatively easier to do due to the following factors: 1(the values of gender education are in line (corresponding) to UNUGHA's Core Values, namely the Core Values of *Ghazalianity* in the value aspect, 2) policies for implementing higher education with a gender perspective, 3) Some gender fighters whose postscript is the management of the Center for Gender Studies (PSG UNUGHA) are also management actors at the university level, work units to study programs, so that it makes it easier for the movement to struggle according to PSG's mission, namely to provide education and teaching with a gender perspective, carrying out research with a gender perspective and carrying out community service with a gender perspective and 4) 44.44% of managers are women, so it is relatively easy to transform a gender perspective in their actions, without denying that men have a gender equality mindset.

2. Peace Education Values in UNUGHA Management Practices

Some of UNUGHA's management practices that are consistent with gender values include: a) **Tolerances.** It can be seen from the philosophy of the Foundation (*"Dadia wong sing bisa ngengken"*: being able to hold back), the value of tolerance itself is in the values of ghazalianity which is a guide in carrying out the daily activities of leaders, faculty staff and students. Differences of opinion are only in the process of meetings, decision-making processes, lecturer discussions, student discussions, and differences of opinion between students and lecturers in learning, only part of the process of making an agreement and at

the same time practicing the value of *tawadlu* in religious values as well, namely submission to the truth, through Al Ghazali's epistemology, i.e. Shak, **b) Based on this also, the value of peace education in the form of tolerance is an embodiment of the values of self-restraint, tawadlu, and syak as part of the core values of ghazalism as well, c) Togetherness.** This value is implemented in the decision-making process by prioritizing the value of togetherness, such as making top management decisions, selecting committee chairs, making decisions on students who have not paid tuition fees but are still given waivers, and appreciating the founders and others, d) **Prioritizing common interests.** Similar to togetherness, small and big decisions prioritize common interests. This is more to technical considerations, derived from togetherness, e) **Helping each other.** The division of main tasks and functions is carried out, but in the context of a team/system, everyone on campus must help each other. Example: forming a study program accreditation team, nearly 50% of which come from outside the study program. Likewise for examination committees, graduations, and general stadiums which incidentally are in the academic field, involving non-academic people, and vice versa, f) **As well as creative.** Each individual lecturer and leader is given the freedom to be creative in order to improve their performance. Lecturers must be creative in finding new sources of funding for research and community service activities, and creative in using new learning resources. Likewise, heads of study programs, deans, heads of institutions, vice-chancellors up to the chancellor must also be creative in finding new strategies, creatively seeking new and abundant funding sources, creating high-quality performance achievements for their work units, for example for annual performance appraisals and for the importance of external performance appraisal such as accreditation, g) **Collaborative.** Collaboration is carried out in the context of university management and work units to achieve their vision. Whereas in the learning aspect, collaboration must be carried out between students in learning facilitated by their lecturers. Collaboration can also be carried out by lecturers and lecturers, lecturers and students in research activities and community service, and h) **Humble.** The manifestation of humility in management practices at UNUGHA can be seen in the absence of absolute truth in the review process to make decisions by management. All perspectives are considered. Likewise in the context of science. All lecturers appreciate the scientific truth of other lecturers' fields of science. Plus, in the management of learning in the classroom, the truth does not have to come from the lecturer but it can come from the students, so they respect each other. There is no term seniority based on age but based on the truth itself and the way to reach the truth.

Based on this data, it can be seen that management practices at UNUGHA have implemented the values of gender education and peace education at the same time. This is not only because it has become a university policy, and also because these values are already in line with the core values of Ghazalianism, making it easier to implement. Through it, UNUGHA is able to create a work climate that is comfortable, calm, conducive, and where there is no conflict.

Summary, Conclusion, and Recommendations

Summary

Based on the results of research and discussion it can be concluded as follows: 1) The values of gender education appear in the form of university regulations and their practices in providing equal opportunities for men and women as leaders and administrators, equal work, equal pay, and equal opportunities to be creative in developing work units, curriculum, and learning management practices that facilitate tolerant, collaborative, communicative, and creative learning, always participate in the process of making management decisions, and 2) The values of peace education in the management of a university are tolerance, togetherness, prioritizing common interests, and helping each other, as well as a creative,

collaborative, tolerant, and humble learning process. Thus, at UNUGHA, a comfortable, calm, conducive work climate is created, and no conflicts are found. So, the recommendation from the results of this study is to develop findings on a management model for higher education based on peace and gender education to create a peaceful university climate to foster peace-loving next generations.

Conclusion

UNUGHA has implemented gender values and peace education within the context of its university management.

Recommendations

By knowing that UNUGHA has implemented the values of gender education and peace education in the context of managing its university, in the future the development of the human resource component of the university's management plan can and must implement gender values. education and promote peace, and in the future researchers to develop gender-based universities. peace management and education models.

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45 - Casteism in India - Conflicts

Faustin, Britney

Belinda, R

Problem Statement: Identifying and establishing a link to the cause of economic disparity due to caste discrimination.

Purpose of the Study: Investigating the negative impact and influence of casteism in the socioeconomic sphere of the Indian population / Qualitative

Literature or Theory: Discrimination in educational institutions, favoritism in labour market, poorly paid jobs between high and low castes, tremendously impacting the economic and occupational mobility causing socio-economic suppression.

Research Methods: Qualitative analysis followed by chi square test.

Summary of Findings: The study concludes that there is a high correlation between caste, educational qualification, income level and economic status.

Conclusion Though: there are a plenty of schemes for the underprivileged sections of the society, the caste system has been a hindrance to the lower section of the society.

Keywords

- 1 Caste discrimination
- 2 Economic status
- 3 Labour market inequality
- 4 Indian economy
- 5 Wage gaps

Area: Justice and Peace

46 – The Role of Service Learning in Building Inner Peace in Students

Rajarathnam, Belinda

Problem Statement: Students when involved in productive work, they will be occupied and will not land up in activities which will disturb their inner peace.

Purpose of the Study: This paper is an attempt to study the role of service learning in building inner peace in students. Inner peace is peace of mind or soul. It is a state of calm, serenity and tranquility of mind that arise due to having no sufferings or mental disturbances such as worry, anxiety, greed, desire, hatred, ill-will, delusion and/or other defilements. The Global Risk Report projects that the youth of today are prone to deterioration of mental health, leaving 80% of young people across the globe vulnerable to depression, anxiety and disillusionment, and making them targets for radicalization.

Literature or Theory: Service learning combines service to the community with student learning in a way that improves both the student and the community. Service-learning improves academic and social outcomes of students by establishing opportunities to apply academic knowledge to everyday problems/issues. Research proves that service-learning has a positive effect on attendance and drop-out rates, academic and civic engagement, reducing youth risk behaviors, reducing discipline problems and betterment of school and classroom climate.

Research Methods: This paper is an attempt to study the role of service learning in building inner peace in students through structured interviews from Five teachers in-charge of service learning and Ten students who undergo service learning.

Summary of Findings: This paper will be able to establish that inner peace can be built in the youth by involving them in community related welfare activities.

Conclusion: This paper will be able to establish the positive peace which can be built in youth by involving in service-learning activities.

Keywords

- 1 Service Learning
- 2 Inner Peace
- 3 Students
- 4 Community work by students
- 5 Peace building in youth

Area: Justice and Peace; Education

47 - Gender Inequity Associated with Increased Child Abuse and Neglect in Rural Economy

Hendry, Asha Belinda, R

Problem Statement: Child abuse can be physical, sexual or emotional. Neglect, or not providing for a child's needs, is also a form of abuse. The efforts to prevent child abuse and neglect might benefit from reducing gender inequity.

Purpose of the Study: The researches show the strong associations between childhood abuse frequency and gender, especially in rural setting due people are more vulnerable. The illiteracy and other societal factors contribute to it. This neglections can cause in the escaping of the actual culprit and victim blaming.

Literature or Theory: child maltreatment interventions targeting individual-and family-level risk factors have led to declines in child physical abuse, prevention efforts that focus on societal-level risk factors like gender inequity would theoretically have a greater and more sustained impact on child maltreatment rates.

<https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10896-017-9925-4>

Research Methods: A critical analysis of previous review of literature

Summary of Findings” Gender inequality does exist in child abuse and neglect in rural economy. Women face a higher risk of abuse and neglect in rural setting.

Conclusion: The complex traumas suffered by the children can impact numerous effects on them in many ways especially mentally and physically.

Keywords

- 1 Child abuse
- 2 Gender inequality
- 3 Rural economies
- 4 Perception
- 5 Justice

Area: Justice and Peace

48 - The Implementation of Peace Education in English for Guidance and Counseling Students of UNUGHA Indonesia

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Abstract

Bullying still becomes an issue in Indonesia recently whether in the form of verbal or non-verbal bullying. Unfortunately, it prevalent happens at school and university. The latest data from Komisi Perlindungan Anak (Child Protection) shows that 81 cases of bullying at school occurred from January until October 2022. To prevent and even stop this issue, it can be carried out through education since it is an effective way to spread peace. Therefore, it is needed to infuse peace education in Indonesia's education curriculum, including English curriculum. This study investigates the implementation and values of peace education in English for Guidance and Counseling students of UNUGHA Indonesia. A descriptive qualitative method was used in this study. Data collection techniques used were observation, interview, and documents. The data was analyzed using descriptive analysis. This study revealed that the teaching methods, materials, and lesson plan used by the lecturer in English classroom has integrated peace education themes such as learn to live together, think critically, respect human dignity as well as be compassionate and do not harm.

Key Terms: Bullying, peace education, English

Introduction

Problem Statement

Bullying still becomes an issue in Indonesia recently whether in the form of verbal or non-verbal bullying. Unfortunately, it prevalent happens at school and university. The latest data from Komisi Perlindungan Anak (Child Protection Committee) shows that 81 cases of bullying at school occurred from January until October 2022. To prevent and even stop this issue, it can be carried out through education since it is an effective way to spread peace. Therefore, it is needed to infuse peace education in Indonesia's education curriculum, including English curriculum.

Language teaching can be contextualized in any field. Since words became tools of communication, everyone can share their ideas, culture and knowledge in English. Education promotes critical thinking about cross-cultural understanding and aspects of local and world cultures. It promotes popularization and significant diversion of linguistic and cultural knowledge in English (Guilherme, 2007).

Research Questions

The research questions are shown as below:

1. How is the implementation of peace education in English for Guidance and Counseling students of UNUGHA Indonesia?

Research Purpose (or Objectives for Quantitative Papers)

This research investigates the implementation of peace education in English for Guidance and Counseling students of UNUGHA Indonesia.

Literature Review

Bullying

UNESCO (2017) defines bullying as unwanted and aggressive behavior by school-age children in which there is a real or perceived power imbalance. Behavior can be repeated over time. Meanwhile, Dan Olweus (1993), a pioneer and expert in bullying and perpetratorization states that bullying is a specific form of deliberate and intentional aggression that creates an imbalance of power between the victim and the perpetrator. and repeats over time. In other words, bullying is repeated aggressive behavior that leads to power imbalance. Bullying is persistent and intentional abuse in relationships through repeated physical (hitting, pushing), verbal (insults, name-calling), non-verbal or emotional bullying (social exclusion, intimidation using gestures, spreading rumors) and cyberbullying (using technology such as the Internet, email, cell phones, to harass or torment someone).

Suellen and Fried (1996) mention the characteristics of bullying. First, intent to harm. The perpetrator enjoys mockery and continues even when the victim's plight is obvious. Second, intensity and duration. Teasing lasts for a long time and the level of provocation hurts the victim's self-esteem. Third, perpetrator power. Perpetrators retain power based on their age, strength, size, and/or gender. Fourth, victim vulnerability. Victims have physical or psychological traits that make them more vulnerable, being more sensitive to teasing, unable to defend themselves well. The fifth is lack of support. Victims feel isolated and exposed. Victims are often afraid to report abuse for fear of reprisal. Last, consequences. The damage to the self-concept is long lasting and the effects on the victim lead to withdrawal and aggressive behavior.

Peace Education

Peace education is a global effort to change the way people think and act to promote peace, and education is an important tool in promoting peace in the world (UNICEF, 1999). Harris (2002) sets goals for effective peace education programs such as: appreciation for peace, understanding of acts of violence, development of cross-cultural understanding, teaching of social justice, respect for life. Salomon (2002) proposes his four categories of peace education as "changing mindsets, developing different skills and attitudes conducive to peace, promoting human rights" and finally "promoting a culture of environmental protection, disarmament and peace" (p. 4).

The peace education curriculum emphasizes that peace education students must learn and practice the basic concepts of peace education. Peace Education provides a curriculum in which students learn and practice concepts such as: Respect for Human rights, social responsibility, rule of law, democratic attitudes. It fosters the acceptance of cultural diversity and equality as an integral part of the curriculum. Peace education content focuses on teaching the values of freedom, equality and respect for the global community (Yemenchi, 2016). Peace education students learn knowledge about specific peace values, such as personal well-being, human rights, diversity, conflict resolution skills, democratic attitudes and social justice (Carter, 2015). Knowledge of the values of peace prepares students to acquire and practice the skills and attitudes necessary to become peaceful person.

UNESCO (2001) suggests a model of peace education that contains 10 themes as basic characteristics of a peaceful person, including: (a) **Think positive**, it is intended to develop a positive mindset; (b) **Be compassionate and do not harm**, it tries to instill empathetic qualities such as love, kindness, friendliness and so on; (c) **Discover inner peace**, it deals with resolving psychological conflicts and problems and finding peace of mind; (d) **Learn to live together**, learn to cooperate with others in a group including: share, help each other, build trust, take group responsibility, lead and follow to reduce students' selfish competitive tendencies; (e) **Respect human dignity**, it seeks to build awareness of recognizing and respecting someone's own rights and others' rights; (f) **Be your true self**, it means the strength of character to express one's needs, feelings and thoughts honestly and without disappointing others; (g) **Developing critical thinking**, it concerns problem-solving skills, decision-making skills, analysis, syntheses, looking at the other sides of an issue, searching for alternatives and logical thinking; (h) **Resolve conflict non-violently**, it includes the skills necessary for conflict resolution, such as conflict analysis, negotiation, active listening, mediation, creative problem solving, and finding alternative solutions; (i) **Build peace in community**, it provides students with opportunities to engage with social realities, understand people's problems, and work with them; (j) **Care for the planet**, under this theme, some interesting activities, projects and assignments can be organized in schools.

Peace Education in English Classroom

Foreign language education can provide an ideal opportunity for peace education. Asking youngster what they can do to make peace in a global context in language classes like English classes can be an important first step in encouraging peacemaking efforts (Walker et al, 2008). This will lead to a "social transformation of schools and their communities in which people accept and adapt to the needs of others" (Carter, 2002). The progressive expansion of participation in the moral universe is an important goal of peace education, and because empathic opposition to violence is essential, this also creates an atmosphere of empathy (Duckworth et al., 2012). Tulgar (2017) revealed that generations receiving peace education in schools, especially in foreign language classes that allow flexibility in course content, may be more aware and persistent in the peaceful approach. Peace education interventions continue to be successful in achieving their goals (Bashir and Akbar, 2021). Therefore, educational institutions need to integrate peace education in schools (Bhat and Jamatia, 2022).

Methodology

The research methodology used in this study was descriptive qualitative research. Descriptive qualitative research produced data that describe "who, what, where, an event or experience" from a subjective perspective (Kim et al., 2017, p. 23). It was aimed at providing or explaining the conditions or phenomena that arise when scientific procedures were used to actually solve problems. Moreover, it attempted to explain existing conditions and relationships, evolving opinions, ongoing processes, effects and impacts occurring, or ongoing trends (Sukmadinata, 2006). This research was focus on English subject for the second semester students of Guidance and Counseling of Teacher Training and Education Faculty, University of Nahdlatul Ulama Al Ghazali (UNUGHA) Cilacap Regency, Central Java Province, Indonesia. Observation, interview, and documentation are used in this research. The data analysis technique used in this research was a non-statistical method, namely descriptive data analysis, meaning that the data obtained through research on the implementation of peace education was reported as it was and then analyzed descriptively to get a picture of the facts.

Findings

The implementation of peace education in English for Guidance and Counseling students of UNUGHA Indonesia

Arikan (2009) stated the relationship between peace education and foreign language education could be found in these more recent education forms of theory and practice as foreign language teaching began to question the individual's place in the social and natural environment. Teachers could contextualize English materials from the environment and society.

Teachers should choose a topic related to the material being discussed. In this case, the lecturer chose a discussion text which discussed controversial issues. The issue could derive from both offline and online news. These authentic materials could deliver real and natural knowledge, abilities and skills. Thus, these were needed to be developed or prepared for educational purposes as lecturer could easily create peace concepts materials for teaching and learning in the English Classroom. One of them was critical thinking. By having critical thinking, the students are expected to care about their society and finally have a contribution to their society.

In addition, students felt like they were in real-life situations when contextual materials such as peace, and social issues were integrated in the English classes. They understood emotions and states and learned something other than structural sentences, vocabulary and academic writing. Promoting the concept of peaceful living by integrating peace education into the English classes has resulted in new experiences and learning from different perspectives and sharpened the sensibilities of students.

In the process of integrating peace education, the way a teacher or lecturer teaches was more important than what he/she taught. Classroom activities should seek to ensure that students understand and were taught about their traditions they need to know to fulfill their civic responsibilities. The teaching method was specifically used to support learning and is intended to link knowledge, skills and attitudes in peace education. It gave a portrait of peaceful living, harmony, diversity and mutual respect. Students were expected to respond to global issues such as war, peace, conflict and violence. In addition, students were able to give solutions to social problems they face in order to create a better and more peaceful life.

From the observation, some teaching methods were used by the English lecturer of UNUGHA to promote peace. First, Collaborative Learning. Students worked in groups of two or more to seek understanding, solutions, or meaning together, or to create a product. In this case, the lecturer divided students into groups of four people. They were asked to seek issues that were currently viral or controversial that could be discussed in discussion text. The group work would make the students learn about cooperation and togetherness since they did the task together. It indicates that the English lecturer has integrated **learn to live together** theme in the English classes. Second, peer review. Peer review is the evaluation of a work by one or more people with similar skills as the work's creator. In the English classes, students were given individual task to review other students' writing about discussion text. This was done by lecturer to make the students' skill in writing more trained. In reviewing others' writing, students learned how to **think critically** and **respect human dignity** such as review politely, gave and accepted others' critics, advice, and opinions.

From the interview with the lecturer and the class observation, it was found that the material used by the lecturer was discussion text. He said that the aim of choosing this topic was to **develop critical thinking** of the students as it was discussed about controversial issues. In this topic, students had to discuss two different points of view of an issue and the problem solution if it is needed. As a result, it will develop students' skills in problem solving, decision

making, analyzing, synthesizing, looking others' opinion, searching for alternatives and thinking logically about the issues they discussed.

Furthermore, it was clearly stated in the lesson plan that some peace values or concept were integrated in the English classes. They were critical, caring for others, kind, and polite. It is in accordance with one of the characteristics of a peaceful person: **be compassionate and do not harm**. It means that students should have empathetic qualities such as love, kindness, friendliness, politeness, caring for others and so on as those qualities are crucial in responding to violence happening in society. In other words, the students were expected to be peaceful people through learning English.

Based on the explanation above, it can be concluded that peace education has integrated in the English classes both in material and method of teaching. Teaching and learning English as a has not only changed the theory of English itself, but also enabled everyone to communicate with each other without being hampered by communication errors and misunderstandings. The lecturer is able to integrate the content of her EFL material and contextualize it with our surroundings. English can convey the concept of peace all over the world. Chaotic situations, conflicts and wars are our responsibility to overcome them. The lecturer should not only teach grammar and fluency, but also take social responsibility and contribute to a better society. The lecturer also should integrate peace education concepts into her EFL materials. We expect to see the birth of a golden generation who are not only academically adept, but also socially sensitive and advocate for a peaceful life for a better future.

Summary, Conclusion, and Recommendations

Summary

Foreign language teaching like English can be an alternative way to spread peace at school or university.

Conclusion

In conclusion, peace education can be infused through education like in English classes. In summary, the teaching methods, materials, and lesson plan used by the teacher in English classroom has integrated peace education themes such as learn to live together, think critically, respect human dignity as well as be compassionate and do not harm.

Recommendations

For further research, it can investigate the effect of implementing peace education toward students' attitude. For teachers or lecturers, peace education should be infused in their classes.

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49 - Working Together and Seeking for Harmony and Integration of Creation

Pulama, Lucy Herlina

Problem Statement: The ecological justice and indigenous religion values of life should be primary agenda in the discourse of religion study.

Purpose of the Study: This paper aims to emphasize that the discourse of justice and peace in society should begin with the discussion about justice towards nature because of the interconnectedness of ecological and social problems.

Literature or Theory: This paper will use comparative mythologies from Wendy Doniger and post-colonial theory.

Research Methods: This study will use qualitative method and literature studies to address the topic.

Summary of Findings: Christianity and colonialism have contributed to the destruction of nature in West Timor-Indonesia however, the indigenous community finds their values of community and protects nature; Therefore, there is a need to learn seriously about the indigenous religion's value of life.

Conclusion: To create ecojustice, Christianity and indigenous religions need to do collaborative work and learn from one another.

Keywords

- 1 Christianity
- 2 Indigenous Religion
- 3 West Timor-Indonesia
- 4 Comparative mythology
- 5 Post colonial study

Area: Justice and Peace

50 - A Study on the Role of Life Skills Education among School Students in Building Peace

Vengatesan, Ruthra

Problem Statement: Life skills are essential for achieving a harmonious life and are often neglected in formal education. Neglecting to teach life skills as part of academic education can have negative impacts on individuals.

Purpose of the Study: This study will be identifying the various ways to promote life skills education and its significance as a valuable tool for building peace.

Literature or Theory: Arjun Bahadur (2022), on the importance of life skills today and why students need to develop them highlights life skills are crucial for a harmonious today and tomorrow to help them be self-aware, embrace diversity and collaborate better.

Research Methods: Descriptive Research Design, Simple Random Sampling technique, Interview Schedule and In-depth Interview for data collection

Summary of Findings: Investing in the development of life skills is an investment in a better future for individuals and society, which is the major focus of the study. Life skills are critical for personal growth and success in all aspects of life.

Conclusion: Life skills education is a valuable tool that helps individuals to achieve a harmonious life. By teaching practical skills, it empowers individuals to take control of their lives.

Keywords

- 1 Role
- 2 Life skills
- 3 Education
- 4 Students
- 5 Peace

Area: Justice and Peace; Education

51 - Role of Culture in Social Development

Kaur, Navdeep

Rai, Monkia

Problem Statement: Role of Culture in Social development

Purpose of the Study: Main purpose of this study to inculcate the social values through culture

Literature or Theory: Culture, social development, and social values

Research Methods: Qualitative

Summary of Findings: Thematic paper in progress

Conclusion: Culture also helps to enhance the social development through interaction with each other

52 - Peace Education and Conflict Handling Mode

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“If we are to reach real peace in the world, we have to begin with the children.” (Gandhi)

Abstract

Political, economic, and educational systems in every society have an impact on its future. The only way to create this atmosphere is to live peacefully. Students who study peace evaluate local, national, and international issues while considering potential peaceful solutions. Establishing a discipline plan that places a strong emphasis on teaching pupils the ability to monitor and control their own behaviour is one of the goals of a peaceful school. Just feeling safe, at ease, and content is what peace is. We frequently have a tendency to think of peace as a global issue unrelated to our everyday lives, yet we fail to recognise that only when all nations are at peace can there be world peace. Every person must be at peace for each nation to be at peace and to be happy. So, it follows that if individuals live in tolerance, a nation can be peaceful and advance. Everyone wants to feel calm. The current imperative is to instill in the next generation a sense of peace and the value of conflict resolution. There is no opportunity in our society or educational system to emphasise the value of peace and conflict resolution. This study, which is based on a reviewing of literature, explains how peace education is crucial to resolving the various types of disputes that exist in our society. Education planners and policymakers should focus their efforts on creating an educational system that promotes peace and helps avert conflicts. It is commonly acknowledged that peace education is a crucial component that would guide humanity to reject violence and live in a peaceful society/world in order to achieve this condition of "peace," especially in the current conflict-ridden globe.

Keywords: Conflict Handling, Conflict Management, Peace Education, Conflict Resolution

Introduction:

Education is regarded as a life-changing activity that equips students to constructively contribute to the expansion and development of a society. It is seen as the process by which a person's behaviour, attitude, and overall perspective on life are altered through the process of learning. According to UNESCO (2005) education for sustainable development is fundamentally about values, with respect for others, particularly those of present and future generations, for difference and diversity, for the environment, and for the resources of the world we call home, at its core. Real education entails both mental flexibility and consistency, and this can only be achieved via the appropriate application of peace

education, which finally results in self-realization, which is considered to be the pinnacle of human achievement. In many conflict-ridden nations, efforts are made to promote peace through changing the educational system to reflect a new vision of society. Children who receive high-quality education are better able to think critically, solve issues, build self-esteem, and work cooperatively with others—skills that can all contribute to the development of a culture of nonviolence in communities that have experienced violent conflict. According to Bush and Saltarelli (2000), peace building education offers the most beneficial strategies for post-conflict societies because it demilitarizes the mind, problematizes the status quo, offers alternate solutions, and delegitimizes violence as a means of problem-solving by focusing instead on tolerance and trust. UNESCO (2011) peace education demonstrates the profound link between quality of education and inclination towards violence. Thus, improving the quality of education is very likely to reduce violence and conflict. The contents of curricula, how they are taught and how the education is organized, has an impact on how prone to violence students might be. Hence, education policies ranging from the language of instruction to the centralization/decentralization of educational planning all impact on conflict prevention and prospects for lasting peace.

According to Thomas (1992), conflict starts when one side believes the other has frustrated or is likely to frustrate one of his concerns. Conflict is an unavoidable element of humanity and typically arises when people hold different beliefs, opinions, or behaviours. A quarrel between two parties occurs when one of the parties feels cheated as a result of those other party's wants, interests, or worries. Even while conflict is frequently avoided, it's not always terrible. Actually, disagreement may be beneficial for organisations since it promotes receptivity and helps counteract the propensity towards groupthink that many of them are prone to. "Not all conflicts are bad and not all conflicts are helpful," (Hocker and Wilmot (1995)). Knippen and Green (2005) asserted that unresolved disputes frequently become larger disputes, and the longer they persist, the higher the likelihood that they will accumulate additional issues.

Methods for resolving conflicts: As conflict seems to be unavoidable, it is evident that managers must be able to identify the dispute's source, consider both its constructive and destructive possibilities, learn how to manage conflict, and effectively execute conflict resolution techniques (Fleetwood, 1987). According to the intensity and willingness of the parties or groups involved in the conflict, there are generally four approaches that can be used to address conflicts in different ways. These are -

Conflict Management: Conflict management does not always entail preventing, lessening, or ending conflict. In order to improve learning and efficacy of any kind, it entails developing efficient techniques to reduce the dysfunctions of conflict and promote the positive functions of conflict. **Conflict settlement:** The goal of conflict settlement is to resolve the conflict without necessarily addressing its underlying causes. It is primarily concerned with respecting established societal norms (of right and wrong) (John Burton and Frank Dukes (1990)). **Conflict resolution** is a strategy that places a strong emphasis on the parties coming to an understanding through discussion and bargaining. Unlike dispute resolution, true conflict resolution frequently calls for a more analytical, problem-solving approach. **Conflict Transformation:** The term "conflict transformation" refers to the way conflict naturally evolves. Relationships are changed by conflicts in predictable ways, altering social structures and communication patterns as well as self- and other-images.

Conflict Handling Modes: Conflict is a necessary component of human existence and an inevitable idea since it might arise whenever people interact and have personal preferences. Conflicts result from the agreements and disagreements we observe among people. According to Robbins (1974), conflict begins when one party believes that another has

negatively impacted or is about to negatively impact something that the first party values. Conflict, according to Sagimo (2002), is a stressful, unpleasant, depressing, unhappy, bothersome, and aggravating situation. When disputes are not resolved peacefully in the beginning, they frequently escalate into violent disputes.

The Thomas-Kilmann Conflict Mode Instrument (TKI) evaluates a person's behaviour in conflict situations, or those when two people's concerns seem to be at odds with one another. We can categorise a person's behaviour in conflict along two fundamental dimensions*: (1) assertiveness, which refers to how much the person tries to address their own worries; and (2) cooperativeness, which refers to how much the person tries to address the concerns of others. Five different approaches to handling conflict can be defined using these two behavioural dimensions. This is a diagram of these five conflict-handling strategies:

Fig 1. This two-dimensional model of conflict-handling behavior is adapted from “Conflict and Conflict Management” by Kenneth Thomas in *The Handbook of Industrial and Organizational Psychology*, edited by Marvin Dunnette (Chicago: Rand McNally, 1976).

Competing is a power-oriented, forceful, and uncooperative mindset. When competing, a person puts their own interests ahead of the other person's and will use all means necessary to advance their position. **Collaborating**: Being cooperative and forceful when you collaborate. While collaborating, a person makes an effort to work with the other person to come up with a solution that fully addresses both of their issues. **Compromising**: In terms of cooperativeness and boldness, compromising is intermediate. Finding a quick, amicable solution that somewhat satisfies both parties is the goal while compromise. **Avoiding** is passive and unhelpful. Avoiding can take the form of politely avoiding a situation, delaying a situation until a better opportunity arises, or simply removing oneself from a dangerous circumstance. **Accommodating**: Competing is aggressive; accommodating is passive and cooperative. It is possible to be accommodating by being benevolent or charitable, following someone else's instructions when you would prefer not to, or submitting to their point of view.

Education's role in promoting a culture of peace: Peace education teaches students how to settle disputes amicably through negotiations and mediations. One of the main purposes of peace education is to teach people how to resolve disputes without resorting to violence. Violent behaviors, street crime, war, marital disputes, ethnic conflicts, and poverty threaten the world and force millions of people to live in a violent environment where they have little

to no security and are fighting to survive. The following considerations are crucial for efficient learning during the process:

- Emphasis should be on the participatory and self-initiated learning
- Preservation and advancement of peace should be integrated into discussions
- Development of curricula on peace and practical approaches
- Imparting of peace related knowledge through media
- Imparting of the knowledge through religious institutions
- Knowledge dissemination through social work projects
- Cooperation and collaboration in the fields of education
- Selection of information and evaluation
- Eliminating bias in conflict information
- Organising campaigns, conducting seminars and talks on peace
- Giving training to the educators of peace to cater to all sections of society
- Promoting volunteerism to provide learning opportunities
- Maintaining consistent motivation levels to promote peace

The following table, created by renowned peace educator Betty Reardon, shows the main learning objectives for tolerance and aids in our comprehension of the many modes of operation.

Values	Knowledge	Capacities and Skills
Human dignity/rights	Varieties of human, personal and cultural identities, social issues	Living with diversity: cross-cultural cooperation; using human rights standards to make judgements
Social justice/democracy	Multiple forms of democratic processes and governance	Exercising responsibility: critical reflection; communication of facts and opinions; political decision-making
Co-operative non-violent society/peace	Alternative ways of responding constructively to human differences and conflicts	Managing conflict: discussion and debate; conflict resolution; reconciliation; social reconstruction; cooperative problem-solving and task achievement

Source: Reardon, 1997: Unit 1, p.53. (Cited in Margaret Sinclair, Learning to Live Together, Encyclopedia of Peace education, Teachers college, Columbia University, 2008. see <http://www.tc.edu/centers/epe/>)

Peace education as an effective tool for conflict handling and resolution: The participatory, comprehensive process known as peace education includes the teaching of social equality and citizens' rights, tranquilly, societal and economic fairness, sexual

fairness, ecological development, decommissioning, effective peaceful skills, global governance, and social safety (Wintersteiner, 2013). Conflict resolution often focuses on a local or domestic level, whereas peace education typically takes a broader global perspective. Moreover, peace education places a higher emphasis on societal fairness ideals and more structured worries about violence than conflict education programs do (Jones, 2004). When one group's actions are seen as hindering or impeding another's goals, demands, or behaviors, conflicts result. Disputes are frequently associated with negative traits and conditions that produce ineffective, incompetent, or dysfunctional consequences (Owan, 2018). In other cases, though, it can promote original problem-solving and improve the situation for everyone involved (Adesanya et al., 2018). Every group of a school's human resources will undoubtedly include people with a range of ethical, religious, sociological, civil, and economic education. These human resources maintain their frequently intricate institutional administration mechanisms (Owan and Agunwa, 2019). Conflicts or disagreements between employees of a company do occur. This is due to the fact that disputes are inevitable in institutions (Arop et al., 2018).

People can discover the causes of conflict and violence, as well as societal compulsion, perception, and depreciation, and take preventative measures through studying peace. It might learn how to resolve conflicts naturally and change society to serve social goals. Since the 20th century, peace education programmes have included maintaining national security, global knowledge, an environmental obligation, social skills, social interaction, passivity, conflict resolution strategies, fairness, civil rights awareness, patience, diversity, harmony, and equal rights and responsibilities of others (McLeod & O'Reilly, 2019). There are various United Nations speeches on peace education. Numerous prior difficulties were transformed into programmes on global social duty and nationalism by the spiritual dimensions of interior harmony (Huda et al., 2020; Kishino & Takahashi, 2019; Woiwode et al., 2021).

Conclusion: It is crucial to keep in mind that peace education is not a new academic discipline we add to the existing curriculum. Instead, we focus on introducing the general orientation through the teachable subjects, literature, and teacher discourses. In efforts to implement that duty, there is now a growing acknowledgment of the critical role that youth play in promoting peace. The moral, social, and political test of the future will be whether humanity can harness the enthusiasm, ingenuity, and vision of youth to advance peace as effectively as it has advanced war. With the advancement of knowledge and contemporary methods, peace education is being incorporated into more and more educational programmes around the globe, with significant assistance from state and national governments in addition to global organisations like UNESCO. Education for world peace is now seen as a sign of brighter times to come.

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53 - Exploring Livelihoods Under Protracted Displacement; A Case Study of Internally Displaced Persons in Kachin State, Myanmar

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Abstract

Armed conflicts caused internal displacement in Kachin state since 2011, and the protracted displacement affected the livelihoods of the IDPs severely. The research aims to comprehensively understand the impacts of protracted displacement on Kachin IDPs' livelihoods and their coping strategies. The study is built upon theoretical concepts on the impacts of internal displacement, sustainable livelihood, and livelihood adaptive capacity. The research employs a qualitative method and was done through the review of literature, reports and documents, case study, and interviews. The preliminary findings are the impacts of displacement on livelihood, the survival and recovery mechanism during protracted displacement, the benefits of livelihood strategies supported by humanitarian and development agencies, and local adaptability, which opens up new opportunities. Insufficient humanitarian aid strengthens self-reliance and adaptation to diversified livelihoods. The research paper concludes that external intervention is not always the answer but coping and adaptive capacity are important keys to achieving livelihood recovery.

Key Terms: Adaptive Capacity, Adaptation Strategies, Internally Displaced Person, Livelihoods, Protracted Displacement

Problem Statement

In 1961, Kachin Independent Organization (KIO) was formed and took up arms to revolt against the Myanmar government that failed to offer autonomy to the Kachin state after the independence. The 1994's ceasefire halted the armed conflict but resurged in 2011. The civil war caused the largest-ever displacement, leaving 89,600 people displaced across Kachin State. A decade after, the coup by Myanmar Armed Forces on February 1, 2021, increased the number of IDPs in Kachin State to 100,700 spreading across 139 camps. (UNHCR Myanmar, 2023). The protracted displacement profoundly affected the livelihoods of the people in the camps. Having abandoned their homes, lands, and former ways of earning a living, they were fostered to adjust to new environments and take on available jobs. Accessing new livelihood was challenging. The displaced persons were disadvantaged in finding decent jobs and sufficient income. They struggled to make ends meet depending on barely enough humanitarian assistance.

Research Questions:

In order to understand the impacts of protracted displacement on Kachin IDPs' livelihoods and their coping strategies the research explored the answers to the following;

1. How did the protracted displacement affect the livelihoods of internally displaced persons?
2. What are the coping mechanisms during protracted displacement?
3. How did their adaptive capacity help them achieve livelihood recovery?

Research Purpose

The main objective of the research is to analyze the consequences of the armed conflicts on the livelihoods of the IDPs, gaining an in-depth understanding of their coping strategies in protracted destitution. The study aims to discover innovative approaches to livelihood recovery in protracted displacement.

Definition of Terms

The followings explain the terms Adaptive capacity, Adaptation strategies, internally displaced person, Livelihoods, and Protracted displacement.

“Adaptive capacity” is the ability to cope with stressors and dynamically adapt to the situation faced, using one’s own reserve resources for survival. (Engle, 2011). The “Adaptation strategies” is usually referred to climate change but in the case of displacement, it can be defined as the choice and combined activities of the households in response to the challenges, to maintain their livelihoods. According to UNHCR, “Internally displaced persons” are people who have been displaced mainly by armed conflicts and natural disasters but remain within their own country without crossing the border to find safety. “Livelihoods” in its simplest definition is a means of earning a living to meet basic needs. A livelihood is comprised of the capabilities, assets, and activities required to make a living. “Protracted displacement” is a situation where the displacement moved past the emergency stage yet the people continue to stay in the place without finding any solution to return home. (Milner et al., 2009).

Literature Review

Impacts of Internal Displacement: Displaced people abandoned their homes and land in search of safety and it disabled them to continue their former livelihoods such as agricultural works and other informal works, leading them to unemployment. Disconnected from their former networks, access to formal employment in the new social setting is difficult. Insufficient income fosters children to drop schooling. Low education reduces the chance of securing decent work and a fair income. The vulnerable displaced were forced to take up available jobs, often exposing them to labor exploitation, dangerous income-generating activities, and human trafficking. In the lack of start-up costs or inability to reestablish former livelihood activities, the displaced were deprived of business opportunities and income equality. Inaccessibility to cash assistance and financial support significantly affected the displaced and they were found heavily indebted.

The direct impact of displacement on livelihoods rippled out to other dimensions of life. Campsite shelters are substandard and the overcrowding of collective housing with no privacy puts the dwellers at risk of potential conflicts with neighbors, abuse, and violence. The lack of sanitation increases the chance of spreading communicable diseases. Poor housing conditions expose the IDPs to weather hazards causing physical and mental stress, and illness. Disruption of education instills a psychosocial impact on the children and the sense of social exclusion cause long-term damage to their growth. The traumatic experience with limited education results in negative outcomes such as domestic violence, sexual abuse, social tension, and violent incidents in the community. Marginalization and social discrimination associated with displacement trigger depression, and anxiety and embed a long-term psychological impact in their social lives. leaving them vulnerable and disadvantaged. (Cazabat, 2018).

Sustainable Livelihood: Chambers and Cornwall (1991) presented the concept of sustainable livelihoods stating the importance of preserving livelihoods through coping with stress and shocks, utilizing available assets, and enhancing the capabilities to continue and improve. The concept mainly focuses on rural livelihood relying on natural resources and is

identical to the case of Kachin State. In the face of stresses and shocks, the ability to avoid if possible or either to withstand and recover is essential. Stresses are those factors that build up gradually and affect the livelihoods eventually. They are different from shocks in that they are continuous and cumulative, predictable and distressing whereas shocks are typically sudden, unpredictable, and traumatic.

Stressors are external and internal, tangible and intangible in nature. The tangible degradation of nature such as rainfall, water scarceness, ecological change in soil erosion, less yield of soils, and lower productivity placed tremendous pressure on humans. The intangible factors such as declining labor work availability, higher cost of living, rising fuel price, and physical disabilities of active adults with growing age, all have significant impacts on livelihoods. The unpredictable shocks are more damaging and cannot be prevented and avoided. They are civil wars, droughts, storms, floods, fires, famine, epidemics of crops, pets, or animals, and the pandemic harming household members. Sudden accidents, the death of a family member, the loss of assets, and the loss of a job all have traumatic effects on people and their livelihoods.

To recover and sustain livelihoods, it is essential to enhance livelihood capabilities and competence. The dynamic and positive ability to foresee the unexpected and adapt to the changing situation is critical. In the face of disasters, uncertain and changing market conditions, currency fluctuation, decreased opportunities, and new livelihood trends, adaptive capacity is a key contributor to livelihood sustainability. Having to abandon traditional livelihoods, it is practical to adapt to open opportunities and adjust to livelihood diversification.

Livelihood Adaptive Capacity: Adaptive capacity in biology is the ability that enables the organism or systems to cope with environmental changes in order to survive and reproduce (Smith & Wandel, 2006. p 283). Human beings possess the capability to take positive adaptations, learn from experience and prepare to face future stresses, to lessen the negative impacts. Adaptive capacity is the ability to adjust to potential damage, take advantage of opportunities, and respond to consequences. Adaptation is the process of responding to unforeseen calamities and unpredictable shocks, learning and adjusting to the encountered situations, and finding a potential solution to the problem. (Persons, 1964).

In livelihood, the adaptive capacity bases its resources on natural, physical, human, financial, and social capital. It is capable of mobilizing scarce resources to anticipate and respond to existing stresses. It is able to respond sufficiently to situations and reduce vulnerability. The adaptive capacity survives disturbances, seeks opportunities, and opens up options. It is the capacity that enables communities to reinstate their livelihood patterns, compromise with the changes, and contribute to resilience and recovery. (Nyamwanza, 2012). Livelihood adaptability comprises the coping mechanism; learning to live with change and uncertainty, finding alternative diversification, learning and nurturing from experience, and self-organizing individually or collectively.

Methodology

The research employed a qualitative method and was done through extensive reading of literature, reports, and related documents, analyzing various situations, visiting internally displaced people (IDP) camps, and interviewing. An in-depth understanding of the research questions was induced through comparative analysis of various cases, and listening to the first-hand experiences of the people in the protracted displacement. Interviews have been conducted in three IDP camps in Myitkyina, Kachin state, to find out the impacts of protracted displacement on livelihoods and how they adapted to the situation for recovery. Three young people attending vocational training from Kachin displaced families were also

interviewed. Camp managers were included in the interviews to find out the administrative work and arrangements for the displaced families.

Findings

The Impacts of Protracted Displacement on the Livelihood of the Kachin IDPs: The protracted displacement since 2011 and the added displacement after the 2021 coup left the Kachin IDPs with no assets to make a living. Before they had land, cattle, and some other means of livelihood. Most of them were forced to flee from their villages and settle in IDP camps that spread across Kachin state. They have difficulty accessing livelihood opportunities and are mostly dependent on humanitarian aid which is barely enough for the family. 12,000-13,000 kyats for each family member. Since they lost their lands, they have to work as casual laborers on the farms of sugarcane, coffee, paddy, corn, banana, watermelon, tea, and lemongrass plantations. The works are seasonal and not on a regular basis, moreover, it is low paid.

Men usually work in construction, agriculture, and mining. The working conditions in mining pose significant risks in terms of physical safety, exploitation, exposure to drugs, and other illicit activities. Women were found selling seasonal fruits and vegetables or working in the houses of well-off families. Some earn their living from daily paid jobs such as working in grocery shops, and restaurants and some settle at home in animal husbandry. With insufficient income, some families faced difficulties to reestablish their small-scale businesses. Due to financial difficulties, elder children were dropped from school to assist in household work or earn a living to support the family income. Some educated youth help in teaching children in the camp. In pursuit of better opportunities, many young people from the camps crossed the border to China in search of jobs legally or illegally, increasing their precarity and vulnerability. Social discrimination and educational level pose as barriers to securing employment in a formal setting.

“Our Children normally work hard in their studies and there were quite a number of high school graduates in the IDP camp. The problem is if you are not a university graduate the chance of getting a job is very thin. There is discrimination especially if you are from the IDP camp, they don’t want to hire you”. Htu Bu from Zion camp.

The Coping Mechanisms for Survival: The displacement in Kachin IDPs is prolonged and with the uncertain future, it has become harder for the households to strive and survive. Living in shabby shelters crammed with family members is challenging and struggling to make ends meet is even more depressing. Having abandoned their own farms, the only agricultural activities in the camps are home gardening. It is mainly aimed at household consumption in their daily meal. Some are for sale. Livestock breeding and animal rearing is few but some residents were able to manage it with the help of an organization and it proved beneficial. Beyond the farm work, some other income-generating jobs are available in restaurants, shops, small-scale vending, and small grocery shops, and work at home such as knitting, weaving, making handicrafts, snacks, jam, and soap. (Kachin Women Peace Network & Gender Equality Network, 2013).

Apart from regular income-generating activities, livelihood strategies supported by humanitarian and development agencies help train the IDPs with skills such as sewing, clothes design, food production, animal raising, and handicraft skills so that they earn some income from those skills. The skills training conducted by different organizations support households to generate incomes through activities such as food processing, carpentry, making handicraft, making cane rattan home goods, making clay stoves, making concrete products, tailoring, and weaving (Tawng, 2020). Handicraft-making skills support families to make some products and get orders to supply in the market.

“We get many skills training and we utilize those skills to make money. Our monthly rations are not enough. We need to work as casual laborers so we can earn at least 4000 Kyats to 5000 Kyats per day. But it is not on a regular basis. Apart from that we also raise 3-4 pigs. Some know how to sew, so they earn some income from that. Some sell vegetables and seasonal fruits. Still, we are struggling to make ends meet”. Roi Gyaung from Maina camp

“Microfinance support from BRIDGE helps small families to invest in income-generation businesses. Loans are available from 500,000 up to 900,000 kyats to help small business startups”, said Brang Mai, one of the Camp administrators.

Some youths received training from NGOs which enables them to join Kachin Baptist Convention as volunteer staff and in some non-governmental projects. Livelihood interventions enhance the capabilities and competence and contribute to livelihood sustainability. Even though they have to abandon their traditional livelihood and take up new ones they cope well and adapt well to the changes and challenges. The IDPs struggle to recover from adversity, and in the case of the Kachin state, it is the Christian faith that heals the wound and anxiety. Faith-based counseling helps them to overcome the trauma. The prospect of returning to their place of origin is vague with no sign of securing the peace agreement. Despite the hardship, the resilience of the displaced sustains them through the years and they continue striving for recovery and living with hope for better days to come.

The Adaptive Capacity for Recovery: The main livelihoods in Kachin State are agriculture and mining. Since displacement affected the traditional livelihoods of the IDPs, they made effort to survive and take on other new livelihoods which require them to new ventures. Young people in the camps tried to find ways to earn their living elsewhere and migrated to larger cities for better opportunities. Kachin is close to the border of China, therefore most young people ventured to find employment in China. (LIFT, 2020) Some venture to take up border trading for small-scale businesses. Most people who remain in the camp are adults, women, and young children. Instead of sticking to old ways of earning a living, they looked for livelihoods that are more sustainable, and possible diversification of livelihoods is determined for adaptation. Skills training provided by different humanitarian organizations solved livelihood challenges. With the new skill set, the IDPs were able to regenerate income to support the basic needs of their households. Some organizations grant the IDPs start-up capital to establish small-scale business cooperatives. Strengthened market linkage and increased product sales help fulfill the needs of the families. Generated income helps pay the bills. Working as a company worker, working in manufacturing sites, workshops, hotels, and restaurants increases their income and improves social cohesion with the host community. Youth trained by local and international NGOs are reemployed in the organizations and through that, they become project experts and are able to contribute back to the development of the community. The protracted displacement heaped up the pressure yet, with the devastation, arise new opportunities and better ways of earning a living

Summary

The protracted displacement left the IDPs with no assets to resume their living. They were forced to restart their livelihoods from the scratch. Striving through the destitution they cope with the stresses and found their way to survival. Not just for the external assistance, but with their resilience, new ways of income generation were adapted backing them to livelihood recovery.

Conclusion

Conflicts, stressors, and shocks are unpredictable and unavoidable. The protracted displacement placed heavy burdens on the Kachin IDPs and with the years the devastating

situations continue to exist. International and local humanitarian assistance supported the displaced well to recover from adversity. The new livelihood skills provided, open up better earning opportunities contrary to traditional livelihoods. The local resilience that withstands and adapts to the prevailing circumstances and the capacity to seek new ventures cannot be undermined by its driving power for recovery.

Recommendation

The study explores the coping strategies and adaptive capacity in regard to livelihood and discovers local resilience which plays a key role in livelihood recovery. There are many other specific dimensions to understanding the impacts of protracted displacement and the prominent role of resilience. Resilience in the IDP setting can further be studied to find a more sustainable solution for the IDPs, that can be effective for both practitioners and policymakers.

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54 - The Tantric Elements in Vaishnav Religion and Literature

Bakshi, Progoti Chetana

Problem Statement: in this paper it will be shown the effect of tantric tradition in vaishnav religion.

Purpose of the Study: how the tantric elements come in vaishnav society Literature or theory tantra and vaishnav cult is different but in which process they are same.

Research Methods: descriptive

Summary of Findings: tantric elements in vaishnav religion and literature

Conclusion even vaishnav religion and literature bears the tantric elements

Keywords

1 tantra

2 cults

3 vaishnavism

4 vaishnav literature

5 worships

Area: Religion

55 - Becoming violent: case study of anti-COVID protest in February 2021 in Dublin

Owczarek, Karolina

Problem Statement: Why did the protest in Dublin in February 2021 become violent?

Purpose of the Study: Protesters became violent because of the interaction with the police

Literature or Theory: Reicher, S., Stott, C., Drury, J., Adang, O., Cronin, P., and Livingstone, A. (2007) "Knowledge- based Public Order Policing: Principles and Practice." Policing: A Journal of Policy and Practice, 1(4): 403-415.; and other protest literature.

Research Methods: To conduct the following study, the qualitative source analysis using the content analysis technique was used.

Summary of Findings: Police responded to the banned demonstration. The protesters felt the police used their power against them instead of securing their human right to protest, and thus their sense of security diminished.

Conclusion: The more visible the reaction of the police the more violence is observed.

Keywords

1 Protest

2 COVID

3 Demonstration

4 Police

5 Riots

Area: Justice and Peace

56 - The Consequences of Partisan Policing for the Development of Civil Disorder during the Protests of Business Owners in Pandemic-ridden Poland

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Abstract

During the coronavirus pandemic in Poland there was a protest of business owners. The latter opposed to restrictions that were introduced for reasons of epidemiological safety, but ultimately hit entrepreneurs. In connection with the protests, the government proposed solutions that were to help them rebuild financial liquidity and become compensation for the introduced restrictions. Researchers indicate that politicization of the police and inadequate actions towards protesters may lead to an escalation of protests. The aim of the study is to answer the following questions: How did the police deal with protesters during gatherings? What were the consequences of politicized protest policing and the use of escalated force policing for the formation of civil disorder during assemblies? The method used in the study is a qualitative content analysis. The study included media materials appearing in the most popular news services in Poland. This will allow to determine the dynamics of relations between protesters and the police by taking into account the activity of both sides during the protests and their possible escalation.

Key Terms: pandemic, Poland, police, protests, civil disorder

Introduction

Problem Statement

Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, there is a need to take measures to prevent the further spread of the virus. Governments communicated about subsequent decisions that related to internal affairs, but also affecting international relations, e.g. restrictions or bans on movement between states or travelling to other states. However, the most severe for citizens were the restrictions preventing them from gainful employment. Many types of activities had to change their nature, look for solutions that would allow them to continue operating in a different way, e.g. transferring employees to remote work. The situation was much worse in the case of entrepreneurs who ran businesses such as restaurants, clubs, rooms for rent for special events, gyms. Initially, their activity was limited, and when it was completely banned, there were numerous protests of entrepreneurs.

Entrepreneurs demanded government action primarily in the field of maintaining jobs, lowering taxes and contributions to the Social Insurance Institution, stopping salary reductions and compensation payments. There were also demands for the resignation of the prime minister, the minister of health and a reduction in salaries for administrative employees, and strong opposition to freezing the economy was expressed (JaM, 2020).

The right-wing Law and Justice (Law and Justice, PiS) are a party that in the years preceding the pandemic was considered an opponent of entrepreneurs by adopting overly burdensome or unfavorable solutions for them (Solska 2019). In addition, protests from various social groups have revealed that there is a risk of politicization of the police, as for example in the case of women's protests (Rezmer-Płotka, 2023). All these factors may have contributed to the violence of the protests and the negative attitude of the protesters

towards the government. In response to the protests, there were proposals for anti-crisis shields, which would also cover business owners.

However, mentioned events may complement the lack of knowledge regarding the actions taken by the police against protesters during the crisis on a global scale and an attempt to determine on this basis the degree of politicization of the security services. Such political involvement would be incompatible with the neutrality of this formation.

Research Questions

Embedded in the problem statement, the study addresses the following research questions:

1. How did the police deal with protesters during gatherings?
2. What were the consequences of politicized protest policing and the use of escalated force policing for the formation of civil disorder during assemblies?

Research Purpose

The paper aims to explain whether the actions taken by the police against protesters could have been political. Moreover, did the security services not abuse force against the gathered? Ultimately, this will determine the possible and real consequences of politicized protest policing.

Literature Review

Researchers are increasingly pointing out that there has been a drift of the protest policing model from negotiated management to escalated force and the resulting increase in the use of violence by protesters (Rak, Owczarek 2022). Paul A. Passavant used the example of #BlackLivesMatter to point out that policing of protest is becoming increasingly militarized. In addition, the increasing use of control technologies means that police actions can become an institutional practice that treats protesters as more than criminals (Passavant, 2021). Jennifer Earl believes that any unjustified repression, and its high frequency they can lead to an intensification of the activity of social movements. The escalation of repression has led to radicalisation and even negative consequences for civil liberties (Earl, 2013). Thus, the question of the legitimacy of such actions arises, because in a democratic state the costs of repression are higher (Davenport, 2007).

The second problem is the politicization of the police, which can be determined by bias, when officers repress some protesters and support or ignore others but also partisan actions, which means that police actions perform political interests of the ruling and act as their loyal supporters (Smith, 2021).

In sum, the politicization of the police combined with unjustified actions may lead not only to an escalation of protests, but also to a loss of trust and credibility in public services. This phenomenon is also worrying from the point of view of the democratic regime, because when the police become a tool in the hands of the government, we can talk about backsliding democracy.

Methodology

The method used in the study is a qualitative content analysis. The study included media materials appearing in the most popular news services in Poland in the period from 1 May to 31 May 2020. Protests of entrepreneurs also took place in previous and subsequent months, but it was in May that the largest and most organized assemblies took place. Also significant is the fact that the candidate in the presidential election Paweł Tanajno announced on May 30, 2020 the creation of a political party called "Strike of Entrepreneurs".

The process of source analysis consisted of skimming, detailed examination, and interpretation of news appearing during this period. The analysis was carried out on two levels in order to answer the research questions posed.

First stage: In the first step, the most popular news services were selected. In 2020, it was indicated that the most opinion-forming media in Poland are: onet.pl, RMF FM, TVN24, Rzeczpospolita, WP.pl, Gazeta Wyborcza, Polsat News, Super Express, Dziennik Gazeta Prawna, Interia.pl, Radio Zet, TVP Info, Fakt, Money.pl, TVN (IMM, 2020). Then, a selection was made consisting in extracting all the information that related to the protests of entrepreneurs. Due to the purpose of the study, after collecting all the materials, only those that took into account the actions of the police and protesters were selected. This will allow to determine the dynamics of relations between protesters and the police by taking into account the activity of both sides during the protests and their possible escalation. The last step was to divide between the actions of the police and the actions of the protesters and an attempt to sort them out.

The second stage is to focus on information about the protests solely on the basis of those that appeared on the tvp.info website. This is justified for several reasons. First, since 2015, the national media in Poland have been completely subordinated to the ruling party. Secondly, Public television has started to play the role not only of creating public opinion but also manipulating information in such a way as to discredit opponents. Thirdly, one of the tools allowing to obtain legitimacy for decisions taken by the ruling party has become national television. Fourth, women's protests in connection with the tightening of abortion law revealed that the media took over the role of law enforcement by categorising who and how broke the law, which is the competence of the police (Rezmer-Płotka, 2022). As in the first stage, initially all information about the protests of May 2020 was collected, and then only those that directly related to the actions of the police and protesters through such key words as: protests, strike, entrepreneurs, pandemic were extracted from them

Findings

Actions of protesters and police on the basis of news services

In the case of protesters, the actions that have been taken are: the "car" form, i.e. driving around one of the most important roundabouts in the capital of Polish; blocking/slowing down traffic, marching to key buildings such as the Sejm, the Chancellery of the Prime Minister, the Council of Ministers; tent cities, arranging a cross made of candles and flowers as a symbol of the burden that entrepreneurs have to carry under the Palace of Culture and Science; verbal presentation of their postulates and by means of various types of posters.

Police actions in the analyzed period include: identification of protesters; fines for non-compliance with social distancing rules; applications for punishment to the sanitary inspection; roadside checks; the liquidation of the protesters' tent city; detention of protesters; calls through loudspeakers to "behave lawfully" and the threat of direct coercion; use of pepper spray; cordoning off journalists; surrounding protesters by police; violation of the immunity of Senator Jacek Bury.

Protester and police activity based on National Television coverage

According to tvp.info reports, actions on the side of protesters are: ignoring police messages, assaulting police officers; violation of the physical integrity of the police; attacks on journalists; jostling with the police; attacking police officers with firecrackers and bottles; breaking many of the restrictions introduced to prevent the spread of the virus; blocking traffic; recording the police when the police take action.

On the side of the police: detention in accordance with the procedures of persons who violated the physical integrity of police officers; legitimizing and cordoning protesters; the use of gas in response to an active assault by protesters; verbal appeals to disperse.

In the meantime, there were information about government aid in the form of i.e anti-crisis shields and messages about the responsibility of the president of the capital Polish about blocking funds to help entrepreneurs, applications to the sanitary inspectorate for punishment in connection with breaking the regulations on restrictions preventing the spread of the virus (tvp.info).

Summary, Conclusion, and Recommendations

Summary

It can be seen that the actions on the side of the protesters and the police presented in the most popular news services and in tvp.info partly overlap. A significant difference lies in the way the information is presented. In the case of National Television, protesters were portrayed as irresponsible, aggressive and responsible for police action. Public service officers were indicated as victims. During the protests that took place in May 2020, there were several escalations and clashes between police and protesters. The Ombudsman also intervened in connection with all these activities. He pointed out that the use of direct coercion should always be a last resort, he also reminded about the protection of senators with immunity and pointed to the conflict of interests related to the legal status in this particular period. The organizers of the assembly were guided by the constitutionally guaranteed freedom of assembly, and the police by a decree issued in connection with the pandemic (RPO, 2021).

Finally, a precedent-setting Supreme Court ruling was issued indicating that the government could not ban the May gatherings. First of all, this ban had no proper legal basis and undermined the constitution (RPO, 2020).

The politicization of the police in this case consisted in following a controversial regulation instead of respecting the freedoms guaranteed by the Constitution. It has been confirmed that the use of excessive force against protesters leads to an escalation and intensification of actions. The use of repression effectively reduces the level of civil obedience and exacerbates anti-government sentiments. Such actions are not legitimized in a democratic system, so they can ultimately lead to partial or total lost legitimacy by the police.

Conclusion

During the protests of entrepreneurs, the police followed the government's guidelines, restricting the freedom of assembly. Based on the information appearing on the most popular websites, it can be concluded that the violence escalated both on the part of the police and protesters. In the case of national television, the responsibility for the escalation lay solely with the protesters, and the police were to act in accordance with the applicable laws. However, the actions of the security services and the way they were presented by the government-subordinate media caused citizens to perceive them as politicised and in line with political discourse. The use of violence by police officers in Poland, which is a country

after political transformation, also leads to negative associations. Especially that in democratic systems one of the most important rights of citizens is the freedom of peaceful assembly. Moreover, every action must be legitimized in order to be accepted by the public.

Police deal with protesters through preventive measures and security measures such as: identification of protesters; fines for non-compliance with social distancing rules; applications for punishment to the sanitary inspection; roadside checks; the liquidation of the protesters' tent city; detention of protesters; calls through loudspeakers to "behave lawfully" and the threat of direct coercion; use of pepper spray; cordoning off journalists; surrounding protesters by police; violation of the immunity of Senator Jacek Bury. At the same time, some of them are assessed by the protesters and the Ombudsman as an abuse of force against peaceful gatherings. The consequences of politicized protest policing and the use of escalated force policing for the formation of civil disorder during assemblies was to reduce the level of trust of citizens and treat the police as a tool in the hands of the government. Moreover, the justification of the activities of the security services by public television may lead to consent to violence.

Recommendations

The protests of entrepreneurs have revealed, firstly, what the legal chaos leads to. In this case, consideration should be given to how to deal with other possible large-scale crises in order to avoid legal uncertainty. Especially that the most important legal act in Poland is the Constitution, which guarantees numerous rights and freedoms. Secondly, measures to change the image of the police in the eyes of citizens should be considered. Unfortunately, both strikes by women and entrepreneurs have once again caused the police to be perceived as politicised and acting in accordance with government policy. Another issue that is equally important is the way in which information is presented on national television. Information appearing on public television should be as objective as possible and devoid of emotional bias. The creation of enemies and the evaluation of various events by this medium may cause it to take over the functions of the security services through categorising who and how broke the law.

These findings are particularly important from the point of view of research on policing protest, so that in the future during other crises it will be possible to prevent the transformation of public orders into civil disorder.

Funding: This work was supported by the National Science Centre, Poland [grant number 2021/43/B/HS5/00290].

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57 - Improving Intergenerational Dialogue and Action for Peace and Security

Gittins, Phill | Proskova, Vanda | FrljK, Emina | Gilbert, Roberts

Poster Session

Abstract

Young people have – on issues from peace, justice, and humanitarian aid to sustainable development, climate change and political, social, and economic participation – been too often overlooked in decision-making and action processes. This is particularly true for youth, peace, and security work. How can we create spaces that support the active and meaningful participation of young people in peace and security issues? What do they need to know, experience, and do to make direct positive impacts on issues of peace and security? How can we improve collaboration, innovation, and impact in peacebuilding by bringing individuals and organizations together to work on intergenerational and cross-cultural peacebuilding efforts? These questions and more will be explored in this interactive session. The session is for those interested or involved in peace and security work with young people. It may also appeal to anyone working with young people in general, providing useful insights and guidance on how to better support the development of young people as leaders and changemakers.

To meet the needs of the target audience, the session will:

- Centre the voices, agency, and lived experiences of young people
- Explore the practical aspects of empowering young with the knowledge, tools, and support needed to make a direct positive impact on issues of peace and security
- Illustrate what is involved in bringing different generations together – from different cultures and contexts – to engage in participatory processes of learning and action specific to peace.
- Demonstrate the process by which young people can move from ideas to impact through the combination of peace education, mentoring, and non-violent direct action.
- Discuss the important role of youth adult partnerships, mentoring, and coaching. The session will feature prominent youth leaders and youth-focused organizations including:
 - ❖ Youth Fusion
 - ❖ Youth for Peace
 - ❖ The Commonwealth
 - ❖ World Beyond War

Area: Justice and Peace

58 - A Descriptive Study of impact of Festivals on Indian Culture

Jadhav, Ravindra

Problem Statement: Festivals are showing the perspectives of the culture. Festival makes significant impact on the preservation of culture in India.

Purpose of the Study: Present study has revealed the Beauty of Indian culture. Also, it will providing useful information about how festivals help in preserving the culture of India.

Literature or Theory: Ms. Lekha Fenn stated in her studies on a Descriptive Study on Cultural Impact on Celebrating Festivals in India that is festivals are motive for human values which create sense of humanity through culture

Research Methods: Causal research design along with primary as well as secondary methods has been used in present study.

Summary of Findings: Festival is the important key player in preserving culture of India. Festivals showing the different culture in different states and religions. Festival is not only preserving the culture but also it makes sense of culture from one generation to next generation.

Conclusion: Festivals play pivotal role in the preserving the culture of India also showing the beauty of Indian culture.

Keywords

1 Festivals

2 Culture

3 Integrity

4 Harmony

5 States and religions

Area Culture; Religion; Justice and Peace

59 - The Challenges and Opportunities for Interfaith Dialogue as Peacebuilding

Ruiz, Alma

Problem Statement: The long history of hostility between Muslims and Christians in the Philippines still exists, therefore an interfaith dialogue is urgently needed.

Purpose of the Study: This study addresses the various challenges and opportunities for interfaith dialogue in advancing peacebuilding efforts.

Literature or Theory: Interfaith Dialogue as Peacebuilding Initiatives

Research Methods: Fieldwork data through interviews, participant observation, and literature research.

Summary of Findings: Interfaith initiatives have helped to rebuild relationships. However, it also demonstrates the limitations and challenges brought on by the imbalance of power between the dominant and minority groups engaged in dialogue.

Conclusion: It takes a sustained dialogue to bring about a meaningful change at the societal level. Recommendation includes looking at the continuing long distance or virtual interfaith dialogue.

Keywords

- 1 Interfaith
- 2 Dialogue
- 3 Peacebuilding
- 4 Southern Philippines
- 5 Challenges and Opportunities

Area: Religion

60 - A Comparative Study of The Attitude of Hindu and Muslim Women, Their Educational Level and Social Change in Sitamarhi District

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Abstract

Education is an important factor in any society, with the help of which both direction and condition of the society change. In ancient India, traditional education was imparted through religious institutions. In the Vedic period, the status of women was very good and high, women were able to work side-by-side with their husbands and could decide for their future life. She had the right over the property of her father and husband. Swayamvar system was the strong foundation of the social status of women. Women were equal to men in the intellectual field. Lopamudra, the wife of sage Agastya, was the author of Vedic hymns. Maitreyi used to discuss the problems of philosophy with her husband. Mundan Mishra's wife Mandavi had even defeated Adi Shankaracharya in a debate. The queen of Jhansi, Laxmibai gained, fame as heroines Begum Hazrat Mahal, Razia Sultana and Ahilyabai as an administrator, the whole society is familiar with Noorjahan's administration. Rama's companion Sita, Krishna's beloved Radha, Meerabai's Spiritual Singing and becoming one with Krishna reveals the form of women's primal power. But during the British Rule, Western Education was introduced in India, which had a unique effect on both Hindu and Muslim women. As a result of the change in their attitude, the women's society took a new turn. In Independent India, the decentralization of power in the fields of politics, the abundant reservation given to women and the facility of education turned the game. The changed perspective of the Indian society and the increasing step of modernization have changed the life of women in many roles and social relations. Both Hindu and Muslim women are no longer confined to their families but are playing active roles outside the home for economic gain and personal goals. Educated Women have brought a change in the traditional outlook by joining many jobs and are playing an influential role for themselves and their families and society. As a result of increasing steps of social change, spread of education political modernization, many types of changes are seen in the Indian society. Sitamarhi district is the birthplace of Maa Janki, where the birth anniversary of Maa Sita is celebrated with great respect, even today Hindu women could not get the respect which they deserved. The condition of Muslim women is even more pitiable; they are limited to their own families their contribution to the society is negligible. The reason behind all this is their low education level and low attitude which is not connecting them with the modern social change. Logical analysis of all such things and complete conclusion will be tried to know in the research paper presented.

Keywords: Attitudes, Social change, Education level, Sitamarhi District, Decentralization

Introduction

In modern times, the spread of education is happening at a rapid pace, and as a result, the pace of social change is also fast in the present period. In any society, when there is a change in social values, ideologies, institutions, social roles, patterns of interaction, etc. then we

name this social change. Change is the eternal law of nature and life. Social change is also a universal truth. This change takes place in the line of Indian Hindu and Muslim women as per their environmental conditions. There are many factors of socio-economic, educational, cultural and political fundamentals. At present, different levels of education have not only played a role in social change, but have also accelerated the pace of social change. Especially the change in the psychological and social thought currents of women is visible in its effective form. In the light of the new education policy, the leading role of today's teacher is to make the subject matter of this research paper present the explanation effectively. People of different religions, communities, and castes have been living in India. They have been expressing their attitude in different languages. They have different ideologies, life-values and cultures, yet there are uniformity and unity in diversity. Hindu and Muslim are to major communities living in India for centuries. Comparatively, the pace of social change in Hindu society has been more rapid than that of Muslim society. A lot of changes have been taking place in their social, educational, economic and cultural fields. In comparison, the transformation of the Muslim community did not take place with the speed that was expected. The main reason for this has been their indifference towards education. The Muslim community, until recently, has been placing more emphasis on religious education received from Maktabas and Madrassas, which have been less concerned with modernity. The Indian constitution has provided equal civil facilities to both the people of the society, yet the Muslim society seems to have lagged behind.

India is a male dominated country since time immemorial; the responsibility of the family has been a major challenge before women participation. The patriarchy of the Muslim society has fixed the workplace of women within the four walls of the house. The size of the family of Muslim women is generally found to be large. She given preference to joint family and her family responsibilities are also more than the women of Hindu society. In such a situation, Muslim women were left behind in thinking in the direction of social and political responsibilities, due to spending most of their time in the discharge of family responsibilities, despite having the ability and capability. Women play a central role in any family. It is the responsibility of the women to nurture the children and provide them proper manners. That's why it is said that a woman being fully educated is like making a whole family educated. At present in the era of rapid social change, women seem to be most affected. This change appears to be reflected especially in their attitude, ideology and their outlook, so we can say that the effect of women's attitude is sufficient clearly reflected in the society. Changes in the world of women have attracted the attention of sociologists and educationist and teachers have started research work in the light of these facts.

A lot of research work has been done and is being done on various social, economic and educational problems related to women's education and attitude, to what extent the attitudes of two different religious Hindu and Muslim women are different towards, the various change happening in the society. There are very few research studies on how much equality is there, how aware they are about these changes and what has been the impact of the new education policy on their attitudes or what is the role of education and teachers in this. Therefore, this research problem has been chosen to answer these question.

Literature Review

1. Pathan, N.M (1986) while presenting his research paper on the educational backwardness of Muslim women said that Muslim women are not educationally strong. The women of the rural society wanted to get their children married at an early age. She hesitated to give more education to her children and did not want to send them out of the house. In the women of rural area, along with the economics reason, the effect of social reasons was also found.

2. Fatima. N.J (1989) conducted research on the women of Bangalore city and concluded that education has improved the status of women. She is now fighting the social evils in a good way and getting employment. To get education she herself is educated and is also educating her children.
3. Vasuki. N (1990) while doing research on women's attitude towards education, found that women of all different classes are quite aware of education. They want to make, their place in the society by getting alms.
4. Aggarwal M. (1992) studied the impact of education on the social and cultural modernization of Hindu and Muslim women's and pointed out that education played an important role in changing the ideologies of femininity. This made a serious impact on the customs and traditions, which affected both Hindu and Muslim women. He has not seen any effect of age on the conservative thinking of Muslim women in modern education.

Objectives of the Study

The objective of the proposed research work is to study the effect of revolution and progress in education due to social change in present times on Hindu and Muslim Women. Following are some of the major dimensions on which the proposed research paper will highlight:

1. To study the attitude of Hindu women and Muslim women towards social change.
2. To study the difference in attitude of Hindu and Muslim Women towards social change.

Research Methodology

In this, research paper descriptive research design has been used. The informations / datas related to the subject of the research paper has been obtained from secondary sources and their analytical analysis has been done.

Research Tools

In the proposed study, a comparative study of Hindu and Muslim women's attitude towards social change with reference to their educational level will be done but due to non-existence of any instrument on this subject a social change attitude scale will also have to be constructed which will be based on Likert Method. The dimension of social change towards which efforts will be made to know the attitude of women in this scale are as follows.

1. Small Family
2. Child marriage, widow marriage and intercaste marriage
3. Religious Tolerance
4. Educational Status of women
5. Freedom of Job / Business for women
6. Participation in Politics
7. Women have the right to higher education
8. Her role in sports, literature and theater.

Hypothesis of Research

In the context of the above objectives of the research work and research analysis, the concept of the proposed research management can be kept in the following forms: -

1. There is a significant relationship between Hindu Women's attitude towards social change and their educational level.
2. There is a significant relationship between Muslim women's attitude towards social change and their educational level.
3. There is no significant relationship between Hindu and Muslim women's attitude towards social change and their educational level. Keeping these causes and consequences in mind, due research and testing is the basis for its treatment.

Delimitation of Research problem

Based on the above reference and practicality, this research study will be delimited as follows:

1. Only Hindu and Muslim women residing in Sitamarhi district will be selected for the present research work.
2. In this study Hindu and Muslim women at different educational levels such as illiterate, low level educated women (8th Standard), medium level educated women (12th Standard) and high level educated (Graduate and above) Hindu and Muslim women are involved in social change, what is the attitude towards is to be studied.

Collection of Data

100 highly educated and medium educated Hindu and 100 Muslim women living in Sitamarhi district were personally contacted for the compilation of data and they were informed about the purpose of the research. After that they were given an attitude scale and asked to put a tick in front of any one of the brackets, strongly agree, unsure, disagree, strongly disagree made in front of the statements given in it. Less educated and illiterate women have also been included in this study, so data has been collected for these women using interview method.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Table 1: Profile of respondents on the basis of Religion

Religion	Respondents	Percentage
Hindu women	112	56
Muslim women	88	40
Total	200	100

Table 2: Profile of respondents on the basis of Education level

Education level	Respondents	Percentage
Technical Education	16	08
Post graduate	20	10
Graduate	30	15
Intermediate	40	20
Matriculation	44	22
Nun-Matriculation	30	15

Literate	20	10
Total	200	100

Conclusion and Further Research

It is clear from the result obtained from the study of the data that the social status of Hindu and Muslim women there is a general level of attitude towards change. Women with higher education expressed less attitude and women with less education expressed more attitude. Education is the only influence which equally broadening the outlook of women towards social change. Therefore, the need today is that education should be developed more and more. The same fact has been accepted the intellectual development of a person as well as its attitudes, beliefs, interests, etc. and broaden its intelligence and thoughts.

This research would be much useful in future for study related to Hindu and Muslim women in different walks of life. Their attitude to educational, economical, religious and social behavior would be points of consideration in future. There are wide possibilities of research study on the research problem and different researchers on the basis of their interest on their aspects of this useful and interesting problem, Research study can be done by selecting. The present research would prove useful and purposive for researchers in times to come.

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61 - Challenges faced in Online Education & Learning in Pakistan during Covid-19 Pandemic

Sain, Zohaib Hassan

Problem Statement: This research is aimed at identifying the challenges faced in online education & learning in Pakistan during Covid-19 pandemic.

Purpose of the Study: The objective of this research is to uncover issues that online learning and education in Pakistan during the Covid-19 pandemic encountered by teachers and students.

Literature or Theory: The social, economic, and political systems around the world have all experienced COVID-19 as a nightmarish. In Pakistan, one of the most damaged sectors is thought to be education. The developed nations have already switched from traditional classroom settings to online learning environments, while Third World nations like Pakistan were most negatively impacted because they lacked the necessary technology for online learning at any point during the COVID-19 pandemic. There have been several difficulties in getting teachers and students to adopt new technology.

Research Methods: The study focuses on the sample society, which consists of students, teachers, and administration from all departments at the six universities in Lahore City that are the subject of the study. The researcher used triangulation in order to carry out the reliability and validity of the data for results. In this study, closed-ended questionnaires were used in a mixed-method research design. In order to conduct triangulation, the researcher issued a polling survey to students (475), a questionnaire to teachers (25), and the management in addition to conducting management interviews (19).

Summary of Findings: The results show a negative attitude toward faculty members using online learning environments for teaching and learning. The difficulties faced by faculty members prevented them from providing effective teaching and learning. Faculty members also needed extensive expertise in teaching online and were not provided the right training to deal with the technical difficulties.

Conclusion This study will assist educators in improving the quality of online teaching in Pakistan by identifying suitable solutions and suggestions by exploring the experiences and difficulties faculty members have with online education and learning.

Keywords

- 1) Online Education & Learning
- 2) Pakistan
- 3) Covid-19 Pandemic
- 4) Online Teaching & Learning Challenges

Area: Education

62 - Reversing Community Relationship from the I-It to I-Thou as a tool for Peace Building in Ethiopia: The Role of Youth Participation in National Dialogue

Tamrat, Sisaye

Problem Statement: Although significant studies have been conducted about the causes of conflict in Ethiopia, none of these studies tried to investigate the nature of community relationship, especially I-It relationship as the root cause of conflict.

Purpose of the Study: By using a qualitative approach, this study aims at appraising the nature of community relationship, including the youth in Ethiopia and analyse how the youth could play a role during national dialogue.

Literature or Theory: This study is based on the theory of I-Thou relationship as a cardinal tool of realizing dialogue.

Research Methods: This study is based on exploratory research design

Summary of Findings: This study finds out that the I-It form of relationship among communities in general and university students in particular is the root cause of conflict in Ethiopia. The I-Thou relationship, which is the fundamental tool of realizing dialogue and build a lasting peace, is virtually absent in the community.

Conclusion: This study recommends that it is imperative to reverse community relationship from the I-It relationship to the I-Thou relationship so that resolving conflicts and achieving a lasting peace would be possible.

Keywords

- 1) peace building
- 2) conflict resolution
- 3) national dialogue
- 4) I-Thou
- 5) I-It

Area: Justice and Peace

63 – Building Sustainable Peace between Migrants and the State in India: Exploring SDG Development Strategies

Prakash, Rochelle

Problem Statement: Despite the potential for migrants to contribute to the development of India, their exclusion from development goals and policies presents a significant challenge to achieving sustainable and inclusive development.

Purpose of the Study: The purpose of this study is to explore the multifaceted contributions of migration to Indian society, with a particular emphasis on the need to prioritize migration in policy and development discussions given its significant impact on the rural-urban divide and economy.

Literature or Theory: The Capability Approach and Social Exclusion/Inclusion theory offer valuable insights into the relationship between migration, development, and peace, emphasizing the importance of enhancing migrants' capabilities and addressing social inequalities to promote sustainable and inclusive development.

Research Methods: Case studies, document analysis, and participatory action research are research methods that the researcher plans on using to investigate the peace of migrants in India from the perspective of sustainable development goals.

Summary of Findings: The study expects to find that the migrant community in India has often been viewed as a burden on society, but is in fact a complex and dynamic part of society that, if properly harnessed, can significantly contribute to the sustainable development of India, promoting peace, economic growth, and social cohesion.

Conclusion: The study expects to conclude that promoting the inclusion and empowerment of migrants in development policies and programs is essential for achieving sustainable and inclusive development, promoting peace, and unlocking the potential of India's diverse and dynamic population.

Keywords

- 1) Migration
- 2) Sustainable Development Goals
- 3) Inclusion
- 4) Empowerment
- 5) Peace

Area: Justice and Peace

64 – Cultural Factors Behind Thailand’s Declining Birth Rate

Franco, Alexander

Problem Statement: How to deal with Thailand's declining birth rate and its aging population.

Purpose of the Study: A review of existing governmental and other data concerning birth rates and aging population.

Literature or Theory: A literature review of governmental, academic, and media data.

Research Methods: Literature review

Summary of Findings: Thailand is lacking in public policy to deal with a declining birth rate and an aging society.

Conclusion: Short-term need to raise retirement age and long-term policies to promote family growth.

Keywords

- 1) Thailand
- 2) Demographics
- 3) Birth rate
- 4) Aging population
- 5) Retirement

Area: Culture

65 - Explicating Reinhold Niebuhr's Christian Realism in Myanmar's Rakhine-Rohingya Conflict

Ying Ting

Problem Statement: Structural and individual change approaches to doing justice have immense limitations, and thus the case of the Rakhine-Rohingya conflict deserves a different approach to justice.

Purpose of the Study: The study is to attempt drawing out the notion of “the balance of power as doing justice,” and explicate it in the context of the Rakhine-Rohingya conflict in Myanmar.

Literature or Theory: The study implies Reinhold Niebuhr's Christian Realism as an approach to justice-seeking in Myanmar's Rakhine-Rohingya Conflict.

Research Methods: This study utilizes philosophical and political arguments developed in Reinhold Niebuhr's Christian political literature and analyzes comparatively with some other counter-argumentative literature from critical race theories, and civil rights movements.

Summary of Findings: The Rohingya minority in Myanmar currently has two solutions for balancing power: armed resistance or international intervention.

Conclusion: At most, the Rohingya minority can hope for UN peacekeepers to intervene to establish a power balance.

Keywords

- 1) Christian Realism
- 2) Justice
- 3) Power Balance
- 4) Structural and Agent Change
- 5) Religious majorities and minorities

Area: Religion; Justice and Peace

66 - The Culture of Violence and the Proliferation of Firearms in Lanao del Sur, Philippines

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Abstract

The continuous resistance of the Bangsamoro people since the coming of the Spaniards, Americans, and Japanese in the Philippines has contributed to their culture of violence particularly the people of Lanao, the 'Mranaws'. The findings of this study reveals that the culture of violence is the result of the resistance of the Mranaws against the western colonizers that leads to the proliferation of unlicensed firearms in Lanao del Sur which deleteriously affects the socio-economic development of the province. Moreover, the poor management over their transfer has become a serious threat to peace and security. To quell this proliferation, there is a need to understand the historical background and condition in which this proliferation causes in order to generate pragmatic interventions and sustainable programs from the local, regional, and national government. As a result, a process must be used in place of coercion. Therefore, it is more critical to conduct extensive study in order to develop a sensible and practical strategy for controlling unsecured firearms and gradually disarming civilians. The researcher used focus group discussions, interviews, data collection, and survey.

Key Terms: *Bangsamoro, Culture of Resistance, Culture of Violence, firearms Mranaw*

Introduction

Problem Statement

The culture of violence is the consequence of the continuing resistance of the Mranaws against the western colonizers and the Philippine government that leads to the proliferation of unlicensed firearms in Lanao del Sur.

Research Questions

This study aims to the following questions:

1. How historical experiences of the Mranaws shaped their behaviour towards possession of unlicensed firearms?
2. How armed struggle of the Mranaws and the Bangsamoro people contributed to the culture of violence in the region?

Review of Related Literature

According to Funtecha (1979), disarmament in Lanao del Sur took place in 1913 implemented by the Americans to the Mranaws and it was later on employed to stop Moro people in general because of plundering operations that persisted after the American era. The Mranaws and other Moros hesitated to surrender their firearms due to fear and doubt. Military force had to be used, precipitating more bloody encounters between them and the government troops. By the latter part of 1913, the disarmament of the Moros was not only of weapons but of fighting knives and spears, was practically complete and the safety of life and property of non-Muslims in the Moro province was, at length, generally accomplished.

Research Purpose

This research aims to determine the historical cause of the development of culture of resistance among the Mranaws and the Bangsamoro people that resulted to culture of violence and proliferation of illicit firearms in Lanao del Sur.

Research Methodology

The researcher used qualitative method in gathering the data. Firstly, the researcher conducted focus group discussions (FGD) with four sessions with random and inclusive setting where participants are coming from various sectors of the community; and ten respondents for Key Informant Interviews (KII) in each four identified municipalities (Butig, Marantao, Pagayawan, and Piagapo) and in addition to the qualitative data, relevant reliable literatures were reviewed and analysed. This included previous survey reports on relevant topics (e.g. civilian firearm possession, *Rido*, Mindanao secessionism, etc.).

Findings

The Culture of Violence and the Proliferation of Firearms: In Historical Lens

Islam initially came in the Sulu archipelago near the end of the 13th century, about in 1280, before the Spanish conquest of Manila in 1565. It is said that a man named Tuan Mashai'ka brought it there after getting married there and founding the first Islamic community (Rodil, 2003: 36). In the work of (Majul, 1973: 57), he supported this as he mentioned that, "The younger Rajah Sipad (Siripada or Sripaduka), who was a descendant of an earlier Sipad, is said to have been the one to whom Tuan Mashaika wedded." In Maguindanao tradition, according to Rudy Rodil, about 1460 and 1515, respectively, a certain Sharif Awliya from Johore and Sharif Kabungsuwan brought Islam to Mainland Mindanao. While the Lanao tradition mentions a man named Sharif Alawi who is supposed to have arrived in the modern-day Misamis Oriental and whose preaching is said to have later extended to Lanao, there is little proof to support this claim (Rodil, 2003: 37). This only indicates that Islam had already begun to take root in Sulu and Maguindanao and that the process of Islamization in the southern Philippines was well underway. Nevertheless, Spain immediately focused on the Moros and made several, ferocious attempts to conquer them. For instance, the following is revealed in the order given on May 23, 1578, by Governor General Francisco de Sande to Captain Esteban Rodriguez de Figueroa regarding an expedition to Maguindanao:

"... You shall tell him that our object is that he be converted to Christianity and that he must allow us freely to preach the law of the Christians, and the natives must be allowed to go to hear the preaching and to be converted, without receiving any harm from the chiefs. And you shall try to ascertain who are the preachers of the sect of Mahoma, and shall seize and bring them before me. And you shall burn or destroy the house where that accursed doctrine has been preached, and you shall order that it be not rebuilt (Blair & Robertson, 1903: 68)."

Even so, Captain Rodriguez de Figueroa's mission was unsuccessful since on April 20, 1596, he was killed in Maguindanao after being struck in the head by a *kampilan*. The contempt shown by Spanish colonists to the Bangsamoro people's culture and religion served as the impetus for their disobedience. As a result, the Bangsamoro resistance to Spanish rule made sure that the colonizers could not effectively dominate Mindanao. The Bangsamoro people not only resisted the Spanish mission of conversion, but they also refused to renounce their independence and submit to the Spanish. According to Najeeb Saleeby's work:

"One expedition after another was sent to Sulu and Mindanao to destroy, burn, and kill. Thousands of Moros were hunted with bullets and swords and hundreds of towns were leveled to the ground and sacked. Spain instigated hostilities and coveted the Moros

domain. It was not the Moros' part to yield. Their love of home and family naturally prompted them to fight, and they did fight well and valiantly (Saleeby, 1913: 07)."

In other words, even to the very final days of Spanish colonization in Luzon and Visayas, the Bangsamoro people resented the Spanish with passionate and unyielding tenacity. Therefore, the 333 years of Bangsamoro resistance were referred to by Spanish historians, particularly Vicente Barrantes and Juan Montero y Vidal, as "*guerras piraticas*" or wars against pirates (Majul, 1973: 121). And worst, in all Spanish documents and mainstream Philippine history books, referring the Moros as "*Tulisanes*" and barbaric. With this, it is important to note that in the context of war (Muslim Moros vs. Spanish and native Christians), Moros began counter-attacks against the Spanish presence in the Philippines, that was 21 years after the decisive offensive attacks of the Spaniards to the Moro territories particularly in Maguindanao and Sulu. As a result, the Bangsamoros were also thought to have an underlying culture of conflict, which could have led to a violent past. Their blatant love of weaponry and military build-up in response to the external threats posed by the western conquerors added to these overall attitudes

The American colonizers seized control of the Philippines from the Spanish in two ways: first, through the Treaty of Paris in 1898, which cost twenty million Mexican pesos; second, through armed conquest, in which they separately crushed the resistance of the Filipino people and the Bangsamoro people. At this point, it is crucial to emphasize that the Sulu and Maguindanao Sultanate, the *Pat a P'ngampong sa Ranao* (Four States/Federals of Lanao), and the Lumads avoided interaction with them and remained free at the time of the pact, which means that Spain did not occupy them. In this historical account, the incorporation of the Bangsamoro people into the Philippine State without their plebiscitary permission is one of the main causes of the Bangsamoro Struggle.

The Bangsamoro people in Mindanao also persisted in their campaign for independence after the Philippine-American war was formally launched in 1902. The American military called the revolts that took place from 1903 through 1913 "Moro rebellions," and they also called them "armed engagements" (Hawkins, 2011). Teodoro Agoncillo, an eccentric and Manila-centric historian, also labelled this the "Muslim Problems." This is evidence that western colonizers and the Filipinos had negative opinion of the Bangsamoros because they saw them as nothing but killers, pirates, and criminals in general. For self-defence against American forces, the Bangsamoros armed themselves. Over the course of the administrations of three military governors, Generals Leonard Wood, Tasker H. Bliss, and John J. Pershing, there was a ten-year period of violent resistance to American rule (Miller, 2009: 01). Mranaws and Moro people have a strong heritage of keeping weapons for self-defence or to prepare for battle against Western invaders. As a result, the decades of struggle finally gave way to a culture of resistance, which aided in the historical resistance to colonialism and any other challenge to their faith, culture, or territory from without. Communities are ready to engage in conflict. The outcome made it possible for communities to become armed, which became a part of Bangsamoro traditions.

General Leonard Wood, a military governor from 1903 to 1906, was one of the American military governors sent to Mindanao and is therefore largely responsible for formulating the strategy of the American military administration (Miller, 2009: 02). Wood's strategy was to concentrate on creating a system of local government for the province. He thought that once the Moros saw the advantages of good administration, they would readily adopt the new American system over their customary and traditional ways of tribe rule.

On the other hand, Tasker Bliss, served as military governor from 1906 to 1909; in his time, ongoing opposition was primarily perceived as criminal activity, and Bliss took actions to

position and adjust his men in accordance with this viewpoint. The military government was unable to increase its influence or deal with the causes of resistance as a result. Security in the province actually declined, but if one truly believed that there was no organized danger to authority still present following the decisive conflicts, Bliss' choices would look wise (Miller, 2009: 03).

Finally, the last military governor of the Moro Province was General John J. Pershing (1909–1913). During his administration, the necessary security framework was ultimately put in place for the handover to civilian authority. When Pershing assumed command, he realized there were security concerns right once, and at first, he thought the transition to civilian rule would take much longer than it did. Security conditions were created after almost two years of concentrated military operations enforcing disarmament, allowing Pershing to hand up administration of the Moro Province to civilians and abolish the military regime. Although Pershing's disarmament policy was the most effective, it was also the one that faced the most resistance, and before it was successful, it resulted in quite a bit of violence.

Furthermore, the US colonial prohibitions on the carrying of traditional weapons were also necessary during his administration and were viewed as a significant move treated seriously by the Americans in their pacification activities in Mindanao, particularly in Lanao province. These agreements with former Sulu sultans and datus included the disarming and management of traditional weapons.

According to records, all unaccounted-for firearms in Jolo had been gathered by June 1912, with the exception of Lati and Luuk, where there was fierce opposition to disarmament. When Gen. John Pershing became the Moro Province's governor and launched a forceful disarmament push in Jolo, this program was launched. However, imposing it in Lanao was unavoidable because of the Mranaws, who continued to harass and ambush American camps long after 1903. As said by Funtecha:

“Muslim lawlessness, including murders of Americans and foreigners caused Gov. General Forbs to issue Executive Order No. 24, Government of the Moro Province, for the purpose of disarming the offenders. A formal order to that effect was promulgated on September 9, by Brig. General John J. Pershing who was the governor of the Moro Province. The principal reason for disarming the Mranaws and other Muslim groups, as advanced by the Americans, was that Muslims could not be trusted with arms (Funtecha, 1979).”

Disarmament took place, and it was employed to stop Moro plundering operations that persisted after the American era. According to Funtecha (1979):

“The Mranaws and other Muslims hesitated to surrender their firearms due to fear and doubt. Military force had to be used, precipitating more bloody encounters between them and the government troops. By the latter part of 1913, the disarmament of the Muslims, not only of guns but of fighting knives and spears, was practically complete and the safety of life and property of non-Muslims in the Moro province was, at length, generally accomplished.”

Therefore, this disarmament includes the traditional weapons of the Mranaws, which were divided into swords like *the Sundang, Pudang, Kampilan, and Barong*, as well as daggers like the *Kris and Gunong*. These weapons were classified by Noralia Ibrahim as being: cannons called *Lantakas*, spears like the *Bangkaw*, shields called the *K'long*, and war drums (Ibrahim, 2022: 21).

Pershing's choice to prioritize security through his disarmament program and the ensuing enforcement actions were primarily responsible for creating the conditions necessary for the end of military rule in the province and the transition to civilian power. Military operations ultimately proved to be the most effective way to put an end to Moro opposition to American

rule, despite only being initially intended as a supporting effort to a more comprehensive whole-of-government approach. Furthermore, because of this US disarmament effort, the traditional weapons that were gathered from the Mranaws and other Moro groups have later come to be valued for their historical and cultural significance.

Furthermore, President Ferdinand E. Marco, Sr. took office in the Philippines after more than 20 years, particularly in the late 1960s, ushering in the most turbulent and violent phase of relations between the Bangsamoro people and the Filipino government. The culture of resistance made a stronger comeback. Without a doubt, this also signalled the start of the proliferation of unsecured weapons in Lanao and the wider Bangsamoro area.

On March 18, 1968, 64 Bangsamoro recruits from Sulu were killed by their military trainers, who claimed they had rebelled. However, other accounts claim they had just petitioned for the payment of their allowance, which had previously been overdue by more than a month. Because of the military training on Corregidor Island's code name, Jabidah, this became known as the infamous Jabidah massacre (Jubair, 1999). The Jabidah massacre is thought to have inspired the creation of Bangsamoro self-determination movements, such as the Mindanao Independence Movement (MIM) in 1968, which was led by Datu Udtog Matalam and publicly declared its goal of creating an Islamic State in the primarily Muslim regions of Mindanao and Sulu (Gowing, 1979). The conflict between Muslims and Christians in Central Mindanao, mainly in the provinces of Cotabato and Lanao, erupted in violence between the 1970s and 1980s. In both provinces, Ilagas was linked to Christians. The "Blackshirts," the Muslim provincial security forces recognized for their all-black uniforms, were connected with the Muslims in the Cotabato region, while the Barracudas, a Mranaw paramilitary group, were affiliated with the Muslims in the Lanao region. Several killings targeting Muslim communities occurred between January and December of 1971.

President Ferdinand Marcos officially imposed martial law in 1972 due to the state-wide revolt led by the Communist Party of the Philippines-New People's Army and the Bangsamoro movement in Mindanao. The Bangsamoro Republic would be founded in the area that the Moro National Liberation Front (MNLF) claimed to be their ancestral homeland, mainly the islands of Mindanao, Sulu, and Palawan. The Bangsamoro communities' continuing extermination and political unrest strengthened their "culture of resistance," which adhered to their traditional and religious belief that they had the right to defend their homeland from invaders and ignited the Bangsamoro struggle.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Conclusion

The Mranaws and the Bangsamoros in general have had unique historical experiences that have been extremely important in shaping the possession of unlicensed firearms in Lanao del Sur. In conclusion, the culture of resistance against western colonizers as well as the advent of the Bangsamoro armed struggle for self-determination has led to the proliferation of unlicensed firearms among the civilians as a means of survival, which unintentionally contributed to the gradual development of a culture of violence.

Recommendations

Following are the two recommendations of this research paper: 1) Local Government Unit (LGU) must find ways to increase the deployment of police visibility in their locality to ensure safeness and reinforcement of law. 2) The key to sustainability and the beginning of conflict transformation is an educational campaign among Lanao del Sur's youth sectors and

communities. This is the first steps to discourage ownership of weapons in the community and prevent the widespread of firearms.

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67 – Understanding Rohingya refugees' journey to and from the refugee camps in Bangladesh

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Problem Statement: The article argues that, despite being portrayed as passive victims of the structural violence, Rohingya refugees do have agency manifested in the flow state during their displacement journey.

Purpose of the Study: It offers the narratives of how the Rohingya have made conscious decisions to leave their homes and communities in search of safety and security not only through victimized lens, but also as empowered agents.

Literature or Theory: In the context of the Rohingya refugees on Bhasan Char Island, we will examine whether flow experiences can be identified among the refugees in their journey to find better opportunities outside of their origin to escape from the challenges posed by the island's security and climate and environment, such as floods and storms (Csikszentmihalyi, 1990). In doing so, this article will incorporate Flow Theory with the concept of 'agency', understood as an individual's ability to act and make decisions within the social and cultural structures that surround them (Bourdieu, 1980).

Research Methods: Findings of this research were generated from 19 in-depth interviews and Focus Group Discussion with participants residing in both Cox's Bazaar camps and those who have been relocated to Bhasan Char Island in Bangladesh

Summary of Findings: findings show that Rohingya refugees face notable obstacles to achieving flow caused by their political persecution and violence. In spite of this, findings suggest that Rohingya refugees are attempting to reconstruct their lives by forming new social networks and seeking support from humanitarian organizations. It argues that it is critical to identify barriers faced by Rohingya refugees and support their efforts to build their lives by providing them with education, employment, and opportunities for social integration. By providing these needs it is possible to create a sense of belonging and agency that can help them overcome challenges of displacement and their continuous journey to find a new home.

Conclusion: Through the exploration of flow theory, this study reviews the experiences of Rohingya refugees on Cox's Bazaar and Bhasan Char Island, to investigate whether flow experiences can be identified among the refugees in their journey to find better opportunities and exercising their agency as an individual in making a life altering decision.

Keywords

- 1) Rohingya
- 2) Refugee
- 3) Flow theory
- 4) Agency
- 5) Recycled refugees

Area: Justice and Peace

68 - Peace Building through Vedanta

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Abstract

Global diversity and heterogeneity are evidenced by the sheer differences in sex, colour, caste, creed etc. apart from the more observable differences in history, geography and culture. Society is an amalgamation of the individual and the institution. To quote Talcott Parsons, this system (society) engulfs within itself multiple and diverse sub-systems (institutions) and tries to maintain a state of equilibrium. This is because every sub system relies on the other; hence changes in one necessitate change in the other to maintain balance and harmony. This however, seems to be the ideal situation; often far removed from the reality. Global conflict today stems from the individual understanding and interpretation of man's social reality influenced by the environmental and religious underpinnings. Narrow, parochial and antagonistic sentiments are fuelled out of perception and contribute to global chaos and conflict. A case in point is the Islamic interpretation of jihad or holy war that has claimed thousands of innocent lives globally- a persistent problem in India's backyard of Kashmir since independence. The object is therefore to examine the extent to which the ancient Indian philosophy of Vedanta (which is predominantly concerned with trying to solve fundamental problems about human existence) can contribute to global peace and harmony by universalizing the end goals of every civilisation and human being.

Keywords: Vedanta, Conflict, Peace, Harmony.

What is Vedanta?

India as a melting pot of diverse religions and cultures and one of the oldest civilisations in the world embodies the spirit of unity in diversity. The civilisation embodies peace as the foremost basis to a sustained and shared co-existence. Vedanta philosophy (around 400-450 AD) is one of the six philosophies in Indian Hindu philosophies. The term Vedanta in Sanskrit means the “conclusion” (anta) of the Vedas. Vedanta is one of the six systems (darshans) of Indian philosophy. Vedanta studies the nature of the relationship between the eternal core of the individual self (atman) and the absolute (brahman). The self (atman) is the agent of its own acts (karma) and therefore the recipient of the fruits (phala), or consequences, of action. While Vedanta emphasizes the harmony of religions, it also stresses the necessity of diving deep into the spiritual tradition of our choice, sticking with it, and working hard.

Vedanta (also known as Uttara Mimansa) constitutes one of the six systems of Hindu philosophy (darshanas) that emerged in ancient India (along with Samkhya, Yoga, Nyaya, Vaisheshikha and Mimamsa). Although it literally means the ‘end or conclusion of the Vedas’ (the oldest and most revered scriptures of Hinduism), Vedanta’s concepts are viewed as the spiritual and philosophical apogee of ideas contained in the Vedas.

The three fundamental texts of Vedanta (called Prasthanatrayi) are:

The Upanishads: The most prominent being the longer and older ones, mainly the Brihadaranyaka, the Chandogya, the Taittiriyya and the Katha.

The Brahma Sutras: Attributed to sage Badaryana or Vyasa, it consists of 555 verses (sutras) in four chapters. The main themes being Brahman (the ultimate reality) and human existence.

The Bhagvad Gita: This 701-verse religious text is also called Gitopanishad (Chapters 23–40 of ‘Bhishma Parva’ in Mahabharata) and is considered the manual for practical application of Upanishad in everyday life.

The spiritual truths contained in the Prasthanatrayi have been discussed and elucidated by philosophers and founders of several Vedanta schools, with varying ontological interpretations. Their commentaries are preserved in the Bhashya texts, which deal with the varied perspectives on the nature of God (known as Brahman), ranging between the assertions of being essentially dvaita (dualistic, ‘God being separate from creation’) in nature to ‘advaita’ (non-dualistic, ‘Godhead and all of creation being essentially one’).

To paraphrase Ramakrishna, one of the celebrated exponents on Vedanta, “If you want to dig a well, you have to choose your location and keep digging until you reach water. It does not do any good to dig a bunch of shallow holes.”

While a shallow spiritual life is probably better than no spiritual life at all, it nevertheless does not take us where we want to go: to freedom, to God-realization. Once we choose which spiritual path we wish to follow, we should doggedly pursue it until we reach the goal.

What is the reason for international strife and conflict?

The oldest religious sentiment ever expressed is perhaps the statement on religious harmony found in the ancient Vedas: Ekam sat, vipra bahudha vadanti, “Truth is one; sages call it by various names.”

The same sentiment has since then echoed and re-echoed in the corridors of time, amplified by enlightened persons of different religions in different parts of the world. As the pagan Roman thinker Quintus Aurelius Symmachus said to St. Ambrose, the dogmatic bishop of Milan: “The heart of so great a mystery cannot ever be reached by following one road only.”

All organised religions of the world propagate the same end goal- that of love, peace and freedom. However, interpretation of religious scriptures and teachings have created a sense of distrust and conflict between religions. This has spread hatred and antagonism among people, prophets and peers of different religious faiths affecting global peace, order and security. A case in point is the scourge of terrorism globally. The holy war “jihad” as propounded by Islamic fundamentalists and terror organisations has no rightful place in Islam. It is meant to pursue narrow and parochial social, economic or political goals at the cost of misinterpreting religion and stirring the emotive sentiments to drive them to spreading hate, fear, violence and terror. According to the Encyclopaedia of Wars, out of all 1,763 known/recorded historical conflicts, 121, or 6.87%, had religion as their primary cause. Jeffrey Russell argues that numerous cases of supposed acts of religious violence such as the [Thirty Years War](#), the [French Wars of Religion](#), the [Protestant-Catholic conflict in Ireland](#), the [Sri Lankan Civil War](#), and the [Rwandan Civil War](#) were all primarily motivated by social, political, and economic issues rather than religion. This evidences the above argument that misinterpretation of religion and its tenants is to blame.

This is a cause of concern because all religions deal with the same basic human problems, we would expect the world’s religions to be in the forefront of promoting harmony—not only among themselves but also at every level of society.

Need for peace and harmonious world

21st of September as World Peace Day by United Nations reflects that the need for peace in the society cannot be over underlined. Peace in an individual is identical with mental quietude or psychological balance. The absence of peace in a person can reduce the one to the level of brutes or lower animals. Hence it is said that violence of any kind is an act of poverty of the mind rather than that of material things. Harmony is a precondition for peace, and peace opens the door to joy. All of us know this from our own experience. In matters of health or study, work or worship, harmony is what we strive to achieve. When harmony is lost, the result is stress and anxiety, pain, and sorrow.

At the societal level, peace is a prerequisite for the achievement of development and productivity and by extension, societal progress. There cannot be progress in the absence of peace. This is the kind of peace which the Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary defined as 'a situation or a period of time in which there is no war or violence in a country or an area'. Wherever there is no peace, chaos becomes the order of the day.

This assumes greater significance in a globalised world order wherein concepts of liberalisation, globalisation and privatisation have integrated global communities and processes making the dream of a "one global village" a reality. Such integration was needed and came as a strong lesson learnt in the aftermath of the World Wars that pursuit of self-driven and narrow interests would threaten world peace and the security of its populations. Countries that have very high levels of peace recorded two percentage points per annum higher GDP growth than countries with very low peace over a sixty-year period to 2019. The global economic impact of violence was \$16.5 trillion in 2021, equivalent to 10.9% of global GDP, or \$2,117 per person. These statistics drive home the point that for social and economic progress peace is non-negotiable.

India, as the world's largest democracy and one of the oldest civilisations globally has reiterated the need of peaceful co-existence- right from Satyagraha, its freedom movement, based on the ahimsa (non-violence) to doctrines of Panchsheel and Non-Alignment that have been corner stones in India's foreign policy. This is noteworthy as India has suffered violence emanating from state sponsored religious fundamentalism since independence from its own neighbourhood, in the Union territory of Jammu and Kashmir, apart from various cities throughout the country. But the path of peace, civilisational to India remains a guiding light for the world to learn from and emulate.

Role of Vedanta philosophy in peace building

The ideal of 'Vasudhaiva Kutumbakam' has been a source of inspiration for Indian culture, which is known for its hospitable and magnanimous attitude towards foreigners since **birth of Indian civilisation**. This ideal has helped India reconcile with ideological differences, plurality of beliefs, cultures and countercultures, religions, and sects, as well as races and ethnicities, over several millennia. In fact, this universalist ideal has not only made us more hospitable in our outlook towards foreigners, it has also made us more accommodating and democratic at home. 'Aham Brahmasmi': Source of Identity, Exclusivity and Rejuvenation The Vedanta texts are categorical in their endorsement of non-violence (ahimsa). The *Chandogya Upanishad* (8.15.1) bars violence against 'all creatures' (*sarva-bhuta*) and the practitioner of ahimsa is said to escape from the cycle of reincarnation. Even Lord Krishna in the Bhagvad Gita proclaims: 'Ahimsa is among the various qualities of living beings created by Me alone.' He also includes ahimsa as among the virtues that constitute knowledge, besides which whatever there may be is ignorance The impact of Vedanta on Indian strategic culture has been immense and has played varying roles for statesmen, political leaders, diplomats, and military generals in a variety of ways

In **medieval times**, it was the monism of Vedanta that captured the imagination of Muslim mystics. With pre-Islamic Shamanic affiliations, the Muslim rulers of Mongol-Turkic origins were drawn to the monistic spiritualism of Vedanta, and surprisingly 'advaita' became the philosophy for the possible formulation of a syncretic culture, right from the fourteenth century, in Bhakti and Sufi saints and poets, like Kabirdas and Amir Khusro. It took a semi-formal shape in Akbar's political doctrine of 'Sulh-i-Kul' (universal peace), which drew on the non-dualist theological strains of Vedantism and Sufi Islam.

There are unmistakable imprints of these spiritual moorings in the writings of Abul Fazal, the most noted ideologue and strategic thinker in Akbar's court. Emperor Akbar is himself reported to have organised a separate quarter for advaita yogis, which was called Jogipura. According to Badauni, Akbar used to visit advaitin yogis, along with close companions, and acquaint himself with Hindu mysticism, their methods of *muraqaba* (meditation) and *mashaghils* (spiritual practices). The tradition passed on to Jahangir, who is said to have held many discussions on spiritual and religious matters with Hindu scholars, particularly Jadurup, a noted Vaishnavite scholar at Ujjain and Mathura. The discussions are said to have convinced the emperor that the Vedantic philosophy and Sufi thought of 'wahdatul wujud' (the oneness of all existence in God) were identical. Jahangir was also close to the noted saint Akam Nath, and their discussions focused on monism and monotheism. It is well known that Dara Shikoh's Sufi leaning brought him closer to Vedanta. He himself translated the Upanishads, which was titled *Sirr-i-Akbar*. His other work, *Majma Al Bahrain*, highlights the attempt at bringing about a strategic cohesion between Hindu and Muslim communities in a bid to forge a nationalist bond. However, Aurangzeb's extreme fanaticism and bigotry prevented the assimilative process from a much-desired outcome.

The evolution of Indian political and strategic culture in modern times begins with the **social reform movements** initiated by Indian intellectuals and spiritual leaders in the **nineteenth century**, such as Raja Ram Mohan Roy (who founded the Brahmo Samaj based on Vedanta ideals), Swami Dayananda Saraswati (who established the Arya Samaj through his call for 'Return to the Vedas') and the chief proponents of the so-called 'Neo-Vedanta movement', namely, Swami Vivekananda, Sri Aurobindo and Radhakrishnan, who popularised the philosophy in India and around the world.

Swami Vivekananda, in his address to the Parliament of World Religion in Chicago in 1893 opined "as the different streams having their sources in different paths which men take through different tendencies, various though they appear, crooked or straight, all lead to Thee." He went on to add that "sectarianism, bigotry, and its horrible descendant, fanaticism, have long possessed this beautiful earth. They have filled the earth with violence, drenched it often and often with human blood, destroyed civilization and sent whole nations to despair. Had it not been for these horrible demons, human society would be far more advanced than it is now. But their time is come; and I fervently hope that the bell that tolled this morning in honour of this convention may be the death-knell of all fanaticism, of all persecutions with the sword or with the pen, and of all uncharitable feelings between persons wending their way to the same goal."

Swami Vivekananda, a born Jnani and Yogi in his own way tempered with the scientific spirit. In the words of Swamiji, the goal of all religions is the same, but the language of the teachers differs. The end of all religions is realizing God in Soul. Real religion begins where this little universe ends. The fear of God is the beginning of religion, but the love of God is the end of religion. Religion is the greatest motive power for realizing that infinite energy which is birth right and nature of every man. Religious quarrels are always over the husks. If a religion cannot help man wherever he may be, wherever he stands, it is not much use. It is a man-making religion that we want. Religion as a science, as a study, is the greatest and healthiest

exercise that the human mind can have. Religion begins where philosophy ends. This rational, man making and universal religion propagated by Swami Vivekananda is the need of the hour, which can ensure peace and prosperity in the society and the world.

This ability to revive and reform Indian society through the power of its ancient religious and philosophical tradition, with Vedanta ideals at its core, gave a sense of identity and pride to Indian society, which eventually ignited political aspiration in a new generation of political leaders. In **latter half of the nineteenth century**, the Vedanta-inspired ideals spurred the imagination of young political figures, like Bal Gangadhar Tilak, Mahatma Gandhi, Subhash Chandra Bose and even the extreme right Hindu nationalist, V.D. Savarkar. All these leaders were deeply influenced by the Vedas, Upanishads and Bhagvad Gita.

The same ideal of Upanishad inspired Rabindranath Tagore to his views against colonialism and of ultimate unification of mankind that were encapsulated in the logo for his university, 'yatra visvam bhavti ekanidam' ('where the whole world meets in a single nest'), which clearly represents the Vedanta outlook. Vedanta meant different things to different Indian leaders of the twentieth century. To Bal Gangadhar Tilak, Vedanta philosophy as enshrined in the Bhagvad Gita was more appealing than the outlook of renunciation preached by Adi Shankara and Ramanuja. He opposed some of the liberal and universal interpretations of Vedanta, which alienated him from a section of Hindu, Muslim and British intellectuals and political figures. On the other hand, for Bhimrao Ambedkar—the great freedom fighter, leader of the untouchables (Dalit) and the principal architect of Indian Constitution—Vedanta ideals like advaita helped overcome the evil of casteism in Indian society and were conducive to India's modern democracy. In his book, *Riddle in Hinduism*, where he criticises many Hindu texts, he praises Vedanta precepts:

But all the same this theory of Brahman has certain social implications which have a tremendous value as a foundation for Democracy. If all persons are parts of Brahman then all are equal and all must enjoy the same liberty which is what Democracy means. Mahatma Gandhi was inspired by the ideals of Vedanta, particularly those enshrined in Bhagvad Gita, which he deemed 'a spiritual dictionary'. In a series of lectures on Gita in 1924, the Mahatma said that people belonging to all faiths can read this scripture, as it does not favour any sectarian point of view. It teaches nothing but pure ethics. Clearly, the universalist message of Gita influenced the Father of the Nation to espouse values of non-violence, tolerance, and secularism. Similarly, for Nehru, India always had a distinct outlook on the world derived from its philosophical heritage, especially the advaita. Although an agnostic by faith, Vedanta ideals had a high station in his worldview. His strategic precepts of 'Panchsheel' and 'unity in diversity' arguably spring from the universalist and pacifist ideals of Vedanta.

India, **at independence** adopted 'Satyamev Jayate' (truth alone triumphs) as its national motto on 26 January 1950, which is a mantra from the Vedantic canon of the *Mundaka Upanishad*. Another *mahavakya* (grand pronouncement) is 'Vasudhaiva Kutumbakam' (the world is one family) from the *Maha Upanishad*, which has been acknowledged as the cornerstone of India's political and cultural diplomacy on several occasions.

Speaking at the World Culture Festival in March 2016, Indian Prime Minister Narendra Modi said, 'Indian culture is very rich and has inculcated in each one of us great values; we are the people who have come from *Aham Brahmasmi* to *Vasudhaiva Kutumbakam*; we are the people who have come from *Upanishads* to *Upgrah* (Satellite).' Earlier, addressing the United Nations General Assembly in 2014, he had said: 'Every nation's world view is shaped by its civilisation and philosophical tradition. India's ancient wisdom sees the world as one family. It is this timeless current of thought that gives India an unwavering belief in multilateralism.'

Today, as India chairs the G20 the theme of one nation, one family, one future resonates India's civilisational goal - *Vasudhaiva Kutumbakam* reiterating the need to go back to the Vedanta for peaceful and long-lasting tool of conflict resolution.

Conclusion

The Vedanta scriptures are not merely theological texts, but profoundly philosophical works, whose insights have fascinated world's greatest intellectuals and even quantum physicists, like Einstein, Schrodinger, Oppenheimer, Bohr and Heisenberg.

In fact, there was a time when the entirety of Hindu philosophy was confused with Advaita Vedantism in the West, and it became particularly popular after Kant's non-empirical 'subjective aspect of knowing'. Many Western intellectuals, like Arthur Schopenhauer, Aldous Huxley, A.N. Whitehead, Arnold Toynbee, Rudolph Steiner, Wilhelm von Humbolt, Will Durant, Lucian Blaga, and Christopher Isherwood, were spellbound by its worldview. There were also its critics among European orientalis, from Hegel to Churchill, who blamed the ascetic introversion of Vedanta teachings to the alleged passivity, fatalism, niggardliness, and obsequiousness of the Indian culture.

Conversely, some Western experts falsely charged Bhagvad Gita with racism and accused it of encouraging violence that allegedly even influenced Nazi Germany's leaders, like Alfred Rosenberg and Heinrich Himmler, who were given to reciting the scripture. However, much of this criticism has proven to be highly exaggerated and politically motivated as it came from scholars supportive of Britain's colonial rule. The time has come to set right such misapprehensions about Vedantic tradition.

In recent years, Deepshikha Shahi's impressive work, *Advaita as a Global International Relations Theory*, and the Vivekananda International Foundation's noteworthy book, *Vasudhaiva Kutumbakam: Relevance of India's Ancient Thinking to Contemporary Strategic Reality*, have made a commendable contribution in highlighting Vedanta ideas within the context of International Relations studies, as well as in the context of Indian strategic culture.

It is possible to view every religion of the world as an expression of the transcendent aspect of religion. The truth every religion represents is an expression of the absolute Truth. It is the transcendent aspect of religion that can be called the religion with a capital "R" or the Religion beyond all religions. It not only transcends every religion but also pervades every one of them. It is the totality of religions.

Vivekananda described this transcendent aspect of religion in the following words:

That one eternal religion is applied to different planes of existence, is applied to the opinions of various minds and various races. There never was my religion or yours, my national religion or your national religion; there never existed many religions, there is only the one. One infinite religion existed all through eternity and will ever exist, and this religion is expressing itself in various countries in various ways.

All religions are expressions of the Religion beyond religions. Every religion is true and authentic, and they all have a thread of harmony connecting them. This thread can be discovered and the underlying harmony can be experienced by truly religious people.

The phrase "truly religious" is, of course, open to interpretation. Vedanta would say that "religious" isn't a valid term for those who merely believe in some dogma or accept some Savior. True religion (to quote Vivekananda again) is not talk, or doctrines; nor is it sectarianism... It is the relation between soul and God... Religion does not consist in erecting temples, or building churches, or attending public worship. It is not to be found in books, or

in words, or in lectures, or in organizations. Religion consists in realization... [We] must realize God, feel God, see God, talk to God. That is religion.

What we need today is a conscious effort to see the thread connecting all religions, forming a beautiful garland adorning the Supreme Being, who is neither a Christian, nor a Jew, nor a Muslim, nor a Buddhist, nor a Hindu, nor belonging to any religion whatsoever. All belong to Him, but He transcends all. When the spirit of religious harmony animates our soul and the awareness of the Religion beyond religions pervades our consciousness, life will hold a new, richer meaning for us. Then the following words of Swami Vivekananda will find a ready resonance in our hearts:

“I accept all religions that were in the past, and worship with them all; I worship God with every one of them, in whatever form they worship Him.... Is God’s book finished? Or is it still a continuous revelation going on? It is a marvelous book—these spiritual revelations of the world. The Bible, the Vedas, the Koran, and all other sacred books are but so many pages and an infinite number of pages remain yet to be unfolded. I would leave it open for all of them. We stand in the present, but open ourselves to the infinite future. We take in all that has been in the past, enjoy the light of the present, and open every window of the heart for all that will come. Salutations to all the prophets of the past, to all the great ones of the present, and to all that are to come!

**Second Annual International Conference on Religion, Culture, and Peace Education
Department of Peace Studies (DPS), Religion, Culture, and Peace Laboratory (RCPL),
in Collaboration with Mennonite Central Committee (MCC)
International College, Payap University, Chiang Mai, Thailand**